

Improving the use of long-term patient-important outcomes in intensive care trials

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, RN, MSc (Health Science)

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Cover image

Inviting patient and public perspectives into research flips the view. The cover image was captured on my summer 2024 holiday in Bornholm and symbolises this shift. Welcoming other perspectives may challenge and reshape your understanding, enriching the journey, and making the outcome both more complex and more rewarding.

Maj-Brit N Kjær

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PhD Thesis

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, RN, MSc (Health Science)

Department of Intensive Care

Copenhagen University Hospital – Rigshospitalet

Denmark

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Author

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, CCRN, MSc (Health Science)

Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital – Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark.
Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

Supervisors

Anders Perner, MD, PhD, professor (principal supervisor)

Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital – Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark.
Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

Ingrid Egerod, RN, MSN, PhD, professor (principal co-supervisor)

Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital – Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark.
Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

Martin Bruun Madsen, MD, PhD (co-supervisor)

Department of Cardiothoracic Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital—Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark.
Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

Assessment committee

Helle Pappot, MD, PhD, Clinical professor (chair)

Department of Oncology, Copenhagen University Hospital—Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark
Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

Søren Mikkelsen, MD, PhD, Clinical professor

Prehospital Research Unit, the Region of Southern Denmark, Odense University Hospital, Denmark
The Mobile Emergency Care Unit, Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care Medicine, Odense University Hospital, Odense, Denmark

Bronwen Connolly, PhD, MCSP, professor

Wellcome-Wolfson Institute for Experimental Medicine, Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom

Preface

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Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, December 2024

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Original papers

This PhD thesis is based on three studies

Study I

- Paper I. Kjaer MBN, Madsen MB, Møller MH, Egerod I, Perner A. Reporting and interpreting missing health-related quality of life data in intensive care trials: Protocol for a systematic review. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand*. 2019 Jul;63(6):796–801.
- Paper II. Kjaer MBN, Madsen MB, Meier N, Granholm A, Møller MH, Egerod I, et al. Non-response for health-related quality of life outcomes in ICU patients: A systematic review of the reporting in randomised trials. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand*. 2023 Aug;67(7):842–52.

Study II

- Paper III. Kjær MBN, Meyhoff TS, Madsen MB, Hjortrup PB, Møller MH, Egerod I, et al. Long-term patient-important outcomes after septic shock: A protocol for 1-year follow-up of the CLASSIC trial. *Acta Anaesthesiologica Scandinavica*. 2020;64(3):410–6.
- Paper IV. Kjær MBN, Meyhoff TS, Sivapalan P, Granholm A, Hjortrup PB, Madsen MB, et al. Long-term effects of restriction of intravenous fluid in adult ICU patients with septic shock. *Intensive Care Med*. 2023 Jul;49(7):820–30.

Study III

- Paper V. Kjær M-BN, Granholm A, Vesterlund GK, et al.: Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients—A protocol. *Acta Anaesthesiologica Scandinavica* 2022; 66:415–424
- Paper VI. Kjær MBN, Bruun CRL, Granholm A, Moeller MH, Rasmussen BS, Mortensen CB, et al. External validation of a core outcome set developed in Denmark for the general ICU patient – protocol amendment to an ongoing modified Delphi consensus process. 2023 Nov 3 [cited 2023 Nov 3]; Available from: <https://osf.io/qugyw>
- Paper VII. Kjaer MBN, Bruun CRL, Granholm A, Møller MH, Rasmussen BS, Mortensen CB, et al. A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients. Accepted for publication in *Critical Care Medicine* on 13 November 2024.

Summary

Background

Critical illness is a complex condition with a high mortality rate, requiring intensive care, organ support, and skilled healthcare professionals using advanced equipment. While care is based on the best available evidence, survivors often face physical, mental and cognitive impairments, affecting their daily lives and placing burdens on caregivers.

Despite efforts to provide the best intensive care, most intensive care treatments lack robust evidence, with an estimated quarter being ineffective or potentially harmful. Addressing this gap requires more randomised clinical trials (RCTs) to systematically evaluate routine practices and improve quality of evidence. The selection of outcomes used in these trials is critical; they must be measurable, relevant, patient-important, and focused on long-term impacts. However, variation in outcomes across studies complicates comparisons and synthesis, slowing progress in generating high quality evidence. Beyond mortality, the most used long-term patient-important outcome is health-related quality of life (HRQoL). However, challenges such as loss to follow-up due to death or other reasons can hinder reliable data collection and impact results.

Methods

Study I: A systematic review and meta-analysis examined HRQoL in intensive care trials, focusing on the extent of loss to follow-up (non-respondents) and how trials handled non-respondents and non-survivors methodologically.

Study II: A long-term follow-up of the CLASSIC trial (Conservative versus Liberal Approach to fluid therapy of Septic Shock in Intensive Care) investigating two approaches to fluid therapy for the treatment of septic shock. Long-term outcomes were mortality, HRQoL, and cognitive function. HRQoL was assessed using the EQ-5D five-dimension (EQ-5D-5L) questionnaire and EQ visual analogue scale (EQ-VAS), while cognitive function was evaluated via the mini version of the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Mini MoCA) test; all administered by telephone one year after randomisation. For deceased patients, EQ-5D-5L, EQ-VAS, and Mini MoCA scores were assigned a value of 0. Multiple imputation was performed if missing data exceeded 5%.

Study III: A Modified Delphi consensus process, supplemented by international validation, was conducted to develop a standardised core outcome set for adult intensive care patients. This process involved multiple methods (literature review, interviews, and survey) and included patient and public involvement (PPI) through research panels comprising patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers.

Results

Study I: From 10,075 screened records, 88 RCTs with 196 HRQoL outcomes were included. An outcome was defined as each HRQoL instance assessed in an RCT (e.g. different tools or time points). For 149/196 (76%) outcomes, data on non-respondents were available with a distribution of 20% [range from 0% to 72%]. Nearly a quarter of the outcomes included non-respondents in the analysis, while close to a third included

non-survivors. In a total of 105/196 (54%) outcomes, it was not specified how non-respondents or non-survivors were handled.

Study II: Of 1,554 participants in the CLASSIC trial, 1,549 were included in the long-term follow-up; five patients withdrew consent to use of their data. Missing data were 2.1% for mortality, 8.7% for HRQoL, and 13.7% for cognitive function. At one year, mortality was similar between groups: 385/746 (51.3%) in the restrictive group vs 383/767 (49.9%) in the standard group. HRQoL and cognitive function were also similar between the groups.

Study III: Of the 380 participants invited, 264 accepted to participate in the survey, and 82 consented to interviews. There were 217 international research panel members from 14 countries involved in the process, with half of the members being patients or family members. After a three round Delphi survey and consensus meetings, the initial core outcome set was finalised. Following international validation, consensus was reached on six outcomes: survival, free of life support, free of delirium, out of hospital, HRQoL, and cognitive function.

Conclusions

The SRMA revealed a high potential for selection bias in the reporting of HRQoL data in ICU RCTs. Many studies relied heavily on complete case analyses that excluded non-survivors and non-respondents. This approach discards valuable data, affecting the interpretability of trial results and limiting insights into patient-important outcomes. Transparency in reporting and analysis is crucial for advancing patient-centred research.

The CLASSIC trial found similar one-year mortality, HRQoL, and cognitive function between restrictive and standard fluid therapy groups at 1-year. These results suggest that restrictive fluid therapy is a safe strategy for ICU patients with septic shock.

The internationally validated core outcome set for general adult intensive care patients includes survival, free of life support, free of delirium, out of hospital, HRQoL, and cognitive function. In future studies, consensus should be established on how these outcomes should be measured.

Summary in Danish (Dansk resumé)

Baggrund

Kritisk sygdom er en kompleks tilstand med høj dødelighed, der kræver intensiv behandling, organ-understøttende behandling og højt specialiseret sundhedspersonale, der kan betjene avanceret udstyr. Selvom behandlingen baseres på den bedst tilgængelige viden og evidens, oplever intensiv-overlevende ofte nedsat fysisk, mental og kognitiv funktion, som påvirker deres dagligdag og belaster pårørende.

På trods af bestræbelser er de fleste behandlinger indenfor intensiv terapi ikke baseret på solid evidens, og det anslås, at en fjerdedel er ineffektive eller potentielt skadelige. Der er behov for flere randomiserede kliniske forsøg (randomised clinical trials—RCT'er) til systematisk at evaluere daglige rutiner og forbedre evidensgrundlaget. Valget af effektmål er afgørende; de skal være målbare, relevante, patientvigtige og fokusere på langsigtede konsekvenser. Variation i anvendte effektmål på tværs af RCT'er komplicerer sammenligninger og syntese, hvilket hæmmer fremskridt mod stærk evidens. Ud over dødelighed er det hyppigst anvendte langsigtede patient-vigtige effektmål, helbredsrelateret livskvalitet (Health-related quality of life—HRQoL), men udfordringer som frafald på grund af død eller andre årsager vanskeliggør pålidelig dataindsamling og påvirker resultaterne.

Metode

Studie I: En systematisk gennemgang og metaanalyse undersøgte HRQoL i forsøg på intensive afdelinger med fokus på frafald af forsøgsdeltagere, og hvordan forsøgene metodisk håndterede afdøde og frafald af forsøgsdeltagere.

Studie II: En langtidsopfølgning af CLASSIC-forsøget (Conservative versus Liberal Approach to fluid therapy of Septic Shock in Intensive Care), der undersøgte to tilgange til væskebehandling af patienter med septisk shock. Langtidseffektmålene var dødelighed, HRQoL og kognitiv funktion. HRQoL blev vurderet med EQ-5D fem-dimensioner (EQ-5D-5L) spørgeskema og EQ Visual Analogue Scale (EQ-VAS), mens kognitiv funktion blev vurderet med miniversionen af Montreal Cognitive Assessment test (Mini MoCA). De blev indhentet telefonisk et år efter randomisering. Afdøde patienter fik tildelt scoren 0 i EQ-5D-5L, EQ-VAS spørgeskema og Mini MoCA testen. Multiple imputationer blev anvendt, hvis manglende data oversteg 5%.

Studie III: En modificeret Delphi konsensusproces, suppleret med international validering, blev udført for at udvikle et standardiseret sæt kerneeffektmål for voksne intensivpatienter. Processen involverede flere metoder (litteraturgennemgang, interviews og spørgeskemaundersøgelser) og inkluderede brugerinvolvering ved oprettelse af forskningspaneler bestående af patienter, pårørende, klinikere og forskere.

Resultater

Studie I: Af 10.075 gennemgåede artikler blev 88 RCT'er med 196 HRQoL effektmål inkluderet. Et effektmål blev defineret som hver gang HRQoL blev vurderet i et RCT (f.eks. med forskellige spørgeskemaer eller tidspunkter). For 149/196 (76%) effektmål var der tilgængelige data om frafald af forsøgsdeltagere, der havde en fordeling på 20% [spænd mellem 0% til 72%]. Næsten en fjerdedel af effektmålene inkluderede frafald af forsøgsdeltagere i deres analyser og en tredjedel inkluderede de afdøde. For i alt 105/196 (54%) effektmål blev det ikke af rapporteret, hvordan frafald af forsøgsdeltagere eller afdøde blev håndteret, hvilket blev tolket som en eksklusion fra analyserne.

Studie II: Af 1.554 deltagere i CLASSIC forsøget blev 1.549 inkluderet i langtidsopfølgningen; fem patienter trak deres samtykke for brug af data tilbage. Manglende data var 2,1% for dødelighed, og manglende besvarelser var 8,7% for HRQoL og 13,7% for kognitiv funktion. Efter et år var dødeligheden sammenlignelig mellem grupperne: 385/746 (51,3%) i den restriktive gruppe vs. 383/767 (49,9%) i standardgruppen. HRQoL og kognitiv funktion var også sammenlignelige mellem grupperne.

Studie III: Af 380 inviterede deltagere accepterede 264 at deltage i spørgeskemaundersøgelserne og 82 gav samtykke til interviews. Der deltog 217 internationale forskningspanelmedlemmer fra 14 lande i forskningsprocessen, hvoraf halvdelen var patienter eller pårørende. Efter Delphi-processens tre spørgeskemaundersøgelserunder og konsensusmøder var der konsensus om et sæt kerneeffektmål. Efter international validering af det oprindelige sæt kerneeffektmål blev der opnået konsensus om seks effektmål: overlevelse, fri af livsunderstøttende behandling, fri af delirium, udskrivelse fra hospital, HRQoL og kognitiv funktion.

Konklusioner

Den systematiske oversigtsartikel og metaanalyse afslørede en høj potentiel risiko for selektionsbias, da mange studier primært baserede sig på fuldstændige besvarelser, hvilket betød eksklusion af frafaldne og afdøde forsøgsdeltagere. Denne tilgang udelukker vigtige data, påvirker fortolkningen af resultater og begrænser indsigt i patientvigtige effektmål. Transparens i rapportering og analyse er afgørende for at fremme patientcentreret forskning.

CLASSIC-studiet viste sammenlignelig et-års dødelighed, HRQoL og kognitiv funktion mellem den restriktive gruppe og standardgruppen. Det tyder på, at restriktiv væsketerapi er en sikker strategi for intensivpatienter med septisk shock.

Det internationalt validerede sæt kerneeffektmål for voksne intensivpatienter inkluderer overlevelse, fri af livsunderstøttende behandling, fri af delirium, udskrivelse fra hospital, HRQoL og kognitiv funktion. I fremtidige studier bør der etableres konsensus om, hvordan disse effektmål bør måles.

List of abbreviations

- AID-ICU* Agents Intervening against Delirium – Intensive Care Unit
- CENTRAL* Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials
- CINAHL* Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature
- CLASSIC* Conservative versus Liberal Approach to fluid therapy of Septic Shock in Intensive Care
- CI* Confidence Interval
- COMET* Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials
- COMS* Core outcome measurement set
- CONSORT* Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trial
- COS-STAR* Core Outcome set-STAndards for Reporting
- COSMIN* Consensus-based Standard for the selection of health Measurement INstruments
- CRIC* Collaboration of Research in Intensive Care
- EMBASE* Excerpta Medica Database
- EQ-5D-5L* EQ-5D 5-levels
- EQ-VAS* EQ visual analogue scale
- ESM* Electronic Supplemental Material
- FACTT* The Fluid and Catheter Treatment Trial
- GRADE* Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation
- GRIPP2-SF* Guidance for Reporting Involvement of Patients and Public vs 2 Short Form
- HRQoL* Health-related Quality of Life
- ICU* Intensive Care Unit
- INCEPT* Intensive Care Platform Trial
- IQR* Interquartile Range
- IV* Intravenous
- LMIC* Low Middle-Income Country
- MAP* Mean arterial pressure
- MCID* Minimal clinical important difference
- MD* Mean difference
- Mini MoCA* Mini Montreal Cognitive Assessment
- MMSE* Mini-Mental State Examination

P Probability

PARAMEDIC Prehospital Assessment of the Role of Adrenaline: Measuring the Effectiveness of Drug Administration in Cardiac Arrest

PhD Doctor of Philosophy

PICO Patient, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome

PICS Post Intensive Care Syndrome

PICS-F Post Intensive Care Syndrome in Family

PPI Patient and Public Involvement

PRACTICE Physical Rehabilitation Core Outcomes in Critical illness

PRISMA Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-analysis

PRO Patient-reported outcome

PROSPERO Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews

PTSS Post-Traumatic Stress Symptoms

QoL Quality of life

RBANS Repeatable Battery for the Assessment of Neuropsychological Status

RD Risk difference

RCT Randomised clinical trial

REM Random effects model

REMAP Randomised, Embedded, Multi-factorial, Adaptive Platform Trials

RoB Risk of Bias

RR Relative risk

SDC Supplemental Digital Content

SF-36 Short Form 36 items

SMS-ICU Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit

SR Systematic review

SRMA Systematic review meta-analysis

SPIRIT-PRO Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials

TICS Telephone Interview for Cognitive Status

WHO World Health Organization

Background

The story of intensive care

Florence Nightingale.

Photo: Wikimedia Commons. Retrieved 11 November 2024

from https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Florence_Nightingale

Florence Nightingale, the 'Lady with the Lamp', was a prime mover for professional nursing and care improvement. She was the first to organise admitted wounded soldiers according to severity of illness during the Crimean war in the 1850s. She did this by placing the sickest patients closest to the staff making observation easier. This was the beginning of critical care nursing [1, 2].

One century later, in 1953, the first intensive care unit (ICU) or 'shock ward' was opened at 'Kommunehospitalet' in Copenhagen, Denmark, following the Polio epidemic [3].

The year before, a girl named Vivi Ebert was dying from Polio at this hospital [4, 5]. Anaesthesiology Bjørn Ibsen, experienced in ventilation via tracheostomy, had been invited to assist polio patients suffering from respiratory failure due to paralysis and Vivi was his first case.

For two days, Bjørn Ibsen used mechanical ventilation with positive pressure to help her breath, sedating her to enable full ventilation. He also cleared her airways for mucus, all while observing her carbon dioxide and oxygen levels. Vivi's cyanosis subsided, and her skin returned to a healthy red colour as she regained consciousness. This groundbreaking success became the standard treatment for polio patients with respiratory failure and was later adapted for other patients with similar conditions.

Based solely on a case report indicating improved clinical outcomes, with stabilised levels of carbon dioxide, oxygen, and survival, Bjørn Ibsen's approach to respiratory failure treatment was rapidly adopted, reducing mortality from 87% to 40% [6]. Vivi was on the ventilator for 7 years before she was discharged. She never became independent or able to take care of herself, but she was happy, even though she had to sit in a wheelchair, unable to walk or use her arms. She passed away 31 years old [5].

Blegdamshospitalet, Copenhagen, 1953. This was during the Polio epidemic with manual ventilation of the children suffering from respiratory failure.

Photo: Medical Museion, University of Copenhagen (reproduced with permission).

Since the 1950s, the ICU setting has evolved to treat all critically ill patients with advanced medical expertise, specialised nursing care, and continuous monitoring. Equipped with sophisticated technology and organ support, ICUs provide essential care in life-threatening situations, playing a pivotal role in managing complex health emergencies [2]. Treatments have been adapted to the ICU with a pathophysiological and physiological rationale as justification for introducing it in practice, as e.g. hemodynamic treatment for septic shock [7].

Sepsis

Septic shock is a severe and life-threatening condition characterised by organ dysfunction due to an uncontrolled and dysregulated response of the body to an infection [8, 9]. This critical state is a common reason for ICU admissions underscoring its impact on healthcare systems globally [10]. Sepsis, which can progress to septic shock if not treated immediately and effectively, is a leading cause of mortality in hospitals, contributing to one in every three hospital deaths [11]. Alarming, on a global scale, sepsis accounts for one in five deaths, highlighting its role as a substantial public health challenge. Furthermore, sepsis is the leading cause of critical illness unrelated to cardiac conditions emphasising its widespread and devastating consequences on both patients and healthcare resources [11–13].

Surviving critical illness

The survival curve in the ICU is generally improving and there is a greater emphasis on understanding the long-term outcomes for those who survive, alongside the societal impacts and the pressure on healthcare systems, including primary care [14].

In 2023, 26,447 patients were admitted to an ICU in Denmark with an overall 30-day mortality of 20% [15]. The 90-day mortality for adult acutely admitted patients in a pantoprazole trial was about 30% [16], but for adult patients with septic shock in a transfusion trial the 90-day mortality was 43% to 45% [17].

Admission to an ICU with critical illness—such as septic shock—is associated with a high burden for patients, family members, and society [14, 18–22]. The trajectory of critical illness for ICU survivors is associated with continuous high risk of death after discharge and negative long-term effects such as new or aggravated physical, cognitive and mental disabilities affecting health-related quality of life (HRQoL) [23–25]. These effects might persist for more than a year after ICU admission [18].

The physical disabilities prevalence ranges from 25% to 100% depending on the assessment method, time of measurement, and whether individuals are predisposed to adverse short- and long-term outcomes [26–29]. Age, weight, comorbidities, mechanical ventilation, length of ICU stay, and sepsis are among other important risk factors [26, 30, 31].

New or worsened *cognitive impairment* is experienced by 10% to 78% of critically ill patients one year after their ICU admissions [14]. This impairment often affects memory, concentration, attention, and executive function diminishing quality of life (QoL) [32, 33]. It also impacts patients' ability to adapt and resume daily activities, often leading them to develop personal strategies to cope with these challenges [34]. Longer duration of delirium is a risk factor for severe cognitive impairment [32]. Patients with sepsis and septic shock also have a higher risk of developing cognitive impairment which might not be reversible [18, 35].

Impaired mental health is an intrusive problem and can be persistent for years after an ICU stay [36, 37]. Twenty percent describe post-traumatic stress symptoms after one year and between 30% and 50% experience anxiety and depression. The conditions are overlapping and all together have a negative impact on HRQoL [14, 18, 38].

To address long-term physical, cognitive, mental, and general health problems of ICU survivors, Needham and colleagues agreed on the terminology 'post intensive care syndrome' (PICS). PICS refers to new or worsened post ICU impairments that patients and their family members deal with when discharged from hospital and for a long time after—if not chronic [39]. Figure 1 illustrates both the patients' and the caregivers' transition through critical illness [40].

Abbreviations: *ICU*: Intensive care unit

Figure 1. The trajectory of critical illness and transition from a previous state to the state after ICU

Reproduced with permission [40] [Haines et al. Crit Care Med 2021, 49:1923–1931.

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There is an increasing awareness that family members of ICU patients also suffer mental- and social health challenges referred to as 'post intensive care syndrome in family' (PICS-F) [39]. These individuals often assume substantial responsibility during the transition of care following critical illness. This can alter their role as family member for a long time and unfortunately few, if any, resources are allocated to prevent PICS-F [40].

How patients and caregivers cope after critical illness, and how they adapt to or accept a new reality, can greatly influence the transition from a normal health state to a new and possibly chronic situation (Figure 1). For example, Vivi Ebert, who developed paralysis after surviving respiratory failure caused by polio, faced such a transition [42]. Her family had to adapt to this new situation as well. According to historical records, Vivi remained happy suggesting that she likely employed effective coping mechanisms, possibly with the support of her family [40, 43, 44].

ICU trials and patient-important outcomes

Since the 1990s, a more critical approach to treatment development and research has emerged emphasising the need for evidence-based treatments in the ICU [45]. In the years following 2000, a new 'less is more' approach aimed to reduce unnecessary treatments which do not benefit patients. These treatments only consume cost that clinicians could otherwise use more effectively [7, 46].

The ICU is a highly specialised environment able to support most organ systems, but only 10% of treatments are based on solid evidence [45, 47]. It is estimated that 20% to 30% of treatments are without effect and could be saved to the benefit of both patients and clinicians, and 10% are harmful [48]. This emphasises the need for high quality ICU trials.

The parental model has influenced the tradition in the outcomes assessed in ICU trials as the clinicians were centred around and appraised by patients and family members [49]. The clinician's approach was disease oriented evaluating physiological outcomes [50], as they were assumed to impact mortality and quality of life (as a surrogate outcome) [51]. This explains the selection of outcomes and hence the tradition that patient-important outcomes were to be objective and immediately measurable [50]. However, the outcomes should also be patient-important as understood by the patients. Today, there is an increased awareness of the limitations to the clinician's approach, and that outcomes should be ensured to be important to the patients as well [14]. In practice, patient-important outcomes are rarely among the primary outcomes of an intensive care trial, and if, it would be survival status [52].

A scoping review examining the use of patient-important outcomes in randomised clinical trials (RCTs) conducted in 2013 found that 78% of these outcomes focused on mortality [23]. In contrast, only 22% addressed QoL, functional, cognitive, or neurological outcomes assessed after ICU discharge. The median time for follow-up was 12 months (interquartile range (IQR) 5 to 12 months) [23]. Patient-reported outcomes (PRO), being the patient assessing and reporting their own outcomes, is the general approach to assess patient-important outcomes in clinical trials systematically and consistently [53].

In ICU trials mortality is the most frequently assessed outcome and most often used as the primary outcome [54, 55], but it should be complemented by long-term outcomes focusing on patient-important outcomes to fully capture the impact of the treatment effect. However, this might not be feasible when doing investigator-initiated large, pragmatical, and late-phase trials on a low budget [54, 56].

Outcomes

RCTs are the golden standard for obtaining high quality evidence, but the quality partly depends on the chosen outcomes and how they are obtained [51, 56]:

- Outcomes should be assessed with high validity and precision
- Outcomes should be associated to the investigated intervention
- Outcomes should be easy to measure and to adapt to the routines of clinical care
- Outcomes should be meaningful to clinicians to impact clinical practice
- Outcomes should be meaningful to patients (and family members)

Health-related quality of life

QoL is a broadly defined term covering overall wellbeing [53]. The World Health Organization (WHO) defined QoL as a 'State of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing, and not merely absence of disease' [57]. A subjective state that differs from individual to individual and the context. HRQoL is restricted to selected domains and represents a distinct aspect of wellbeing that influences overall QoL as impacted by health conditions, but it needs to be assessable in clinical medicine and trials [53]. The dimensions could span multiple domains. Generally, the instruments for measuring HRQoL are multidimensional covering physical, emotional, and social functioning, excluding cognitive function [53].

Over the years, instruments have been developed, starting with Karnofsky's Performance Scale in 1947 – defining a scale from 0 (equal to death) to 100 (being normal without complaints and evidence of disease)

to more distinguishing instruments assessing physical, psychological, and social dimensions with an additional overall health state rating [53]. HRQoL instruments can obtain multidimensional patient perspectives to be used in clinical trials and for health cost analysis, but they can also be used for other purposes [53].

In summary, HRQoL aims to capture not only the objective aspects of a person’s health but also their subjective experience. This includes perception of physical, emotional, and social functioning. By focusing on self-reported data, HRQoL assessments highlight personal experience and individual wellbeing, offering a more comprehensive and holistic approach to evaluating health outcomes [53].

Health-related quality of life assessment in intensive care trials

Since 1986 clinical trials in general have increasingly assessed HRQoL using PROs with patients reporting their subjective health state to ensure a PRO [53]. Mortality was the most frequent primary outcome in ICU trials [13, 50, 56], but HRQoL became important in order to evaluate the aftermath of disease and experimental treatments in general. This helped to make sure that the treatments were at least not harming patients’ HRQoL afterwards [42, 45]. HRQoL is the most frequent assessed long-term PRO in intensive care trials, and it is negatively associated with disabilities and impairments among ICU survivors [52, 59, 60].

A systematic review concerning ICU trials assessing patient-important outcomes (not including mortality) demonstrated that HRQoL was the most frequently assessed PRO (65%), and the most used HRQoL instruments were; the Short Form (SF)-36 [23, 61], and the EQ-5D-5 level (EQ-5D-5L) [23, 62] (Table 1).

Concerning the psychometric properties, both questionnaires have been validated for their general use [63–66]. They are both multidimensional and include physical disabilities and mental health, but they do not include cognitive function as the last domain of PICS [58].

Table 1. Overview of the SF-36 and EQ-5D questionnaires

Questionnaires	SF-36 [61, 67]	EQ-5D and EQ-VAS [62, 68, 69]
Population	Generic, non-disease specific	Generic, non-disease specific
Dimensions/concepts	Physical and mental health dimension consisting of 8 health concepts: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Physical functioning 2. Role limitations because of physical health problems 3. Bodily pain 4. Social functioning 5. General mental health being psychological distress and psychological wellbeing 6. Role limitations because of emotional problems 7. Vitality concerning energy and fatigue 8. General health perception 	EQ-5D Physical, mental, and social functioning by 5 dimensions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mobility 2. Self-care 3. Usual activities 4. Pain or discomfort 5. Anxiety or depression EQ-VAS <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Current health state
Items (questions)	36	5 + 1
Points	From 3 to 5 options for each item.	EQ-5D-3L: three levels/options for each item

Questionnaires	SF-36 [61, 67]	EQ-5D and EQ-VAS [62, 68, 69]
		EQ-5D-5L: five levels/options for each item. EQ-VAS: there is 1 option
Total range	0 to 100 (A higher number indicates better health)	An index value using preferences from a country specific value set (if available). EQ-5D-5L: -0.76 to 1.00 using the Danish index value based on the Danish general population (a higher number indicates better health) [69]. EQ-VAS: 0 to 100 The imaginable health state going from 0 (worst) to 100 (best).
General population		For the Danish general population, they had an overall index value of 0.9 (standard deviation (SD) =0.16) in 2021 [69].
Possible informants	Patients Proxy (closest family member)	Patients Proxy (closest family member)
Possible methods	Telephone Paper	Telephone Paper
Nonsurvivors	Death equals 0	EQ-5D: Death equals 0, and below 0 being worse than death. EQ-VAS: Death is not defined

Abbreviations: *EQ-5D-5L*: EQ-5D 5-levels, *EQ-VAS*: EQ visual analogue scale, *SF-36*: Short Form 36 items, *SD*: standard deviation.

Long-term HRQoL

Assessing long-term follow-up presents important challenges, particularly in relation to patients lost to follow-up and nonsurvivors [23, 52, 70, 71]. Collecting PROs is especially difficult since reaching patients can be complicated by factors like admission to other facilities, emigration, or other unknown reasons. Additionally, patient deterioration or death adds further obstacles [72].

Psychometric concerns, such as construct validity, are also important. Lengthy assessment instrument can be burdensome and might lead to higher non-response rate [53]. Missing data can compromise trial interpretations, introducing bias from attrition [73, 74]. More critically, missing data from patients with extreme outcomes could potentially affect the trial result [75, 76].

In a post hoc analysis of an RCT comparing higher versus lower blood transfusion triggers in septic shock patients, SF-36 HRQoL responses one year after randomisation were compared between respondents and non-respondents using registry data [17, 75, 77]. Non-respondents who survived follow-up were associated with being younger, sicker (more days at hospital), and more likely to live without a partner [75]. This suggests that missing data might not be random, posing a risk of selection bias that could hamper the HRQoL results [76].

Missing long-term trial data and lost to follow-up are well-known issues that could include risk of bias [23, 52]. While missing data is less concerning if under 5% or missing completely at random [73], rates exceeding 20% could undermine the results [73]. The nature of missing data for HRQoL outcomes likely falls in the spectrum of missing at random and not missing at random, raising further concerns [73, 78].

Non-survivors

A structured methodology review of RCTs assessing functional outcomes in high mortality patients found that most analyses included only survivors [55]. However, excluding non-survivors when assessing HRQoL (truncation due to death) might distort the treatment effect, especially if the intervention impacts mortality [55]. Scenarios could include patients who survive unaffected by allocation ('always survivors'), those who benefit from intervention allocation, but would die under the control allocation ('mortality benefiteres'), those who would die regardless of allocation ('always diers'), and finally, those who die before follow-up caused by the intervention allocation, but would survive under the control allocation ('specials') [55]. These scenarios illustrate how the treatment effect might be influenced by underlying factors when an analysis only includes survivors.

Including non-survivors could provide a more accurate and transparent understanding of the treatment effect. How missing data, non-respondents, and non-survivors are managed in ICU HRQoL trials remains unclear. Additionally, shorter questionnaires like the EQ-5D might yield higher response rates than longer ones like the SF-36. Also, HRQoL is often a secondary outcome and retention efforts might be limited, affecting response rates [79, 80].

The concerns surrounding the assessment and management of HRQoL are not exclusive to this outcome. They should also be considered for other long-term patient-important outcomes, and PRO [81]. Ideally there should be consensus on the same long-term outcomes within the ICU setting, and there should be strategies to address methodological challenges [81].

Collaboration of Research in Intensive Care

The partners behind the research network 'Collaboration of Research in Intensive Care' (CRIC) aim to improve evidence-based medicine, and they have conducted large, pragmatic, clinical intensive care investigator-initiated trials to bring value to the clinical practice and the patients. They have investigated daily routines as, e.g. fluids for resuscitation and blood transfusion thresholds for patients with septic shock [82, 83]. The original CRIC network was initiated 10 years ago and over the years the importance of assessing long-term patient-important outcomes has come into focus, and they are now prioritised among other outcomes in the CRIC trials [84, 85].

Core outcome set

High-quality research in the intensive care setting (or any clinical setting) often relies on RCTs or systematic reviews with meta-analyses to provide robust answers to research questions or assess treatment effects, especially when outcomes can be synthesised [54, 81, 86–88]. A scoping review focusing on patient-important outcomes, aside from mortality, identified 103 different functional, cognitive, and neurological outcomes, as well as 29 different HRQoL outcomes [70].

The variability in outcomes and measurement methods across ICU trials hampers the quality of evidence, making both meta-analyses and any comparison of results challenging [56, 70, 89, 90]. A core outcome set, defined as a minimum set of standardised outcomes, is recommended to be consistently assessed within a specific health condition area [91]. Using standardised core outcomes could improve the evidence of research by making it easier to achieve the highest level of evidence and, if performed well, ensure a high certainty of evidence [54, 87, 92, 93].

This underscores the importance of developing and using core outcome sets and measurement sets, which can be tailored for, e.g. clinical trials interventions, or routine care [91, 94, 95]. Currently, existing core outcome sets for critically ill patients are disease specific or focused on particular interventions [96]. However, there is no standardised core outcome set and measurement set for the general adult critically ill patients [9, 97].

A core outcome set and measurement set developed by Needham and colleagues focused on patients with respiratory failure, a subgroup within the heterogenous ICU population [98, 99] (Figure 2). The development process involved patients and family members (n=19) together with clinicians (n=19), funding organisations (n=4), and researchers (n=35) [98]. This level of involvement ensured that the outcomes were meaningful and relevant to patients and their families [100, 101]. However, the measurement set faced challenges due to concerns about psychometric properties, and therefore several outcomes lacked consensus on which measurement instruments to use [99].

Figure 2. Core outcomes for patients with respiratory failure (top row) [98], and a modified version (bottom row).

Elements of the core outcomes were considered in the CRIC trials when evaluating which patient-important outcomes to assess. Given concerns about the number of outcomes, the HRQoL outcome was utilised as an umbrella outcome encompassing multiple core outcomes (Figure 2, bottom row). Nevertheless, there remains a need for a core outcome and measurement set specifically developed for the general ICU population.

The CRIC trial ‘Conservative versus Liberal Approach to fluid therapy of Septic Shock in Intensive Care’ (CLASSIC) investigated the recommended use of intravenous (IV) fluid therapy as a central treatment strategy in septic shock, as the evidence on fluid management was of low quality and quantity [21, 22, 102]. It was planned to assess long-term HRQoL and cognitive function at 1-year after randomisation [103], due to the concern that a liberal use of fluids might impact both HRQoL and cognitive function [104, 105]. This had not been assessed in previous fluids trials [106].

Patient and public involvement in health research

The tradition of involving patients and other relevant stakeholders in health research is recent, particularly in the intensive care setting and within networks like CRIC. However, given that the patients and their family members often suffer long-term consequences from the critical illness period in the ICU, including PICS and PICS-F, their insights could offer valuable perspectives for health research.

Globally, the past decade has seen an growing interest in patient and public involvement (PPI) and engagement in health research [107]. The emphasises is on conducting research ‘with’ the patients, rather than ‘about’ them, by fostering democratic interactions and forming an equal partnership between stakeholders [108, 109]. While PPI can be time consuming and introduce challenges that might slow down the research process, it is ultimately rewarding as it provides valuable perspectives that researchers could overlook on their own (as illustrated in the cover image) [110].

In the context of clinical trials, there is an ethical responsibility to ensure that research is not only clinically relevant to professionals but also meaningful to patients [97]. Patient involvement must be thoughtful and authentic, rather than superficial or driven by tokenism [111]. A meta-epidemiological review on PPI in larger ICU RCTs revealed that only 20% of trials incorporated PPI, primarily in trial design, discussions, and interviews [112, 113].

PPI has the potential to significantly enhance the research process by providing insights into which outcomes are truly important to patients. Involving patients alongside other relevant stakeholders, such as family members, clinicians, and researchers, can enhance decision-making, and specifically it can support the creation of core outcome sets which include patient-important outcomes [109, 114, 115].

Overall aim of this thesis

To improve long-term outcomes, we need to consider the trajectory of critical illness, but we also need to consider the methodological issues related to ensuring long-term results are not hampered by non-respondents and non-survivors. Furthermore, we should consider what are patient-important outcomes to the patients by asking them.

The three studies in this thesis range from a meta perspective where existing methods are discussed, then a specific long-term follow-up of an RCT in which methods to minimise bias were conducted, and then finally looking forward by involving patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers in the discussion of what should be general core outcomes to assess in all intensive care trials in the ICU setting.

- Study I** Conduct a systematic review to investigate how HRQoL outcomes in RCTs within the ICU setting have been methodologically addressed, particularly in relation to missing data and nonsurvivors.

- Study II** A long-term follow-up of the CLASSIC trial evaluating mortality, HRQoL, and cognitive function 1-year after randomisation to restrictive vs. standard fluid therapy in the ICU.

- Study III** Create a core outcome set for adult general ICU patients in a process involving patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers.

STUDY I

**A systematic review of health-related quality of life
as an outcome in randomised clinical trials in ICU**

Key information for Study I

Non-respondents

All eligible trial participants who were invited for HRQoL follow-up and were alive at the time of follow-up but did not complete/respond the HRQoL questionnaire at that time point were classified as non-respondents. This could be due to factors such as emigration, withdrawal of consent, loss to follow-up, or other reason. Trial participants who did not receive the intervention were not categorised as non-respondents, in alignment with the modified intention-to-treat principle [116].

Non-survivors

All trial participants who died before the HRQoL follow-up time point.

Respondents

Trial participants who answered the HRQoL questionnaire (patients' or by proxy).

Multiple imputation

An advanced analysis conducted by using all available data associated with the missing data. Different characteristics, such as baseline characteristics and patient outcomes with missing HRQoL, will be utilised to predict the score of the missing values. The analysis is repeated multiple times comparing the dataset with patients with fully obtained HRQoL. This could be repeated 50.000 times trying to come as close as possible to the true value [73, 74, 117, 118]. In addition, sensitivity analysis could be used to test the rigour of the results by presenting other scenarios or possible results for the dataset, e.g. choosing the best/worst case scenario compared with the worst/best case scenario to reveal the most extreme variation of an outcome [119].

Non-response for health-related quality of life outcomes in ICU patients: A systematic review of the reporting in randomised trials

Aim

In Study I (Paper I and II) [120, 121], our objective was to describe the extent and pattern of missing HRQoL data in ICU RCTs and to detail the statistical approaches used to address both missing data and non-survivors.

Objectives

Table 2. Overview of the primary, secondary, and tertiary objectives in Study I.

Primary objectives	<i>Proportion of non-respondents at follow-up</i> <i>Proportion of non-survivors at follow-up</i>
Secondary objectives	<i>Proportion of baseline characteristics between respondents and non-respondents</i> <i>Proportion of analytic strategies performed to handle non-respondents and non-survivors</i>
Tertiary objectives	Proportion of non-respondents in the following subgroups: <i>Risk of bias (low vs some concerns vs high)</i> <i>Trial size (small trials $n \leq 100$ vs large trials $n > 100$)</i> <i>Outcome level (primary vs secondary vs tertiary)</i> <i>Length of tool (short being EQ-5D vs long being SF-36/RAND-36)</i> <i>Follow-up time in days (≤ 90 vs > 90 vs ≤ 180 or > 180)</i>

Abbreviations: SF-36/RAND-36: Short form 36 items

Methods

Study design

We performed a systematic review and meta-analysis of RCTs (paper II) in line with a published protocol (paper I) [121], which was registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) [120]. The protocol followed the Cochrane Collaboration recommendations [122], and we assessed risk of bias using the Risk of Bias 2.0 tool (RoB 2) [76]. We reported the systematic review in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) 2020 statement.

Eligibility criteria for the included RCTs:

Population: Adult ICU patients

Intervention: Trial intervention administered or initiated during the ICU admission

Comparator: No limitations

Outcome: HRQoL reported as an outcome assessed by any tool

RCTs where full text was unobtainable were excluded.

Search strategy

The Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL) in The Cochrane Library, PubMed, Excerpta Medica Database (Embase) Ovid, and Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) were searched. We also searched reference lists of related RCTs, systematic reviews, meta-analyses and editorials concerning HRQoL follow-up. The initial search was performed 6 September 2019, a second search was undertaken 6 January 2022, and the last search was updated 3 October 2022.

Data collection

A minimum of two to three authors independently performed the title and abstract screening, full-text screening, data extraction, and RoB 2 assessment. Any discrepancies were discussed with supervisors.

Risk of bias assessment

For every trial we assessed RoB for the HRQoL outcome using the treatment assignment, e.g. the intention-to-treat principle [76].

Statistical analysis

As outcomes were related to HRQoL assessment, there could be multiple outcomes within a single trial. Each follow-up time point or use of different HRQoL assessment tool was considered an additional outcome for the RCT.

Trial characteristics and proportions for both non-respondents and non-survivors were descriptively presented using medians with IQR as well as full ranges.

We used random effects models in the meta-analysis of proportions, based on the assumption that the proportions would vary across RCTs. This approach allowed us to calculate mean values along with a 95% confidence interval (CI) to account for between-study variability.

For the subgroup analyses an absolute risk difference (RD) between the subgroups were performed together with a test-of interaction probability (P) value. As it was possible that several outcomes were recorded from the same trial, the mean numerators/denominators across the outcomes from the same RCT were used for meta-analysis.

Results

Trial characteristics

A total of 196 outcomes from 88 RCTs published between the years 2002 and 2022 were included. The RCTs included 20 to 7000 participants and assessed 1 to 9 HRQoL outcomes, with a median follow-up time of 180 days, ranging from 0 to 1461 days.

Assessment of risk of bias

Among the 88 RCTs, 22% were adjudicated potentially overall 'low risk of bias', 17% 'some concerns', and 61% had potentially overall 'high risk of bias' (Figure 3). The 'high risk of bias's were mainly due to missing HRQoL data (above 20% of missing data), and due to not blinding the outcome assessor, who was typically the patient or proxy rather than the trial person.

Figure 3. Distribution of the risk of bias assessment for the 88 RCTs included in Study I. Reproduced from Paper II, Page 846 [121] [Kjaer et al. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand* 2023, 67 (<https://doi.org/10.1111/aas.14250>)] with copyright permission via CC BY NC license 4.0 [41]

Objectives

For 50% of the outcomes, the handling of non-respondents was reported. In 20% of the trials, potential risk of bias due to non-respondents was considered in the paper. In 48/196 (24%) of outcomes, non-respondents were included in the analysis, while 57/196 (29%) outcomes included non-survivors.

Primary objectives

Among the 76 RCTs that reported non-respondents (12 RCTs did not report non-respondents), the crude median proportion of non-respondents was 20% (IQR 9% to 38%). The mean proportion estimated by meta-analysis was 15%, (95% CI 11% to 19%).

Among the 81 RCTs that reported non-survivors (7 RCTs did not report survival status), the crude median proportion of non-survivors was 27% (IQR 16% to 38%). The mean proportion estimated by meta-analysis was 19% (95% CI 15% to 25%).

Secondary objectives

Baseline characteristics were compared between respondents and non-respondents in 17% of the outcomes. For 80% of the outcomes, complete case analysis was used (or not reported) and the remaining 20% used multiple imputation. For 78% of the outcomes, non-survivors were not included in the analysis.

Tertiary objectives

For the subgroup analyses the proportion of non-respondents based on the follow-up time was statistically significant with an RD on 24% (95% CI 16% to 28%) for follow-up time above 180 days, and 3% (95% CI -5% to 8%) for more than 90 days and ≤ 180 days compared with ≤ 90 days ($P < 0.001$). The distribution of non-respondents over follow-up time is also illustrated in Figure 2 in Paper II.

There was a not statistically significant association towards a higher non-response rate for:

- High risk of bias compared with low risk of bias (P=0.096)
- For HRQoL as a secondary or tertiary outcome compared with the primary outcome (P=0.05)
- For longer HRQoL questionnaires compared with shorter ones (P=0.053)

Finally, there was no association between trial size and the proportion of non-respondents (P=0.786).

Conclusions

In this systematic review we found that missingness due to death or non-response was substantial for HRQoL outcomes in ICU RCTs. There was an association between longer follow-up time and higher non-response rate. There was a lack of transparency in the handling of non-respondents which weakens the interpretation of the results for this patient-important outcome.

STUDY II

Long-term follow-up of the CLASSIC trial

Key information for Study II

The Conservative versus Liberal Approach to Fluid Therapy of Septic Shock in Intensive Care (CLASSIC) trial was a European, open-labelled, investigator initiated, parallel-group, and analyst blinded trial randomising 1554 participants by a 1:1 computer generated allocation sequence list with stratification for metastatic or haematologic cancer and trial site [103, 123, 124].

The CLASSIC protocol was published and covered all trial details [103]. The primary outcome for the CLASSIC trial was ‘all-cause mortality’ at day 90 and no statistical significant difference between restricted and standard IV fluid therapy for patients with septic shock was found [123]. Table 3 and 4 describe the inclusion and exclusion criteria together with a short description of the intervention.

Table 3. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are listed in the table, reproduced from the protocol [103].

Inclusion criteria fulfilled for all trial participants:	Exclusion criteria
Age ≥18 years	Septic shock for >12 hours when screening for inclusion (septic shock as defined in the inclusion criteria)
Admitted or planned admitted to the ICU regardless of trial participation	Life-threatening bleeding with need of blood transfusion as defined by the clinicians
Septic shock defined according to the Sepsis-3 criteria [21]: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site of infection or positive blood culture are either suspected or confirmed • Infusion of vasopressor or inotrope agent are ongoing to maintain a mean arterial blood pressure (MAP) ≥65mmHg • Plasma lactate of ≥2 mmol/L within the last three hours 	Acute burn injury of >10% of the body surface area
Received minimum 1 litre of IV fluid administered 24 hours before screening. IV fluids include all crystalloids, colloids or blood products including medication and nutrition.	Known pregnancy
	Unable to obtain consent before inclusion as per the model approved for the specific site

Table 4. Intervention and recommended fluid administration reproduced from the protocol, for the two groups in the CLASSIC trial: restrictive-fluid group and the standard-fluid (liberal approach) group [103].

Restrictive-fluid group	Standard-fluid group
1. Severe hypoperfusion defined by either: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lactate ≥4 mmol/liter • Mean arterial pressure (MAP) <50 mmHg despite infusion of vasoactive agent • Mottling beyond the edge of the kneecap [125] • Severe oliguria (<0.1 ml/kg/hour) in the first 2 hours 	1. Haemodynamic improvement in parameters according to the Surviving Sepsis Campaign guideline [21]
2. Documented fluid loss (e.g. drain loss or diarrhoea)	2. Documented or expected fluid loss
3. Dehydration or electrolyte deficiencies that could not be corrected enterally	3. Dehydration or electrolyte deficiencies
4. IV fluid intake of <1 litre per day, and no possibility of giving the participants enteral fluids	4. Maintenance fluids if the ICU used this as the usual care

Trial registration

EudraCT number: 2018-000404-42

ClinicalTrials.gov identifier: NCT03668236

Long-term effects of restriction of intravenous fluid in adult ICU patients with septic shock

Aims

In Study II (Paper III and IV) [124, 126], the aim was to evaluate the impact of restrictive versus standard IV therapy on long-term patient-important outcomes, including HRQoL, cognitive function, and all-cause mortality at 1-year post-randomisation.

Methods

Study design

We conducted a 1-year follow-up study of the CLASSIC trial with a predefined protocol and analysis plan [124, 126], and reported according to the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trial (CONSORT) 2010 Statement.

Sites and patients

There were 31 ICUs across 8 European countries enrolling 1554 patients from November 2018 to November 2021. We included 1554 patients with septic shock following the sepsis-3 criteria [21], with verified fluid resuscitation of minimum 1 litre IV fluid in the last 24 h, and no longer than 12 h from when septic shock commenced.

Outcomes

In the CLASSIC protocol we prespecified the secondary outcomes planned to be assessed 1-year after randomisation; all-cause mortality, HRQoL using the EQ-5D-5L and EQ-VAS, and cognitive function using the Mini MoCA test (see Figure 4). The outcomes were obtained by blinded trial personal who were trained in obtaining HRQoL and certified in testing for cognitive function. This was outlined in a standard operating procedure (Paper IV, Electronic Supplementary Material (ESM), Page 6) to ensure consistent data collection.

Retention strategies: We aimed for a high response rate and repeatedly attempted to contact participants for at least a 4-week period from the 1-year follow-up date. We monitored the process at the coordinating site in Copenhagen, Denmark, to support and assist sites with the follow-up if there were a lack of resources, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Statistical analysis plan

Deviations from the pre-planned analysis plan [124] are described in the ESM [126].

For the primary analysis we included non-survivors using the value 0, equal to death, for EQ-5D-5L and using the worst score, corresponding to '0', for EQ-VAS and for Mini MoCA.

We adjusted all outcomes for stratification variables. We also did G-computation with 50,000 bootstrap resamples for both the logistic and linear regressions to present results as risk differences (RDs), relative risks (RRs), mean differences (MDs), and ratios of means with 99% confidence intervals.

As we had more than 5% missing outcome data for EQ-5D-5L, EQ-VAS, and Mini MoCA, we performed a Little's test to check whether missing outcome data were not missing completely at random. To address the issue of missing outcome data, we employed multiple imputation using the predictive mean matching method, generating 50 imputed datasets for each of the two trial groups. The imputation model included stratification variables, baseline values, and outcomes. We did additional sensitivity analyses.

Figure 4. Description of long-term outcomes assessed in the CLASSIC trial

Outcomes	All-cause mortality	HRQoL	Cognitive function
Domains assessed	Survivorship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility • Self-care • Usual activities • Pain and discomfort • Anxiety and depression 	Cognitive function by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attention - Executive functions and language - Orientation - Memory
Data collection	Medical records	Telephone interview of participant or proxy	Telephone interview of participant
Outcome measure	Yes or no	EQ-5D-5L: -0.76 to 1.00 ^a EQ-VAS: 0 to 100	Mini MoCA: 0 to 30 If less than 30 points and less than 12 years of education the participants score was added with 1 point to compensate for the cognitive reserve associated with lower level of education, which could impact the cognitive function [35].
Non-survivors	-	EQ-5D-5L: 0 equal to death EQ-VAS: 0 being the worst score	Value: 0 being the worst score
Missing outcome data	Complete cases	>5% missing: - Little's test - Multiple imputation with additional sensitivity analyses	>5% missing: - Little's test - Multiple imputation with additional sensitivity analyses
Analyses	Logistic regression Kaplan-Meier survival curve	Linear regression Kryger Jensen and Lange test for P-values [127] Multiple imputation for the missing outcome data and sensitivity analyses	

Abbreviations: *EQ-5D-5L*: EQ-5D five-dimension, *EQ-VAS*: EQ visual analogue scale, *Mini MoCA*: Mini Montreal Cognitive Assessment test

^a Lowest negative value equals health state worse than death differs between value sets. This is for the Danish value set [69].

Results

After one year there were five patients withdrawn from the study population leaving 1549 participants included in the trial results [126]. Overall, balanced baseline characteristics were well balanced between groups.

Primary outcome

All-cause mortality

In the restrictive group 385 out of 767 (51.3%) died after one year compared with 383 out of 782 (49.9%) in the standard fluid group, resulting in an adjusted risk difference of 1.5% (99% CI, -4.8% to 7.8%) and a p-value=0.55.

HRQoL

The EQ-5D-5L index value was 0.00 (99% CI, 0.00 to 0.82) for the restrictive fluid group compared with 0.00 (99% CI 0.00 to 0.81) for the standard fluid group. The adjusted mean difference was 0.00 (99% CI, -0.06 to 0.05). Similarly, the EQ-VAS score was 0 (99% CI, 0 to 70) for the restrictive fluid group compared with 0 (99% CI, 0 to 70) for the standard fluid group. The adjusted mean difference was -0.65 (99% CI, -5.40 to 4.08) in the EQ-VAS score.

Cognitive function

The Mini MoCA test was 0 (99% CI, 0 to 22) for the restrictive fluid group compared with 0 (99% CI, 0 to 22) for the standard fluid group, resulting in an adjusted mean difference of -0.14 (99% CI, -1.59 to 1.31).

No statistically significant differences were observed in any of the outcomes between the restrictive and standard fluid groups.

Conclusions

In summary, restrictive IV fluid therapy led to similar survival rates, HRQoL, and cognitive function after one year in adult ICU patients with septic shock when compared to standard IV fluid therapy.

STUDY III

**Developing a core outcome set using modified
Delphi consensus process with additional
international validation**

Key information for Study III

The Intensive Care Platform Trial (INCEPT) was developed to assess the effects of interventions used in adults acutely admitted to the ICU [128, 129]. The wide-ranging nature of the platform trial served as a key motivation for the development of a universally applicable core outcome set for adult ICU patients.

Core outcome set

An agreed-upon standardised minimum set of core outcomes for a specific clinical area to be reported consistently [95].

Modified Delphi consensus process

The Delphi consensus process is a consensus method designed to achieve agreement through repeated anonymous feedback [130]. We used a modified version starting with a literature review to compile all relevant outcomes. This process was supplemented with interviews to inform the survey, which then provided repeated rounds of anonymous feedback [95, 131].

Nominal group technique

Another consensus method is the nominal group technique. Traditionally, this involves face-to-face meetings where individuals vote on the most important outcomes which are then shared with all other meeting members afterward [132, 133]. However, the nominal group technique can also be implemented in different ways.

We have used a nominal group technique within research panels to ensure that all participants were treated equally during the meetings with the opportunity to share their perspectives and listen to the views of others. Listening to the perspective of each participant and engaging in discussion is crucial for reaching consensus. Additionally, having face-to-face meetings with a focused agenda to reach consensus.

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Aims

In Study III (Paper V, VI, VII) [134–136] the aim was to develop a standardised core outcome set to be used in clinical intensive care trials concerning adult general ICU patients. We were encouraged to extend the scope of our protocol which initially only involved Danish participants [137, 138]. Therefore, we added an additional aim of doing an international validation of the initial core outcome set [135].

Methods

Study design

We conducted a core outcome set using a modified Delphi consensus process. The design consisted of multiple methods: literature review, surveys, semi-structured interviews, consensus meetings, and a pragmatic international validation of the established Danish core outcome set which was registered in the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) database. Figure 5 provides an overview of the process and the methods used. The protocol for the modified Delphi consensus process was published before initiating step 2, Figure 5 [134], and the amendment for the international validation was registered before initiating it (between step 3 and 4) [135].

Figure 5. Overview of the process for developing a core outcome set

Reproduced from Paper VII [136] [Kjaer et al. Registration at MedRxiv 2024, (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.05.29.24308094>)], open access registration, CC BY license 4.0 [41]

We developed the core outcome set in alignment with the COMET Handbook [95], and we reported according to the Core Outcome set-STANDards for Reporting (COS-STAR) statement [139] and Guidance for Reporting Involvement of Patients and the Public short form (GRIPP2-SF) [140].

Participants

Eligibility criteria for participants in the interviews, survey, and research panels were adults having a lived experience with the ICU setting (patients and family members) or a work relation with the ICU speciality.

Research panels

We established research panels to facilitate involvement of four essential categories of partners from the ICU setting:

1. Patients: persons with lived experience (adult survivors)
2. Family members to survivors or deceased patients
3. Clinicians: multi professional healthcare workers being medical doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, occupational therapists etc.
4. Researchers: multi professional as for clinicians

Survey and interview

We recruited patients and family members in the ICUs when obtaining consent or collecting data for 1-year follow-up on ICU trial participants or their family members. We aimed for diversity (when possible) using a matrix to be considered during recruitment in all four regions in Denmark (Table 5).

Table 5. The matrix used to aim for diversity of interview and survey participants

	Age*	Sex	Ethnicities	SMS-ICU score**	ICU length of stay***	Multi professions	Years affiliated with an ICU
Patients	X	X	X	X	X		
Family members	X	X	X		X		
Clinicians and researchers						X	X

ICU: intensive care unit, SMS-ICU: The Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit [141].

*Young (18 to 50 years), Middle age (51 to 75 years), and Old (More than 75)

** We aimed to achieve a balanced distribution of patients with higher mortality risk (≥ 17 , corresponding to a predicted 90-day mortality risk of 25.3% or higher) vs. lower risk (< 17 corresponding to a predicted 90-day mortality risk of 22.8% or lower) [141].

*** Less than 7 days or 7 days and above

Clinicians and researchers were recruited through clinical and research networks associated with the study's steering committee.

Involvement

As illustrated in Figure 5 there were parties involved in the entire process from initial literature review to the final consensus meeting agreeing on the revised core outcome set.

Consensus definition

Consensus meetings

By using nominal group technique, we had an open dialogue including perspectives from all participants aiming for an agreed conclusion and thereby reaching consensus during meetings with the research panels and the steering committee [132].

Survey

In the survey, each outcome was rated for importance on a Likert scale from 1-9 [95, 134].

- 1-3 was considered 'not important'
- 4-5 'important, but not critical'
- 7-9 'critical'

For all three survey rounds, consensus on an outcome was achieved when:

- 70% or more rated the outcome as 'critical'
- 15% or less rated the outcome 'not critical'

For the second and third survey round, the participants received their individual scores, ratings from all four groups (patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers), and a summary score representing the percentages of ratings in the three categories used to divide the Likert scale.

International validation

All countries participating in the international validation established local research panels within which they would reach consensus on whether they accepted the core outcome, if it needed adaption, or if it was rejected. . Recording minutes was recommended for a transparent process. There was not a cut-off for consensus internationally, but we aimed to reach consensus by nominal group technique at our meetings.

Results

For the initial core outcome set (Figure 5, step 1-4), 264 of the 380 invited participants for both survey and interviews took part in the survey. There were 86 who accepted the invitation for the interview and 82 who completed.

Modified Delphi consensus process.

Within the modified Delphi process the 329 outcomes identified in the literature review were condensed to 50 outcomes. This was the first step involving the research panels. At the same time, interviews were conducted resulting in 9 additional outcomes. Discussions with the research panels revealed that these outcomes were already included in the condensed set of 50 outcomes.

The survey process for all 50 outcomes is illustrated by heatmaps in the supplemental material (Figure S151 and S152, Paper VI, Supplemental Digital Content (SDC), Page 224 and 225). These heatmaps illustrate the

consensus process in the surveys and even small differences between the survey rounds can be seen. For patients and family members most of the outcomes were rated important.

Core outcome set

In Figure 6, the initial Danish core outcome set is listed. The core outcome set was the result of consensus in the steering committee (step 4) and across the 4 Danish research panels.

Figure 6. The initial Danish core outcome set and the revised international core outcome set

Reproduced from Paper VII [136] [Kjaer et al. Registration at MedRxiv 2024, (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.05.29.24308094>)], open access registration, CC BY NC license 4.0 [41]

For international validation, the initial Danish core outcome set—together with the 50 outcomes and the rationale and conclusions—was shared with all 13 countries accepting to participate. International consensus meetings were held across countries in 17 local research panels, and they reported back with minutes from all meetings held. All input was condensed based on international considerations, and changes were made to accomplish higher consensus across all participating countries. For the initial Danish core outcome set, between 76% to 100% consensus was reached on each of the 6 core outcomes with three outcomes suggested being rejected by 1 or 2 countries.

Countries marked with their respective flags participated in the international validation

The revision of the outcomes was done primarily to clarify the outcomes and revise them from being measurements to

outcomes. For the revised international core outcome set consensus was reached (Table 6) between 90% to 100% and only 1 country suggested 1 outcome rejected.

Table 6. The consensus percentages for the revised six core outcomes presented to all 21 research panels.

Revised international core outcome set	Number of research panels reaching consensus out of 21 possible outcomes (%)
Survival	21 (100%)
Free of life support	21 (100%)
Free of delirium	20 (95%)
Out of hospital	19 (90%)
Health-related quality of life	21 (100%)
Cognitive function	19 (90%)

Conclusions

We developed a core outcome set suitable for general adult ICU patients. It has been validated for 14 countries. We encourage future intensive care trials to consistently assess our 6 core outcomes: survival, free of life support, free of delirium, out of hospital, health-related quality of life, and cognitive function. These core outcomes were the most important outcomes to assess, adjudicated to be important for patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers across the participating countries.

Discussion

Principal findings

Study I revealed a substantial amount of missing data in intensive care trials assessing HRQoL. Half of the trials lacked transparency regarding the potential impact of non-respondents and non-survivors on HRQoL results and the potential level of bias. This could compromise the findings and potentially lead to misinterpretations due to insufficient or absent statistical handling of missing data. The study underscores the importance of addressing the risk of loss to follow-up a priori in the trial's analysis plan and ensuring transparency in all methodological choices to effectively leverage these patient-important outcomes for future research and evidence.

In **Study II**, we found that restrictive IV fluid therapy, compared to standard IV fluid therapy, resulted in similar survival rates, HRQoL, and cognitive function one year after randomisation in the CLASSIC trial. This was the first fluid intensive care trial assessing long-term outcomes besides survival, and it revealed that either choice of fluid therapy would be safe and not affect patient-important outcomes on the long-term.

In **Study III**, we developed a consensus-based core outcome set for adult general ICU patients intended for use in clinical trials within the ICU setting. The core outcomes, agreed upon by patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers from 14 countries, were: survival, free from life support, free from delirium, out of hospital, HRQoL, and cognitive function.

Strengths and limitations

Overall, a key strength was that all studies were preplanned with published protocols ensuring the studies were thoroughly considered and outlined in detail before being conducted.

Study I—the systematic review

The main strength of Study I is the stringent research methodology used including a rigorous risk of bias assessment, a broad search strategy with no limitations, and adherence to the Cochrane Handbook with reporting in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. The protocol deviations led to improvements providing a more nuanced risk of bias assessment and a more carefully considered statistical analysis.

Methods

Conducting a systematic review requires a strict methodology and a thorough process. It could be questioned whether such a level of thoroughness was necessary to address the research question, and to some extent, we might have acquired similar insights through, e.g. a scoping review, as demonstrated by Granholm and colleagues [70]. They conducted this scoping review within a limited timeframe, a limitation in searched journals, and they omitted a risk of bias assessment, while they did include all patient-important outcomes except mortality. Nonetheless, in Study I we chose to include a risk of bias assessment to investigate whether a higher level of bias was associated with a higher non-response rate. Both reviews provide valuable insights highlighting the lack of transparency in both reporting and managing non-respondents and non-survivors in patient-important outcomes.

Study population

There was a broad diversity among the patients as there were no limitations on the study populations in the included trials or the interventions conducted. Moreover, ICU patients represent a highly heterogeneous group, further enhancing the diversity of the study.

Statistical analysis

In the protocol, all analyses were initially planned to use Fisher's exact test without accounting for heterogeneity between trials leading to a simple aggregation of outcomes across multiple trials in various sizes. This would not have provided the most accurate or nuanced results given that Fisher's exact test has limitations in this context as it is primarily suited for small sample sizes and binary outcomes. Furthermore, it does not account for variation between trials potentially resulting in an oversimplified analysis [142]. Therefore, we deviated from this plan and adopted a more comprehensive approach by estimating mean proportions and risk differences and applied this in the meta-analyses of proportions using a random-effects model. Unlike Fisher's exact test, the random-effects model accounted for heterogeneity between trials allowing an estimation of mean proportions with associated uncertainty for the primary outcome, thereby providing more robust and valid results.

Ideally, there was no missingness but in practice this is unrealistic. There is a need to consider how to handle the missing data and prespecify this before doing the analyses to avoid risk of bias [76]. Transparency including a statistical analysis plan outlining how to analyse data with high risk of missingness is recommended [74, 76].

There are several statistical options, e.g. complete case analysis only using the dataset with full response, simple imputation where you, e.g. carry the last observation forward, or more advanced statistics using multiple imputation.

We could have extended the analyses to explore the impact of including non-respondents illustrating the use of multiple imputation compared to other methods of handling [73, 118]. We could also have conducted extended analyses to include non-survivors to further demonstrate the variation in results when non-survivors are included, which we argue is crucial for obtaining valid trial results. However, data were frequently unobtainable, even after contacting the corresponding author.

Non-survivors

Excluding non-survivors from primary analyses of trials assessing interventions—particularly those likely to impact mortality in populations with high baseline mortality rates (e.g. all intensive care trials)—is prone to produce seriously misleading conclusions [55]. Assigning the worst value, or a value anchored to death as in the EQ-5D (which assigns a score of zero) [143], could result in a peak (zero-inflation) in the distribution, as observed in Study II [126], leading to a non-normal distribution. If not properly addressed, this could bias the results. If the treatment affects mortality, it is likely to increase survival among the sickest patients, who are also more likely to have low HRQoL later. Thus, beneficial interventions that increase survival might paradoxically appear to have, misleading, detrimental effects on HRQoL. While secondary analyses of HRQoL in survivors are reasonable, primary analyses in these cases should include all patients to maintain the intention-to-treat analysis.

For long-term outcomes, reaching a consensus on the handling of non-survivors and non-respondents in reporting standards is essential to improve the interpretation of trial results [144]. The chosen method, whether employed or omitted, should be clearly stated in the trial protocols. This practice should be incorporated into guidelines such as the CONSORT statement, explicitly addressing the handling of non-survivors and non-respondents during long-term follow-up [145], an area particularly lacking in relation to secondary long-term outcomes [70, 121, 144].

A pertinent example is the Prehospital Assessment of the Role of Adrenaline: Measuring the Effectiveness of Drug Administration in Cardiac Arrest (PARAMEDIC2) trial [146]. This trial demonstrated an association between adrenalin favouring survival across all time points and a lower HRQoL for the survivors completing follow-up (128/8014=2.0%) [146]. It highlights that if an intervention affects mortality, it might confound the assessment of treatment effects on HRQoL as discussed in the Background section. Explanations could be that the survivors were:

- *'mortality benefitters'*, i.e. the sickest patients survive due to the intervention but with a low HRQoL
- *'specials'* dying before follow-up due to the intervention but would have survived if being allocated to the control group

Distinguishing between these groups can be challenging as identifying the 'always survivors' would require expert assessment or estimation [55]. This underscores the importance of addressing 'truncation due to death' when considering long-term patient-important follow-up outcomes, such as cognitive function and HRQoL, in populations with high mortality rates [55].

Outcome considerations

In designing the search strategy, we considered the Patient, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome (PICO) framework. For this systematic review, we initially chose not to restrict the search by specific interventions or comparisons, but searching solely based on the study population yielded an unmanageable number of records. Consequently, we included the HRQoL outcome despite being aware that this approach is not recommended [147].

Searching for HRQoL as an outcome might have influenced our search results as HRQoL is not consistently indexed in databases for trials with long-term follow-up, potentially resulting in relevant studies being overlooked. Additionally, we did not include 'health status' as a search term which was noted in peer review. This might have limited the records in our search results, and it could explain why we identified additional trials at a later stage.

We could have considered the methodological framework developed for PRO in clinical trial protocols, the Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials – Patient Reported Outcome (SPIRIT-PRO) Extension [148]. The framework addresses key considerations for reporting PROs. Our data extraction from all trials included most of the extended issues covered in the SPIRIT-PRO; however, we did not include the psychometric properties, sample size when HRQoL was a primary outcome, or statistical analysis concerns for Type I errors [148].

Risk of bias assessment

We deviated from the protocol in the assessment of risk of bias, which was planned using the former risk of bias (RoB) tool from the Cochrane Handbook version 5.1 [149], by using the revised risk of bias version 2 (RoB2) [76]. The framework of RoB2 consists of signalling questions for five domains ensuring a more nuanced and qualified conclusion on the level of bias for the outcome assessed. We assessed RoB2 for the HRQoL outcomes, which we knew were prone to involve non-respondents, however, with the signalling questions there were other questions to consider than just to arbitrarily conclude 'high risk of bias' if exceeding a limit of 20% missing values. Domain 3 'RoB due to missing outcome data' and domain 4 'RoB in measurement of the outcome' posed challenges when assessing HRQoL as an outcome [76]. These domains were carefully considered by the three RoB assessors and their supervisors due to the concerns that missing could (likely) depend on its true value and how non-blinded trials could affect the patients' HRQoL assessment as patients were the outcome assessors. The conclusions could have been different in other research settings, but we defined how to conclude on these outcomes to avoid inconsistency in the bias level (Paper II, Supplement, Page 19). The RoB2 guide could have been more detailed to ensure inter-rater-reliability in the bias assessment.

Study II—long-term follow-up of the CLASSIC trial

The CLASSIC trial was an open-label high quality randomised clinical trial. We conducted intention-to-treat analysis, i.e. we included all participants in the follow-up, also the non-survivors, except five patients who withdrew consent for use of trial data. This approach ensured that randomisation was preserved, thereby enhancing the internal validity of the trial. Both the statistician and research personnel were blinded to the allocation. The long-term follow-up of patient-important outcomes beside mortality at one year was the first of its kind in fluid trials.

Study population

We included patients with septic shock defined according to the Sepsis-3 criteria [150]. Comparing this population with other studies was challenging due to variations in the definition of sepsis, but this will be easier going forward if we continue to use the same definition. Additionally, the timing of follow-up, the handling of non-respondents and non-survivors, and tools used for assessing the HRQoL and cognitive function, vary between studies [70, 121]. As the trial was conducted in Europe, its generalisability and potential for external validation might be limited outside of Europe.

We were aware of the risk posed by non-respondents in the long-term follow-up. To address this, we performed a standard operating procedure (SOP) for the follow-ups. It included retention strategies such as extending the follow-ups by four weeks and conducting follow-ups via phone (Paper IV, ESM, Page 5). To do follow-ups via phone has proven to be more efficient than by snail-mail when enrolling patients without compensation for patients [151]. Despite having more than 5% non-respondents, we had a relatively low rate of non-respondents (8.7% for EQ-5D-5L in total; 13.6% for EQ-5D-5L if looking at survivors only) compared with Study I (median of 20% non-respondents, IQR 9% to 38%) [121]. For retention we facilitated centrally monitored follow-ups and reminder notifications along with additional support when needed—especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Statistical analysis

With the anticipated high number of deceased patients, we proactively outlined this in our protocol by designating outcomes as ‘truncated due to death’ when analysing the functional outcomes [55, 124]. Following the EuroQol recommendations, we aligned zero as a value equivalent to death [143]. In consensus, we also decided that death should be considered a worse outcome than a low cognitive function score, which we assigned a value of zero as well. This was also done for the EQ-VAS. We acknowledge that this approach might have missed important nuances, such as ‘mortality benefiterers’—patients who survived due to the intervention but with low HRQoL or cognitive function. Conversely, this approach could overlook patients who benefited from the control allocation (‘specials’), but died prior to follow-up. In large-scale trials, it is essential to make the best possible decisions that enable manageable and inclusive analyses.

We deviated substantially from the protocol [124], but these changes ultimately improved the results of the trial. While deviations from the pre-planned analyses are generally disapproved, we conducted these adjustments transparently by outlining the reasons for the deviations in the ESM of Paper IV. We believe these changes were essential, as the original analysis plan would not have been appropriate and might have introduced greater uncertainty about the results making them harder to interpret.

The uncertainty of the estimates for the between-group differences, reflected in the 99% CIs, could potentially include clinically important differences. To be more confident about the results we would need more trial participants, but the power calculation was based on the primary outcome, all-cause mortality day 90, and not the secondary outcomes [123]. Thus, concluding that no difference exists would be a misinterpretation as ‘*absence of evidence is not evidence of absence*’ [152].

Furthermore, we did not define the minimal clinical important difference (MCID) beforehand for either EQ-5D or the Mini MoCA. However, with a simulation-based approach, the MCID for the EQ-5D-5L index value has been estimated for Canada, China, Spain, Japan, England, and Uruguay to be between 0.037 and 0.069 [153]. In the CLASSIC trial the adjusted risk difference was 0.01 but with a 99% CI ranging from -0.05 to 0.07.

The only way to include all randomised patients without compromising the intention-to-treat principle would be to assign a value equivalent to death for non-survivors. This approach would require expert consensus to define an appropriate value if the instrument or tool does not already provide one as with EQ-5D-5L [55]. In the PARAMEDIC2 trial, the results might have been different if non-survivors had been included with an alternative value representing death [144].

A complete case analysis which ignores non-respondents, both conflicts with the intention-to-treat principle, and comes with a potential risk of bias, depending on the mechanisms of missing data [73, 154]. In the CLASSIC trial, we preplanned to use multiple imputation with extra sensitivity analyses if non-response exceeded 5% [124, 126]. Baseline characteristics of the complete cases, non-survivors, and non-respondents (Paper IV, Table 1) allowed readers to assess potential differences and the risk of selection bias [126]. Unsurprisingly, non-survivors were sicker (e.g. higher predicted 90-day mortality and admissions from the ward), while non-respondents were less ill (e.g. more emergency admissions). Although displaying baseline characteristics is straightforward and effective, it remains underused as shown in Paper II [121].

Multiple imputation, which predicts plausible values based on existing data, is preferred over complete case analysis for missing data [154]. It produces several datasets for analysis offering more reliable estimates [117, 154]. Non-respondents likely range between ‘missing at random’ and ‘missing not at random’ making the use of multiple imputation appropriate [73, 75, 154]. In the CLASSIC trial, results from

multiple imputation and complete case analysis were similar (Paper IV, ESM, Page 9), enhancing both transparency and robustness.

Mortality rates were similar between groups suggesting the intervention did not influence mortality. While excluding non-survivors might seem justified, the trial accounted for 'truncation due to death' [103, 124], and the EQ-5D-5L index included death in its values [143]. This approach simplifies the statistical handling of non-survivors and informs the interpretation of results in a meaningful way, making it a valuable method to consider for other long-term outcomes [55].

Outcome considerations

As mentioned in the introduction, the CRIC network aimed to include long-term patient-important outcomes besides mortality in the trials such as HRQoL and cognitive function. There are many ways of assessing these outcomes, but the instruments used should be valid and manageable yet also accessible for participants to avoid overburdening them or, even worse, deterring them from participating and responding. This could have been clarified using PPI in the research process. In the CLASSIC trial, we aimed to assess cognitive function via phone calls alongside HRQoL. This approach proved to be both manageable for research personnel and accessible for the participants, as evidenced by feedback from the research teams and the relatively high response rate.

A limitation of our study is the absence of baseline HRQoL and cognitive function data. Consequently, we are unable to evaluate whether the intervention had an impact on outcomes by comparing values from before the intervention to one year later. We can only determine whether there were differences between the two fluid groups.

HRQoL

Needham and colleagues reached consensus on the use of the two generic questionnaires, the SF-36 and the EQ-5D-5L, and they also reached consensus on how to assess pain [99]. The EQ-5D-5L was chosen for the CLASSIC trial because experience from previous trials within the CRIC network demonstrated high rates of non-respondents when using SF-36 [77, 155], and it was also time consuming to conduct [75]. Both questionnaires are strongly correlated which favours the shorter questionnaire [156]. Neither questionnaire has fully covered construct or content validity for critically ill patients [58, 64]. However, part of the construct validity (criterion validity) was found to be excellent for EQ-5D-5L [64]. There might be challenges regarding the sensitivity of the EQ-5D-5L in assessing HRQoL, but the EQ-5D is based on preferences from the general population, and it uses a value set developed in many countries to reflect differences in culture and healthcare systems [62, 143, 157]. The handling of non-survivors is incorporated with a value set ranging from a negative value (HRQoL worse than being dead) to 0 (equal to death), and up to 1.00 (being the perfect health) [143].

In the CRIC network it has been discussed whether EQ-5D has limited use in clinical trials (also by reviewers of Paper IV in our case), and whether it only has a health economic purpose. However, Devlin et al. state that EQ-5D can be used to compare health economics and also be used in clinical trials without limitation [143]. The EQ-5D is available in numerous languages, but the country-specific value set, for which the index score was calculated, was not available for Switzerland, Norway, and the Czech Republic; we used the German, Danish, and the Polish value set for these three countries, respectively. The EQ-5D is based on preferences from the general population using a value set which has been developed in many countries to

encompass differences in culture and healthcare systems [62, 143, 157]. We also conducted a preplanned comparison using the Danish value set for all patients, and this yielded similar results.

Cognitive function

Choosing an instrument to assess cognitive function was difficult for Needham and colleagues, and they did not reach consensus on a valid test to use for their core outcome measurement set (COMS) [99]. This is in line with a systematic review concerning the psychometric properties of cognitive instruments used for adult ICU survivors [52]. The gold standard for assessing cognitive function is face-to-face interviews using the Repeatable Battery for the Assessment of Neuropsychological Status (RBANS) [158]. Due to the comprehensive face-to-face test, this instrument was considered too burdensome for all international trial sites in two international CRIC trials, and it was planned to be done only in the largest three Danish sites [159, 160].

The Mini MoCA test was introduced as a 5-minute test designed to be conducted by phone. To ensure interrater reliability, certification was required for its use. This simplified version of the MoCA test has been validated for assessing cognitive function in stroke patients [161], but it has not been validated for critically ill patients. Although the Mini MoCA correlates well with the full MoCA [162], the full MoCA test aims to assess mild cognitive function which might underestimate the true cognitive function. This is particularly relevant as cognitive function can be severely impaired for years after discharge with septic shock being a notable risk factor [163]. Using the Mini MoCA test was a pragmatic choice, but it was not officially available at the time of planning and initiating follow-up in the CLASSIC trial. In collaboration with the MoCA institute, we adapted the test to be used for all trial sites, including translations to the languages of non-English participating countries. The point system we used mirrored that of the validation study for stroke patients [161]. Alternatives included the Telephone Interview for Cognitive Status (TICS), which was the most commonly used cognitive test in large studies, and, like the Mini MoCA, has been validated for stroke patients [164]. Both tests show a strong correlation with the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) [161, 164].

During the CLASSIC trial, the MoCA institute released their official MoCA 5-Minute test which employed a different scoring system [165]. It does not compensate for years of education, and it does not award points for the attention domain, i.e. words to remember are now repeated twice instead of once as in our protocol. Consequently, our Mini MoCA test differed slightly from the official version in its scoring scale and was thus named the 'modified Mini MoCA'. We consulted a neuropsychologist to confirm that our version still effectively assessed cognitive function even if it might yield slightly lower cognitive scores than the official test. All participants received the same cognitive test ensuring that any observed differences were valid for analysis.

Other outcomes

We conducted a pragmatic trial intentionally focusing on easily accessible clinically relevant outcomes that could be widely applied to all ICUs treating septic shock patients, irrespective of level of care. By selecting these outcomes, we ensured patient safety (through assessment of serious adverse events and reactions), and we ensured a focus on long-term patient-important outcomes. The results indicate that both fluid

treatments are safe for patients and yielded similar outcomes in both groups – outcomes that are important to patients and supported by the findings in Study III [136].

The Fluid and Catheter Treatment Trial (FACTT) was the only fluid trial assessing patient-important outcomes beyond mortality when the CLASSIC trial was planned [166]. This trial assessed HRQoL as well as long-term cognitive and psychiatric impairment [105]. We chose not to assess neuropsychological outcomes, such as Post-Traumatic Stress Symptoms (PTSS), anxiety, and depression, as these were partially covered by the domains in EQ-5D-5L. Including these outcomes would have extended the follow-up process increasing the risk of a higher non-response rate due to the burden placed on participants.

Most of the outcomes assessed in the CLASSIC trial are part of our core outcome set except for ‘free of delirium’. This could have been a relevant additional outcome as sepsis is a known risk factor for delirium in the ICU [167, 168], and fluid management might also impact brain function, potentially contributing to delirium [104]. It could be valuable to explore if there is an association between fluid treatment or septic shock and the occurrence of delirium. This could be explored using datasets on the co-enrolled patients in both the CLASSIC and the Agents Intervening against Delirium (AID-ICU) trials including patients with delirium [169, 170].

Study III—the core outcome set

A core outcome set for the general ICU patient was developed through extensive involvement of patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers. We used rigorous methodology following the Delphi consensus method, the COMET Handbook, and the COS-STAR statement. The additional international validation, involving a wide range of countries, allowed us to capture diverse perspectives and increase the generalisability of the core outcome set. The entire process is illustrated in Figure 5.

Study population

All research panel members, interview informants, and survey respondents in the study were recruited via outpatient clinics, trial long-term follow-up, or self-referral following a posting. This recruitment strategy carries a high risk of selection bias, but we made efforts (see Table 5) to recruit a diverse range of participants across all categories. This was a pragmatic approach given the challenges and time-consuming nature of recruitment. Even with dedicated researchers in Denmark achieving the initial target of 90 interviews and 400 survey participants proved difficult. We were not able to document reasons for non-participation as we had no legal rights to collect these data. Consequently, those who agreed to participate likely represent a selected group, perhaps individuals who demonstrate more functional coping mechanisms and are willing to share their experience [44]. As one patient expressed it:

"I didn't find any meaning in my critical illness at the time, but I do find meaning in using that experience now" (research panel member, October 2024)

A recently published review on Delphi surveys concluded that having 60 to 80 participants ensures a high level of replicability, but for individual stakeholder groups (such as ours), a sample size of 20-30 per group is recommended [171]. Throughout our interviews, Delphi survey, and research panels, we have consistently had more than 20 participants. When comparing our core outcome set with the work of Needham and colleagues [98, 99], it is fair to state that our approach demonstrates robust involvement, providing a strong and prominent voice to the patients and family members relevant to our core outcome set.

The level of diversity among the participating countries could also be discussed. A key limitation is that only one Low Middle-Income Country (LMIC) was included. The reason is that the international validation process adopted a pragmatic approach reaching out to collaborating countries in the CRIC network, but without this approach, there would likely have been no international validation at all. The single included lower-middle income country, India, accounts for one-sixth of the world's population and shares similarities with other LMICs healthcare systems and cultures. Additionally, the study featured two research panels located in different regions of India. This provides at least some degree of representation for the LMIC category.

A newer core outcome set was published this year in the field of critical illness, specifically for trials on Physical Rehabilitation Core Outcomes In Critical illness (PRACTICE) [172]. It identified core outcomes aligned with its focus: physical function, activities of daily living, exercise capacity, as well as survival, HRQoL, cognitive function, emotional and mental wellbeing, and frailty [172]. While the PRACTICE core outcomes were more focused on physical rehabilitation, all core outcomes listed were also relevant to our own stakeholders. In our core outcome set, all physical activities were included under the HRQoL umbrella. Our study involved more patient and family participation compared to the PRACTICE study for which 24 patients and family members (7%) participated. This discrepancy in engagement might explain some of the differences in the identified core outcomes.

Methods

We initially planned a Danish core outcome set to guide the core protocol for INCEPT. A key question is whether the outcomes would have differed if all countries were included from the beginning, but involving research panels internationally, conducting interviews, translating the Delphi survey, and organising consensus meetings would likely have substantially extended the study timeline. Furthermore, although existing core outcome sets for subgroups of critical illness do show some differences, they are not extensive [96].

Throughout the Delphi consensus process and international validation, an important challenge was to avoid transitioning into the next step; developing the core outcome measurement set. This process has been discussed on all levels, with the research panels, the steering committee, and the international committee. While many ideas and perspectives were noted, it constrained the freedom in discussions. However, this approach was necessary, as the focus was solely on reaching consensus about the core outcomes, without it being influenced by considerations of accessibility or manageability.

Various rating scales can be used in the Delphi consensus process and the choice of scale might influence the process. Deciding on what to prioritise is not straightforward, but asking the participants directly might provide the simplest answer. The test-retest reliability varied for different rating scales, partly due to the thresholds set for reaching consensus, but the nine-point scale had the highest weighted kappa value (0.78) [173] and it was considered fair to use. The variability in the scale should be carefully considered, when designing the forthcoming Delphi survey for the core outcome measurement set.

We required more than 70% of all stakeholder groups to rate an outcome 'critical' for inclusion, in line with the consensus criteria in the COMET Handbook [95]. The research panels participated in the consensus meetings, and outcomes rated as 'critical' by all stakeholder groups were prioritised. While this approach did not strictly adhere to the protocol or fully align with the guidance outlined in the COMET Handbook, the active involvement of the research panels facilitated broader discussions. This ensured that perspectives on outcomes deemed important by patients, but not necessarily by clinicians (and vice versa), were not

overlooked. In hindsight, we could have specified more clearly which outcomes were considered ‘critical’ during each survey round. This might have altered the final core outcome set if only those had been considered. If a ‘critical’ outcome was not included as a core outcome, it was nevertheless included for further consideration in the core outcome measurement set that is to be developed (Table 7).

Table 7. Considerations for the core outcomes to be included in the core outcome measurement set

Revised international core outcome set	Considerations when deciding on the measurement
Survival	Timepoint for assessment.
Free of life support	Questions concerning haemodialysis in the daily living – how does this count.
Free of delirium	There is a variation in practice both in handling and assessing delirium, and sedation.
Out of hospital	‘Days alive and out of hospital’. During the discussion ‘home in same condition as before ICU’ and ‘home and independent and being able to perform activities of daily living’ were also considered.
Health-related quality of life	HRQoL was considered an umbrella outcome covering 18 outcomes out of the 50 outcomes in the survey, e.g. pain and usual role. Wellbeing and physical strength/function were discussed as to whether they really should be included in HRQoL or if they should have been individual outcomes.
Cognitive function	To be or not to be a part of HRQoL

Abbreviation: *ICU*: Intensive care unit, *HRQoL*: Health-related quality of life

We considered using multiple imputation for the Delphi survey results given a non-response rate of just below 20%. While this could have potentially improved the rigour of the results, we adhered to the protocol as planned [134]. Multiple imputation might have influenced the findings, but since most non-respondents were clinicians, the missing data mechanism was likely more random than if most non-respondents had been patients. Furthermore, the level of participation achieved should ensure reproducibility [171].

Patient and public involvement

With guidance from the COMET Initiative and other collaborators, we reached valuable input on how and when to incorporate PPI into the process. We regret there was no PPI in step 4 of the Delphi consensus process (Figure 4) which was limited to the steering committee. This step involved reaching consensus on the 6 core outcomes identified for the initial Danish core outcome set prior to international validation. Including the research panels—or at least some of their participants—in this consensus meeting could have influenced the wording of the initial core outcome set. Nonetheless, all research panels reviewed and discussed the initial core outcome set afterwards, leading to revisions and consensus on a final core outcome set.

During the international consensus meetings, minutes were recorded which included evaluations of participant involvement. These evaluations were predominantly positive, highlighting the value of bringing patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers together to reach consensus on the core outcomes. All international research panels reported a fair distribution of comments and discussions across the four participant categories. However, a more detailed approach would have allowed for a clearer assessment of the specific impact of PPI. For example, what did PPI contribute to the process? Existing evaluation tools

remain limited. We used the GRIPP2-SF [140] which asks directly what impact PPI had. This can be rather difficult to assess, and it will be descriptive and not an effect-size estimate. Grotz et al. recommend building a logic model, which consists of questions to be answered before PPI, e.g.: What is the problem?; What specific actions will help make the difference?; How will we measure the effects (or outputs) of those specific actions? [111]. If known when we planned the development of the core outcome set, we could have stated these questions before beginning the process and then we might have been able to assess the impact more easily on the process.

Another question to consider is whether assessing impact of PPI contribution is necessary and, if so, for what purpose. Researchers using PPI have argued that for PPI to achieve meaningful impact, the conditions under which it operates must be carefully considered. The right to equality and principle of co-production in conversations between stakeholders often overlook the inherent realities of hierarchical structures within academic life [174]. Epistemic justice plays a key role, ensuring that experiential knowledge is both equitably shared and taken seriously [175]. For our research panel members, we could have assessed whether they felt equally qualified to contribute to the research panels and fully involved in the process. The degree of involvement could be measured and evaluated using the Patient Engagement in Research Scale (PEIRS-22) [176]. This evaluation is ongoing, and the questionnaire will soon be distributed among Danish research panels to assess their level of involvement in developing the core outcome set. The results are expected soon.

Outcome considerations

The initial challenges in the development of a core outcome set and the collaboration with research panels included the understanding of what constitutes an outcome and recognising that a core outcome must be consistently assessed across all trials. During discussions on outcomes and their importance, new research questions often emerged which were noted for future investigation. Further considerations regarding the measurement set are detailed in Table 7.

There were minor discrepancies among the stakeholder categories regarding the 50 survey outcomes, e.g. clinicians and researchers prioritised health economics while patients and family members emphasised sexual function. The research panels, representing all stakeholders, resolved these differences by including health economics as an optional outcome for relevant trials and placing sexual function under the HRQoL umbrella which encompasses 18 out of the 50 outcomes (Paper VII, SDC, Page 32). These discrepancies highlight the importance of including stakeholder categories in the decision-making process to ensure that every voice is heard.

Delirium was undoubtedly an important outcome throughout the survey rounds, interviews, and minutes from the research panel meetings of all countries. While one country rejected it, achieving consensus on consistently assessing this outcome across sites might prove challenging as we work toward finalising the set. Potential confounders include local sedation policy, delirium-assessment policy (if any), and treatment strategies. A recent, well-conducted trial carefully considered how delirium was evaluated in ICUs [169, 170]. One way to manage these confounders could be through stratification by site. This was done in the CLASSIC trial to equalise variations in practice regarding fluid management [123].

Current evidence and perspectives

The recently revised Helsinki Declaration emphasises the importance of involving ‘potential and enrolled participants’ in research to incorporate their perspectives on priorities and values [177]. It also highlights the need to ensure that participants understand the dissemination of results, advocating for engagement of participants and communities before, during, and after medical research [177]. The World Health Organization (WHO) also revised their guideline in September 2024, including recommendations for optimal practices in clinical trial management to include engagement of patients, participants (enrolled and potential), and communities in the research process of conducting a trial to ensure needs are met and trust is maintained [178].

These recommendations highlight the value of collaboration with relevant stakeholders and emphasise the importance of maintaining such engagement. We have involved research panels in our work over the past three years, and the degree of involvement increased as we became more familiar and confident working together with these panels. In Figure 7, the green area represents dimensions in which research panels were involved, and the red areas represent dimensions in which they were not; this distribution might change given further collaboration.

Figure 7. A modified Circle of Control tailored to our collaboration with the research panels. The green area represents where they were involved and could exert influence, while red areas indicate what was beyond their control. The figure is inspired by [Nissan et al [179] Research Involvement and Engagement 2018, 4:24.

(<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-018-0106-2>) open access publication, Copyright permission via CC BY NC license 4.0 [41].

In this thesis, the studies represent different levels of the evidence hierarchy; a systematic review and meta-analysis (SRMA), an RCT, and a cross sectional study with expert opinions [86]. The studies will hopefully provide evidence and impact in the opposite direction with consensus on a core outcome set with extended PPI. This follows the recommendations from the Helsinki Declaration and WHO and might

affect the future RCTs and SRMAs to provide treatment and care based on high quality evidence for the critically ill patients [177, 178].

In a recent review, the use of the core outcome set in general was explored for use in practice guidelines throughout specialities [180]. It is not well-established yet, but hopefully this generally applicable core outcome set will be easier to incorporate [180]. In another review, focussing on the use of core outcome sets in Cochrane SRs in 2022, the authors reported 13% of SRs cited a core outcome set [181]. It was reported as an increased use, but it could be much better since 39% did not cite a core outcome set even though there was a relevant one available. As part of the Cochrane SR, a survey was distributed among authors of the included SRs highlighting the positive perspectives of using a core outcome set, and the barriers, e.g. a core outcome set not being applicable for the SR [181]. Our broad core outcome set might be applicable for many settings, but it could also be too broad depending on the scope of the SR. When a core outcome set is published, there is an important task in encouraging its uptake, ensuring awareness, and to discuss its purposes and possibilities [93]. The dissemination of our core outcome set has already been conducted in minor settings with a research panel member (a patient), who spoke about the equality in the process and emphasised the relevance of all core outcomes. This could inspire others to pursue similar opportunities.

It is important to discuss the measurement of long-term core outcomes such as HRQoL, and determine which instruments are psychometrically valid to ensure reliability, content validity (using PPI), and construct validity [182]. While generic HRQoL tools may be broadly valid, the face validity of both EQ-5D-5L and SF-36 is lacking [58]. This is particularly important for our study population, who often experience long-term cognitive impairments.

In addition to the handling of non-survivors, another equally important issue is the handling of non-respondents. In Paper II, concerns were raised about a lack of transparency, which could be improved with a preplanned protocol including long-term outcomes [121]. Besides trying to prevent missing data, it is important to note that longer follow-up periods are associated with higher non-response rates [121], necessitating careful consideration on how to address this issue.

A key question is the timing for measuring HRQoL—or other patient-important outcomes—given the trajectory of critical illness. A study has been planned to develop a method for measuring HRQoL that accounts for the intertwined effects on survival and HRQoL [183], using simulations on existing datasets, including the data from the CLASSIC follow-up (Paper IV) [126]. The study also aims to capture early improvements, i.e. patients who recover faster and reach their stable long-term HRQoL sooner. Such a method, using multiple HRQoL measurements from the same person, could be superior and more sensitive than conventional one-off sampling approaches. Unfortunately, this study is currently on hold due to unforeseen logistical challenges, awaiting a future opportunity to be able to proceed.

Finally, it is important to address the question of how many outcomes and timepoints to assess, and the related concerns which can be raised about multiple comparisons. An increasing number of outcomes leads to more analyses, and a higher risk of Type I errors, potentially resulting in false-positive results [184]. While this can be managed using methods such as the Bonferroni correction, this approach might also increase the risk of Type II errors, potentially overlooking true effects [185]. The purpose of a core outcome set is to ensure consistent assessment of the same outcomes across trials in a given research field, emphasising the importance of thoughtful consideration and involvement with relevant stakeholders [93]. However, if additional outcomes are relevant for the trial and could provide valuable insights for the study

population, they could be assessed as exploratory outcomes, with an a priori acknowledgment of a lower certainty of evidence.

Moving forward

Figure 8. Including all participants informs the interpretation of results and highlights the importance of involving relevant stakeholders when assessing patient-important outcomes.
Created in BioRender.

This thesis emphasises three issues to improve long-term patient-important outcomes (Figure 8). First, to include all participants, including non-respondents and non-survivors to ensure valid results. Secondly, to provide information on all participants when reporting trial results to enable valid interpretation. Finally, to involve relevant stakeholders to ensure patient-important outcomes are appropriately assessed.

Given the WHO's new guidance for clinical trials, emphasis is placed on involving stakeholders in the research process, including underrepresented populations such as children and pregnant individuals. The guidance also encourages conducting trials with small effect sizes, provided there is a rationale for health improvements and a need to generate evidence [178]. This will require large, carefully designed trials that follow rigorous methods such as using randomisation to reduce bias and blinding to ensure fairness, along with suitable statistical analysis to produce reliable results. At the same time, it is important to confirm that the intervention is safe for participants, and that it can be accurately measured to assess its effectiveness [178].

The CLASSIC trial investigated a relatively straightforward intervention, fluid therapy, which is the initial treatment for sepsis and is practised globally [21, 123]. Despite the external validity possibly being limited outside Europe, adopting restrictive fluid management could safely save on IV fluids and enable treatment of more patients in LMIC [123].

Within the CRIC network, several investigator initiated trials have been conducted, addressing issues such as stress-ulcer prophylaxis, oxygen therapy, haloperidol against delirium, and the use of corticosteroids in patients with COVID-19 [16, 169, 186, 187]. Of these, only the last trial included an LMIC, India [187]. The collaborative framework of the CRIC network is founded upon mutual interest and commitment, thereby facilitating the next phase of research: the implementation of the Intensive Care Platform Trial (INCEPT). This initiative is expected to generate robust evidence in alignment with the WHO recommendations [178]. The collaborative effort will hopefully extend to LMICs and prioritise the inclusion of, e.g. pregnant women, addressing important gaps in representation [178].

The foundation for INCEPT was laid in autumn 2020 with the aim of improving treatments for critically ill adult patients in the ICU [128, 129]. Drawing on experiences of the randomised, embedded, multi-factorial, adaptive platform trial for community (REMAP) [129], INCEPT is an innovative platform trial design which allows simultaneous testing of multiple treatments for the same condition within a shared framework. Its adaptive nature facilitates the efficient discontinuation of ineffective treatments during the trial, making it a more dynamic and resource-effective approach compared to traditional trials [129, 188], as also encouraged by the WHO [178].

A central component of the platform trial is the core protocol, a permanent yet adaptable document that provides a unified framework. This protocol covers key elements, including legislative and ethical considerations, statistical analysis plans, and methods for handling, e.g. non-respondents, non-survivors, and outcomes [54]. It ensures consistency and reusability across domains. In the context of this thesis, the protocol also required the development of a standardised set of core outcomes (Paper VII), which now serves as the foundation for the next step; operationalising these outcomes through a core outcome measurement set with PPI tailored to general ICU patients [56, 109, 129, 189].

This thesis underscores the importance of integrating diverse perspectives through the involvement of stakeholders as also detailed in the INCEPT core protocol. Stakeholder involvement is embedded as part of the advisory board to ensure consistent involvement in tasks across domains. This includes developing materials for informed consent, lay descriptions, and dissemination strategies. By incorporating such perspectives, the platform aligns with the revised Helsinki Declaration [177], the new WHO clinical trial guidance [178], and the increasing emphasis on PPI in research. This approach, which reflects the growing recognition of patient and healthcare professional insights, is particularly relevant in the creation of core outcome sets, as detailed in this thesis [9, 56, 110, 114].

The INCEPT platform should soon be ready to start randomising critically ill adult patients into investigator-initiated domains. The research presented in this thesis contributes to the foundation of the new platform, in particular with an emphasis on collaboration, innovation, and the inclusion of diverse perspectives to advanced ICU care.

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The PhD programme leading to the present thesis has undergone major changes. Initially, it focused on Artificial Intelligence (AI) using data from large intensive care trials in Denmark, incorporating HRQoL outcomes and leveraging Big Health Data in collaboration with the University of Copenhagen. The aim was to develop and validate a prediction model to estimate HRQoL without the need to contact patients. This approach sought to address the issue of non-respondents and mitigate the potential risk of bias in trial results. Exploring whether such a prediction is feasible remains an interesting prospect, as it could save research personnel important time and relieve patients of the burden of answering questions if they prefer not to actively participate. We performed analyses of two trials with obtained HRQoL [186, 187], exploring if there were any association between long-term HRQoL (one year) and days alive without life support or days alive and out of hospital (day 28 or day 90), to more easily estimate HRQoL. However, the correlation was poor [190] which is why it was not explored any further.

We had also planned to validate the Mini MoCA test by examining its correlation with the longer cognitive test RBANS. The goal was to determine whether the shorter test could reliably assess cognitive function in

large trials, providing a time-efficient alternative for both patients and researchers if it proved sufficiently sensitive.

However, when the foundations for the INCEPT project were laid, we decided to prioritise the development of a core outcome set. It was immediately evident that this initiative aligned well with the overall aim of the PhD and that it would be an important contribution to the improvement of long-term patient-important outcomes in intensive care trials.

Conclusions

Randomised clinical trials are considered to be the gold standard for advancing evidence-based medicine in intensive care. Integrating all stakeholders in the research process—from design and execution to analysis and dissemination—can help dismantle barriers between stakeholder groups, including patients, family members, clinicians, researchers, policy makers, funders and others. Such collaboration and co-production have the potential to improve healthcare research by fostering mutual respect and understanding. Improved cooperation could accelerate the generation of evidence needed to eliminate unnecessary or potentially harmful treatments, thereby freeing clinicians from irrelevant tasks and enhancing patient care.

This PhD thesis has contributed with high quality research on the understanding of how to improve long-term patient-important outcomes in RCTs. This contribution is encapsulated in the three studies:

Study I: When reporting HRQoL (or other long-term outcomes), it should include all participants to ensure an intention-to-treat analysis, preserving the integrity of randomisation by avoiding the exclusion of certain participants. Transparency can be improved by developing a detailed protocol that accounts for non-respondents and non-survivors, along with a well-considered analysis plan. Additionally, assessing HRQoL at follow-up within 180 days—potentially using shorter instruments such as the EQ-5D-5L—could improve participant retention and response rates.

Study II: Comparing restrictive versus liberal IV fluid therapy for septic shock patients revealed no significant effect on patient-important outcomes: 1-year mortality, HRQoL, and cognitive function. Through central coordination of long-term follow-up, we achieved a higher response rate. Despite non-respondents exceeding 5% we maintained transparency in our analyses and data reporting. This transparency allows readers to assess whether non-respondents may have influenced the results. Such an approach is recommended and has been employed in other trials in the CRIC network.

Study III: By involving relevant stakeholders and employing a multiple methods design, we developed a standardised core outcome set prioritised by patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers. Crucially, the core outcome set emphasises patient preferences. Consistent use of this core outcome set can enhance evidence quality for critically ill patients, enabling straightforward comparison and data integration. This approach aims to provide rigorous evidence to be able to draw definitive conclusions about treatments, potentially eliminating the need for further trials in areas with existing conclusive results.

This PhD aimed to improve our understanding of long-term patient-important outcomes in patients surviving (and not surviving) critical illness. It aspired to contribute practical solutions for obtaining more valid outcomes relevant to ICU survivors, family members, clinicians, and researchers. Ultimately, these contributions provide an opportunity to improve the design and execution of future long-term follow-up of ICU patients and thereby enhance clinical follow-up programmes.

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Conflicts of interest

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær declares no conflicts of interest.

Declarations

ChatCPT4.0 has been used for grammar and wording though with a critical mindset.

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Appendix

The appendix contains the full manuscripts of the studies discussed in this thesis.

PAPER I

*Reporting and interpreting missing health-related quality of life data in intensive care trials:
Protocol for a systematic review*

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Reporting and interpreting missing health-related quality of life data in intensive care trials: Protocol for a systematic review

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær¹

¹Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

²Centre for Research in Intensive Care (CRIC), Copenhagen, Denmark

Correspondence

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark.
Email: maj-brit.noerregaard.kjaer@regionh.dk

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Background: Health-related quality of life is often used as a patient-important outcome in randomized clinical trials in the intensive care unit setting. Missing data are a challenge in randomized clinical trials as they hamper the interpretation of the results, but the extent and handling of missing health-related quality of life data are unknown. Therefore, we aim to describe and evaluate the extent, pattern, and handling of missing health-related quality of life data in randomized clinical trials conducted in the intensive care unit setting.

Methods: We will conduct a systematic review of randomized clinical trials in intensive care patients that report health-related quality of life. We will systematically search the Cochrane Library, PubMed, excerpta medica database ovid, and cumulative index to nursing and allied health literature for relevant literature. We will follow the recommendations by the Cochrane Collaboration and the preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis statement. We will extract information about missing data, including how the analyses and reporting of missing data were performed. We will assess the risk of systematic errors (bias) and compare the number of nonresponders vs responders in (a) low vs high risk of bias trials and in (b) small ($n \leq 100$) vs large randomized clinical trials ($n > 100$).

Discussion: With this outlined systematic review, we will describe the handling of missing health-related quality of life data in randomized clinical trials in the intensive care unit setting and the impact on the interpretation of results.

Systematic review registration: International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO): reg. no.: CRD42019118932.

1 | INTRODUCTION

1.1 | Rationale

Quality of life (QoL) means different things to different people in different situations, and thus, QoL has a broad perspective in its meaning. In clinical trials, we want to evaluate aspects of QoL that are affected by the disease or treatment, as assessed by a Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL) measure. HRQoL is a subjective patient-reported outcome measure (PROM) intended to assess physical, mental, and social well-being.¹

Patients surviving critical illness in the intensive care unit (ICU) have long-term morbidity including new or aggravated physical and

mental disabilities.² Therefore, the use of HRQoL, which is of importance to the understanding of the impact of critical illness, has increased in the past 40 years (Figure 1). HRQoL is the most frequently used patient-important outcome and PROM for patients surviving critical illness in ICU.³⁻⁵

Missing data are a well-known challenge in randomized clinical trials (RCTs), in particular during long-term follow-up of HRQoL.^{3,5-7} Collecting PROMs is particularly challenging due to death, inability to contact the patient, lack of response, or the patient may be too ill to answer or admitted to another facility.⁷ Missing HRQoL data are prone to competing risk due to death in a very sick population.⁸ Missing data challenge the interpretation of results, as

HRQoL answers are unavailable from patients that left the study, resulting in skewed data and increased risk of bias.⁶⁻⁸ The challenges increase if data are missing due to unknown reasons that may influence the outcome. Thus, critically ill patients who are lost to follow-up may compromise the results when measuring HRQoL.^{3,7,9,10} This may introduce attrition bias as missing and non-responders are unlikely to be missing at random, and as they may be more sick with worse HRQoL than those who respond.^{3,7,9,10} Therefore, the more transparent reporting and handling of missing data, the more trustworthy HRQoL results.¹¹

1.2 | Why is it important to do this review?

The extent, handling, and potential impact of missing HRQoL data in RCTs conducted in the ICU setting are unknown.

1.3 | Objectives

We aim to evaluate the extent, pattern, handling, and impact of missing HRQoL data for patients enrolled in RCTs conducted in the ICU setting.

Research question: What is the extent of missing HRQoL data in RCTs in the ICU setting and how are the missing data handled?

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study design

We will conduct a systematic review of RCTs following the recommendations of the Cochrane Collaboration¹² and the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA).¹³

2.2 | Study registration

We have prepared this protocol according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) guidelines¹⁴ (checklist included in Appendix S1), and it is registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews.

(PROSPERO) (www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero; registration number: CRD42019118932).

2.3 | Eligibility criteria

2.3.1 | Types of studies

We will include any RCT including adult ICU patients reporting HRQoL. We will not search for unpublished trials.

2.3.2 | Types of participants

We will include adult, as defined in the original trials, ICU patients reporting HRQoL as an outcome.

2.3.3 | Types of interventions

All ICU interventions.

2.3.4 | Types of outcome measures

HRQoL by any score (as defined by the original trials).

2.3.5 | Assessment time points

As reported in the included RCTs.

FIGURE 1 Number of yearly publications from 1975 to 2017 when searching “HRQoL/QOL AND critically ill/intensive care” in PubMed

2.4 | Search methods for identification of studies

2.4.1 | Electronic searches

We will search for RCTs using a systematic and sensitive search strategy designed to include trials without limitations to language, publication year, and journal.¹²

We will search the following electronic databases:

- The Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL) in the Cochrane Library
- PubMed
- Excerpta Medica Database (Embase) Ovid
- Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL).

The tentative search strategies are presented in the Appendix S2.

To continuously identify newly published studies, we will use PubMed's 'My NCBI' (National Centre for Biotechnology Information) email alert service.

Before we submit the final review draft to an international peer-reviewed journal, we will perform an updated search on all specified databases. If we identify new trials, these will be assessed and if relevant included in our review before submission of the final review draft. If we detect additional relevant key words during any of the electronic or other searches, we will modify the electronic search strategies to incorporate these terms and document the changes.

2.5 | Searching other resources

We will hand-search the reference lists of relevant trials, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and editorials on HRQoL follow-up.

FIGURE 2 PRISMA flow diagram [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

2.6 | Data collection and analysis

2.6.1 | Selection of studies

Two review authors (MNK and MBM) will independently screen the abstract, title, or both, of every record retrieved, to determine which trials should be assessed further. This will be conducted in Rayyan technology platform, Rayyan QCRI.¹⁵ We will assess all potentially relevant articles as full-text. We will resolve any discrepancies through consensus or recourse to MHM or AP. We will present an adapted PRISMA flowchart of the study selection (see Figure 2).¹³

If there are duplicate publications, companion documents, or multiple reports of a primary study, we will use the most complete dataset aggregated across all known publications. In case of doubt, the publication reporting HRQoL as a primary or secondary outcome will be prioritized.

2.6.2 | Data extraction and management

Two review authors (MNK and MBM) will independently extract information from each included trial using a predefined data extraction form done in Rayyan QCRI. The data extraction will be tested and evaluated after the first 10 papers.

2.6.3 | Definitions

When using the term “missing data,” we refer to missing due to death or nonresponders.

Nonresponders refer to all eligible patients to reply the HRQoL questionnaire at the follow-up time point, but who do not respond due to emigration, withdrawal of consent, loss to follow-up, decline, or not responding the questionnaire for any other reason.

Trial characteristics:

- first author;
- year of publication;
- number of randomized patients;
- trial intervention;
- trial comparator;
- characteristics of the trial participants (inclusion and exclusion criteria);
- baseline characteristics (male/female ratio, age, SAPS, APACHE score, SOFA score, days with mechanical ventilation, dialyses, and vasopressors, and number of patients with septic shock);
- was HRQoL measured for a health economic analysis purpose (yes/no)?
- what method was used (eg, mailed letter, telephone interview);
- was HRQoL a primary or secondary outcome (P/S);
- what follow-up time point(s) was used;
- what HRQoL tool(s) was used;
- how many patients were alive at the main HRQoL follow-up time point.

2.7 | Outcomes

Extracted primary outcomes:

- proportion of missing HRQoL data due to death before follow-up;
- proportion of missing HRQoL data due to nonresponders (loss to follow-up, not responding or declining to answer);
- were missing data reported in quantity and discussed? (Y/N).

Extracted secondary outcomes:

- were baseline characteristics compared between responders and nonresponders? (yes/no);
- (if) what analytic strategy was used for the handling of missing data? (complete case analysis, imputations (for the dead, those lost to follow-up, and/or the nonresponders), best-worst-case analysis, others).

Setup of outcomes (see Table 1).

2.8 | Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

We will assess the risk of systematic errors (bias) of the included trials according to the Cochrane Handbook.¹² The assessment will be performed independently by two authors (MNK and MBM) in RevMan 5.3 software. (Copenhagen, Denmark; The Nordic Cochrane Centre, The Cochrane Collaboration) Disagreements will be resolved by consensus upon consultation with all authors.

The following domains will be assessed: (a) random sequence generation, (b) allocation sequence concealment, (c) blinding of participants and personnel, (d) blinding of outcome assessment, (e) incomplete outcome data, except for HRQoL outcomes, (f) selective reporting, (g) other bias, including financial conflicts of interests.

Risk of bias will be assessed for the HRQoL outcome measure only. If one or more domains are judged as being high or unclear, we will classify the trial as having overall high risk of bias.¹² A “risk of bias” figure will summarize the authors’ judgments (according to the Cochrane handbook)¹² for each bias domain for each included study (*red*: high risk, *green*: low risk, *yellow*: unclear).

2.9 | Analysis plan

We will conduct a descriptive analysis of the extent, pattern, handling, and impact of missing HRQoL data among all the included RCTs (numbers and percentages). We will compare outcomes between trials with low vs high risk of bias and between small ($n \leq 100$) vs larger trials with a Fisher's exact test. A probability (P)-value < 0.05 will be interpreted as statistically significant.

To explore heterogeneity, we will conduct subgroup analyses, where we (a) compare trials with HRQoL as primary vs secondary outcome as we expect more effort for retention and thereby higher response rate when HRQoL is a primary outcome, (b) compare the

TABLE 1 Outcomes

Author Year	Missing data (primary outcomes)			Missing data (secondary outcomes)	
	Dead (n/%) ^a	Nonresponders (n/%) ^b	Reported nonresponders in quality (Y/N)	Discussion of potential attrition bias (Y/N)	Comparing responders vs nonresponders (Y/N)
Xx					Method used to handle missing data
Yy					
Zz					

^aDead between randomization and follow-up.

^bNonresponders includes patients that were lost to follow-up, withdrew, declined to answer, emigrated, or for other reasons did not respond.

response rate for the two most used assessment tools as we expect still is SF-36 and EQ-5D⁵ as we believe EQ-5D has a higher response rate due to the shorter form, and finally (c) compare dichotomized follow-up time points ≤ 6 months vs > 6 months as we expect higher response rate with shorter follow-up time.

3 | DISCUSSION

Randomized trials in the ICU setting should aim for improvement in both long-term survival and HRQoL.^{3,4,6,16-18} A general challenge with HRQoL follow-up is missing data. In this systematic review, we aim to explore challenges associated with the extent, analysis, and reporting of missing HRQoL data in RCTs in the ICU setting.

This systematic review will describe the frequency and pattern of missing data and the choice of method and handling of missing data in each RCT. No meta-analyses will be carried out. The search for RCTs using HRQoL as an outcome will be challenging because these outcomes may not always be reported in the title or abstract. We will screen full-texts of other systematic reviews on HRQoL in the ICU setting in addition to the abstracts of RCTs identified in our search; with this approach, we expect to limit bias if any. With that in mind, we will follow all recommendations for conducting a thoroughly systematic review and provide data on how missing HRQoL data have been handled in RCTs in the ICU setting and the potential implications for the interpretation.

We believe that the result of our review will improve the quality of the design, conduct, analysis, and reporting of RCTs in the ICU setting and that this ultimately will increase the value of these trials for patients, caregivers, and society.

ETHICS APPROVAL

Not applicable.

Consent for publication: Not applicable. This manuscript does not contain any data from any individual person.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIAL

Not applicable. This manuscript does not contain any data.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None of the authors have any competing interests on the subject. The Department of Intensive Care, Rigshospitalet, has received support for research from Fresenius Kabi, CSL Behring, and Ferring

Pharmaceuticals. No other potential conflict of interest relevant to this manuscript is reported.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

MBK, MBM, and AP contributed to the conception of the study protocol and search strategy, which was refined by MBK, MBM, MHM, and AP. The manuscript was drafted by MBK and was critically revised by all other authors. MBK registered the protocol in the PROSPERO database. All authors reviewed the manuscript. All authors have approved the publication of the protocol in its current form.

ORCID

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6536-0504>

Martin Bruun Madsen <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0186-8971>

Morten Hylander Møller <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6378-9673>

Ingrid Egerod <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9576-4390>

Anders Perner <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4668-0123>

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of the article.

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Supplementary material S1

PRISMA-P checklist for *Reporting and interpreting missing health-related quality of life data in critical care trials: a protocol for a systematic review*

Section and topic	Item No	Checklist item	
ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION			
Title:			
Identification	1a	Identify the report as a protocol of a systematic review	Page 1
Update	1b	If the protocol is for an update of a previous systematic review, identify as such	Not relevant
Registration	2	If registered, provide the name of the registry (such as PROSPERO) and registration number	Page 1
Authors:			
Contact	3a	Provide name, institutional affiliation, e-mail address of all protocol authors; provide physical mailing address of corresponding author	Page 1
Contributions	3b	Describe contributions of protocol authors and identify the guarantor of the review	Page 1
Amendments	4	If the protocol represents an amendment of a previously completed or published protocol, identify as such and list changes; otherwise, state plan for documenting important protocol amendments	Not relevant
Support:			
Sources	5a	Indicate sources of financial or other support for the review	Page 1-2
Sponsor	5b	Provide name for the review funder and/or sponsor	
Role of sponsor or funder	5c	Describe roles of funder(s), sponsor(s), and/or institution(s), if any, in developing the protocol	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	6	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known	Page 3
Objectives	7	Provide an explicit statement of the question(s) the review will address with reference to participants, interventions, comparators, and outcomes (PICO)	Page 4

METHODS

Eligibility criteria	8	Specify the study characteristics (such as PICO, study design, setting, time frame) and report characteristics (such as years considered, language, publication status) to be used as criteria for eligibility for the review	Page 4
Information sources	9	Describe all intended information sources (such as electronic databases, contact with study authors, trial registers or other grey literature sources) with planned dates of coverage	Page 4-5
Search strategy	10	Present draft of search strategy to be used for at least one electronic database, including planned limits, such that it could be repeated	Page 5
Study records:			
Data management	11a	Describe the mechanism(s) that will be used to manage records and data throughout the review	Page 5 & 7
Selection process	11b	State the process that will be used for selecting studies (such as two independent reviewers) through each phase of the review (that is, screening, eligibility and inclusion in meta-analysis)	Page 5
Data collection process	11c	Describe planned method of extracting data from reports (such as piloting forms, done independently, in duplicate), any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators	Page 5
Data items	12	List and define all variables for which data will be sought (such as PICO items, funding sources), any pre-planned data assumptions and simplifications	
Outcomes and prioritization	13	List and define all outcomes for which data will be sought, including prioritization of main and additional outcomes, with rationale	Page 6
Risk of bias in individual studies	14	Describe anticipated methods for assessing risk of bias of individual studies, including whether this will be done at the outcome or study level, or both; state how this information will be used in data synthesis	Page 7
Data synthesis	15a	Describe criteria under which study data will be quantitatively synthesised	
	15b	If data are appropriate for quantitative synthesis, describe planned summary measures, methods of handling data and methods of combining data from studies, including any planned exploration of consistency (such as I^2 , Kendall's τ)	
	15c	Describe any proposed additional analyses (such as sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression)	

	15d	If quantitative synthesis is not appropriate, describe the type of summary planned	Page 7
Meta-bias(es)	16	Specify any planned assessment of meta-bias(es) (such as publication bias across studies, selective reporting within studies)	Not relevant
Confidence in cumulative evidence	17	Describe how the strength of the body of evidence will be assessed (such as GRADE)	Not relevant

Supplementary material S2

Tentative search strategy for ***Reporting and interpreting missing health-related quality of life data in critical care trials: a protocol for a systematic review***

PubMed

Population #P

1. "Intensive Care Units" [MeSH]
2. "Critical care" [Mesh]
3. "Critical Illness" [Mesh]
4. critically ill [tiab]
5. critical care [tiab]
6. Intensive Care Units [tiab]
7. Intensive care unit [tiab]
8. intensive care [tiab]
9. icu [tiab]
10. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5 OR 6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 = 341203 (Filters: humans)

(((((("Intensive Care Units"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh])) OR ("Critical Care"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh])) OR ("Critical Illness"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (critically ill AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (critical care AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (intensive care unit AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (intensive care units AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (intensive care AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (icu AND Humans[Mesh])

11. randomized controlled trial [pt]
12. controlled clinical trial [pt]
13. randomized [tiab]
14. placebo [tiab]
15. drug therapy [sh]
16. randomly [tiab]
17. trial [tiab]
18. groups [tiab]
19. clinical trial [sh]

20. 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 = 4336303, Filters: humans = 3281426

((randomized controlled trial[pt] OR controlled clinical trial[pt] OR randomized[tiab] OR placebo[tiab] OR drug therapy[sh] OR randomly[tiab] OR trial[tiab] OR groups[tiab]))

21. 10 AND 22= 38606

22. Quality of Life [MeSH Terms]

23. Quality Life [All Fields]

24. Quality of Life [All Fields]

25. Health Related Quality Life [All Fields]

26. Life Quality [All Fields]

27. Quality adjusted life years [Mesh]

28. Quality adjusted life years [All Fields]

29. 22 OR 23 OR 24 OR 25 OR 26 OR 27 OR 28= 313375 (Filters: Humans)

(((((("Quality of Life"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (quality life AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (quality of life AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (life quality AND Humans[Mesh])) OR ("Quality-Adjusted Life Years"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (Quality-Adjusted Life Years AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (health related quality life AND Humans[Mesh]))

PubMed: 10 AND 20 AND 29 = **3828**

EMBASE Ovid

Population #P

1. intensive care unit.ab,kw,ti.

2. critical care.ab,kw,ti.

3. critically ill.ab,kw,ti.

4. icu.ab,kw,ti.

5. critical illness.ab,kw,ti.

6. intensive care.ab,kw,ti.

7. critically ill patient.ab,kw,ti.

8. intensive care unit/

9. critical illness/

10. critically ill patient/

11. intensive care/

12. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5 OR 6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10 OR 11 = 359676
13. Double-blind procedure.ab,sh,ti.
14. crossover prodecure.ab,sh,ti.
15. single-blind procedure.ab,sh,ti.
16. (crossover* or cross over*).ab,ti.
17. placebo*.ab,ti.
18. (doubl* adj blind*).ab,ti.
19. allocate*.ab,ti.
20. trial.ab,ti.
21. randomized controlled trial.ab,sh,ti.
22. randomised controlled trial.ab,sh,ti.
23. random*.ab,sh,ti
24. 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23= 2002009
25. "Quality of life"/
26. Quality of life.mp.
27. health related quality of life.mp.
28. quality life.mp.
29. life quality.mp.
30. quality of life assessment.mp.
31. "quality of life assessment"/
- 32 "quality adjusted life years"/
33. 25 OR 26 OR 27 OR 28 OR 29 OR 30 OR 31 OR 32= 500510
37. 12 AND 24 AND 33 = **1297 Filters:human=1243**

CINAHL

Population #P

1. (MH "Critical Illness") OR (MH "Critically Ill Patients")
2. (MH "Critical Care+")
3. (MH "Intensive Care Units+") OR (MH "Critical Care Nursing+")

4. AB (critical illness) OR AB (critical care) OR AB (intensive care unit)
5. TI (critical illness) OR TI (critical care) OR TI (intensive care unit)
6. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5 =85340
7. (MH clinical trials+)
8. PT clinical trial
9. TX clinic* n1 trial*
10. TX ((singl* n1 blind) or (singl* n1 mask*)) or ((doubl* n1 blind*) or (doubl* n1 mask*)) or ((tripl* n1 blind*) or (tripl* n1 mask*)) or ((trebl* n1 blind*) or (tebl* n1 mask*))
11. TX randomi* control* trial*
12. (MH random assignment)
13. TX random* allocate*
14. TX placebo*
15. (MH placebos)
16. (MH "quantitative studies")
17. TX allocate* random*
18. 5 OR 6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 = 983,464
17. (MH "Health and Life Quality (Iowa NOC)+") OR (MH "Quality of Life+") OR (MH "Quality of Life (Iowa NOC)") OR (MH "Quality-Adjusted Life Years")
18. (MH "Patient-Reported Outcomes")
19. (TX quality of life) OR (TX health related quality of life) OR (TX patient-reported outcomes)
20. 17 OR 18 OR 19 =103548
21. 6 AND 18 AND 20 = **706**

COCHRANE Library

Population #P

1. (critical care):ti,ab,kw
2. ("intensive care"):ti,ab,kw
3. ("critically ill"):ti,ab,kw
4. MeSH descriptor: [Critical Illness] explode all trees
5. MeSH descriptor: [Intensive Care Units] explode all trees

6. MeSH descriptor: [Critical Care] explode all trees
7. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5 OR 6= 85761
8. MeSH descriptor: [Quality of Life] explode all trees
9. MeSH descriptor: [quality adjusted life years] explode all trees
10. (quality of life)
11. (quality life)
12. (health related quality of life)
13. (hrqol)
14. ("QOL")
15. ("quality adjusted life expectancies")
16. (health assessment questionnaire)
17. 8 OR 9 OR 10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 = 23408
18. 7 AND 17 = 1647 (Only trials: **1647**)

Hits total = 7424

PAPER II

*Non-response for health-related quality of life outcomes in ICU patients: A systematic review
of the reporting in randomised trials*

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Non-response for health-related quality of life outcomes in ICU patients: A systematic review of the reporting in randomised trials

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær¹ | Ingrid Egerod¹ | Anders Perner¹

¹Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

²Department of Cardiothoracic Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

Correspondence

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Blegdamsvej 9, DK-2100, Copenhagen, Denmark.
Email: maj-brit.noerregaard.kjaer@regionh.dk

Abstract

Background: Health-related quality of life (HRQoL) is frequently assessed in randomised clinical trials (RCTs) in the intensive care unit (ICU), but data are limited regarding the proportions of patients without responses or not surviving to HRQoL follow-up and the handling of this. We aimed to describe the extent and pattern of missing HRQoL data in intensive care trials and describe how these data and deaths were handled statistically.

Methods: We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis following a published protocol. We searched PubMed, EMBASE, CINAHL and Cochrane Library for RCTs involving adult ICU patients reporting HRQoL as an outcome and excluded RCTs unobtainable in full text. We performed risk of bias assessment independently and in duplicate.

Results: We included 196 outcomes from 88 RCTs published in the years 2002–2022; the numbers of patients alive and eligible to respond HRQoL were reported in 76% of trials. At follow-up, median 27% (interquartile range 14%–39%) of patients had died, and median 20% (9%–38%) of survivors did not respond across outcomes. Analyses of 80% of outcomes were restricted to complete cases only. The handling of non-survivors in analyses were reported for 46% of outcomes, with 26% of all outcomes reported as including non-survivors (using the value zero or the worst possible score).

Conclusion: For HRQoL outcomes in ICU trials, we found that mortality at time of follow-up was high and non-response among survivors frequent. The reporting and statistical handling of these issues were insufficient, which may have biased results.

KEYWORDS

attrition bias, HRQoL, long-term outcomes, non-respondents, non-survival

Editorial Comment

Long-term follow-up is important with quality of life reporting after interventional clinical studies, and missing values for these outcomes present challenges for understanding trial results. In

this systematic review, intensive care unit trial results were assessed for quality of life outcome reporting, where missing values were shown to be prominent for some studies. How missing values are managed in study analysis is a challenge, as a possible major source of systematic error (bias) influencing results.

1 | INTRODUCTION

More patients survive intensive care unit (ICU) admission,¹ but survivors frequently experience long-term morbidity including new or aggravated physical, psychological and mental disabilities.^{2,3} As a consequence more ICU research is now using other patient-important outcomes including health-related quality of life (HRQoL).⁴⁻⁶

In systematic reviews, it has been highlighted that missing HRQoL assessments are common and present a well-known challenge in randomised clinical trials (RCTs), particularly in long-term follow-up of HRQoL, where loss-to-follow is frequent.⁶⁻¹¹ A scoping review of RCTs in the ICU setting found high mortality as an additional challenge complicating analysis, reporting and interpretation of HRQoL outcomes.⁶ Furthermore, interventions might affect both death and HRQoL, possibly in opposite directions (i.e., if the intervention results in survival of sicker patients, who most likely will have lower HRQoL¹²), thus further complicating interpretations.

Loss-to-follow-up, and thereby missing data, may impact HRQoL results^{7,8,13,14} and introduce attrition bias, as non-response may be associated with severity of illness and other patient characteristics.^{7,8,13,14} Transparency in reporting and handling of missing data is therefore imperative for valid interpretation of trial results.^{12,15,16}

Complete case analysis, which disregards patients with missing data, has been reported as the most frequent approach for HRQoL outcomes,¹⁷ however, excluding patients with missing data impacts the power and potentially the validity on the outcome if data are not missing completely at random.¹⁸ In a systematic review of RCTs with long-term outcomes across medical specialties, 50% handled missing data using mean imputation as a sensitivity analysis supplementing the complete case analysis.¹¹ This is not recommended as it does not correct potential bias and gives a falsely increased precision of the result.¹⁸ Further, one third of the RCTs did not provide reasons for missing outcome data.¹¹

Research into missing HRQoL data in ICU RCTs is limited with undisclosed questions considering non-response equated with methodological issues to the RCTs design. The mentioned systematic reviews concerning HRQoL, and missing data were limited in time-span, included not only RCTs, and risk of bias was not assessed. Therefore, we primarily aimed to describe the extent and pattern of missing HRQoL data in ICU RCTs and how missing data and death were handled statistically, as we hypothesised that many data on HRQoL would be missing and that higher risk of bias, larger RCTs, HRQoL being a non-primary outcome, HRQoL assessed with an extensive tool, and longer follow-up time would be associated with increased non-response.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study design and registration

We conducted a systematic review of RCTs in accordance with a published protocol and analysis plan¹⁹ and the recommendations of the Cochrane Collaboration.²⁰ The protocol was registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) (www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospere; registration number: CRD42019118932). Protocol deviations and rationales are described in the supplement.

Results are reported according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) 2020 statement (checklist included in the supplement).²¹

2.2 | Objectives

Our primary objectives were to assess the proportions of missing HRQoL data due to non-response and to assess the proportion of non-survivors at the HRQoL follow-up time-point. For the primary objectives, we also assessed whether the proportion of non-respondents was reported quantitatively and discussed, and how the proportion of non-response was affected by relevant trial or outcome characteristics.

Secondary objectives were to assess whether baseline characteristics were compared between respondents and non-respondents, and which analytic strategies were used for handling missing data and non-survivors in the HRQoL analyses.

Tertiary objectives were testing of the aforementioned hypotheses by exploring the distribution of proportion of non-respondents in the following subgroups: risk of bias (low, some concerns or high), trial size (small trials $n \leq 100$ or large trials $n > 100$), outcome level (primary, secondary or tertiary outcome), length of tool used (short being the EQ-5D questionnaire in all variations or long being SF-36 or RAND-36), and follow-up time (≤ 90 days, >90 and ≤ 180 days or >180 days).

2.3 | Eligibility

We included RCTs of adult ICU patients (as defined in the original RCT) where HRQoL (by any score as defined by the original trial) at any follow-up time point(s) was reported as an outcome. Trials assessing interventions that started or were administered in the ICU were included. We only excluded RCTs that we were unable to obtain in full text.

2.4 | Search methods for identification of studies

We applied a systematic and sensitive search strategy designed to include RCTs without limitations to language, publication year or journal.²² We searched four databases: The Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL) in The Cochrane Library, PubMed, Excerpta Medica Database (Embase) Ovid, and Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL). The search strategies for all databases are presented in the supplement. The final search was conducted on 3 October 2022.

We used the PubMed e-mail alert service My National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) to keep track of newly published studies. We also searched other resources by hand-searching reference lists of relevant RCTs, systematic reviews, meta-analyses and editorials on HRQoL follow-up. For RCTs published as posters/abstracts/letters, we sought the full manuscripts by contacting the authors twice before excluding the RCTs in question.

2.5 | Study selection and data extraction

Two authors (Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Nick Meier) independently and in duplicate screened titles/abstracts. Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Martin Bruun Madsen and Nick Meier independently assessed all potentially relevant papers as full-texts and categorised the excluded papers (to be found in the supplement). Discrepancies were resolved through consensus or by discussion with a senior author (Morten Hylander Møller or Anders Perner). If there were duplicate publications, companion documents or multiple reports of a primary study, we used the most complete dataset aggregated across all known publications. If in doubt, the publication reporting HRQoL as a primary or secondary outcome was prioritised. We used Rayyan QCRI (Rayyan Systems Inc., Boston, MA) for study screening and selection.²³

Data were extracted independently and in duplicate by Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær and Martin Bruun Madsen or Nick Meier. We pilot-tested and refined the extraction sheet (Table S1, supplement) after the first 5 and subsequent 10 papers.

2.6 | Extracted characteristics

We extracted both trial characteristics and baseline characteristics according to our protocol.¹⁹ For the primary and secondary aim, we extracted follow-up time (days); method(s) for obtaining HRQoL; description regarding the handling of missing data; method(s) used to handle missing data; method(s) used to handle non-survivors; the number of patients alive at the main HRQoL follow-up time point; the number of non-respondents; the number of non-survivors; risk of bias; trial size; whether HRQoL was a primary, secondary, or other outcome; reported follow-up time point(s); the HRQoL tool(s) used; and whether HRQoL was used for health economy analyses. For RCTs reporting HRQoL outcomes at multiple time-points

and/or using multiple tools, these were included as separate outcomes.

For RCTs where we could not locate a protocol or statistical analysis plan, we contacted the corresponding author twice per e-mail, to make sure we did not miss these supplemental materials.

Data extraction was performed using Excel (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA).

2.7 | Definitions

1. Non-respondents were defined as all eligible patients invited to answer the HRQoL questionnaire at the follow-up time point (i.e., non-survivors are not considered non-respondents), but who did not respond due to emigration, withdrawal of consent, loss to follow-up,²⁴ or failure to answer the questionnaire for any other reason. Those who did not receive the intervention were not considered non-respondents (modified intention-to-treat principle).
2. Respondents were defined as those who replied to the questionnaire and includes both patients and proxies' responses.
3. Non-survivors were all patients that died before the follow-up time-point of the HRQoL outcome.

2.8 | Risk of bias

We assessed risk of bias using the Risk of Bias tool 2 (RoB 2) for the HRQoL outcomes,²⁵ according to the treatment assignment (i.e., the intention-to-treat principle). The assessment was performed independently and in duplicate by two of three authors (Maj-Brit Nørregaard

TABLE 1 Trial-level characteristics.

Variable	All trials (n = 88)
Year	2019 (2016–2021) [2002–2022]
Sample size	311 (116–892) [20–7000]
<i>Trial design</i>	
Fully blinded ^a	30 (34%)
International	30 (34%)
Number of countries	1 (1–2)
Full protocol available	57 (65%)
HRQoL outcomes per trial	2 (1–3) [1–9]
HRQoL assessed as part of health-economic analysis	58 (30%)

Note: Numeric data are presented with medians (interquartile ranges) [full ranges] and categorical data are presented with numbers and (percentages). There were no missing data for the variables presented in this table.

^aTrials were categorised as fully blinded if (1) patients and clinicians were blinded, (2) the participant was blinded; this way, the HRQoL outcome assessor (patient) and the trial personal obtaining the outcome were fully blinded.

TABLE 2 Outcome-level.

Variables	All (n = 196 outcomes)
Follow-up time (days) ^a	
All outcomes ^b	180 (90–180 [0–1461])
Day 90 ^b	42 (26%)
Day 180 ^b	58 (36%)
Day 365 ^b	27 (17%)
Methods for obtaining HRQoL ^c	
Telephone	71 (49%)
Ordinary mail	61 (42%)
By proxy ^d	25 (17%)
Personal interview	24 (17%)
Retention strategy ^e	51 (35%)
Other ^f	3 (2%)
Descriptive handling of missing data ^g	
Not reported: assumed to be complete case analysis	104 (53%)
Number of non-respondents reported	165 (84%)
Discussion of potential attrition bias	93 (47%)
Baseline characteristics compared between respondents and non-respondents?	33 (17%)
Method used to handle missing data ^h	
Not reported: assumed to be restricted to survivors only	105 (54%)
Complete case analysis	55 (28%)
Simple imputation ⁱ	3 (2%)
Multiple imputation	39 (20%)
Sensitivity analysis ^j	6 (3%)
Method used to handle non-survivors ^k	
Not reported: assumed to be survivors only	105 (54%)
Survivors only	41 (21%)
Dead assigned zero or the worst score	51 (26%)
Other ^l	6 (3%)

Note: Numeric data are presented with medians (interquartile ranges) [full ranges] and categorical data are presented with numbers (percentages).

^aMissing for 33 outcomes (17%).

^bThere were 19 different follow-up time points and trials could have several time points. The presented time points (day 90, 180 and 365) are presented separately as they were the most common. Day 0 was at admission to the ICU.

^cMissing for 52 outcomes (28%). More than one method could be used.

^dEither by face-to-face interview or telephone interview.

^eRetention strategy is when trying more than one way to obtain HRQoL assessment and includes gift vouchers (6.1%) and a reminding phone call (26.5%) among others.

^fLetting the patient choose what is best for them—either mail or phone.

^gNo missing data due to the category ‘not reported’.

^hThe total percentage will not match 100% as some outcomes used more than one method to handle missing data.

ⁱLast assessment carried forward.

^jSensitivity analyses used for these outcomes were best-worst/worst-best (or the other way around) case scenarios.

^kThe total percentage will not match 100% as some outcomes used more than one method to handle non-survivors.

^lOther ways to handle non-survivors were imputation of dead using ‘survivor average causal effect’ (2 outcomes), better worst case scenario (one outcome), sensitivity analyses (one outcome) and composite score (“Lachin 3”) where (a) survivors were ranked higher than non-survivors with non-survivor ranking according to time to death with early mortality considered worse than late mortality and (b) the EQ-5D-3L health state scale, lower health scores were considered a worse outcome than higher scores (one outcome).

Kjær, Nick Meier and Martin Bruun Madsen). Disagreements were resolved by consensus upon consultation with Anders Granholm, Morten Hylander Møller, or Anders Perner. If an RCT had more than one outcome, they were assigned the same risk of bias assessment.

2.9 | Statistical analyses

Trial-level and outcome-level characteristics (including the proportion of outcomes for which the number of non-respondents was reported)

were summarised descriptively using medians with interquartile ranges (IQRs) and full ranges for numeric data and numbers with percentages for categorical data. The proportions of missing data are presented for all variables.

The proportions of non-survivors and non-respondents across all outcomes were similarly summarised descriptively using medians with IQRs and full ranges. Proportions were meta-analysed using random effects models, which assume that the underlying proportions vary across RCTs, but follows normal distributions of which the mean values along with their 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were estimated.²⁰ In addition to the primary analyses, separate subgroup analyses were conducted, with proportions in each subgroup analysed similarly and absolute risk differences (RDs) between subgroups with 95% CIs calculated based on the separate subgroup results.¹⁹ Overall subgroup differences were assessed with test-of-interaction *P*-values. In cases where multiple outcomes from the same RCT were included in one of the overall analyses or in a specific subgroup, the mean numerators/denominators across those outcomes from the same RCT were meta-analysed, to avoid double counting and due to high expected correlations in the proportions of non-respondents and non-survivors. The approximate total numbers of individual patients in each meta-analysis (including subgroups) were estimated by using the highest denominator for each outcome from the same RCT included in a particular outcome/subgroup analysis.

A *P*-value <.05 is interpreted as statistically significant. Analyses were conducted using R (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria) v. 4.2.1 with the *meta* package v. 5.5-0.

3 | RESULTS

After removing duplicates, we found 10,075 unique records that were screened (Figure S1) and included 196 outcomes from 88 RCT reports published from 2002 to 2022. In the included RCTs, sample sizes ranged from 20 to 7000 participants and numbers of HRQoL outcomes from 1 to 9.

3.1 | Characteristics

Trial-level characteristics are summarised in Table 1, with additional details presented in Tables S2 and S3 in the supplement. Outcome-

level characteristics are summarised in Table 2. The follow-up time point was reported in 83% of the outcomes with a median of 180 days (range 0 to 1461 days).

3.2 | Primary objectives

The number of non-respondents was reported for 149 of 196 (76%) outcomes. The crude median proportion of non-respondents was 20% with an IQR of 9%–38%. The meta-analysis estimated mean proportion was 15% with a 95% CI of 11%–19% among 149 outcomes from 76 RCTs. The crude median proportion of non-survivors was 27% (IQR 14%–39%), while the meta-analysis estimated mean was 19% (95% CI 15%–25%) among 167 outcomes from 81 RCTs. Data on the primary objective for all RCTs and outcomes are presented in Table S4 in the supplement.

3.3 | Secondary objectives

For 33 outcomes (17%) a comparison of baseline characteristics for respondent's versus non-respondents was presented, although the potential of attrition bias was discussed in 47% (Table 2). In 17 of 88 RCTs (20%) it was discussed whether non-response might have caused bias and affected the result; in five (6%) the difficulty of obtaining long-term data from the critically ill population was stressed, and in two (2%) it was suggested that non-respondents were in poorer health than respondents.

Analysis methods for missing HRQoL outcomes were not described for 54% of the 196 outcomes, and therefore assumed to be complete case analysis, while complete case analysis was explicitly mentioned as the primary analysis method for 28% of outcomes. Multiple imputation was used for 20% of outcomes (Table 2). Handling of non-survivors in the analyses was reported for 46% of outcomes and in 26% of outcomes assigned to a value of zero or worst possible score.

HRQoL outcomes were adjudicated as overall low and high risk of bias in 22% and 61% of the RCTs respectively. Details on risk of bias assessments are presented in Figure 1 and Table S5 in the supplement. The most frequent domain with high risk of bias was 'missing outcome data', which was assigned if non-response was >20%. RCTs

FIGURE 1 Overall risk of bias of all 88 trials included.

TABLE 3 Primary objective and subgroup analyses of the proportion of non-respondents across trials.

Primary objective	Description of data included in the analysis	Distribution of proportion of non-respondents ^{a,b}	Mean proportion of non-respondents ^c (95% CI)	Outcomes with missing data		
Non-respondents	149 outcomes 76 trials 41,045 patients ^d	20% (9%–38%) [0%–72%]	15% (11%–19%)	47 (24%)		
Dead at follow-up	Description of data included in the analysis 167 outcomes 81 trials 62,445 patients ^d	Distribution of proportion of dead at follow-up ^{a,b} 27% (14%–39%) [0%–58%]	Mean proportion of dead at follow-up ^c (95% CI) 19% (15%–25%)	Outcomes with missing data 29 (15%)		
Subgroup analyses	Description of data included in the analysis	Distribution of proportion of non-respondents ^{a,b}	Mean proportion of non-respondents ^c (95% CI)	Risk difference ^c (95% CI)	Outcomes with missing data	Test for subgroup differences (p-value)
1. Risk of bias						
Low	34 outcomes 19 trials 18,570 patients ^d	9% (8%–16%) [2%–39%]	10% (8%–13%)	0% (reference)	47 (24%)	0.096
Some concerns	19 outcomes 12 trials 7288 patients ^d	19% (9%–41%) [0%–53%]	13% (6%–26%)	3% (–8%–9%)		
High	96 outcomes 45 trials 15,187 patients ^d	29% (13%–43%) [0%–71%]	17% (11%–26%)	7% (1%–11%)		
2. Trial size						
Small trials n ≤ 100	28 outcomes 13 trials 649 patients ^d	10% (7%–19%) [0%–39%]	15% (11%–18%)	0% (reference)	47 (24%)	0.786
Larger trials n > 100	121 outcomes 63 trials 40,396 patients ^d	25% (10%–42%) [0%–71%]	15% (11%–21%)	1% (–6%–6%)		
3. HRQoL outcome						
Primary	16 outcomes 10 trials 1063 patients ^d	8% (1%–13%) [0%–45%]	5% (1%–17%)	0% (reference)	63 (32%)	0.050
Secondary or tertiary	117 outcomes 57 trials 36,607 patients ^d	21% (9%–37%) [0%–71%]	17% (13%–22%)	12.3% (0%–16%)		
4. Shorter versus longer HRQoL tool						
					70 (36%)	0.053

(Continues)

TABLE 3 (Continued)

Subgroup analyses	Description of data included in the analysis	Distribution of proportion of non-respondents ^{a,b}	Mean proportion of non-respondents ^c (95% CI)	Risk difference ^c (95% CI)	Outcomes with missing data	Test for subgroup differences (p-value)
EQ-5D ^e (shorter)	80 outcomes 39 trials 30,697 patients ^d	21% (9%–40%) [0%–71%]	19% (15%–25%)	0% (reference)		
SF-36 ^f (longer)	46 outcomes 32 trials 6471 patients ^d	16% (8%–30%) [0%–48%]	12% (8%–18%)	–8% (–18%–0%)		
5. Follow-up time					70 (36%)	<0.001
≤90 days	47 outcomes 35 trials 13,937 patients ^d	16% (6%–30%) [0%–48%]	12% (8%–18%)	0% (reference)		
>90 and ≤180 days	52 outcomes 37 trials 22,705 patients ^d	18% (8%–38%) [0%–71%]	15% (10%–21%)	3% (–5%–8%)		
>180 days	27 outcomes 19 trials 7317 patients ^d	37% (22%–48%) [9%–63%]	35% (28%–43%)	24% (16%–28%)		

^aRaw proportion of non-respondents/non-survivors calculated presented as median percentages (interquartile ranges) [full range] across all outcomes.

^bSome trials reported multiple HRQoL outcomes, as HRQoL was reported at different time-points, assessed using different tools, or combinations thereof. The number of non-respondents is a proportion of the number of survivors at the time of follow-up.

^cEstimated mean proportions and risk-differences (with 95% CIs) obtained from meta-analyses of proportions using random effects models across all outcomes, assuming that the proportions follow a normal-distribution to account for between-trial heterogeneity in proportions. More detailed description in the 'statistical analysis' plan in the methods.

^dApproximate number of patients calculated as described in the methods section, by using the highest number of patients represented for a HRQoL outcome in each trial (to avoid double counting).

^eEQ-5D, EQ-5D-3L and EQ-5D-5L.

^fIncludes SF-36 and RAND-36.

where the trial participants were not blinded to the intervention was the most frequent methodological source of bias, as it is the participant who is the outcome assessor.²⁶ For 26 out of 88 (30%) trials the blinding procedure was not transparent and for 32 out of 88 (36%) the trial outcome assessor was blinded, but the participant unblinded (further details in Table S5).

3.4 | Tertiary objectives

The five subgroup analyses are presented in Table 3.

The main finding from the subgroup analyses were that non-response was statistically significant according to time to follow-up with a RD for non-response was 24% (95% CI 16%–28%) for >180 days and 3% (–5%–8%) for >90 and ≤180 days compared with ≤90 days ($p < .001$).

Figure 2A illustrates the proportion of non-respondents according to follow-up times, RCT sizes, and HRQoL tools used and Figure 2B the proportion of non-respondents according to year of publication.

4 | DISCUSSION

In this systematic review, we explored the reporting, analysis, and interpretation of missing HRQoL data in 88 ICU RCTs reporting 196 different HRQoL outcomes. We found that the proportions of non-respondents were substantial and in half of the RCTs the impact of missingness was not interpreted in relation to the results. Further, the statistical handling of non-response and non-survival was poorly reported (for half of the outcomes, not reported at all). Longer follow-up was associated with higher proportions of non-respondents.

A recent scoping review of ICU RCTs they found a lower number of missing HRQoL data.⁶ The reason for this difference was primarily due to the denominator including non-survivors in their calculation and we excluded the non-survivors resulting in higher missing, also findings may be explained by different timespan for including studies, and the inclusion of interventions commenced before ICU admission in the scoping review. Our results also varies from other reviews due to differences in settings, populations, study design, follow-up durations, and timespan for including studies.^{5,7–10,17} For this reason results are difficult to compare across reviews.

FIGURE 2 (A) Proportion of non-respondents according to follow-up time (on a logarithmic scale). The bubbles' sizes are relative to the sizes of each trial and colours illustrate the HRQoL tool used. EQ covers EQ-5D-3L, EQ-5D-5L and EQ-5D not defined further. RAND-SF36 covers both RAND-36 and SF-36. Other covers EQ VAS, SF-6D and so forth. The timepoints marked with lines are day 90, day 180 and day 365 seen from left. (B) Proportion of non-respondents according to year of population with the same illustration of trial size and HRQoL tool used as Figure 2A.

Missing HRQoL data are a challenge, which is aggravated when information regarding handling of incomplete data and comparison of baseline characteristics are unavailable,^{7,12,15} making it difficult to interpret whether or not missing data could bias the results.^{5,15,16} Non-response is a valid concern because of risk of selection bias,^{8,13,14,25} particular as non-response in ICU survivors has been shown to be associated with patient characteristics such as being male, younger, sicker and without a partner.¹⁴ Three of the RCTs included in the present study suggested that non-respondents could be in poorer health, more difficult to contact, or unable to complete the questionnaire.²⁷⁻²⁹ This is supported by other systematic reviews in ICU populations.^{5,7-9} In the present study, complete case analysis was used for almost 81% of outcomes.

Another review covering different medical specialties and study designs, described that missing data were handled by complete case analysis in most cases (79%) or single imputation techniques (19%), for example, either mean imputation, single regression imputation or last observation carried forward.¹⁷ Sensitivity analyses (not further detailed) were conducted in 11% of the studies to investigate the influence of missing data on their results.¹⁷ Another review concerning reporting and handling of missing values showed that 46% of ICU RCTs analysed missing HRQoL data using complete cases only, 36% did not provide information, 14% reported no missing data, while 5% used more advanced methods.¹⁰ Our findings are similar to these results as most outcomes in our study were analysed using complete case analysis, some using multiple imputation (20%), and a few single imputation (2%) or alternative methods (3%).

Non-survivors were not described for 54% of outcomes, which we interpreted as survivors only being included in the analyses. In the previously mentioned scoping review, they also found a fifth of the analyses being restricted to survivors only, and a quarter of the analyses assigned non-survivors zero or the worst score possible.⁶ Non-survivors are a challenge in RCTs with high mortality¹² and restricting analyses to survivors only may hamper interpretation of the results, especially if interventions have differential effects on mortality and HRQoL.¹² Mortality may be more appropriately handled by using methods with a precise value anchored to death, for example, as for EQ-5D index values,³⁰ where zero is considered as bad as being dead and values below zero correspond to health states worse than death.³¹

Our subgroup analysis confirmed our hypothesis that longer follow-up time was associated with higher non-response rate. Shorter HRQoL tool and trials using HRQoL for non-primary outcome had higher non-response rates, but level of risk of bias and trial size did not statistically significantly influence the response rate; however, this does not rule out that associations exist and the proportion of non-respondents seemed to be higher with increasing risk of bias.

The findings of this systematic review emphasise the challenges with reporting and interpretation of HRQoL outcomes and that the proportion of missing HRQoL data has not decreased over time. We found that inadequate reporting and handling of missing data is a significant concern in ICU RCTs reporting HRQoL outcomes as missing data are probably not missing completely at random. There are patient

reported outcome (PRO) checklists outlining the importance of considering how to minimise and report missing data.^{32,33} Retention strategies are important for long-term follow-up and should be pre-planned,^{34,35} together with pre-defined analyses including non-survivors in the primary HRQoL analyses along with survivors only, and finally, describing how missing data will be handled.

4.1 | Strengths and limitations

This systematic review has several strengths. We followed the methodology outlined in the published protocol,¹⁹ including adherence to the Cochrane Handbook's recommendations,²⁰ and reporting in accordance with the PRISMA statement.²¹ Further, we had no limitation of time or language in our search beside being able to obtain a full text manuscript of the RCT.

This systematic review also has some limitations, including several protocol deviations. One was to use the new RoB2 tool,²⁵ which is more nuanced regarding missing data than its pre-decessor, and became available after the protocol was written. Further, we deviated from the original analysis plan to properly estimate differences and uncertainty, and to improve our handling of between-study variation and the inclusion of multiple outcomes from some studies. Another limitation was that our search strategy included search terms for HRQoL, which may not have been indexed in search databases in all cases, potentially leading to relevant RCTs not being identified. Our search did not include the term 'health status'. Of note, we found 18 additional RCTs outside the search through hand search of other reviews.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

In this systematic review of RCTs conducted in the ICU with HRQoL reported as an outcome, we found that both non-response and non-survival was frequent. The proportions of non-respondents and non-survivors were insufficiently reported with sparse information regarding the statistical handling in most RCTs. Non-respondents and non-survivors were excluded from most analyses. Finally, longer follow-up times were associated with increased number of non-respondents. Together these findings call for improvements in the planning and design of RCTs in the ICU setting.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Martin Bruun Madsen, Morten Hylander Møller, Ingrid Egerod and Anders Perner contributed to the study conceptualization, and methodology. Anders Granholm conducted the formal analysis and visualisation, including the statistical changes to the published analysis plan. Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Martin Bruun Madsen and Nick Meier contributed to the search, screening and extraction of data. Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær wrote the original draft of the article. All authors contributed to writing, reviewing, and editing the article for critically important intellectual content. Anders Perner

was the supervisor. All authors approved the final version of the article.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

None of the authors have any relevant competing interests on the subject. The Department of Intensive Care, Rigshospitalet has received funding from The Novo Nordisk Foundation, Pfizer, Sygeforsikringen "danmark", and Fresenius Kabi and conducted contract research for AM-Pharma. The remaining authors have disclosed that they do not have any potential conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. All data are available in the supplement.

ORCID

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6536-0504>

Martin Bruun Madsen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5832-2262>

Nick Meier <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-4761-3228>

Anders Granholm <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5799-7655>

Morten Hylander Møller <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6378-9673>

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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Supplementary material to:

Nonresponse for health-related quality of life outcomes in ICU patients - A systematic review of the reporting in randomised trials

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Martin Bruun Madsen, Nick Meier, Anders Granholm, Morten Hylander Møller, Ingrid Egerod, Anders Perner

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Protocol deviations

The protocol was published in 2018¹. Afterwards, the following adjustments were made to the protocol:

In accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) 2020 statement we agreed to follow the new updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews.²

We assigned an additional author to independently and in duplicate extracting information from the included trials due to high number of trials included. Furthermore, we used Microsoft Excel, and not Rayyan QCRI, for data extraction.

If HRQoL was published as an additional/extended analysis of a primary published trial we extracted trial patient characteristics from the original trial, and details regarding HRQoL were extracted from study that published the HRQoL follow-up data.

We used the second version of the Risk of Bias tool (RoB2), published in 2019, instead of the protocolized original RoB tool from 2008. RoB2 has a more nuanced assessment of bias compared to the original RoB tool and assess risk of bias by signalling questions in five domains.

Instead of using Fisher's exact test for all analyses, we applied a more comprehensive method where estimated mean proportions and risk differences were used in meta-analyses of proportions using a random effects model across all outcomes, which considered heterogeneity across trials and allowed estimation of mean proportions with uncertainty for the primary outcomes. Fisher's exact test would have required raw pooling of all outcomes across multiple trials without considering between-trial heterogeneity and as this would not allow the estimation of differences with appropriate uncertainty measures (confidence intervals).

Fig. S1. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram

SAP statistical analysis plan, *ICU* intensive care unit, *HRQoL* health-related quality of life, *RCT* randomised clinical trial

*All authors were contacted for full-text paper if only abstract or letter available and excluded due to no reply, no full-text paper, or no librarian able to find the paper.

**Excluded reports with references are to be found in the supplement.

***Either HRQoL was not reported or the RCT did not use an HRQoL tool to calculate health economics.

From: Page MJ, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

Search Strategy

Databases:

PubMed, EMBASE, CINAHL & Cochrane Library

PubMed

Population #P

1. "Intensive Care Units" [MeSH]
2. "Critical care" [Mesh]
3. "Critical Illness" [Mesh]
4. critically ill [tiab]
5. critical care [tiab]
6. Intensive Care Units [tiab]
7. Intensive care unit [tiab]
8. intensive care [tiab]
9. icu [tiab]
10. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5 OR 6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 (Filters: humans)
((((((((("Intensive Care Units"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh])) OR ("Critical Care"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh]))
OR ("Critical Illness"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (critically ill AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (critical care
AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (intensive care unit AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (intensive care units AND
Humans[Mesh])) OR (intensive care AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (icu AND Humans[Mesh]))
11. randomized controlled trial [pt]
12. controlled clinical trial [pt]
13. randomized [tiab]
14. placebo [tiab]
15. drug therapy [sh]
16. randomly [tiab]
17. trial [tiab]
18. groups [tiab]
19. clinical trial [sh]
20. 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19, Filters: humans
((randomized controlled trial[pt] OR controlled clinical trial[pt] OR randomized[tiab] OR placebo[tiab] OR
drug therapy[sh] OR randomly[tiab] OR trial[tiab] OR groups[tiab]))
21. 10 AND 22
22. Quality of Life [MeSH Terms]
23. Quality Life [All Fields]
24. Quality of Life [All Fields]
25. Health Related Quality Life [All Fields]
26. Life Quality [All Fields]
27. Quality adjusted life years [Mesh]
28. Quality adjusted life years [All Fields]
29. 22 OR 23 OR 24 OR 25 OR 26 OR 27 OR 28 (Filters: Humans)
((((((((("Quality of Life"[Mesh] AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (quality life AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (quality of life
AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (life quality AND Humans[Mesh])) OR ("Quality-Adjusted Life Years"[Mesh] AND
Humans[Mesh])) OR (Quality-Adjusted Life Years AND Humans[Mesh])) OR (health related quality life AND
Humans[Mesh]))

EMBASE Ovid

Population #P

1. intensive care unit.ab,kw,ti.
2. critical care.ab,kw,ti.
3. critically ill.ab,kw,ti.
4. icu.ab,kw,ti.
5. critical illness.ab,kw,ti.
6. intensive care.ab,kw,ti.
7. critically ill patient.ab,kw,ti.
8. intensive care unit/
9. critical illness/
10. critically ill patient/
11. intensive care/
12. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5 OR 6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10 OR 11
13. Double-blind procedure.ab,sh,ti.
14. crossover prodecure.ab,sh,ti.
15. single-blind procedure.ab,sh,ti.
16. (crossover* or cross over*).ab,ti.
17. placebo*.ab,ti.
18. (doubl* adj blind*).ab,ti.
19. allocate*.ab,ti.
20. trial.ab,ti.
21. randomized controlled trial.ab,sh,ti.
22. randomised controlled trial.ab,sh,ti.
23. random*.ab,sh,ti
24. 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23
25. "Quality of life"/
26. Quality of life.mp.
27. health related quality of life.mp.
28. quality life.mp.
29. life quality.mp.
30. quality of life assessment.mp.
31. "quality of life assessment"/
32. "quality adjusted life years"/
33. 25 OR 26 OR 27 OR 28 OR 29 OR 30 OR 31 OR 32
37. 12 AND 24 AND 33

CINAHL

Population #P

1. (MH "Critical Illness") OR (MH "Critically Ill Patients")
2. (MH "Critical Care+")
3. (MH "Intensive Care Units+") OR (MH "Critical Care Nursing+")
4. AB (critical illness) OR AB (critical care) OR AB (intensive care unit)
5. TI (critical illness) OR TI (critical care) OR TI (intensive care unit)
6. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5
7. (MH clinical trials+)
8. PT clinical trial
9. TX clinic* n1 trial*
10. TX ((singl* n1 blind) or (singl* n1 mask*)) or ((doubl* n1 blind*) or (doubl* n1 mask*)) or ((tripl* n1 blind*) or (tripl* n1 mask*)) or ((trebl* n1 blind*) or (tebl* n1 mask*))

11. TX randomi* control* trial*
12. (MH random assignment)
13. TX random* allocate*
14. TX placebo*
15. (MH placebos)
16. (MH "quantitative studies")
17. TX allocate* random*
18. 5 OR 6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17
17. (MH "Health and Life Quality (Iowa NOC)+") OR (MH "Quality of Life+") OR (MH "Quality of Life (Iowa NOC)") OR (MH "Quality-Adjusted Life Years")
18. (MH "Patient-Reported Outcomes")
19. (TX quality of life) OR (TX health related quality of life) OR (TX patient-reported outcomes)
20. 17 OR 18 OR 19
21. 6 AND 18 AND 20

COCHRANE Library

Population #P

1. (critical care):ti,ab,kw
2. ("intensive care"):ti,ab,kw
3. ("critically ill"):ti,ab,kw
4. MeSH descriptor: [Critical Illness] explode all trees
5. MeSH descriptor: [Intensive Care Units] explode all trees
6. MeSH descriptor: [Critical Care] explode all trees
7. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5 OR 6
8. MeSH descriptor: [Quality of Life] explode all trees
9. MeSH descriptor: [quality adjusted life years] explode all trees
10. (quality of life)
11. (quality life)
12. (health related quality of life)
13. (hrqol)
14. ("QOL")
15. ("quality adjusted life expectancies")
16. (health assessment questionnaire)
17. 8 OR 9 OR 10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16
18. 7 AND 17

Excluded full text records

First search (6 September 2019):

Protocol/SAP (1–9)

Other setting/study population (10–33)

HRQoL not assessed (34–42)

Not an RCT (43–47)

Duplicate (10,11,48–52)

Secondary study to one already included - none

Other (poster, abstract, thesis, etc.) (53–68)

Second search (6 January 2022):

Protocol/SAP (69–73)

Other setting/study population (74–77)

HRQoL not assessed (78–81)

Not an RCT (82–85)

Duplicate (86–91,91–93)

Secondary study to one already included (89,90,94–97)

Other (trial not assessing HRQoL yet, poster, abstract, thesis, etc.) (98,99)

Third search (3 October 2022):

Protocol/SAP

Other setting/study population (74)

HRQoL not assessed (100–105)

Not an RCT (106,107)

Duplicate (86,86,89,96–98,106,108–112)

Secondary study to one already included (113–115)

Other (trial not retaining the allocation when assessing HRQoL, trial not assessing HRQoL yet, poster, abstract, thesis, etc.) (116–119)

Excluded full text records – references to the records

1. Cuthbertson BH, Rattray J, Johnston M, Wildsmith JA, Wilson E, Hernandez R, et al. A Pragmatic Randomised, Controlled Trial of Intensive Care follow up programmes in improving Longer-term outcomes from critical illness. The PRACTICAL study. *BMC Health Services Research*. 23 July 2007;7(1):116.
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Risk of Bias tool 2 – clarifications of how domains were assessed

We assessed risk of bias using the Risk of Bias tool 2 (RoB 2) for the HRQoL outcomes,³ according to the treatment assignment (i.e., the intention-to-treat principle). Each trial was identified according to the trial acronym and/or primary author and with reference to both the primary trial and sub-study if the HRQoL data were published as a secondary publication.

The five domains of the Risk of Bias tool 2 in details:

1) Bias due to the randomisation process. This domain refers to the primary publication of the trial. Some trials failed to describe the randomisation sequence, which left concerns regarding the randomisation process. We focused on the variables for HRQoL as age, pre-existing comorbidity, chronic health score, self-reported symptoms and social deprivation.⁴

2) Bias due to deviations from intended interventions. If the patient was not aware of the intervention or was unaware of the inclusion arm, we chose “N”. We also took into consideration the information the patients received if they received information from trial personal when obtaining consent. E.g., in a trial of early vs. standard nutrition we assigned “PY”, as we assume most patients would find out which allocation they received. If e.g., music therapy was compared with none while receiving noninvasive ventilation, “Y” was assigned.

3) Bias due to missing outcome data. For the signalling question 3.1 we chose “Y”, if more than 20% were nonrespondents and if missing completely at random (MCAR). In absence of extent of missing outcome data (e.g., no CONSORT diagram), “NI” was chosen. According to the ROB2 guideline, an arbitrary value of more than 20% missing results in concern about the missing data. This was our standard even though less missing might leave concerns for the self-reported HRQoL outcome.

Concerning signalling question 3.2. Evidence that missing was not biased. “Low ROB” was assigned if a sensitivity analysis was done. Sensitivity analyses needed to assess the potential impact that missing not at random could have on the estimated result.⁵ Comments were added if, e.g., the range of the sensitivity analysis was not included in the manuscript or supplement.

Concerning signalling question 3.3. If missing could depend on its true value. A difficult question for an outcome that should have been measured but was not. We investigated the author’s discussion and whether it was considered if the missing outcome was missing not at random, missing at random or missing completely at random? Was it transparent with nonrespondents compared between allocation groups? Missing HRQoL data would be something between missing at random and missing not at random and assigned; “Y” or “PY” if no comparison between groups was done and if it was not shown that missing not at random was likely.

4) Bias in measurement of the outcome. Double blinded trials were categorised as “Low ROB” as the assessor of HRQoL outcome predominantly was the patient.

4.3 All trials where the patient was not blinded were categorised as either “Y” or “PY”, as the patient was the outcome assessor when assessing HRQoL. Blinded outcome assessors (interviewers, e.g., clinicians or trial personal) were frequently used, and this reduced the risk of bias for 4.2, as it seemed unlikely that the blinded outcome assessors would differ from the interview procedure when they did not know which

allocation the patient had. The interviewer (research personal) were not the ones assessing HRQoL, but only the patient or the relative or alike if by proxy.

4.4 Patients might not have been aware of the allocation during the trial (as assessed in domain 2), e.g., in trials assessing fluid therapy or oxygenation targets. But the assessment of the HRQoL outcome was done after the patients gave informed consent and thereby becoming aware of the allocation. This awareness could affect the assessment if they, or family members, remember, or if they had an opinion about the intervention compared with standard care. E.g., patients might be aware of the allocation if the intervention was early physical therapy or rehabilitation; especially if the intervention continued beyond ICU admission.

4.5 "PY" was assigned. "Y" was assigned if there was doubt whether the patient was unaware of the allocation and if it was likely that this knowledge would affect the assessment. E.g., if rehabilitation intervention was continued after discharge versus a control group without rehabilitation intervention.

5) Bias in selection of the reported result. To assess bias in this domain demands the protocol or SAP, which we requested by e-mailing the corresponding author up to two times. This included trials only registered on clinicaltrials.gov or similar. In case of no reply, the domain would be assigned "some concerns" as we could not clarify whether any risk of bias occurred in the trial.

Table S1. Data extraction form

This is the final data extraction form after revision from the pilot-testing after the first 5 and subsequent 10 RCTs.

Author the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Year	DOI secondary paper	Secondary analysis or subgroup analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Protocol available?	Author (from the original trial)
Study details							
International (more than 1 country)	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Also published in:	Year (published)	Trial Intervention	Trial Comparator
Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Trial design (e.g. quasi - blinding)	No. Of patients randomised (ITT)	No. of arms	Primary outcomes	Secondary outcomes	Tertiary outcomes
Excluded before intervention (modified intention-to-treat)	No. of patients in arms (the study population for the original trial study)	Male (no. or pct.) (number preferred)	Male	Female (no. or pct.)	Female	Patients with septic shock (no. or pct.)	Patients with septic shock
		Baseline characteristics (as reported in the paper) - from the original trial.					
Age (mean or median)	Age	Age variation (IQR, Range or SD)	Age variation	SAPS (mean or median)	SAPS (2)	SAPS variation (IQR, range or SD)	SAPS variation
APACHE score (mean or median)	APACHE score	APACHE score variation (IQR, range or SD)	APACHE score variation	SOFA score (mean or median)	SOFA score	SOFA score variation (IQR, range or SD)	SOFA score variation

Patients with invasive mechanical ventilation (no. or pct.)	Patients with invasive mechanical ventilation	Patients with dialysis (no. or pct.)	Patients with dialysis	Patients with vasopressor (no. or pct.)	Patients with vasopressor	Patients with sepsis/severe sepsis (as defined by author) (no. or pct.)	Patient with sepsis/severe sepsis (as defined by author)
Planned follow-up time point (days)	Actual follow-up time point	Number of patients missing HRQoL data due to death before follow-up (numerator), each time point (number of deaths)	Number of patients missing HRQoL data due to death before follow-up (denominator) (n)	Proportion of missing HRQoL data due to nonresponders (all missing except death) (numerator), each time point	Proportion of missing HRQoL data due to nonresponders (denominator), each time point	Were missing data reported in quantity (Y/N)	Were missing data discussed (Y/N)
Extracted primary outcomes, repeated for all follow-up timepoints							
Comment (any comments from author)	Were baseline characteristics compared between respondents and nonrespondents (Y/N)	HRQoL tool used	HRQoL tools (if other or multiple)	Method used for obtaining HRQoL	Method - other (specify if different methods used at different time points)	Was HRQoL Primary or Secondary outcome (as described in the main trial)	Was HRQoL measured for a health economic analysis purpose
Secondary outcomes							
Analytic strategy was used for the handling of missing data?	Analytic strategy used - other	Analytic strategy - comment	Analytic strategy for missing due to death?	Analytic strategy for missing due to death - other	Analytic strategy for missing due to death - comment		

Table S2. Trial design

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Study details											
Hodgson, 2016	Australia, New Zealand	Critical Care Medicine	TEAM	DOI: 10.1097/CCM.00000000001643				RCT, feasibility, multicenter, outcome assessor-blinded	50	2	
Sosnowski, 2018	Australia	Pilot and Feasibility Studies	-	10.1186/s40814-017-0224-x				RCT singlecenter, feasibility. Outcome assessor blinded.	30	2	
Harvey, 2016	UK	Health technology assessment	CALORIES	10.3310/hta20280				RCT, multicenter, non-blindet	2400	2	12 participants requested complete
Messika, 2019	France	Eur Respir Journal	Mus-IRA	10.1183/13993003.01873-2018				RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor-blinded	113	2	
Lall, 2015	UK	Health technology assessment	OSCAR	10.3310/hta19230				RCT, multicenter, non-blinded	795	2	
Gates, 2013	UK	Health technology assessment	BALTI-2	10.3310/hta17380				RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	326	2	

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Allingstrup, 2017	Denmark	Intensive Care Medicin	EAT-ICU	10.1007/s00134-017-4880-3				RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor-blinded	203	2	2 died before randomisation and 2 withdrew consent
Doig, 2013	Australia, New Zealand	JAMA	EPaNIC	10.1001/jama.2013.5124				RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor-blinded.	1372	2	9 patients withdrew consent (not shown in consort diagram).
Troillet, 2011	France	Annals of Internal Medicine		10.7326/0003-4819-154-6-201103150-00002				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	216	2	
Kayambu, 2015	Australia	Intensive Care Medicine		DOI: 10.1007/s00134-015-3763-8				RCT, singlecenter, pilot-study. Double blinded	50	2	
Schaller, 2016	Germany, Austria, USA	Lancet		DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(16)31637-3				RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor-blinded	200	2	
Fossat, 2018	France	JAMA		DOI: 10.1001/jama.2018.9592				RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor-blinded	314	2	2 died before intervention

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Denehy, 2013	Australia	Critical care		DOI: 10.1186/cc12835				RCT phase II, singlecenter, outcome assessor-blinded	150	2	
Brummel, 2014	USA	Intensive Care Medicine	ACT-ICU	DOI 10.1007/s00134-013-3136-0				RCT, feasibility, singlecenter, outcome assessor-blinded	87	3	
Angus, 2006	USA	Crit Care Med		DOI: 10.1097/01.CCM.0000248727.29055.25	Long-term outcomes and cost cohort. New consent for follow-up needed (n=368) excluding a part of the original study population.	Taylor, 2004 , USA, <i>JAMA</i>	DOI: 10.1001/jama.291.13.1603	RCT, multicenter, triple-blinded	385	2	
Schädler, 2017	Germany	Der Anaesthesist		DOI: 10.1007/s00101-017-0276-6	Follow-up study of the ASOPI-trial.	Schädler, 2012 , Germany, <i>American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine</i>	DOI: 10.1164/rccm.201106-1127oc	RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	317	2	17 patients consent withdrawn or could not be reconstructed

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Taylor, 2016	Australia	Lancet, Respiratory Medicine		DOI: 10.1016/S2213-2600(16)30120-5	Pre-specified cost-effectiveness analysis of patients included in New South Wales, a cohort (n=3537) in the Crystalloid versus Hydroxyethyl Starch Trial (CHEST)	Myburgh, 2012 , Australia, <i>NEJM</i>	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1209759	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	7000	2	250 withdrew consent, 8 lost to follow-up
Madsen, 2017	Denmark	ICM	INSTINCT	10.1007/s00134-017-4786-0				RCT, singlecenter, double-blinded	100	2	
Jones, 2015	UK	Journal of Critical Care		10.1016/j.jcrc.2015.05.002				RCT, singlecenter, the nutrient double-blind and the physiotherapist single-blind to assessment	93	4	
Noguchi, 2017	Japan	Prostaglandins, Leukotrienes and Essential Fatty Acids		DOI: 10.1016/j.plefa.2017.09.018	Secondary analysis for the follow-up. In the analysis only responders were included (n=99).	Matsuoka, 2015 , Japan, <i>Journal of clinical psychiatri</i>	DOI: 10.4088/JCP.14m09260	RCT, singlecenter, double blinded	110	2	1 did not receive intervention.

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Jackson, 2010	Canada	American Journal Respir Crit Care Med		DOI: 10.1164/rccm.200903-0442OC	A priori planned substudy of the ABC trial. The substudy was a singlecenter study.	Girard, 2008 , USA, <i>Lancet</i>	DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(08)60105-1	RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	187	2	3 due to stroke, 1 due to cardiac surgery, 1 due to neurosurgery, and 2 due to dementia
Rygaard, 2016	Denmark	Intensive Care of Medicine	TRISS	DOI: 10.1007/s00134-016-4437-x	Predefined secondary analysis for 1-year follow-up of the TRISS trial. HRQoL reported for only Danish participants (n=777).	Holst, 2014 , Denmark, <i>NEJM</i>	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1406617	RCT, multicenter, partially blinded (statistician blinded for the allocation during analysis)	1005	2	1 withdrew consent for the use of data (1 randomisation in error and 4 withdrew consent not divided in allocation)
Gallagher, 2014	Australia	PLOS medicine	POST-RENAL	DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001601	Extended follow-up of the RENAL trial for participants alive at day 90 from randomisation (=810)	Bellomo, 2009 , Australia, <i>NEJM</i>	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa0902413	RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	1508	2	44 refused or withdrew.

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Cronberg, 2015	Sweden, Czech Republic, Denmark, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Norway, Australia, UK, Switzerland	JAMA Neurology	TTM	DOI: 10.1001/jamaneurol.2015.0169	Explorative analysis of cognitive function and QoL in the TTM trial (n=939)	Nielsen, 2013 , Sweden, <i>NEJM</i>	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMOA1310519	RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	950	2	11 (4 withdrawn on patients or surrogates request, 3 no cardiac arrest, 1 awake, 1 was not admitted to the ICU, 1 did not receive intervention and 1 SAH).

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Dinglas, 2016	USA	Thorax	SAILS	DOI: 10.1136/thoraxjnI-2015-208017	Follow-up study to the SAILS trial. Additional exclusion criteria were applied: <18 years old, non-English speaking, homeless or cognitively impaired, evaluated based on patients' status prior to hospitalisation using medical record review and/or interview with the patient and/or proxy (n=272)	Truwit, 2014, USA, NEJM	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMOA1401520	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	745	2	
Azevedo, 2019	Brazil	The Revista Brasileira de Terapia Intensiva		10.5935/0103-507X.20190025				RCT Phase II, singlecenter, non-blinded	138	2	17 (Dead <48h=2, Extubation=1, Misjudged criteria=7, Contra-indication to EN/PN=5, Other=2)

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Antonelli, 2005	Italy	Critical care medicine		10.1097/01.CCM.0000163401.77581.86				RCT, singlecenter, follow-up assessment double-blinded.	139	2	
Marasco, 2013	Australia	Journal American college of Surgeons		10.1016/j.jamcollurg.2012.12.024				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	46	2	
Wittbrodt, 2013	Denmark	Critical Care	6S	DOI: 10.1186/cc12586	Post-hoc analysis of the Danish survivors of the 6S-trial with HRQoL as primary outcome (n=295)	Perner, 2012 , Denmark, Sweden, Iceland, Finland, Norway, NEJM	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1204242	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	804	2	Two withdrew consent for use of their data (4 excluded after randomisation, but not seperated in allocation)
Freeman-Sanderson, 2016	Australia	Critical Care Medicine		10.1097/CCM.0000000000001610				RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor blinded (for some outcomes)	30	2	
Van Maastrigt, 2006	The Netherlands	Crit Care Med		10.1097/01.CCM.0000191266.72652.FA				RCT (equivalence), singlecenter, non-blinded	600	2	1 patient underwent CABG and additional surgery, 1 died during surgery

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Agus, 2017	UK, Ireland	Critical Care		DOI: 10.1186/s13054-017-1695-0	Cost-utility analysis alongside the HARP-2 trial	McAuley, 2014 , Northern Ireland, NEJM	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1403285	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	540	2	8 (2 were receiving a statin, 1 had elevated aminotransferase, 2 unable to have nasogastric tube inserted, 1 had elevated creatinin kinase level, 1 withdrew consent, 1 had other reason)
Dubois, 2017	Belgium, The Netherlands	Critical Care	LOGIC-2	10.1186/s13054-017-1799-6				RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	1550	2	
Ingels, 2001	Belgium	European Heart Journal		DOI:10.1093/eurheartj/ehi855	Pre-planned sub-analysis (n=970)	Van den Berghe, 2001 , Belgium, NEJM	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa011300	RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor blinded	1548	2	Excluded 14 - 5 due to participating in other trials and 9 were moribund (no consort diagram to see the distribution).

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Walsh, 2015	UK	Health Technology Assessment	UK-ABLE	DOI: 10.3310/hta21620	Only British participants from the international ABLE-trial (n=359). The primary objective for this subgroup analyses were not to compare the groups, but to compare EuroQol 5D utility scores with two different levels (EQ-5D-5L and EQ-5D-3L)	Lacroix, 2015, Canada, NEJM	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1500704	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	2510	2	Consort diagram does not fit with number in each group as according to table 1 (numbers used) even though intention-to-treat are used.
Zhu, 2018	Australia, New Zealand	Critical Care Medicine		DOI: 10.1097/CCM.00000000003221	Post hoc hypothesis-generating analysis of the Nephro-Protective trial (Doig et al.)	Doig, 2015, Australia, Intensive Care Medicine	doi: 10.1007/s00134-015-3827-9	RCT, multicenter, phase II, non-blinded	474	2	
Kurtoglu, 2015	Turkey	Turkish J Phys Med Rehab		DOI: 10.5152/tftrd.2015.04378				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	30	2	

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
Wright, 2017	UK	Thorax	EPICC	doi: 10.1136/thoraxjnl-2016-209858				RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	308	2	
Wischmeyer, 2017	USA, Canada, Belgium, France	Critical Care	TOP-UP	DOI: 10.1186/s13054-017-1736-8				RCT, multicenter, pilot trial, non-blinded	125	2	
Giraud, 2016	UK	Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience		DOI: 10.3389/fnagi.2016.00228				Pilot time-cluster RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	223	2	
Amundadottir, 2019	Iceland	European Journal of Physiotherapy		doi:10.1080/21679169.2019.1645880				RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	50	2	
Deane, 2020	Australia, New Zealand	American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine	TARGET	DOI: 10.1164/rccm.201909-1810OC	Secondary analysis to the target trial with	Chapman, 2018, Australia, NEJM	doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1811687	RCT, multicenter, patient-blinded	4000	2	N=42; Withdrew consent n=36, did not meet all in-/exclusion criteria and did not receive intervention n=5, no contacted for

Author, publication year for the follow-up study (if divided)	Country	Journal	Trial acronym (if any)	Identifying number (DOI/ISSN) for the HRQoL study	Secondary analysis or sub group analysis to the trial (descriptive)	Author, publication year (from the original trial, Country, Journal)	Identifying number: DOI/ISSN	Trial design (e.g. quasi) - blinding	No. Of patients randomised	No. of arms	Excluded before randomisation/after randomisation (modified intention-to-treat)
											consent n=1, duplicate n=1)
de Azevedo, 2021	Brazil	BMC Anesthesiology		doi:10.1186/s12871-021-01492-6				RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor blinded	211	2	N=30; due to death <48t, nutrition not provided etc.
Fan, 2021	China	American Journal of Translational Research		ISSN:1943-8141/AJTR0129071				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	116	2	
Hammond, 2020	Australia, New Zealand, Saudi Arabia, Denmark, UK	ICM	ADRENAL	doi.org/10.1007/s00134-020-06169-1	6-month follow-up from the ADRENAL trial for patients discharged from hospital.	Venkatesh, 2018 , Australia, NEJM	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMOA1705835	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	3800	2	Modified ITT 114 = 3,686 (27 provided consent for baseline data only, 87 consent not provided)
Irving, 2019	Australia, New Zealand, Ireland, Finland, Saudi Arabia	Critical care medicine	TRANSFUSE	DOI: 10.1097/CCM.0000000003781	Secondary study	Cooper, 2017 , Australia, NEJM	DOI: 10.1056/NEJMOA1707572	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	4994	2	N=75; 39 withdrew consent and 36 lost to follow-up

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Liu, 2017	China	Patient Education and Counseling		doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2021.10.004				Cluster RCT, multicenter, non-blinded	548	2	
Mao, 2020	China	International Journal of Clinical Experimental Medicine		ISSN:1940-5901/IJCEM0102547				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	86	2	
Martin, 2021	USA	Annals ATS		DOI: 10.1513/AnnalsATS.202010-1282OC				RCT, multicenter, feasibility, blinded assessor of speech intelligibility	20	2	
Mou, 2020	China	International Journal of Experimental Medicine		ISSN:1940-5901/IJCEM0120861				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded.	106	2	No consort diagram
Nickels, 2020	Australia	Journal of Critical Care	CYCLIST	10.1016/j.jcrc.2020.05.008				RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor blinded	74	2	

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Nielsen, 2020	Denmark	Australian Critical Care	DRIP	10.1016/j.aucc.2019.01.004				RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	116	2	2 did not receive intervention (withdrawal of consent).
Olsen, 2021	Denmark, Norway, Sweden	Acta Anaesthesiologica Scandinavica	NONSEDA	10.1111/aas.13775	Follow-up of the NONSEDA trial	Olsen, 2020, Denmark, NEJM	10.1056/NEJMoa1906759	RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	710	2	N=10; 7 withdrew consent, 1 home ventilated and 2 never intubated
Pandian, 2020	USA	The Laryngoscope	-	10.1002/lary.28211				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded.	50	2	
Perkins, 2019	UK	Health Technology Assessment	Breathe	10.3310/hta23480				RCT, multicenter, non-blinded	364	2	
Rood, 2019	The Netherlands	Anesthesiology	REDUCE	10.1097/ALN.00000000002812	Predefined substudy in 9 of the 21 ICUs participating (n=1245). The substudy consists of those completing the baseline questionnaire.	van den Boogaard, 2018, The Netherlands, JAMA	10.1001/jama.2018.0160	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	1796	3	7

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Viana, 2021	Switzerland	Clinical Nutrition	-	10.1016/j.clnu.2021.07.018				RCT, singlecenter, double-blinded.	37	2	N=7; 2 withdrew consent, 1 lost in transfer, 4 early death
Waldauf, 2021	Czech Republic	Thorax	-	10.1136/thoraxjnl-2020-215755				RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor blinded	150	2	
Xu, 2021	China	Annals of Palliative Medicine	-	10.21037/apm-21-1192				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	140	2	N=30, 19 lost to follow-up on data, 11 lack complete clinical information
Zeng, 2021	China	American Journal Translational Research	-	ISSN:1943-8141/AJTR0127249				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded	134	2	NA
Morris, 2016	USA	JAMA		doi: 10.1001/jama.2016.7201				RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor-blinded.	300	2	

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Rublee, 2002	USA, Czech Republic, South Africa, UK, Denmark, Germany (and 13 others)	Critical care		DOI: 10.1186/cc1529	Not preplanned follow-up study. Not described in the main manuscript. They refer to a protocol in Warren et al. though not able to locate. Asked author.	Warren, 2001 , USA, JAMA	doi:10.1001/jama.286.15.1869	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded.	2339	2	N=25; 21 no intervention received, 2 withdrew consent, 2 28-day status unknown
Lemkes, 2020	The Netherlands	JAMA Cardiology		doi:10.1001/jamacardio.2020.3670	In the 1-year analysis presented herein, data were included for all patients who had the 1-year follow-up and did not retract consent (n=522).	Lemkes, 2019 , The Netherlands, NEJM	DOI:10.1056/NEJMoa1816897	RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded.	552	2	14 refused informed consent
Mackle, 2020	Australia, New Zealand	NEJM	ICU-ROX	doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1903297				RCT, multicenter, assessor-blinded	1000	2	35 withdrew consent for ascertainment of the primary outcome
Bagshaw, 2020	Canada + 17 countries	NEJM	STARRT-AKI-2020	doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2000741				RCT, multicenter, non-blinded.	3019	2	50 randomised not eligible, 27 withdrew consent, 15 LTFU

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Dixon, 2021	Australia	Lancet	CHARLI	doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(20)30470-7				RCT, multicenter, double blinded.	256	2	4 (3 withdrew consent, 1 ineligible)
Ginde, 2019	USA	NEJM	VIOLET	doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1911124				RCT, multicenter, double-blinded.	1360	2	33 (14 did not receive vitamin D, 1 withdrew consent, 1 received placebo but had not provided adequate consent and 17 did not receive placebo)
Hughes, 2021	USA	NEJM	MENDS2	doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2024922				RCT, multicenter, double blinded.	432	2	10 did not receive trial drug
Lamontagne, 2020	UK	JAMA	65-trial	doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.0930				RCT, multicenter, non-blinded	2600	2	2 duplicate patients not divided in allocation (first randomisation included)

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Laterre, 2019	Belgium, Denmark, France, the Netherlands, USA	JAMA	SEPSIS-ACT	doi:10.1001/jama.2019.14607				RCT, adaptive phase 2b/3, multicenter, double-blinded.	868	2	40 (28 not eligible at planned dosing, 6 died, 5 withdrawn by investigator, 1 withdrawn by investigator)
Litton, 2021	Australia	ICM	ROCIT	doi.org/10.1007/s00134-020-06322-w				RCT, multicenter, double-blinded.	221	2	1 had pacemaker, 1 had pacemaker and heart valve, 1 received immunosuppressive medication.
Amrein, 2014	Austria	JAMA	VITdAL-ICU	doi:10.1001/jama.2014.13204				RCT, singlecenter, double-blinded	492	2	17 (9 did not receive vitamin D3, 3 did not receive placebo, 5 withdrew consent)
Moss, 2019	USA	NEJM	ROSE	doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1901686				RCT, multicenter, unblinded.	1008	2	2 withdrawn - ineligible

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Parke, 2021	New Zealand	CCM		doi: 10.1097/CCM.00 0000000004883				RCT, multicenter, open-label, participants blinded to allocation	715	2	0
Pickkers, 2018	The Netherlands, Austria, Brussels, USA, France, Ireland, Finland, Spain, Germany, Italy, Czech Republic	JAMA	STOP-AKI	doi:10.1001/jama.2018.14283				Adaptive, two stages RCT, multicenter, double blinded.	301	2	0
Ridley, 2018	Australia, New Zealand	CCM		doi: 10.1186/s13054-018-1939-7				RCT, pilotstudy, non-blinded	100	2	1 withdrew consent and all data
Roquilly, 2021	France	JAMA	COBI	doi:10.1001/jama.2021.5561				RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded	370	2	0

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Shehabi, 2019	Australia, Ireland, Italy, Malaysia, New Zealand, Saudi Arabia, Switzerland, and UK	NEJM	SPICE III	doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1904710				RCT, multicenter, non-blinded	4000	2	96 withdraw consent and use of data
Wade, 2019	UK	JAMA	POPPI	doi:10.1001/jama.2019.0073				Cluster RCT, multicenter, unblinded	669	2	3 withdrew and 1 ineligible
Laterre, 2021	Belgium, Denmark, France, the Netherlands, USA	ICM	AdrenOSS-2	doi.org/10.1007/s00134-021-06537-5				RCT Phase 2a, multicenter, double-blinded	301	2	0
Granholt, 2022	Denmark, Sweden, Switzerland, India	ICM	COVID STEROID 2	doi.org/10.1007/s00134-022-06677-2	Pre-planned long term outcomes from the COVID STEROID 2 trial.	Munch, 2021 , Denmark, Sweden, Switzerland, India, JAMA	doi.10.1001/jama.2021.18295	RCT, multicenter, double-blinded	1000	2	18
Silversides, 2022	UK	ICM	RADAR-2	doi: 10.1007/s00134-021-06596-8				RCT, multicenter, feasibility, outcome assessor-blinded.	180	2	1 withdraw consent

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Crescioli, 2022	Denmark, Finland, Iceland, the Netherlands, Norway, Switzerland, UK	ICM	HOT-ICU	doi: 10.1007/s00134-022-06695-0	Pre-planned longt term outcomes from the HOT-ICU trial.	Scjørring, 2021 , Denmark, Finland, Iceland, the Netherlands, Norway, Switzerland, UK, NEJM	10.1056/NEJMOA2032510	RCT, multicenter, outcome assessor blinded.	2928	2	40 had consent for the use of data withdrawn or unobtainable - 4 lost to follow-up
Bellingan, 2022	UK, USA	ICM	MUST-ARDS	doi: 10.1007/s00134-021-06570-4				RCT (1/2), multicenter, double-blinded	30	2	0
Campos, 2022	Brazil	CCM		doi: 10.1097/CCM.0000000000005557				RCT, singlecenter, non-blinded.	139	2	65 (48 deaths, 17 not able to complete the protocol)
Bisset, 2022	Australia	Australian Critical Care	IMPROVe	doi: 10.1016/j.aucc.2022.07.002				RCT, singlecenter, outcome assessor blinded.	70		
Lamontagne, 2022	Canada, France and New Zealand	NEJM	LOVIT	doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2200644				RCT, multicenter. Double-blinded.	872		8 not eligible per adjudication, 1 withdrew consent for all data

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Boyle, 2022	UK	Thorax	REST	doi: 10.1136/thoraxjn I-2022-218874		McNamee, 2021, UK, JAMA	doi: 10.1001/jama. 2021.13374	RCT, multicenter. Non-blinded.	412		

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Study details/design							
Hodgson, 2016	Early goal-directed mobilisation	Standard care	1) Expected invasively ventilated the day after tomorrow, 2) ≥18 years, 3) <48 hours since eligibility criteria were met	1) Second or subsequent ICU admission during a single hospital admission, 2) If unable to follow simple verbal commands in English, 3) Death was deemed inevitable and imminent by the ICU consultant, 4) If unable to walk without assistance of another person prior to the ICU admission, 5) If unable to walk without assistance of another person prior to the ICU admission, 6) If they were diagnosed with dementia prior to current acute illness as assessed by hospital records, 7) If they had written rest in bed orders due to documented injury or process that precluded mobilization such as suspected or proven instability of spine or pelvis, 8) Severe acute brain injury, 9) If in the opinion of the treating clinician it was unsafe to commence mobility therapy	If Early goal-directed mobilisation resulted in: a) higher maximum level of activity assessed by ICU mobility scale and b) increased duration of activity measured in minutes per day during the ICU	Time from admission to randomisation and from admission to first mobilisation, Duration of mechanical ventilation, Total inpatient stay (days in the acute hospital and the rehabilitation hospital), Serious adverse events, Ventilator-free days, ICU-free days at day 28, Physical function (with Physical Function in ICU Test, the Functional Status Score in ICU test, and the Medical Research Council Manual Muscle Test (MRC-SS)), ICU-acquired weakness.	Telephone follow-up was tested in survivors at 6 months by a blinded central assessor. The independent activities of daily living, return to work, health-related quality of life, healthcare utilization, and Hospital Anxiety and Depression (HADS) were measured.

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Sosnowski, 2018	The ABCDE bundle	Standard Care	1) > 18 years, 2) Mechanical ventilated, 3) >48 hours, 4) expected another 24 hours of MV	1) Premorbid functional or cognitive impairment precluded engagement in exercise, 2) Inability to mobilise 3 meters before the current ICU illness, 3) Diagnosed with neuromuscular disease that could impair ventilator weaning, 4) Had suffered an acute stroke, 5) Were not for active resuscitation, 6) Readmitted to ICU within current hospitalisation, 7) Not expected to survive current ICU admission	Functional Independence measure (FIM)	Physical Function ICUT Test-score and SF-36 day-90, and feasibility outcomes.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Harvey, 2016	Early nutritional support via parenteral route	Early nutritional support via enteral route	1) ≥ 18 y, 2) Unplanned admission, 3) Expected to receive nutritional support for ≥2 days in the critical care unit, 4) Not planned discharge within 3 days from the critical care unit.	1) Admitted in critical care unit for >36 hours, 2) Previously randomised into the CALORIES trial, 3) Pre-existing contradictions to PN or EN, 4) Received PN or EN within 7 days prior to admission, 5) Admitted with percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy/jejunostomy, 6) Needle/surgical jejunostomy or nasojejunal tube in situ, 7) Admitted for palliative care, 8) Expected stay in the UK <6 months or 9) Known pregnant.	Mortality day 30, Cost-effectiveness at 1-year.	Duration of organ support in ICU, infectious and non-infectious complications in ICU, duration of ICU and acute hospital length of stay, survival at 90-days and 1-year, HRQoL day-90 and at 1-year, costs at day-90 and 1-year and estimated lifetime incremental cost-effectiveness.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Messika, 2019	Musical intervention (30 min) or Sensory deprivation intervention (30 min) of each NIV session	NIV as routinely performed	1) ≥ 18 y with acute respiratory failure (ARF), 2) GCS ≥12 and 3) requiring NIV.	1) Hearing impairment, 2) Palliative care or 3) Participating in another trial dealing with ARF.	Change in respiratory comfort	Evolution of respiratory discomfort during all NIV sessions, changes in respiratory parameters, changes in cardiovascular parameters, percentage of patients requiring endotracheal intubation, agreement between duration of the prescribed and the actually delivered NIV session, number of sessions interrupted before the end of prescribed time, percentage of patients requiring physical restraint or sedative/anzolytic treatments during NIV sessions and ICU stay, anxiety and depression, HRQoL, peri-traumatic stress on ICU discharge and day-90, overall assessment of NIV at ICU discharge and day-90.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Lall, 2015	High-frequency oscillatory ventilation /HFOV)	Standard mechanical ventilation	1) ≥ 16 year, 2) Admitted at ICU with expected > 48 hours or greater required ventilation time, 3) Receiving artificial ventilation via an endotracheal or tracheostomy tube, and 4) ARDS, 5) Ventilated for < 7 dage (≤168 hours), 6) Expected to require artificial ventilation until at least the evening of the day after enrolment.	1) Patients with left atrial hypertension from any cause, 2) Patients who had been mechanically ventilated for more than 7 consecutive days, 3) Patients with moderate or severe airway disease expected to cause expiratory airflow limitation, 4) Patients who would have had a lung biopsy or resection during this hospital admission, 5) Patients with any other condition the clinician believed would make receiving HFOV hazardous	All cause mortality day-30	Mortality rate at first discharge from ICU, ICU length of stay, Number of ventilator-free days day-30, Advanced/Basic respiratory support-free days, Days of renal support/ gastrointestinal support/dermatological support/liver support, Exhaled minute volume, Total respiratory rate, PEEP, Plateau pressure, Arterial blood gas, Length of acute hospital stay. 6-months: SF-12, EQ-5D scale. 12-months: mortality rate, respiratory function, EQ-5D, SF-12, Number of days with antimicrobial use and sedative use.	-

Gates, 2013	<p>Infusion of Salbutamol 15 µg/kg ideal body weight for up to 7 days.</p>	<p>Placebo (infusion of 0.9% sodium chloride</p>	<p>1) Patient intubated and ventilated, 2) Within 72 hours of onset of ARDS, 3) ARDS according to American-European Consensus Conference definition: i. acute onset ii. severe hypoxaemic respiratory failure [PaO₂-FiO₂ ≤ 26.7 kPa (200 mmHg)] iii. bilateral infiltrates on the chest radiograph in the absence of clinical evidence of left atrial hypertension, and 4) Aged ≥ 16 years.</p>	<p>1) Patient known to be pregnant, 2) Current treatment with i.v. β₂-agonists or requirement for ongoing regular nebulised/inhaled β₂-agonists, 3) Current treatment with β-adrenergic antagonists ('β-blockers'), 4) Treatment withdrawal imminent, 5) Chronic liver disease, defined as Child-Pugh grade C32 (assessed at the time of consideration for trial eligibility), 6) Enrolled in another clinical trial of an investigational medicinal product in the last 28 days, 7) Patient or personal legal representative or professional legal representative unwilling to give informed consent.</p>	<p>All-cause mortality day-28</p>	<p>Mortality at first discharge from ICU, Mortality at first discharge from hospital, Number of ventilator-free days, Number of organ failure-free days, Mortality at 12 months, Side effects (tachycardia, new arrhythmia/lactic acidosis) sufficient to stop intervention, HRQoL at 6- and 12 months, Length of stay in ICU and in hospital.</p>	<p>-</p>
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Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Allingstrup, 2017	Early goal directed nutrition	Standard nutritional care	1) Inclusion before 24 h after ICU admission, 2) Age ≥ 18 yrs, 3) Acutely admitted to the ICU, 4) Expected length of stay in ICU > 3 days, 5) MV, 6) Central Venous Catheter, 7) Proxy consent obtained, 8) Able to read and understand Danish.	1) Contraindications to use enteral nutrition as judged by the clinicians, 2) Contraindications to use parenteral nutrition, 3) Receiving a special diet, 4) Burn injury of more than 10% of the total body surface area, 5) Severe hepatic failure, 6) Traumatic brain injury, 7) Diabetic ketoacidosis, 8) Hyperosmolar non-ketotic acidosis, 9) Known or suspected hyperlipidaemia, 10) BMI ≤ 17 or severe malnutrition, 11) Pregnancy, 12) The clinician finds that the patient is too deranged or that death is imminent.	Physical component summary score at 6-months after randomisation.	Accumulated energy- and protein balance, New organ failure in the ICU, Metabolic control, Rate of nosocomial infections, New onset of renal replacement therapy, Percent of days alive without renal replacement therapy/mechanical ventilation/inotropic or vasopressor at day-90, Length of stay in ICU and hospital at 6-months, Mental component summary score at 6-months, Serious adverse reactions, Cost analyses.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Doig, 2013	Early parenteral nutrition (Kabiven G19%)	Standard care	1) Patient expected to remain in ICU today and tomorrow, 2) ≥ 18 years, 3) Admitted to the study ICU less than 24 hours, 4) Central venous access line through which parenteral nutrition could be delivered, 5) The patient is not expected to receive enteral, parenteral or oral nutrition today or tomorrow.	1) Known pregnancy or currently breastfeeding, 2) Previously been enrolled and randomised into this study, 3) Receive palliative care only and is not expected to survive ICU or hospital discharge, 4) Admitted to this, or another, ICU during this current hospitalisation, 5) Patient admitted to the study ICU directly from another ICU, 6) Moribund and not expected to survive 24 hours, 7) Brain dead or suspected to be brain dead, 8) Long term contraindications to enteral or oral nutrition such that the patient would normally be supported with parenteral nutrition, 9) Requires treatment of thermal injury to greater than 20% of total body surface area, 10) Primary reason for admission to the ICU for the treatment of a condition that requires timely nutritional support, 11) Body weight < 35kg, 12) Height < 140 cm, 13) Contraindication to treatment with Kabiven G19%	Day-60 mortality	Day-60 HRQoL and physical function	Location of the patient day-60, Days of clinically significant organ dysfunction, Clinically significant infectious complications, ICU and hospital length of stay, Vital status at hospital discharge, Days of invasive mechanical ventilation, Days of renal replacement therapy, duration and severity of pressure ulcers, Days of antibiotic usage

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Trouillet, 2011	Immediate early percutaneous tracheotomy	Prolonged intubation with tracheotomy 15 days after randomisation	1) Are 18 years of age or older, 2) Have undergone cardiovascular surgery, 3) Are still on invasive mechanical ventilation on day 4 after surgery, 4) Have failed the screening test or the spontaneous breathing trial, and 5) Have signed the informed consent (patient or legal representative)	1) Age less than 18, 2) Pregnant woman, 3) Intubation more than 48 hours before cardiovascular surgery, 4) More than 5 days on mechanical ventilation after cardiac surgery, 5) Artificial heart implantation, 6) Concomitant neck surgery (carotid), 7) Previously tracheostomized, 8) Major hemorrhagic risk, 9) Persistence of platelet count less than 50.000/mm ³ after platelet transfusion, 10) Prothrombin time less than 30% despite coagulation factors administration, 11) Clinical evidence of ongoing infection at the proposed tracheotomy site, 12) Anatomical deformity of the neck making risky a tracheostomy, 13) Probability of dying the day of randomization defined by SAPSII more than 80, 14) Irreversible neurological lesions, 15) Decision of care limitation, 16) Prior inclusion in a trial with morbidity-mortality as main judgement criteria, 17) Previous enrollment in this trial, 18) Consent refusal	Number of ventilator-free days from MV and day 60 after study enrolment	Mortality rate (day 60, in-ICU, in-hospital), ICU length of stay, Hospital length of stay, Duration of MV in survivors, Organ failure evolution, Infectious complications, Early laryngeal and tracheal complications, Sedation needs, Patient comfort, Outcome on day 90	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Kayambu, 2015	Early physical rehabilitation	Standard Care	1) ≥18years, 2) Ventilated for ≥48 hours, 3) Diagnosed with a sepsis syndrome or high clinical suspicion of sepsis.	1) Head injuries, 2) Burns, 3) Spinal injuries, 4) Multiple fractured lower limbs requiring specific rehabilitation regimes, 5) Patients with septic shock who are unresponsive to maximal treatment and those who are moribund or have an expected mortality within 48 hours will be excluded.	Acute Care Index of Function (ACIF), Physical Function ICU Test (PFIT), HRQoL at discharge and at 6 months	Interleukin-6, Interleukin-10 and tumour necrosis factor -α, blood lactate, fat-free muscle mass, exercise capacity, muscle strength and anxiety.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Schaller, 2016	Patient mobilisation discussed on rounds, SOMS score goal created, specific attempt to mobilise patient and achieve goal throughout day.	Usual mobilisation as per standard care	1) Adults (18 years of age or greater) 2) Who have been on mechanical ventilation for less than 48 hours and are expected to continue for at least 24 more hours, 3) Who meet criteria for baseline functional independence (Barthel Index greater than or equal to 70 obtained from a proxy describing patient function 2 weeks before admission	1) Irreversible disorders with 6-month mortality greater than 50%, 2) Rapidly developing neuromuscular disease, 3) Cardiopulmonary arrest, 4) Motor component of Glasgow Coma Scale <5, 5) Elevated intracranial pressure, 6) Ruptured/leaking aortic aneurysm, 7) Acute MI before peak troponin has been reached, 8) Absent lower limbs, 9) Pregnancy, 10) Unstable fractures contributing to likely immobility, 11) Hospitalization prior to ICU admission >5 days, 12) Enrollment in another clinical trial	Mean SICU Optimal Mobilisation Score (SOMS) level.	SICU length of stay, 'Mini' Modified Functional Independence Measure at ICU discharge and hospital discharge, SF-36 following 3 months after hospital discharge, Muscle strength at ICU and hospital discharge, Side effects of mobilisation therapy (during and 30 minutes after mobilisation), Genetic Polymorphisms as related to the other outcomes.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Fossat, 2018	Standardized early rehabilitation program plus daily electrical muscle stimulation and leg cycling exercises	Standardized early rehabilitation program	1) Age over 18 yrs, 2) Admitted to the ICU less than 72 hours before randomisation, 3) were deemed to need more than 48 hours of care in the ICU, and 4) An independent walking ability and a Barthel index greater than 55 within 15 days before ICU admission as assessed by interview of the patient	1) Pregnant, 2) Cardiac arrest was the cause of ICU admission or had cardiac arrest before screening, 3) Had a pacemaker or implantable cardioverterdefibrillator, 4) Had acute cerebral disease requiring deep sedation for at least 72 hours, 5) Had acute polyradiculoneuropathy, 6) Myasthenia, 7) Advanced dementia, 8) Deep venous thrombosis or pulmonary embolism treated for less than 48 hours, 9) Contraindication to electrical muscle stimulation or leg cycling for musculoskeletal, dermatologica, or surgical reasons, 10) Contraindication to standing or transfer to a chair, 11) Lower limb that was amputated, or 12) Previously included in the present study.	Patient's global muscle strength assessed using the Medical Research Council (MRC) grading system.	SICU length of stay, 'Mini' Modified Functional Independence Measure at ICU discharge and hospital discharge, SF-36 following 3 months after hospital discharge, Muscle strength at ICU and hospital discharge, Side effects of mobilisation therapy (during and 30 minutes after mobilisation), Genetic Polymorphisms as related to the other outcomes.	-

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Denehy, 2013	Physiotherapist provided both respiratory and mobility management based upon individual patient assessment according to unit protocol beside the intensive exercise in the ICU, the ward and as outpatient.	Physiotherapist provided both respiratory and mobility management based upon individual patient assessment according to unit protocol	1) ICU Length of Stay (LOS) of ≥5 days, 2) Able to understand written and spoken English, 3) Reside in greater Melbourne within 50 kilometer radius of the hospital, 4) ≥18 Years,	1) Permanent neuro damage 2) Outside metro area 3) Refused consent 4) Spinal cord injury 5) Imminent death 6) Inadequate english 7) Inability to exercise	Physical function with 6 minute walk test at ICU discharge	Assessing differences in physical function using the Timed Up and Go (TUG) Test, Physical Function in ICU Test (PFIT) and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) at 6 and 12 months using both the Assessment of Quality of Life (AQoL) Instrument and the Short Form 36 Health Survey, version 2 (SF-36v2)	-

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Brummel, 2014	Multi-component program (either physical rehabilitation OR cognitive, functional, and physical rehabilitation).	Usual Care	1) At least 18 years old 2) Being treated for respiratory failure and/or septic, cardiogenic or hemorrhagic shock 3) Resided within 120 miles of Nashville	1) already been critically ill for more than 72 h since the opportunity to administer early cognitive and physical therapy had passed 2) been in the ICU for more than 5 days in the previous 30 days 3) unlikely to benefit from rehabilitation targeting acute declines in cognitive or functional status due to a moribund state 4) ever preexisting dementia or physical disability in activities of daily living (e.g., bathing, dressing, etc.) 5) unlikely to continue the intervention in the outpatient setting because of active substance abuse, active psychiatric disorder, or loneliness	Executive functioning (Tower test) at 3 months post discharge	Global cognitive function, physical functioning, and HRQoL at 3 and 12 months by assessing: TUG, Functional Activities Questionnaire, EQ-5-Global scores, Katz Activities of Daily Living (ADL) scale, Activities-Specific Balance Confidence Scale (ABC), AD8, Dysexecutive Questionnaire, TRAILS A & B , General and Employment Questionnaire, Canadian Study of Health and Aging Frailty Scale, Short-informant Questionnaire of Cognitive Decline in the Elderly (short IQCODE), and Mini Mental State Exam (MMSE). Mortality at 2 months post hospital discharge. Rehospitalisation rate and number of hospital days 12-months post hospital discharge.	-

Angus, 2006 (Taylor)	Inhaled nitric oxide at 5 ppm until 28 days, discontinuation of assisted breathing, or death	Placebo (nitrogen gas)	1) Nonpregnant adults (≥ 18 y), 2) Developed Acute Lung Injury (ALI) within the preceding 72h defined as: $pao_2/Fio_2 \leq 250$, Bilateral infiltrates on frontal chest radiograph, Pulmonary artery occlusion pressure ≤ 18 mmHG, 3) ALI resulting from at least 1 of the following: pneumonia, aspiration pneumonitis, toxic gas inhalation, pulmonary contusion, acute pancreatitis, massive blood transfusion, multiple trauma, elective or emergency major surgery, fat emboli, postpartum ALI, 4) Fio_2 of 0.50-0.95 or a set PEEP ≥ 8 cm H ₂ O	1) History of immunocompromise, 2) Persistent systemic hypotension, defined as systolic blood pressure < 90 mmHg, or a nonpurposeful reduction of systolic pressure by ≥ 40 mmHg and who met any of the following conditions within 4 hours before the initiation of treatment gas: systemic vascular resistance < 800 dynes-sec-m ³ and an elevated cardiac index > 4 L/m ² /min, white blood cell count $> 20,000/\mu L$ or $< 4000/\mu L$, 3) Evidence of nonpulmonary organ dysfunction, defined as 1 or more of the following: creatinin ≥ 1.5 mg/dL, total bilirubin ≥ 4.0 mg/dL and aspartate aminotransferase or alanine aminotransferase level > 2 times the upper limit of normal, platelet count $\leq 50 \times 10^3/\mu L$, prothrombin time ≥ 1.5 times the upper limit of normal.	Days alive and off assisted breathing	All cause mortality day-28, Days alive and meeting oxygenation criteria for extubation, Days alive following a successful unassisted ventilation test.	-
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Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Schädler, 2017	Automated Weaning group	Control group	1) Intubated or tracheotomised patients requiring mechanical ventilation at 9:00 am for longer than 9 hours	1) Cerebral trauma / surgery, 2) Age < 18 years, 3) Do-not-resuscitate-order, 4) Duration of mechanical ventilation > 24 h, 5) Patient is currently participating in this trial (including 90 days follow-up period)	Total ventilation time during ICU.	Time in the zone of respiratory comfort during invasive mechanical ventilation, Number of ventilator alarms during invasive mechanical ventilation, Number of ventilator manipulations during invasive mechanical ventilation, Length of ICU and hospital stay, 28-day and 90-day mortality	-

Taylor, 2016 (Myburgh)	6% Hydroxyethyl Starch (HES)	0.9% Saline	<p>1) Consent obtained, 2) Fluid resuscitation is required to increase or maintain intravascular volume that is in addition to maintenance fluids, enteral and parenteral nutrition, blood products and specific fluids to replace ongoing insensible or fluid lossess from other sites, 3) The ICU clinician consider that both 6% hydroxyethyl starch and saline are equally appropriate for the patient and that no specific indication or contraindication for either exists, 4) The requirement for fluid resuscitation must be supported by AT LEAST ONE of the following clinical signs: a) Heart rate >90 beats/min, b) Systolic blood pressure (SBP) < 100mmHg or mean arterial pressure (MAP) < 75mmHg or at least 40mmHg decrease in SBP or MAP from the</p>	<p>1) Previous allergic reaction to hydroxyethyl starch solution, 2) Primary non-traumatic intracranial haemorrhage or severe traumatic intracranial haemorrhage (mass lesion > 25 ml), 3) Patients who are receiving renal replacement therapy or in whom the ICU physician considers renal replacement therapy is imminent (i.e. renal replacement therapy will start in 6 hours), 4) Patients with documented serum creatinine value $\geq 350\mu\text{mol/L}$ and urine output averaging $\leq 10\text{ml / hr}$ over 12 hours, 5) Severe hyponatraemia (Serum sodium > 160 mmol/l) or severe hyperchloraemia (Serum chloride > 130 mmol/l), 6) Women of child bearing age (18-49 years old), unless evidence of documented menopause, hysterectomy or surgical sterilisation or negative pregnancy test before randomisation, 7) Breastfeeding, 8) Patients who have received > 1000mL hydroxyethyl starch in the 24 hours before randomization, 9) Patients admitted to the ICU following cardiac surgery; patients admitted to ICU following cardiac surgery, 10) Patients admitted to the ICU for the treatment of burns or following liver transplantation surgery, 11) Death is deemed imminent and inevitable or the patient has an underlying disease process with a life expectancy of < 90 days, 12) A limitation of therapy order has been documented restricting implementation of the study</p>	All cause mortality day-90	Renal failure requiring renal replacement therapy day-90, SOFA day-90, ICU-, hospital-, 28-day, and 6-months mortality, Quality of life with EQ-5D at 6-months, Functional status (Glasgow Outcome score) at 6-months.	-
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baseline recording,	protocol or the treating clinician
c) Central venous	deems aggressive care
pressure <	unsuitable, 13) Patient has
10mmHg, d)	previously been enrolled in the
Pulmonary artery	CHEST study, 14) Patient has
wedge pressure <	previously received fluid
12 mmHg, e)	resuscitation that was prescribed
Respiratory	within the study ICU during this
variation in systolic	current ICU admission, 15)
or mean arterial	Patient has been transferred to
blood pressure of	the study ICU from another ICU
>5 mmHg, f)	and received fluid resuscitation
Capillary refill time	for the treatment of volume
> one second, g)	depletion in that other ICU.
Urine output < 0.5	
ml/kg for one hour	

Madsen, 2017	Intravenous polyspecific immunoglobulin G (IVIg) for three consecutive days	Placebo for three consecutive days	1) Necrotizing soft tissue infection (NSTI) based on surgical findings, 2) Age >18 years, 3) Admitted to or planned to be admitted to the ICU at Rigshospitalet	1) >48 hour from the primary diagnosis to arrival at RH, 2) More than one dose of IVIG given within current admission, 3) Known hypersensitivity to IVIG, 4) Hyperprolinaemia (obtained from hospital notes), 5) Pregnancy or breast feeding	Physical Component Summary Score (PCS) of Short-Form 36 (SF-36) 6 months after randomisation	Mortality day-28, 90 and 180, Time to resolution of shock during ICU admission (Maintenance of a systolic blood pressure of at least 90 mmHg without vasopressor support for 24 hours), Severe bleeding during ICU admission (clinical bleeding and use of 3 units of red blood cells within 24 hours at any time in the ICU), Any bleeding in the ICU during ICU admission, Use of blood products during ICU admission (total volumes during the ICU admission), SOFA scores (AUC), excluding the Glasgow Coma Score (GCS) score day 1-7, Use of renal replcement therapy (RRT), ventilation and vasopressor in the ICU during ICU admission, Days alive off life support in the 90 days after randomisation 90-days after randomisation, Days alive and out of hospital in the 180 day follow-up period, Amputation, any location within 180-days.
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Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Jones, 2015	Nutrition supplement with a recovery manual only OR supplemented with a program of enhanced physiotherapy and structured exercise (PEPSE) (2 intervention arms)	Placebo (ward based physiotherapy) with OR without PEPSE (2 placebo arms)	1) ≥45 years, 2) Combined ICU and pre-ICU stay of ≥5 days and able to undertake physiotherapy program.	1) <45 y, 2) Combined ICU or pre-ICU stay <5 days, 3) Unable to undertake physiotherapy, 4) Unable to take nutritional drink, 5) Too confused to give informed consent, 6) Discharged for palliative care, 7) Malignant disease, 8) Persistent nonrecovering severe liver - or kidney failure.	Physical recovery (6 MWT at 3 months).	HRQoL (SF-36 + EQ-5D), Anxiety and depression.	-

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Noguchi, 2017 (Matsuoka)	Seven Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) capsules for 12 weeks.	Placebo capsules for 12 weeks.	(1) age ≥ 18 years; (2) native Japanese speaker; (3) contact with us within 240 h (10 days) of injury; and (4) physical and psychological ability to understand the scope of the trial and provide written consent for study participation.	(1) obviously irretrievable acute injury to the brain parenchyma, or subdural or subarachnoidal bleeding; (2) Mini-Mental State Examination score < 24 [16]; (3) alcohol abuse/dependence; (4) smoking ≥ 40 cigarettes/day; (5) history and current suspicion of psychosis or bipolar I disorder; (6) suspicion of alcohol- or substance-related disorder or eating disorder; (7) serious psychiatric condition requiring emergent intervention, such as suicidal attempt, dissociation, or stupor; (8) regular treatment with antiepileptic medication, lithium, ethyl-icosapentate, aspirin, or warfarin within the last 3 months; (9) regular consumption of PUFA supplements within the the 3 months prior to injury; and (10) eating fish ≥ 4 times per week.	Clinical-Administrated PTSD Scale	Incidents of diagnosis of PTSD, MADRAS score, incidents of depression by MINI, Autonomic response, Impact of Event Scale revised, HADS score, HRQoL with SF-36, Conner-Davidson Resilience Scale, Brain-derived neutotrophic factor, Days of leave from injury, Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire, Clinician-Administrated PTSD Scale, Dehydroepiandrosterone, Neuropeptide Y, Interleukin 1 beta, Interleukin 6, Tumor necrosis factor alpha, D-serine, L-serine, DL-serine, Activin.	-

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Jackson, 2010 (Girard)	Daily spontaneous awakening trial with spontaneous breathing trial	Usual care consisting of patient-targeted sedation and an spontaneous breathing trial protocol	1) Require mechanical ventilation for more than 12 hours, 2) Over 18 years old, 3) Under the services of medicine, cardiology, and neurology.	1) Admission after cardiopulmonary arrest, 2) continuous mechanical ventilation more than 2 weeks before potential enrollment, 3) Moribund state and/or withdrawal of life support, 4) profound neurological deficits that prevented patients from living independently, 5) Enrollment in another clinical trial, 6) Cardiac surgery or neurosurgery or had a stroke before or during the trial from the long-term component of the trial.	Time breathing without assistance.	Length of stay in the ICU and hospital, 28-day and 1-year survival, Duration of coma and delirium, Cognitive function -, Psychological status -, Functional status - and Quality of life at discharge, 3 months and 12 months.	-
Rygård, 2016 (Holst)	Transfusion when Hb ≤ 7.0 g/dl (4.3mM)	Transfusion when Hb ≤ 9.0 g/dl (5.6 mM)	1) Adult ≥18 Y, 2) Anaemia (Haemoglobin (Hb) ≤9g/dl, 3) Fulfill the criteria for septic shock	1) Documented wish against transfusion, 2) Previous SAR with blood products, 3) Presence of ongoing myocardial ischaemia at time of randomisation, 4) Life-threatening bleeding at time of randomisation, 5) RBC transfusion during current ICU admission administered before randomisation, 6) Withdrawal from active therapy or brain death, 7) Acute burn injuries regardless of severity or total burn surface area, 8) Lack of informed consent	Mortality day-90	Mortality day-28 and 6 months and 12 months after randomisation, Life support day-5, 14 and 28 post randomisation, SAR, Ischaemic events in the ICU, Days alive and out of hospital, Days alive without mechanical ventilation day-90, Days alive without vasopressor/inotropic day-90, 1-year HRQoL for Danish patients with SF-36)	-

<p>Gallagher, 2014 (Bellomo)</p>	<p>Higher intensity haemofiltration</p>	<p>Lower intensity haemofiltration</p>	<p>1) The treating clinician believes that the patient requires CRRT for acute renal failure, 2) The clinician is uncertain about the balance of benefits and risks likely to be conferred by treatment with higher intensity or lower intensity CRRT, 3) The treating clinicians anticipate treating the patient with CRRT for at least 72 hours, 4) Informed consent has been obtained, 5) The patient fulfils ONE of the following clinical criteria for initiating CRRT: Oliguria (urine output < 100ml/6hr) that has been unresponsive to fluid resuscitation measures, Hyperkalemia ([K+] > 6.5 mmol/L), Severe acidemia (pH < 7.2), Urea > 25 mmol/liter, Creatinine >300 micromol/L in the setting of ARF, Clinically significant organ oedema in the setting of ARF (eg: lung).</p>	<p>1) Patient age is <18 years, 2) Death is imminent (<24 hours), 3) There is a strong likelihood that the study treatment would not be continued in accordance with the study protocol, 4) The patient has been treated with CRRT or other dialysis previously during the same hospital admission, 5) The patient was on maintenance dialysis prior to the current hospitalisation, 6) The patient's body weight is <60 kg or >100kg, 7) Any other major illness that, in the investigator's judgment, will substantially increase the risk associated with the subject's participation in this study</p>	<p>All-cause mortality at 90 days after randomisation</p>	<p>Death within the in the intensive care unit at 90-days, Death within 28-days of randomisation, Death prior to hospital discharge at 90-days, Length of ICU stay at 90-days, Length of hospital stay at 90-days, The need for and duration of other organ support (inotropic/vasopressor support and positive pressure ventilation at 90-days, CRRT-free days at 90-days, Dialysis-independent survival)</p>	<p>-</p>
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Cronberg, 2015 (Nielsen)	Core body target temperature 33°C for 24 hours	Core body target temperature 36°C for 24 hours	1) Age ≥ 18 years old, 2) Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) of presumed cardiac cause, 3) Return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC), 4) Unconsciousness (Glasgow Coma Score < 8) (patients not able to obey verbal commands) after sustained ROSC	1) In-hospital cardiac arrest, 2) OHCA of presumed non-cardiac cause, e.g. after trauma or dissection/rupture of major artery OR Cardiac arrest caused by initial hypoxia (i.e. drowning, suffocation, hanging), 3) Known bleeding diathesis (medically induced coagulopathy (e.g. warfarin, clopidogrel) does not exclude the patient), 4) Suspected or confirmed acute intracranial bleeding, 5) Suspected or confirmed acute stroke, 6) Unwitnessed asystole, 7) Known limitations in therapy and Do Not Resuscitate-order, 8) Known disease making 180 days survival unlikely, 9) Known pre-arrest CPC 3 or 4, 10) Temperature < 30°C on admission, 11) > 4 hours (240 minutes) from ROSC to screening, 12) Systolic blood pressure < 80 mm Hg in spite of fluid loading/vasopressor and/or inotropic medication/intra aortic balloon pump	All-cause mortality through the end of the trial (minimum 180-days)	Composite outcome of all-cause mortality and poor neurological function (CPC 3 and 4) and composite outcome of all-cause mortality and poor neurological function (modified Rankin Scale 4 and 5) day-180. Safety measures: Bleeding day 1-7 of intensive care treatment, Neurological function day-180, Cerebral Performance Category, Modified Rankin Scale, Pneumonia during day 1-7 of intensive care treatment, Electrolyte disorders during day 1-7, Hyperglycaemia > 10 mmol/l during day 1-7 of intensive care treatment, Hypoglycemia < 3mmol/l during day 1-7 of intensive care treatment, Cardiac arrhythmia during day 1-7 of intensive care treatment, The need for renal replacement therapy during day 1-7 of intensive care treatment, Landmark all-cause mortality day-180, Cerebral Performance Category (CPC) day-180	Quality of life day-180 (SF-36), Neurological function (Complete neurological recovery) including day-180, Neurological function at hospital discharge and best neurological function during follow up period day-1-180.
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Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Dinglas, 2016 (Truwit)	Rosuvastatin	Placebo	1) Systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) defined as meeting at least 1 of 3 criterias for a systematic inflammatory response, 2) Suspected or proved infection, 3) Acute Lung Injury (ALI),	1) No consent/inability to obtain consent, 2) Age < 18 years, 3) More than 7 days since initiation of mechanical ventilation, 4) More than 48 hours since meeting ALI inclusion criteria, 5) Patient, surrogate, or physician not committed to full support, 6) Unable to receive or unlikely to absorb enteral study drug, 7) Rosuvastatin specific exclusions, 8) Severe chronic liver disease, 9) Moribund patient not expected to survive 24 h, 10) Chronic respiratory failure, 11) Home mechanical ventilation, 12) Diffuse alveolar hemorrhage from vasculitis, 13) Burns >40% of total body surface area, 14) Interstitial lung disease of severity sufficient to require continuous home oxygen therapy, 15, Unwillingness or inability to utilize the ARDS network 6ml/kg PBW ventilation protocol, 16) Cardiac disease classified as NYHA class IV, 17) Myocardial infarction within past 6 months, 18) Intraparenchymal CNS bleed within a month of randomisation.	Hospital mortality to day-60	Ventilator free days at day-28. Other outcomes: Hospital mortality to day 28, Organ failure free days at day 14, ICU-free days at day 28, Hospital-free days at day 60, Increase in PaO2/FiO2 ratio and Oxygenation Index on study days 1-7, VTE at day 14 a) Documented by venous ultrasound, impedance plethysmography, contrast venography, ventilation-perfusion lung scan, CTPA/V, or pulmonary angiography, Composite end-point of myocardial infarction, bowel ischemia or ischemic stroke to day 28, Arrhythmias during ICU stay or day 14, whichever is first, Development of acute kidney injury, Changes in plasma concentrations of CRP from day 0 to day 6 and 14. Blood and urine will be reserved beyond study completion for additional biomarker studies	Complete neurological recovery, Neurological function (MMSE, IQCODE, two questions; see below), and Quality of life at 180 days, CPC at hospital discharge, Best neurological outcome during trial period according to the CPC-scale

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Azevedo, 2019	Optimised nutritional therapy with caloric intake determined by calorimetry and high protein (2.0 to 2.2 g/kg/day)	Nutritional therapy with 25kcal/kg/day and protein 1.4-1.5 g/kg/day	1) Adults >18 y, 2) Non-pregnant, 3) Mechanically ventilated, 3) Expected length in the ICU > 2 days	1) Not expected to stay in the ICU for < 3 days, 2) Requirement for inspired oxygen (FIO2) >0.60, 3) High output bronchopleural fistula, 4) Presented evidence of severe cognitive dysfunction	Physical component summary (SF-36) at 3 and 6 months after randomisation	Handgrip strength 7th, 14th and day-30 after admission, ICU mortality day-30, Hospital mortality 6 months,	
Antonelli, 2005	Percutaneous translaryngeal tracheostomy (TLT)	Surgical tracheostomy (ST)	1) Patients requiring tracheostomy (established by the ICU physician) - due to verified difficulties in weaning the patient from mechanical ventilation or anticipated need for long-term ventilation	1) Indication for emergency tracheostomy, 2) Age 18 yrs, 3) Severe coagulopathy, 4) Surgical wounds near the tracheostomy site, 5) Previous or preexisting tracheostomy, 6) Conditions that compromised adequate visualization of normal anatomic landmarks, and 7) Generally accepted contraindications for PT.	NA	NA	(Not specified primary or secondary outcomes) HRQoL (SF-12) at 1-year, Survival at 1-year))

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Marasco, 2013	Operative rib fixation	Nonoperative management	1) Patients with multiple (>3) fractured ribs between the level of ribs 3 to 10 resulting in a paradoxical movement of the chest wall	1) Age > 80 years, 2) Spinal injuries which would preclude placement of the patient in a lateral decubitus position, 3) Open rib fractures with soiling or infection, 4) Severe head injury, 5) Uncorrected coagulopathy, 6) Sepsis	Duration of Mechanical ventilations, and Duration of Intensive care stay (hours)	Number of respiratory complications (pneumonia, pneumothorax, intercostal catheter usage), rate of failed extubation, rate of tracheostomy, readmission to intensive care, duration of hospital stay, cost assessment of the operation.	-
Wittbrodt, 2013 (Perner)	HES 130/0.42	Ringers acetate	Adult patients who 1) Undergo resuscitation in the ICU, 2) Fulfillment within the previous 24 hours of the criteria for severe sepsis (SCCM/ACCP), 3) Consent is obtainable either from the patient or by proxy.	1) Age < 18 years old, 2) Previously randomised in the 6S trial, 3) Allergy towards hydroxyethyl starch or malic acid, 4) Treatment with > 1000 ml's of any synthetic colloid within the last 24 hours prior to randomisation, 5) Any form of renal replacement therapy, 6) Acute burn injury > 10% body surface area, 6) Severe hyperkalaemia, p-K > 6 mM, 7) Liver or kidney transplantation during current hospital admission, 8) Intracranial bleeding within current hospitalisation, 9) Enrollment into another ICU trial of drugs with potential action on circulation, renal function or coagulation, 10) Withdrawal of active therapy	Composite outcome measure of 90-day mortality or end stage kidney disease	Mortality day-28, Mortality 6-months, Mortality 1-year, SOFA score day-5, Days free of ventilation day-90, Days free of dialysis day-90, SAR until ICU discharge, Need of dialysis/haemofiltration day-90, Need of ventilation day-90, Kidney failure until ICU discharge, Hospital length of stay day-90, and Coagulation analysis day-5.	-

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Freeman-Sanderson, 2016	Early cuff-deflation and insertion of an in-line speaking valve during mechanical ventilation	Control received standard cuff deflation and a speaking valve during self-ventilation	Adult patients who 1) Undergo resuscitation in the ICU, 2) Fulfillment within the previous 24 hours of the criteria for severe sepsis (SCCM/ACCP), 3) Consent is obtainable either from the patient or by proxy.	1) Age < 18 years old, 2) Previously randomised in the 6S trial, 3) Allergy towards hydroxyethyl starch or malic acid, 4) Treatment with > 1000 ml's of any synthetic colloid within the last 24 hours prior to randomisation, 5) Any form of renal replacement therapy, 6) Acute burn injury > 10% body surface area, 6) Severe hyperkalaemia, p-K > 6 mM, 7) Liver or kidney transplantation during current hospital admission, 8) Intracranial bleeding within current hospitalisation, 9) Enrollment into another ICU trial of drugs with potential action on circulation, renal function or coagulation, 10) Withdrawal of active therapy	Time to verbal communication (hours from trache insertion to verbal communication)	Mortality day-28, Mortality 6-months, Mortality 1-year, SOFA score day-5, Days free of ventilation day-90, Days free of dialysis day-90, SAR until ICU discharge, Need of dialysis/haemofiltration day-90, Need of ventilation day-90, Kidney failure until ICU discharge, Hospital length of stay day-90, and Coagulation analysis day-5.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Van Maastrigt, 2006	Short ICU stay (8 hrs)	Stay overnight in the ICU (standard care)	1) Admission for CABG surgery	1) Age of >78 yrs, 2) Ejection fraction of <30%, 3) Stage 3 obesity (body mass index of >40 kg/m ²), 4) Hemodialysis (kidney-replacing therapy), 5) Pulmonary hypertension (systolic pressure of >40 mm Hg), 6) Recent cardiovascular accident (1 month), 7) Recent myocardial infarction (<24 hrs), 8) Cardiogenic shock (systolic blood pressure of <80 mm Hg), 9) Central filling pressure of >20 mm Hg, cardiac index of <1.8 Lmin ⁻¹ m ⁻²), need for inotropic therapy (>5 mg microg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ dopamine or dobutamine), ongoing infarction (a significant increase of myocardial muscle creatine kinase isoenzyme within 4 hrs before surgery), or the need for intraaortic balloon pump. Other reasons for exclusion were, for instance, inability to give informed consent, inability to speak/read/understand the Dutch language, emergency surgery. For details on reasons of refusal and exclusion criteria.	ICU readmissions and total hospital stay	Postoperative morbidity and mortality, Total hospital costs, Quality of Life (EQ-5D).	-

<p>Agus, 2017 (McAuley)</p>	<p>Enteral simvastatin 80mg daily for up to 28 days</p>	<p>Placebo</p>	<p>1) Patient must be receiving invasive mechanical ventilation, 2) Patient must have ALI as defined by acute onset of: a) hypoxic respiratory failure (PaO2/FiO2 40 kPa from 2 blood gases >1 hour apart), b) bilateral infiltrates on chest X-ray consistent with pulmonary, oedema, c) No clinical evidence of left atrial hypertension or if measured, a pulmonary arterial occlusion pressure (PAOP) less than or equal to 18 mmHg. If a patient has a PAOP > 18 mmHg, then the other criteria must persist for more than 12 hours after the PAOP has declined to < 18 mmHg, and still be within the 48-hour enrolment window</p>	<p>1) Age < 16 years, 2) More than 48 hours from the onset of ALI, 3) Patient is known to be pregnant, 4) CK >10 times the upper limit of the normal range, 5) Transaminases >5 times the upper limit of the normal range Protocol No: 10072DMcA-CS, Version No: 1.0, Date: 24-Jun-2010 18, 6) Patients receiving ongoing treatment with any of the following; itraconazole, ketoconazole, erythromycin, clarithromycin, HIV protease, inhibitors, nefazodone or cyclosporine, 7) Patients with severe renal impairment (calculated creatinine clearance less than 30ml/minute) not receiving renal replacement therapy, 8) Severe liver disease (Child's Pugh score >12; Appendix 1), 9) Current or recent treatment (within 2 weeks) with statins, 10) Physician decision that a statin is required for proven indication, 11) Contraindication to enteral drug administration, e.g. patients with mechanical bowel obstruction. Patients with high gastric aspirates due to an ileus are not excluded, 12) Domiciliary mechanical ventilation, 13) Participation in other investigational medicinal product (IMP) trials within 30 days, 14) Consent declined, 15) Treatment withdrawal imminent within 24 hours</p>	<p>Ventilator-free-days up to day-28</p>	<p>Change in oxygenation index (OI) from baseline to day, 3, 7, 14 and 28; Change in sequential organ failure assessment (SOFA) score from baseline to day 3, 7, 14 and 28; All cause mortality 28-days post randomisation; Mortality at (first) discharge from ICU; Mortality at (first) discharge from hospital; Mortality at 12 months post randomisation; Safety; Biological mechanisms; Health-related quality of life; Cost effectiveness</p>	<p>-</p>
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Dubois, 2017	Algorithm-guided blood glucose control (LOGIC-C)	Blood glucose control by trained nurse (Nurse C)	1) Signed informed consent from patient or the next of kin, obtained as soon as possible after admission to the ICU (<24 hours). Blood glucose control is an important issue in the treatment of critically ill patients and should be initiated immediately after admission to the ICU. If the patient or the next of kin does not agree with the study and does not sign the informed consent within the first 24 hours after admission to the ICU, the patient will be withdrawn from the study 2) Patients admitted to the ICU with an expected stay of at least two days and already receiving or potentially needing insulin infusion for blood glucose control (these patients should already have or need an arterial and central venous line), 3) Patients should be older than 18 years.	1) Not critically ill, 2) Age under 18 years, 3) Patients already enrolled in another intervention randomized controlled trial, 4) Patients expected to die within 12 hours (=moribund patients), 5) No arterial line or central venous line needed, 6) Pregnancy or lactating, 7) Patients suffering from ketoacidotic or hyperosmolar coma on admission, 8) Patients who have been previously included in the LOGIC-2 study, 9) Allergy to insulin	Glycemic Penalty Index (GPI) up to 14 days post-randomisation	Incidence of mild hypoglycaemia (blood glucose level < 70 mg/dL or 3.9 mmol/L) per patient (up to 14 days) ("Safety of glycaemic control") * Mean and median arterial blood glucose concentration (up to 14 days) * Adequacy of reaching and maintaining the target range for blood glucose, as assessed by the Hyperglycaemic index (HGI)(22) (up to 14 days) * Time in target range (up to 14 days) * Time to target range (up to 14 days) * Daily maximal blood glucose difference, as a marker of blood glucose fluctuations (up to 14 days) * Incidence of severe hypoglycaemia (blood glucose level < 40 mg/dL or 2.2 mmol/L) per patient (up to 14 days) * Incidence of severe hypoglycaemia (blood glucose level < 40 mg/dL or 2.2 mmol/L) as a proportion of all blood glucose measurements (up to 14 days) * Incidence of mild hypoglycaemia (blood glucose level < 70 mg/dL or 3.9 mmol/L) as a proportion of all blood glucose measurements (up to 14 days) * Interval between blood glucose measurements, as a marker of workload (up to 14 days) * Protocol compliance in the intervention group (up to 14 days): the number and proportion of patients
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in which the LOGIC-Insulin was not followed for a time period of at least 8 hours, which is the duration of one nurse shift. * Overrides in the intervention group (up to 14 days): the number and proportions of recommendation by the software that were overruled by the bed-side nurses

- o Minor overrides: absolute insulin dose difference of >0.1 and $< 1\text{IU/h}$
- o Major overrides: absolute insulin dose difference of $\geq 1\text{IU/h}$

o Major overrides will also be qualitatively assessed *

Incidence of new infections in the ICU (up to 90 days): The diagnosis of "new infection" will be based on the administration of antibiotics, beyond the prophylactic scope *

- * Length of stay in the ICU (up to 90 days)
- * Length of stay in the hospital (up to 90 days),
- Mortality in the ICU (up to 90 days)
- * Mortality in the hospital (up to 90 days),
- Landmark 90-day mortality,
- All direct medical costs from a healthcare payer's perspective (time horizon from randomisation to hospital discharge, up to 90 days)
- * The EuroQol-5D questionnaire at ICU and hospital discharge, and at 90 days.

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Ingels, 2006 (Van den Berghe)	Intensive insulin therapy	Conventional insulin therapy	1) Adults receiving mechanical ventilation, 2) Admitted to ICU	NA	Death from any cause during intensive care.	In hospital death, Number of days in ICU (more than 14 days) or readmission, Need for ventilatory support, Renal replacement therapy, Inotropic or vasopressor support, Critical-illness polyneropathy, Markers of inflammation, Bloodstream infection and use of antibiotics for more than 10 days, Transfusion requirements, Hyperbilirubinemia.	-

<p>Walsh, 2017 (Lacroix)</p>	<p>Exclusively fresh RBCs stored ≤7 days throughout hospital stay</p>	<p>Standard issue RBCs throughout hospital stay.</p>	<p>1) Critically ill patients, 2) Age ≥18 years (≥16 years in Scotland), 3) Expected to require mechanical ventilation for ≥48 hours and 4) Requiring the first transfusion during the first 7 days in the ICU.</p>	<p>1) Who are less than 16 years of age, 2) Who were previously enrolled in the ABLE study, 3) Who have already been transfused with red cells during the current hospitalisation, 4) Who have an obvious terminal illness documented in the medical record with a life expectancy of less than 3 months, 5) Who have undergone routine cardiac surgical care, 6) Where a decision to withdraw/withhold some critical care had been made, 7) Who are obviously brain dead, 8) When there are no red cells with a storage time of 7 days or less available in the blood bank that cannot be transported from the blood supplier, 9) Who require more than 1 unit of uncross-matched red cells, 10) With a known objection to blood transfusions, 11) With autologous blood donations, 12) Who pose difficulties in securing blood products (rare blood groups), and who are difficult to match.</p>	<p>90-day all cause mortality</p>	<p>Other mortality rates and survival times as measured at ICU discharge, hospital discharge, 28 days and 6 months post-discharge, Number of cases of multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS), highest number of organ failures per patient, MODS score and time to development of MODS as measured while in the ICU, Serious nosocomial infections including a) Nosocomial pneumonia, b) Deep tissue infections (e.g. peritonitis, mediastinitis), c) Bacteraemia from organisms not considered normal skin flora and judged important enough to treat by the attending team, as measured while in the ICU, Adverse events and transfusion reactions as measured while in ICU, Length of stay (ICU and hospital), Length of time requiring respiratory, haemodynamic and renal support as measured while in ICU</p>	<p>-</p>
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<p>Zhu, 2018 (Doig)</p>	<p>Amino acid supplement</p>	<p>Standard care</p>	<p>1) First or Second calendar day of admission to the study ICU, 2) Expected to remain in the ICU at least 2 days after enrollment, 3) The patient has a working central venous access line through which the study intervention could be delivered, 4) Able to tolerate at least 1L of fluid volume per day, 5) 18 years of age or older</p>	<p>1)Is the patient currently receiving an NSAID with specific emphasis on COX-2 inhibitors?['Currently receiving'means the patient will continue to receive the NSAID or COX-2 inhibitor during their ICU stay. If the patient does NOT plan to continue receiving one of these drugs daily, they may be enrolled: the COX-2 inhibitors Celecoxib, Paracoxib, Etoricoxib or > 160mg Aspirin or any dose of Ibuprofen, Naproxen, Piroxicam, Indomethacin, Meloxicam, Mefenamic Acid, Diclofenac, Piroxicam, Ketoprofen, Tiaprofenic Acid, Ketorolac.] 2)Is the patient currently enrolled into a clinical trial evaluating a nitric oxide (NO) inhibitor? 3)Is the patient currently receiving Acetazolamide, which is a diuretic that works on the proximal tubule? 4)Is the patient's current serum creatinine greater than the allowable age and gender adjusted maximum reported in the Maximum Creatinine Table? (see page 19)5)Does the patient have severe Acute Kidney Injury, defined as:Current serum creatinine (SCr) increased 3 times pre-acute illness value OR SCr >350 µmol/L with recent increase greater than 44 µmol/L?[Note: If pre-acute illness creatinine values are unknown, assume upper limit of normal: 90 µmol/L for females and 110 µmol/L for males.]6)Is the patient currently receiving or scheduled for dialysis / renal replacement therapy?</p>	<p>Days of clinically significant renal dysfunction at ICU</p>	<p>Use of RRT and eGFR estimated from serum creatinine using the equations developed by Levey et al. and eGFR estimated fromserum cystatin C using the equations developed by Ste-vens et al.</p>	<p>Vital status at Study Day 90, Zubrod/WHO Performance Status, RAND-36 General Health Status Ver 1, RAND-36 Physical Function scale Ver 1, and other measures of in-hospital care (ICU stay, hospital stay, mechanicalventilation days, organ dysfunctions etc.</p>
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7)Has the patient ever had a kidney transplant? 8)Is the patient expected to receive palliative care only and is not expected to survive ICU or hospital discharge?9)Is the patient moribund and not expected to survive 24 hours? 10)Is the patient brain dead or suspected to be brain dead? 11)If the patient has been admitted to the study ICU directly from another ICU, is the total number of calendar days from other ICU admission until today greater than two calendar days?12)Does the patient require treatment of a burn injury to greater than 20% of total bodysurface area?13)Has the patient been taking Nardil (phenelzine) within the last 6 weeks?[Nardil (phenelzine) is an uncommonly used anti-depressant. It may be used in people who are resistant to other treatment for major depression or anxiety disorders. Because of its unique side-effect profile, and explicit drug interactions (meperidine, epinephrine, norepinephrine), a history of Nardil (phenelzine) use is usually found clearly documented in the patient's charts.]14) Has the patient previously been enrolled and randomised into this study?15)Does the patient have a documented contraindication to the study intervention (IV amino acids), as listed onthe TGA product licensing document?Australian Therapeutic Goods Association

Product Licensing
Contraindications, Synthamin 17
EF: (Answer NO to all
questions) 15A. Is the patient
known to be pregnant or
currently
breastfeeding? 15B. Does the
patient have severe liver
disease (Biopsy proven
cirrhosis, or documented portal
hypertension with a known past
history of either upper GI
bleeding attributed to portal
hypertension or of hepatic failure
leading to encephalopathy /
coma)? 15C. Does the patient have
a documented hypersensitivity
(known allergy) to one or more of
the included amino acids?
[Known allergies will be clearly
documented in the Patient's
Charts. See Product Details for
complete list of
Ingredients.] 15D. Does the
patient have a documented
inborn error of amino acid
metabolism? [Ex.
Phenylketonuria (PKU), Maple
Syrup Urine Disease. These
disorders are actively screened
for during childhood. If present,
they will be clearly documented
in the patient's charts and will
likely be accompanied by strict
directions to consult a Dietitian
prior to providing nutritional
support. Other less common
inborn errors include: atypical
phenylketonuria, hereditary
tyrosinaemia, biotinidase
deficiency, methylmalonic
aciduria, glutaric acidemia,
methylglutaconic acidemia.

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Kurtoglu, 2015	Neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES) to auxiliary respiratory muscles 20 min/day for the first 10 days.	Control	1) COPD patients who developed respiratory failure, 2) Patients satisfying the criteria for the need of ICU, 3) Patients who were followed for at least 24 h in the ICU	1) Unstable cardiovascular disease (unstable angina, aortic valve disease), 2) Uncontrolled hypertension, 3) Malignancy, 4) Liver and/or kidney failure, 5) Severe systemic chronic diseases, 6) Orthopedic problems (fracture, joint subluxation, etc.) that could interfere with rehabilitation programs, 7) The patients with fever and who are under the probable effects of acute medication changes were not included in the study	NA	NA	NA

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Wright, 2017	Target delivery of 90 minutes physical rehabilitation/day	Standard group had target delivery of 30 minutes physical rehabilitation/day	1) Age 18 years or over, 2) Invasive or noninvasive ventilation for more than 48 hours	1) End-of-life care, 2) Acute brain or spinal cord injury (or admitted following brain or spinal cord surgery), 3) Multiple trauma if mobilisation therapy was judged unlikely to be possible, 4) Burns, 5) Rapidly progressive neuromuscular disease, 6) Patients enrolled in another clinical trial without a co-enrolment agreement in place, 7) Patients previously enrolled in this trial. Patients who had suffered a cardiac arrest could be recruited if the clinical team believed that there was a possibility of recovery.	Physical Component Summary (part of SF-36) at 6 months.	Changes in mental health at 6 months (MCS by SF-36), Physical ability at ICU discharge (Modified Rivermead Mobility Index), Length of ICU and hospital stay, Exercise capacity (6 min walk test), Functional status (Functional Independence Measure), Hand grip strength, Survival status, and place of residence at 3 and 6 months following randomisation. The health economic evaluation used utility values derived from the EuroQol 5 dimension survey (EQ-5D)20 (administered at hospital discharge, 3 and 6 months) and from the SF-36, using the algorithm provided by the SF-6D, Survival data up to 6 months.	

<p>Wischmeyer, 2017</p>	<p>Supplemental PN+EN</p>	<p>EN</p>	<p>1) Critically ill adult patient (≥ 18 years) admitted to ICU, 2) Acute respiratory failure (defined as expected to require mechanical ventilation >72 hours), 3) Receiving EN or were to be initiated on EN within 48 hours of ICU admission, 4) BMI of <25 or >35, based on pre-ICU actual or estimated dry weight.</p>	<p>(1) >72 hours from ICU admission to consent, (2) not expected to survive an additional 48 hours from screening evaluation, (3) lack of commitment to full, aggressive care (anticipated withholding or withdrawing treatments in the first week, but isolated do-not-resuscitate order acceptable), (4) an absolute contraindication to EN deemed to require PN for the first 7 days of ICU admission (e.g., gastrointestinal obstruction or no gastrointestinal tract access for any reason), (5) already at goal rate of EN from screening evaluation (receiving $\geq 60\%$ estimated needs and no evidence of intolerance [i.e., high gastric residual volumes, etc.]), (6) already receiving PN on admission to ICU, (7) admitted with diabetic ketoacidosis or nonketotic hyperosmolar coma, (8) pregnant or lactating, (9) clinical fulminant hepatic failure, (10) dedicated port of central line not available, (11) known allergy to study nutrients, and (12) enrollment in another industry-sponsored ICU intervention study (coenrollment in academic studies were considered on a case-by-case basis)</p>	<p>Calorie and Protein Intake 7 days + in the first 27 days post randomisation</p>	<p>Feasibility of implementing the SPN intervention, quality measures regarding protocol adherence, and success in intervention delivery</p>	<p>ICU, hospital, and 6-month mortality; development of infectious complications; and duration of mechanical ventilation, ICU stay, and hospital stay. In addition, functional indices were assessed, including admission and discharge Barthel Index, handgrip strength, and 6-minute walk test at discharge. At 3 and 6 months post-randomization, patients were contacted by telephone to record vital status and SF-36 (36-Item Short Form Health Survey) scores.</p>
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Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Giraud, 2016	Structured mirrors intervention	Usual Care	1) Aged 70+ years, 2) Admitted to ICU after elective or urgent cardiac surgery	1) Inability to obtain informed consent, 2) Care pathway anticipating admission elsewhere than to ICU following surgery, 3) Severe visual impairment impeding ability to recognise self in mirror, 4) Physical or communication barriers likely to impede effective, 5) Administration of study procedures, 6) Severe mental disability likely to impede effective administration of study procedures or assessment of delirium, 7) History of psychiatric illness previously requiring hospitalisation.	Delirium incidence during ICU or until 12 weeks after surgery.	ICU days with delirium, proportion of ICU LOS with delirium, ICU days with altered mental status and inattention as assessed by direct care teams using the RASS (Sessler et al., 2002) and CAM-ICU, physical mobilization at ICU discharge as assessed by a research nurse using the ABCScale, total length of ICU stay, factual memories and incidence of delusional memories at 12 weeks after surgery as assessed by a research nurse using the ICU MT (Jones et al., 2000), HRQoL at 12 weeks after surgery assessed by a research nurse using the EQ-5D VAS and index score (EuroQol Group, 1990), and acceptability of the intervention assessed on the basis of the proportion of mirror uses as indicated, proportion of instances where patients refused, and total adherence rate.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Amundadottir, 2019	Intensive upright mobilisation twice daily	Daily mobilisation	1) 18-80 years of age, 2) Requiring mechanical ventilation for over 48 hours, 3) Able to ambulate independently before the onset of acute illness and able to cooperate and comply with assessment for one year after ICU discharge.	1) Poor survival prognoses, 2) Admitted to the hospital more than two weeks prior to admission to the ICU, 3) If progressive upright mobilisation was contraindicated .	Duration of mechanical ventilation, ICU- and hospital lengths of stay.	HRQoL (SF-36v2), Physical function (6MW and the Medical Research assess exercise capacity (MRC-SS) assessed at three to six-time points, modified Barthel Index (MBI)	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Deane, 2020 (Chapman)	Energy-dense (1.5kcal/ml) enteral nutrition	Routine (1.0kcal/ml) enteral nutrition	1) Age ≥18, 2) Intubated and receiving mechanical ventilation, 3) About to commence enteral nutrition or enteral nutrition commenced within the previous 12 h, 4) Expected to be receiving enteral nutrition in ICU at least until the day after tomorrow.	1) Any enteral or parenteral nutrition for >12h in this ICU admission, 2) Treating clinician considers the enteral nutrition goal rate to be clinically contraindicated, 3) Patient requires specific nutritional therapy as determined by the treating doctor or dietitian, 4) Death is deemed to be imminent or inevitable during this admission and either the attending physician, patient or substitute decision maker is not committed to active treatment, 5) Underlying disease that makes survival to 90 days unlikely, 6) ≥15% acute burns, 7) Previously enrolled in this study	All-cause mortality day 90 after randomisation.	Cause-related mortality at day 90, All-cause mortality at hospital discharge, All-cause mortality at 28 days after randomisation, Time from randomisation until death, Number of days alive and not in the ICU or not in hospital to day 28, Ventilator-free/vasopressor-free/renal replacement-free days to day 28, Proportion of patients with positive blood cultures, proportion of patients requiring intravenous antimicrobials, all-cause mortality at 180 days, Functional outcomes at 180 days after randomisation (EQ-5D-5L, World Health Organisation Disability assessment Schedule (WHODAS) 2.0, the Australian Labour Force Survey and the Adelaide Activities Profile).	

<p>de Azevedo, 2021</p>	<p>High protein intake and early exercise</p>	<p>Standard nutrition and routine physiotherapy</p>	<p>1) Aged above 18 years, 2) Admitted to ICU for more than 3 days, 3) Submitted to mechanical ventilation</p>	<p>1) Pregnant, 2) Moribund, 3) Under ventilation for more than 96 h before enrolment, 4) Unable to walk without assistance before the acute illness that led to ICU admission (use of an assistance device to walk was not an exclusion criteria), 5) If they suffered from severe cognitive impairment before hospitalization, 6) Neuromuscular diseases that compromised weaning from ventilation, 7) Acute pelvic fracture, 8) Unstable spinal trauma, 9) Severe liver disease, 10) If it was impossible to start a diet according to the institutional protocols; 11) If they did not sign the written informed consent, 12) In some situations patients will not be included in the resistive exercise program for as long as a temporary limiting factor remains: 13) Patients undergoing neuromuscular blocking drugs, 14)) Patients under high-dose vasoactive drug use, 15) Mechanical ventilation with FIO2 (fraction of inspired oxygen) ≥ 60% and / or PEEP (positive end-expiratory pressure) > 12 cm H2O. 11) Intracranial hypertension, 16) Open abdomen, 17) Status epilepticus.</p>	<p>Physical component summary (PCS) 3 and 6 months after randomisation</p>	<p>Handgrip strenght at ICU discharge, Duration of mechanical ventilation -, Length of ICU stay for up to 20 days, Hospital mortality at 6 months</p>	<p>-</p>
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Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Fan, 2021	Observation group adopted comprehensive nursing	Convention nursing	1) Patients requiring mechanical ventilation	1) Lung infection, 2) Less than 48 h of mechanical ventilation, 3) Expected to die within 48 h from the primary disease.	Mechanical ventilation time, hospitalisation time, VAP incidence, [09:07] Nick Meier The main indicators of blood gas (oxygenation index, P(A-a)DO2/PaO2 and oxygen partial pressure).	Psychological condition, Self-rating anxiety scare, Self-rating depression scale, Quality of life (SF-36)	-

<p>Hammond, 2020 (Venkatesh)</p>	<p>Assigned 200mg Hydrocortisone/day administered as infusion over 24h for a maximum of 7 days</p>	<p>Placebo</p>	<p>1) Aged 18 years or older, 2) Documented site of infection, or strong suspicion of infection, with 2 of the 4 clinical signs of inflammation: a) Core temperature > 38oC or < 36oC, b) Heart rate > 90 beats per minute, c) White cell count > 12 x 10⁹/L or < 4 x 10⁹/L or > 10% immature neutrophils, d) Respiratory rate > 20 breaths per minute, or PaCO₂ < 32 mmHg, or mechanical ventilation, 3) Being treated with mechanical ventilation at the time of randomisation, 4) Being treated with vasopressors or inotropes to maintain a systolic blood pressure > 90mmHg, or mean arterial blood pressure > 60mmHg, or a MAP target set by the treating clinician for maintaining perfusion, 5) Administration of vasopressors or inotropes for ≥ 4 hours and present</p>	<p>1) Met all inclusion criteria more than 24-hours ago 2) Clinician expects to prescribe systemic corticosteroids for an indication other than septic shock (not including nebulised or inhaled corticosteroid) 3) Patients treated with etomidate 4) Patients receiving treatment with Amphotericin B for systemic fungal infections at time of randomization 5) Patients with documented cerebral malaria at the time of randomization 6) Patients with documented strongyloides infection at the time of randomization 7) Death is deemed inevitable or imminent during this admission and either the attending physician, patient or surrogate legal decision maker is not committed to active treatment, 8) Death from underlying disease is likely within 90 days, 9) Patient has been previously enrolled in the ESCAPE study.</p>	<p>All cause mortality at 90 days after randomisation</p>	<p>1) All-cause mortality at 28 days and 6 months after randomisation, 2) Time to resolution of shock, 3) Recurrence of shock, 4) Duration of ICU stay, 5) Duration of hospital stay, 6) Frequency and duration of mechanical ventilation, 7) Frequency and duration of renal replacement therapy, 8) Development of bacteraemia between 2 and 14 days post randomisation, 9) Bleeding requiring blood transfusions received in the ICU, 10) Quality of Life assessment at 6 months.</p>	<p>-</p>
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at time of
randomisation.

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Irving, 2019 (Cooper)	Short-Term Storage	Long-Term Storage	1) Patients 18 years of age or older, 2) Admitted to a participating ICU, 3) Had an anticipated ICU stay of at least 24 hours, 4) The medical staff had decided to transfuse one or more red-cell units	1) Previous red-cell transfusion or cardiac surgery during the hospital admission, 2) Hematologic cancer, 3) Organ transplantation, 4) Pregnancy, 5) Expected death in less than 24 hours, 6) Objection to the administration of human blood, 7) Participation in a competing study, 8) Opinion of the treating physician that randomization would not be in the best interest of the patient (lack of equipoise	All cause mortality day 90	28-day mortality, persistent organ dysfunction or death at day 28, days alive and free of mechanical ventilation at day 28, days alive and free of renal-replacement therapy at day 28, new bloodstream infection in the ICU, febrile nonhemolytic transfusion reactions, length of stay in the hospital and in the ICU, and quality of life at day 180 after randomization	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Liu, 2021	Family-Clinician Shared Decision-Making (FCSDM)	Usual care	1) Terminal cancer with multi-organ metastasis, 2) Severe intra-cerebral hemorrhage, 3) End-stage COPD and respiratory failure, 4) Advanced malignancy and shock, 5) Any disease with a APACHE II score ≥ 20 ,	1) Patients whose families with language barrier, 2) Age over 18 years, 3) Patients estimated to be discharged within 3 days (changed to 48h after the pilot study), 4) Patients whose families reject to sign the informed consent	Satisfaction for shared decision-making; Medical costs.	Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), Quality of Life scale (QoL2), Collaboration and Satisfaction about Care Decisions (CSACD)	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Mao, 2020	Empowerment nursing	Conventional nursing	1) Diagnosed as critically ill after neurosurgery according to the 2006 neurosurgery critical illness diagnosis and treatment guidelines, 2) Aged ≥18 years old, 3) With family caregivers, 4) Unable to completely take care of themselves when admitted to the hospital with a functional life scale score ≤60, 5) recovering in their family home after discharge.	1) Complicated with other serious diseases, such as a malignant tumor, heart failure, renal failure, etc.	After 6 weeks: Family responsibility nursing questionnaire	-	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Martin, 2021	Feasibility of accelerated (≤ 24 h) one-way speaking valve placement	Standard (≥ 48 h) one-way speaking valve placement	1) Patient who received a percutaneous tracheostomy, 2) Glasgow Coma Scale score ≥ 9 , 3) Confusion Assessment Method –ICU (CAM-ICU): negative, 4) Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale (RASS): -1 to +1, 5) Able to understand English	1) Open tracheostomy, 2) Laryngectomy, 3) Presently using OWSV or capped trach, 4) Foam-filled cuffed tracheostomy tube, 5) Presence of known severe airway obstruction, 6) Presence of post-operative bleeding requiring transfusion or packing, 7) Presence of air-leak around the cuff resulting in respiratory decompensation	Pace of participant recruitment and adherence to protocol (feasibility trial)	Quality of Life (QOL-MV), Patient-reported satisfaction, Progression of swallow, Time to decannulation, ICU and hospital lengths of stay, and mortality, Number of Participants With Bleeding	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Mou, 2020	Systematic nursing (Patients: psychological counseling, sleep intervention, early rehabilitation and diet care; Family member: Establishing trust and mutual assistance relationships and care and expressing wishes)	Routine nursing (strict disinfection of the ward and 24-h monitoring)	1) Aged between 35 and 75 years old, 2) Patients firstly admitted to ICU, 3) The core family members of patients aged between 25 and 55 years old, 4) Informed consent was signed by the patients or their families	1) Need of surgical treatment, 2) Patients with mental illness, 3) Patients with severe cognitive impairment, 4) Patients who were in a coma or could not complete the questionnaire independently, when they were admitted to the hospital, 5) Patients with severe dysfunction of important organs, 6) Those with mental diseases, 7) Various acute and chronic diseases in core family members.	Quality of life (SF-36) before and after intervention	Hamilton Anxiety Scale (HAMA) and Hamilton Depression Scale (HAMD), Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI) - all the day of hospitalisation and the day of discharge. Pulmonary infection, pressure sores, lower extremity venous thrombosis were compared during ICU.	-

Nickels, 2020	In-bed cycling in addition to usual care	Usual care	1) expected to be mechanically ventilated for more than 48 h, 2) recruited within 96 h of their ICU admission, and 3) expected to remain in the ICU for more than 48 h from study enrolment	1) were under 18-years old, 2) had pre-existing condition that impaired mobility, 3) had a new neurological disorder, 4) had injuries precluding in-bed cycling, 5) were over 135 kg (cycle ergometer maximum weight capacity), 6) were pregnant, 7) had uncontrolled seizures or status epilepticus, or 8) were unlikely to survive the current hospital admission.	Muscle atrophy day 10 (ultra sound)	In addition to RFCSA, rectus femoris thickness (RFT) and vastus for each assessment parameter (RFCSA, RFT and VIT) at each assessment timepoint was calculated. Physical outcomes measured by physiotherapy assessors blinded to group allocation were: i) manual muscle strength using the Medical Research Council sum score (MRC SUM) of 12 tested muscles with a score range of 0 to 60, ii) handgrip strength (HGS) using a Jamar Digital Dynamometer measured bilaterally with three attempts each hand, iii) functional status measured using the Functional Status Score for the ICU, all measured at ICU discharge and one week following ICU discharge, and iv) a single 6MWT [31] measured one week following ICU discharge. intermedius thickness (VIT) were also measured by sonographers at baseline, Day 3, Day 7, Day 10 post-study enrolment, and seven-days following ICU discharge. Change in muscle thickness and RFCSA at these timepoints were evaluated as secondary outcomes for acute muscle wasting. The coefficient of variation of participants' ultrasound scans	i) participants' best level of function while admitted to the ICU using the ICU Mobility Score, ii) time from ICU admission until the participants achieved functional milestones of sitting out of bed, standing, assisted mobility, and independent mobility, iii) delirium incidence and days using routinely recorded nurse recorded Confusion Assessment Method (CAM)-ICU measures, iv) participants self-rated quality of life at Day 10, three- and six-months post ICU admission using the EQ5D-5 L
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Nielsen, 2020	Intervention group, the relative was supplied with a hardcover notebook and guided by ICU nurses on how to write a diary for the ICU patient and later share the diary with the patient.	Usual care	1) ≥ 18 years, 2) expected to stay in the ICU (LOS-ICU) ≥ 48 h, 3) expected to be mechanically ventilated ≥ 24 h, 4) the patient must have one close relative willing to participate in the study, 5) patients must be able to read Danish, as information about the study and the questionnaire is only available in Danish, 6) relatives ≥18 years, 7) identify themselves as a close relative to the patient	1) patients and relatives will be excluded from study if the patient's LOS-ICU < 48 h or mechanically ventilated <24 h, (patients with prior documented severe cognitive impairments or neurological damage will not be considered for the study), 2) relatives will not be excluded from study if the patient dies or does not consent to study participation	Post traumatic Stress Symptoms-14 inventory (PTSS-14) at 3 months	Ventilator free days at day-28. Other outcomes: Hospital mortality to day 28, Organ failure free days at day 14, ICU-free days at day 28, Hospital-free days at day 60, Increase in PaO2/FiO2 ratio and Oxygenation Index on study days 1-7, VTE at day 14 a)
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Olsen, 2021	None/light sedation Sedation	1) Endotracheally intubated, 2) Expected time on ventilator > 24 hours, 3) Age ≥ 18 years, 4) Informed consent	1) Severe head trauma, 2) Therapeutic hypothermia, 3) Status epi-lepticus, 4) Had participated in our previous trial, 5) Had transferred from another ICU with a length of stay more than 48 hours, 6) Were comatose on admission (not medically induced), 7) Were brain-dead, 8) Had a ratio of the partial pressure of arterial oxygen (measured in kilopascals) to the fraction of inspired oxygen of 9 or lower. They were also excluded if sedation was anticipated to be necessary for oxygenation or for the patient to remain in a prone position'	All-cause mortality at day 90 days after randomisation	were the number of days until death up to 90 days after randomization, the number of thromboembolic events (pulmonary embolus or deep-vein thrombosis) up to 90 days after randomization; the number of days free from coma or delirium (RASS score of at least -3 and a negative CAM-ICU assessment) within 28 days after randomization; the highest score on the Risk, Injury, Failure, Loss of Kidney Function, and End-Stage Kidney Disease (RIFLE) assessment, which classifies acute kidney injury according to severity, within 28 days after randomization ¹² ; the length of stay in the ICU up to death or 28 days after randomization, whichever occurred first; and the number of days without mechanical ventilation within 28 days after randomization. Days free from coma or delirium were recorded during the ICU stay, and days alive after discharge from the ICU up to day 28 were counted as delirium-free days	Exploratory outcomes were all-cause mortality at 28 days after randomization; the length of stay in the ICU up to death or 90 days after randomization, whichever occurred first; the number of days until the patient was no longer in need of mechanical ventilation within 90 days after randomization; the length of hospital stay within 90 days after randomization; organ failure when the patient was discharged from the ICU; the number of accidental extubations that led to reintubation within 1 hour; and the number of accidental removals of central venous catheters that led to reinsertion within 4 hours
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Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Pandian, 2020	Portex BlueLine Ultra Suctionaid Tracheostomy Tube with Speech Language Pathologist consultations	Standard of care (receives talking tracheostomy tube a week later post assessments completed)	1) Mechanically ventilated via tracheostomy, 2) Awake, alert, and attempting to communicate, 3) Able to understand English, 4) Could not tolerate one way speaking valve	1) Delirium, 2) Fresh tracheostomy within 48 hours, 3) Laryngectomy	Quality of life day 1 and 5	Speech Intelligibility test (SIT) scores, independence, satisfaction, and ICU and hospital LOS	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Perkins, 2019	Non-invasive weaning - patients were extubated to NIV	Invasive weaning - patients continued to receive invasive MV with daily spontaneous breathing trial (SBT)	1) Mortality (day 30, 90 and 180), duration of invasive mechanical ventilation, 2) Time to meeting ICU discharge criteria, 3) Proportion of patients receiving antibiotics for a presumed respiratory infection and HRQoL (EQ-5D-3L + SF-12 at baseline (estimated -0.402 for all patients) and 3 and 6 months).	-	Time to liberation from ventilation (hours)	1) Age ≥ 16 years, 2) Patients with respiratory failure who have received invasive ventilation for more than 48 hours (from the time of intubation), 3) Patients who are ready for weaning, 4) Fail a spontaneous breathing trial (SBT)	1) Patient known to be pregnant, 2) Presence of tracheostomy, 3) Unable to protect airway due to profound neurological deficit, 4) Any absolute contraindication to NIV, 5) Home ventilation prior to ICU admission (This does not include nocturnal CPAP) , 6) Decision not to re-intubate or withdrawal of care anticipated, 7) Further surgery / procedure requiring sedation planned in next 48 hours, 8) Previous participation in the Breathe study, 9) Ventilator unavailable to deliver NIV

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Rood, 2019 (van den Boogaard)	Prophylactic haloperidol (1 OR 2 mg)	Placebo (0.9% sodium chloride)	1) Patients aged 18 years or older 2) Who were delirium free, 3) With an anticipated ICU stay of at least 2 days as estimated by the attending intensivist	1) Delirium prior to inclusion, 2) Parkinson disease, 3) Dementia, 4) Alcohol abuse 5) Acute neurological condition, 6) History of a psychiatric disease and use of antipsychotic agents 7) History of clinically relevant ventricular arrhythmia in the last 12 months, QTc time of at least 500 milliseconds, 8) Pregnant or breastfeeding, 9) Expected death within 2 days, 10) Known allergy or intolerance to haloperidol, and 11) Inability to give or have no one able to give informed consent	Survival days in 28 days	number of days survived in 90 days following inclusion, delirium incidence, number of delirium-free and coma-free days over 28 days, duration of mechanical ventilation, and length of ICU and hospital stay. Additional prespecified secondary end points included incidence of unplanned removal of tubes and catheters, incidence of ICU readmission, and the long-term quality-of-life outcome by SF-12 (the results of which will be reported elsewhere)	Adverse effect monitored

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Viana, 2021	Beta-hydroxy-Beta-methylbutyrate (HMB) 3g/day from day 4 and on for 30 days	Placebo (maltodextrin from day 4 on for 30 days	1) Aged >18 years and on mechanical ventilation, 2) Central venous catheter, 3) A functional gastrointestinal tract, 4) Receiving a full treatment, 5) likely to survive more than 7 days	1) Major burns (>20% body surface), 2) Admission for cardiorespiratory arrest or brain injury, 3) Pregnancy or lactation, 4) Patient on parenteral nutrition, 5) Participation in another interventional trial and absence of consent.	Magnitude of loss of muscle mass (skeletal muscle area by ultrasound of the thigh day 4 and 15)	Day 4 and 15 of the phase angle measured by multi frequency bioimpedance, amino acid metabolism using amino acid tracers, and global health and mobility assessed by the SF-12 questionnaire at 30 and 60 days.	-

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Waldauf, 2021	Progressive mobility programme (90 minutes exercise a day until discharge or 28 days)	Routine practice	1) Adult (≥ 18 years) 2) Received mechanical ventilation for less than 72 hours, but 3) Predicted to need ICU for a week or more	1) known primary systemic neuromuscular disease or spinal cord lesion at admission, 2) Severe lower limb injury or amputation, 3) Bedridden pre-morbid state (Charleston Comorbidity Score >4), 4) Approaching imminent death or withdrawal of medical treatment within 24 h, 5) Pregnancy, 6) Presence of external fixator or superficial metallic implants in lower limb, 7) Open wounds or skin abrasions at electrode application points, 8) Presence of pacemaker, implanted defibrillator or another implanted electronic medical device, 9) Predicted as unable to receive first rehabilitation session within 72 hours of admission or transferred from another ICU after more than 24 hours of mechanical ventilation, 10) Presence of other condition preventing the use of FESCE or considered unsuitable for the study by a responsible medical team, 11) Prior participating in another functional outcome-based intervention research study	Physical Component Summary (PCS) score of the SF-36 quality at 6 months in ICU survivors	Four-item Physical Fitness in Intensive Care Test (PFIT-s), 37 rectus muscle cross-sectional diameter on B-mode ultrasound, mean daily nitrogen balance, muscle power as per the Medical Research Council score, number of ventilator-free days and ICU length of stay, all measured at discharge from ICU or day 28, whichever occurred earlier. Safety outcomes were the number of episodes of elevated ICP and dialysis interruptions	-

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Xu, 2021	ICU nursing risk management combined with a cluster nursing model	Routine nursing	1) Compliance with the diagnostic criteria of ARDS; 2) Mechanical ventilation time (≥48 h) and the occurrence of VAP; 3) Complete clinical data; This study was approved by the ethics committee of Wuhan Jinyintan Hospital, and the patients and their families knew the purpose and process of this experimental study, and signed the informed consent.	1) Expected survival time less than 3 months; 2) Combination with other respiratory diseases; 3) Cognitive impairment such as mental disorders; 4) Acute hemorrhage and intracranial hypertension.	Efficacy evaluation (respiratory secretions, body temperature, leukocytes, ELISA, IL-8, IL-6, TNF-alfa)	APACHE II before and after nursing, Pulmonary function detector (Vital capacity, total lung capacity, forced expiratory volume 1 second, forced vital capacity, SF-36 before and after intervention.	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Zeng, 2021	Humanized care additionally to routine nursing care	Routine nursing care	1) Diagnosed with CVDs; 2) Patients without other diseases that have a major impact on our conclusions; 3) Patients with normal postoperative vital signs and no mental abnormalities; 4) Patients without communication disorders.	1) Patients with other diseases that have a major impact on our conclusion; 2) Patients with dysfunctions of organs (the liver, kidney, heart, etc.); 3) Patients with mental disorders; 4) Pregnant or lactating women.	Cardiopulmonary function (day 7), Self-efficacy (admission, day 7 and 14), Sleep quality (admission, day 7 and 14), Anxiety and depression (admission, day 7 and 14), Quality of life (day 14) with SF-36, Incidence of adverse reactions, Patient satisfaction with a self-made satisfaction questionnaire.	-	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Morris, 2016	Standardised rehabilitation therapy for 7 days a week through hospital discharge	Usual care received routine care by physician in weekdays.	1) Admission to a medical ICU, 2) Being 18 years or older, 3) Mechanical ventilation via endotracheal tube or noninvasive ventilation by mask, 4) Arterial oxygen partial pressure to fractional inspired oxygen (PaO2/FIO2) ratio less than 300.	1) Inability to walk without assistance prior to the acute ICU illness (use of cane or walkers were not exclusions), 2) Cognitive impairment prior to acute ICU illness described by surrogate, 3) Asnonverbal, 4) Acute stroke, 5) Body mass index (BMI; calculated as weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared) greater than 50, 6) Neuromuscular disease impairing weaning from mechanical ventilation, 7) Acute hip fracture, 8) Unstable cervical spine or pathologic fracture, 9) Mechanically ventilated more than 80 hours or current hospitalization (including transferring hospital) more than 7 days, 10) Orders for do not intubate on admission, 11) Considered to be moribund by the primary attending, or 12) Enrolled in another research study.	Length of hospital stay.	Length of time in the ICU, Functional status (Short Performance Physical Battery (SPPB) and handgrip dynamometer, Muscular strength of the shoulder flexors, elbow flexors and extensors, hip flexors, knee flexors and extensors, and ankle dorsiflexors was measured thrice bilaterally, Functional Performance Inventory (FPI) and SF-36 physical health survey, Quality of life (SF-36), Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) score. and adverse events.	-

Rublee, 2002 (Warren)	Total of 30,000 IU plasma-derived AT III	placebo solution (1% of human albumin)	Adult hospitalized men and women (≥18 years) were admitted to the study if they gave informed consent and met the following criteria within a 6-hour period: clinical evidence of sepsis with a suspected source of infection, body temperature (rectal or core) higher than 38.5°C or lower than 35.5°C, and leukocyte count higher than 10 × 10 ³ /μL or lower than 3.5 × 10 ³ /μL. Additionally, 3 of the following 6 signs had to be met within the same 6-hour period: tachycardia (heart rate >100/min); tachypnea (>24/min) or mechanical ventilation because of septic indication; hypotension with systolic blood pressure lower than 90 mm Hg despite sufficient fluid replacement or the need of vasoactive agents to maintain systolic blood pressure of 90 mm Hg or	Advanced directive to withhold life-sustaining treatment (except cardiopulmonary resuscitation); condition other than sepsis anticipated to be fatal within 28 days; pregnancy or breastfeeding; history of hypersensitivity to study medication; treatment with other investigational drugs within the last 30 days; treatment with an antithrombin III concentrate within the last 48 hours; treatment with heparin (except subcutaneous low dose or intravenous [IV] line flushing) or coumarin derivatives; nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug treatment within previous 2 days; known bleeding disorder or ongoing massive surgical bleeding; platelet count of less than 30 × 10 ³ /μL; immunocompromised status; acute myocardial infarction (within previous 7 days); third-degree burns (≥20% of total body area); incurable malignancy with documented metastases and life-expectancy of less than 3 months; hematologic neoplasia during cytostatic treatment; bone marrow aplasia; preexisting dialysis-dependent renal failure; end-stage liver disease; transplantation (postoperative state); history of stroke within the last year; severe cranial or spinal trauma within the last year; planned cranial or spinal surgery (except nontraumatic lumbar puncture) within the next 48 hours	28-day all-cause mortality	Survival status after 28 days, survival time, length of ICU stay, occurrence of new organ dysfunction within 7 days, SAPSII, Surgical interventions and bleeding events recorded for 28 days, Antithrombin III plasma concentrations at baseline and after 24h, thromboplastin time and prothrombin time.	-
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greater;
thrombocytopenia
with platelet
counts of less than
 $100 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$;
elevated lactate
levels (above upper
limit of normal
range) or metabolic
acidosis (pH <7.3 or
base excess ≤ -10
mmol/L) not
secondary to
respiratory
alkalosis; oliguria
with urine output
of less than 20 mL
per hour despite
sufficient fluid
replacement

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Lemkes, 2020	Immediate angiography either immediate angiography (as soon as possible and was initiated within 2 hours after randomization)	Delayed angiography (performed after neurologic recovery, in general after discharge from the intensive care unit.)	1) Age > 18, 2) Comatose patients (Glasgow coma score < 8) with ROSC after OHCA, 3) Ventricular tachycardia or ventricular fibrillation as initial arrest rhythm. Including patients treated with an AED	1) Signs of STEMI on the ECG at the emergency department (including new LBBB or isolated ST depression in V1-V3 due to an true posterior infarct), 2) Hemodynamic instability unresponsive to medical therapy. Defined as a prolonged (>30 min), 3) Systolic blood pressure <90 mmHg at the time of screening, 4) An obvious or suspected non-coronary cause of the arrest, 5) A known severe renal dysfunction (GFR<30 ml/min), 6) Obvious or suspected pregnancy, 7) Suspected or confirmed acute intracranial bleeding, 8) Suspected or confirmed acute stroke, 9) Known limitations in therapy or DO Not Resuscitate-order, 10) Known pre-arrest Cerebral Performance Category 3 or 4, 11) >4 hours (from return of spontaneous circulation to screening), 12) Refractory ventricular arrhythmia, 13) Known inability to complete 90-day follow-up.	Survival at 90 days	90-days survival with good, minor or moderate disability. Defined as a Cerebral Performance Category of 1 or 2, Myocardial injury measured by troponine and CK MB as area under the curve, Duration of inotropic support, Occurrence off acute kidney injury according to AKIN criteria, Need for renal replacement therapy, Time to optimal hypothermia, Neurological status at ICU discharge, Markers of shock: lactate and SVO2 at day 1, 2 en 3, Recurrence of ventricular tachycardia needing defibrillation or electrical cardioversion, Duration of mechanical ventilation, Reason for discontinuation of treatment, Left ventricular function on cardiac ultrasound or MRI, Functional performance at 1 year, MACE and survival at 1 and 5 years	-

Mackle, 2020	Conservative oxygen SAT \leq 97%	Usual oxygen	1) The patient is aged \geq 18 years, 2) The patient requires invasive mechanical ventilation in the ICU, 3) The patient is expected to be receiving mechanical ventilation beyond the next calendar day	1) In the view of the treating clinician, hyperoxia is clinically indicated for reasons including (but not limited to) carbon monoxide poisoning or a requirement for hyperbaric oxygen therapy, 2) In the view of the treating clinician, avoidance of hyperoxia is clinically indicated for reasons including (but not limited to) COPD, paraquat poisoning, previous exposure to bleomycin, or chronic hypercapnic respiratory failure, 3) Pregnancy, 4) Death is deemed to be inevitable as a result of the current acute illness and either the treating clinician, the patient or the substitute decision maker are not committed to full active treatment, 5) Patients with a life expectancy < 90 days due to a chronic or underlying medical condition, 6) Patients admitted after a drug overdose (including alcohol intoxication), 7) Long term dependence on invasive ventilation prior to this acute illness, 8) Confirmed or suspected diagnosis of any of the following: Guillain–Barré syndrome, cervical cord injury above C5, muscular dystrophy, or motor neurone disease, 9) Enrolment not considered in the patient’s best interests, 10) Enrolled in any other trial of targeted oxygen therapy, 11) Previously enrolled in the ICU-ROX study, 12) More than 2 hours of invasive mechanical ventilation or non-invasive ventilation in an ICU during this hospital admission	Ventilator-free days to day 28	All cause mortality day 28, 90 and 180, Cause specific mortality, Duration of survival day 180, HRQoL day 180, Functional outcome assessed by Extended Glasgow coma scale day180, proportion of patients in paid employment at baseline who are unempoloyed at 180 days (by telephone), Cognitive function assessed using telephone day 180.
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(includes time ventilated in
another hospital's ICU)

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Bagshaw, 2020	Accelerated strategy of renal-replacement therapy.	Standard strategy	1) Age ≥18 years, 2) Admission to an ICU, 3) Evidence of kidney dysfunction, 4) Evidence of severe acute kidney injury	1) Potassium at time of screening >5.5 mmol/L, 2) Bicarbonate at time of screening <15 mmol/L, 3) Presence of a drug overdose or dialyzable toxin that necessitates RRT, 4) Lack of commitment to provide RRT as part of philosophy care, 5) Receipt of any RRT in the preceding 2 months, 6) Kidney transplant within the past 365 days, 7) Known advanced chronic kidney disease, 8) Presence or strong clinical suspicion of renal obstruction, rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis, vasculitis, thrombotic microangiopathy or acute interstitial nephritis, 9) Immediate RRT was mandated, 10) Deferral of RRT was mandated.	Death from any cause at 90 days	Renal replacement therapy (RRT) dependence at day 90, Composite of death or dependence on RRT, major adverse kidney event, Death in the ICU at 28 days, number of days free of RRT at day 90, Number of ventilator free and vasoactive-free days at 28 days, Length of hospitalization and hospitalization-free days at 90 days, Health-related quality of life as assessed 90 days,	-

Dixon, 2021	Nebulised unfractionated heparin sodium 25000 IU in 5 ml every 6 hour to day 10 while invasively ventilated	Identical placebo (sodium chloride 0.9%) in 5 ml every 6 hour to day 10 while invasively ventilated	1) Age ≥ 18 years, 2) Receiving invasive mechanical ventilation via an tube, 3) Started ventilation via an endotracheal tube yesterday or today 4) Intubated on the day of randomisation or the preceding day, 5) Impaired oxygenation defined by an arterial partial pressure of oxygen to fraction of inspired oxygen ratio (PaO ₂ /FiO ₂) of less than 300 while invasively ventilated, 6) Expected to require invasive ventilation beyond the end of the following day, 7) Active (heated) ventilator circuit humidification.	1) Previously enrolled in this study, 2) Enrolled in another randomised intervention study, unless approved, 3) Allergy to heparin, 4) Any history of heparin induced thrombocytopenia, 5) Platelet count less than 50 x 10 ⁹ /L, 6) APTT is prolonged to greater than 80 seconds and this is not due to anticoagulant therapy, 7) Uncontrolled bleeding, 8) Pulmonary bleeding during this hospital admission (Pulmonary bleeding is frank bleeding in the lungs, trachea or bronchi with repeated hemoptysis, or requiring repeated suctioning, and temporally associated with acute deterioration in respiratory status), 9) Neurosurgical procedures during this hospital admission or such procedures are planned, 10) Epidural catheter in place, 11) Any history of intracranial, spinal or epidural hemorrhage, 12) Hepatic encephalopathy or any history of gastrointestinal bleeding due to portal hypertension or biopsy proven cirrhosis with documented portal hypertension, 13) Tracheostomy in place, 14) Usually receives home oxygen, 15) Usually receives any type of assisted ventilation at home e.g. continuous positive airway pressure for obstructive sleep, 16) apnoea, 17) Cervical spinal cord injury associated with reduced long-term ability to breathe independently, 18) Spinal or peripheral nerve disease with a likely prolonged reduction in the ability to breathe	SF-36 physical function score at day 60	1) development of new ARDS among at-risk patients to day 5 2) deterioration in the MLIS to day 5 3) time to ventilator separation to day 28 4) time to intensive care unit (ICU) separation to day 28 5) tracheotomy, institution of new respiratory rescue therapies, and ICU readmission, each by day 28 6) vasopressor therapy-free days to day 28, and renal replacement therapy-free days to day 28, with non-survivors assigned 0 therapy-free days and reported separately for all patients and survivors; mortality at day 28 7) acute hospital length of stay and acute hospital discharge destination 8) mortality, place of residence, and quality of life, assessed using the EQ-5D-3L, at day 60 and at day 180; and proximate cause of death and SF-36 Physical Function Score of survivors at day 180	-
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independently e.g. Guillain-Barré syndrome, motor neurone disease, 19) Receiving high frequency oscillation ventilation or the treating Intensivist has made a definite decision to commence high frequency oscillation ventilation, 20) Receiving extra-corporeal membrane oxygenation or the treating Intensivist has made a definite decision to commence extra-corporeal membrane oxygenation, 21) Treatment limits restrict the provision of renal replacement therapy, inotropes, vasopressors or prolonged invasive ventilation, 22) Usually treated with hemodialysis or peritoneal dialysis for end-stage renal failure, 23) Dementia, 24) Death is deemed imminent or inevitable or there is underlying disease with a life expectancy of less than 90 days 6 - Pregnant or might be pregnant. Women aged 18 to 49 are excluded unless there is documented menopause, hysterectomy or surgical sterilisation, or a pregnancy test is negative, 25) Objection from the treating clinician, 26) Consent refused by the patient or substitute decision maker.

Ginde, 2019	Single enteral dose of 540,000 IU of vitamin D3	Matched placebo	1) Age ≥18 years, 2) Intention to admit to ICU from emergency department, hospital ward, operating room or outside facility, 3) One or more of the following acute risk factors for ARDS and mortality contributing directly to the need for ICU admission; Pulmonary: Pneumonia, Aspiration, Smoke inhalation, Lung contusion, Mechanical ventilation for acute hypoxemic or hypercarbic respiratory failure or Extra pulmonary: Shock, sepsis, pancreatitis, 4) Vitamin D deficiency (screening 25OHD level <20 ng/mL)	1. Inability to obtain informed consent, 2. Unable to randomize within 12 hours of ICU admission decision, 3. Unable to take study medication by mouth or enteral tube, 4. Baseline serum calcium >10.2 mg/dL (2.54 mmol/L) or ionized calcium >5.2 mg/dL (1.30 mmol/L), 5. Known kidney stone in past year or history of multiple (>1) prior kidney stone episodes, 6. Decision to withhold or withdraw life-sustaining treatment (patients are still eligible if they are committed to full support except cardiopulmonary resuscitation if a cardiac arrest occurs), 7. Expect <48 hour survival, 8. If no other risk factors present, a) mechanical ventilation primarily for airway protection, pain/agitation control, or procedure; or b) elective surgical patients with routine postoperative mechanical ventilation; or c) anticipated mechanical ventilation duration <24 hours; or d) chronic/home mechanical ventilation for chronic lung or neuromuscular disease (non-invasive ventilation used solely for sleep-disordered breathing is not an exclusion), 9. Prisoner, 10. Pregnancy	All cause, all location mortality day 90	1) All-cause, All Location Mortality to Day 28 2) Hospital Mortality to Day 90 3) Alive and Home 4) Hospital Length of Stay to Day 90 5) Healthcare Facility Length of Stay to Day 90 6) Ventilator-free Days (VFDs) to Day 28 7) Health-related Quality of Life by EuroQol (EQ-5D-5L) 8) Number of Participants Who Developed (New) ARDS to Day 7 9) Severity of Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome 10) Worst Acute Kidney Injury 11) New Renal Replacement Therapy 12) Highest Creatinine Levels 13) New Vasopressor Use to Day 7 14) Highest Cardiovascular SOFA 15) 25OHD Levels at Day 3 16) Highest Total Calcium to Day 14 17) Highest Ionized Calcium to Day 14 18) Hypercalcemia to Day 14 19) Kidney Stones to Day 90 20) Fall-related Fractures to Day 90 21) Falls to Day 90	-
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Hughes, 2021	Dexmedetomidine (0.2 to 1.5 microgram per kg bodyweight per hour) for up to 14 days	Propofol (5 to 50 microgram per kg per minute) for up to 14 days	[1] adult patients (≥18 years old), [2] in a medical and/or surgical ICU, and [3] on MV and requiring sedation, and [4] have suspected or known infection	1) Rapidly resolving organ failure, indicated by planned immediate discontinuation of MV, at time of screening for study enrollment, 2) Pregnant or breastfeeding, 3) Severe dementia or neurodegenerative disease, defined as either impairment that prevents the patient from living independently at baseline or IQCODE >4.5, measured using a patient's qualified surrogate. This exclusion also pertains to mental illnesses requiring long-term institutionalization, acquired or congenital mental retardation, severe neuromuscular disorders, Parkinson's disease, and Huntington's disease. It also excludes patients in coma or with severe deficits due to structural brain diseases such as stroke, intracranial hemorrhage, cranial trauma, malignancy, anoxic brain injury, or cerebral edema. 4) History of 2nd or 3rd degree heart block, bradycardia < 50 beats/minute, pacemaker for bradyarrhythmias or uncompensated shock.If patient has a pacemaker for bradyarrhythmias, then patient does not meet this exclusion criterion and may be enrolled. 5) Benzodiazepine dependency or history of alcohol dependency based on the medical team's decision to institute a specific treatment plan involving benzodiazepines (either as continuous infusions or intermittent intravenous boluses) for this dependency.6) Active seizures during this ICU admission being treated with intravenous	Days alive without delirium or coma during the 14-day intervention period	Ventilator-free days at 28 days, 90-day survival, Neuropsychological function and ADL at 6 months, Markers of inflammation day 1, 3, 5, 7, and 14, Secondary infections, Organ dysfunction, Acute respiratory distress syndrom	Longterm follow-up at 6 months: delirium, neuropsychological phone battery, ADL, EQ-5D
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benzodiazepines. 7) Expected death within 24 hours of enrollment or lack of commitment to aggressive treatment by family/medical team (e.g., likely to withdraw life support measures within 24 hrs of screening)
Inability to understand English or deafness or vision loss that will preclude delirium evaluation. The inability to understand English (for example in Spanish-only or Mandarin-only speaking patients) will not result in exclusion at centers where the research staff is proficient and/or translation services are actively available in that particular language; these patients will not be followed in the long-term follow-up phase of the trial since the testing materials are primarily available only in English. Patients with laryngectomies and those with hearing deficits are eligible for enrollment if their medical condition permits them to communicate with research staff.
8) Inability to obtain informed consent from an authorized representative within 48 hours of meeting all inclusion criteria, i.e., developing sepsis and qualifying organ dysfunction criteria for the following reasons: Attending physician refusal, Patient and/or surrogate refusal, Patient unable to consent and no surrogate available, 48-hour period of eligibility was exceeded before the patient was screened.9)
Prisoners. 10) Medical team following patient unwilling to use the sedation regimens. 11)

Documented allergy to propofol or dexmedetomidine. 12) Current enrollment in a study that does not allow co-enrollment or that uses delirium as a primary outcome. 13) Patients who are on muscle relaxant infusions at time of screening with plans to maintain paralysis >48 hours. 14) Greater than 96 hours on mechanical ventilation prior to meeting all inclusion criteria.

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Lamontagne, 2020	Vasopressors guided by MAP target 60-65mmHg	Vasopressors guided according to usual care	1) Age 65 years or older, 2) Vasodilatory hypotension as assessed by treating clinician, 3) Started infusion of vasopressors within prior 6 hours (if noradrenaline, then a minimum dose of 0.1 µg kg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹), 4) Adequate fluid resuscitation is completed or ongoing, 5) Vasopressors expected to continue for 6 hours or more as assessed by treating clinician	1) Vasopressors being used solely as therapy for bleeding, acute ventricular failure (left or right) or post-cardiopulmonary bypass vasoplegia, 2) Ongoing treatment for brain injury or spinal cord injury, 3) Death perceived as imminent, 4) Previous enrolment to the 65 Trial	All cause mortality at day 90 (clinical effectiveness) and QALYs (cost-effectiveness)	Mortality at discharge from the critical care unit and acute hospital, Duration of survival to longest available follow-up, Duration of advanced respiratory and renal support (defined according to the Critical Care Minimum Dataset [CCMDS]) during the critical care unit stay, Days alive and free of advanced respiratory support and renal support, Duration of critical care unit and acute hospital stay, Cognitive function assessed using the Informant Questionnaire on Cognitive Decline in the Elderly (IQCODE, short version) at 90 days and one year, Health-related quality of life, assessed using the EuroQol EQ-5D-5L questionnaire, at 90 days and one year, Resource use and costs at 90 days and one year, Estimated lifetime incremental cost-effectiveness	-

Laterre, 2019	Selepressin 0.3mg/mL	Placebo (sterile 0.9% sodium chloride solution	1. 18 years of age or older, 2. Proven or suspected infection, 3. Septic shock defined as hypotension (systolic blood pressure less than 90 mmHg OR MAP less than 65 mmHg) requiring vasopressor treatment (i.e. any dose of norepinephrine / noradrenaline base greater than 5 µg/min) despite adequate fluid resuscitation (at least one litre for hypotension), 4. Informed consent obtained in accordance with local regulations.	1. Not possible to initiate IMP treatment within 12 hours from onset of vasopressor treatment for septic shock, 2. Primary cause of hypotension not due to sepsis (e.g. major trauma including traumatic brain injury, haemorrhage, burns, or congestive heart failure/cardiogenic shock), 3. Previous severe sepsis with ICU admission within this hospital stay, 4. Known/suspected acute mesenteric ischaemia, 5. Suspicion of concomitant acute coronary syndrome based on clinical symptoms and/or ECG during this episode of septic shock, 6. Chronic mechanical ventilation for any reason OR severe COPD requiring either continuous daily oxygen use during the preceding 30 days or mechanical ventilation (for acute exacerbation of COPD) during the preceding 30 days, 7. Received bone marrow transplant during the preceding 6 months or chemotherapy during the preceding 30 days for lymphoma or leukemia, 8. Known to be pregnant, 9. Decision to limit full care taken before obtaining informed consent, 10. Use of vasopressin in the past 12 hours prior to start of the IMP infusion or use of terlipressin within 7 days prior to start of the IMP infusion, 11. Prior enrolment in the trial, 12. Prior use of an investigational medicinal product within the last month OR planned or concurrent participation in a clinical trial for any	Vasopressor- and mechanical ventilator- free days up to day 30	All-cause mortality at Day 90, RRT-free days up to Day 30, Intensive care unit (ICU)-free days up to Day 30, Vasopressor-free days up to Day 30, Mechanical ventilator-free days up to Day 30, Duration of septic shock (i.e. vasopressor use) up to Day 30, Duration of mechanical ventilation up to Day 30, Incidence of RRT up to Day 30, Duration of RRT up to Day 90, Daily overall and individual organ scores using a modified version of the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) until ICU discharge, Incidence of new organ dysfunction and new organ failure (based on the SOFA score) up to Days 7 and 30, ICU length of stay up to Day 30, All-cause mortality at Days 30 and 180, Daily and cumulative fluid balance until ICU discharge (for a maximum of 7 days), Daily and cumulative urine output until ICU discharge (for a maximum of 7 days), Change in utility (HRQoL) up to day 180
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investigational drug or
investigational device

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Litton, 2021	Probiotic therapy for 60 days	Placebo	1. Adult patient within 48 hours of admission to an ICU, 2. Expected to require ICU-level care beyond the next calendar day	1. <18 years of age, 2. Absolute contraindication to receiving medication via the enteral route, 3. Known to be receiving probiotic therapy at the time of index hospitalisation, 4. Acute pancreatitis as a cause or complication of current admission, 5. Immunosuppression (defined as chemotherapy within the preceding four weeks, or receiving $\geq 1.5\text{mg/kg}$ methylprednisolone daily or equivalent), 6. Neutropenia (neutrophil count $\leq 1 \times 10^9/\text{L}$), 7. Prosthetic heart valve or permanent pacemaker, 8. Death is deemed to be inevitable as a result of the current acute illness AND either the treating clinician, the patient or the substitute decision-maker, are not committed to full active treatment, 9. Enrolment is not considered in the patient's best interest, 10. Previously enrolled in ROCIT, 11. Unlikely to be residing near or visiting a study centre in 60 days, 12. Participating in a competing interventional study, 13. Pregnancy, 14. Admitted to hospital from a high-level nursing facility or rehabilitation facility	Days alive and out of hospital day 60	Occurrence of specified nosocomial infections (hospital-acquired pneumonia, ventilator-associated pneumonia, C. difficile-associated diarrhoea, surgical-site infection, urinary tract infection and blood stream infection) defined according to Centre for Disease Control criteria, Antibiotic-free days to day 60, ICU and hospital LOS, and ICU, Hospital and 60-day mortality, Quality of life at day 60	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Amrein, 2014	Cholecalciferol (single dose 540.000 IU vitamin D, monthly doses 90.000 IU D up to month 6	Placebo identical in colour, smell and texture	1) 18 years or older, 2) Expected to stay in the ICU for 48 hours or more, 3) Found to have a 25-hydroxyvitamin D level of 20 ng/mL (to convert to nmol/L, 4) Multiply by 2.496) or lower were eligible for study participation	1) Severely impaired gastrointestinal function; 2) Other trial participation, 3) Pregnant or lactating women; 4) Hypercalcemia (total calcium of >10.6 mg/dL or ionized serumcalcium of >5.4mg/dL [to convert both to mmol/L, 5) Multiply by0.25]); 6) Tuberculosis; 7) Sarcoidosis; 8) Nephrolithiasis within the prior year; 9) Patients not deemed suitable for study participation	Hospital stay for 6 months (hours; starting from ICU admission)	ICU stay, Mortality in ICU, in hospital, at day 28 and at 6 months, Percentage of patients with 25(OH)D ≥ 30 ng/ml at day 7, Laboratory parameters including serum calcium, 25(OH)D at days 0,3,7 and 28 (if the patient is still hospitalised), Duration of mechanical ventilation, Cardiac function (NT-proBNP levels, days on catecholamine support), TISS 28 scores during ICU stay	Number of falls, fractures, hospital admissions, respiratory tract infections, SF-12, performance status score at 6 months

Moss, 2019	Cisatracurium infusion	Control group	<p>1) Mechanical ventilation through an endotracheal tube and 2) Following criteria present for less than 48 hours: a) Pao₂:Fio₂ of less than 150 mm Hg with a PEEP of 8 cm or more of water; b) bilateral pulmonary opacities on chest radiography or c) on computed tomography that could not be explained by effusions, pulmonary collapse, or nodules; and d) respiratory failure that could not be explained by cardiac failure or fluid overload, 3) Age above 18 y</p>	<p>1) Lack of informed consent, 2) Continuous neuromuscular blockade (NMB) at enrollment (>2 NMB boluses excluding NMB given for reasons other than ARDS management [e.g., intubation or transport] or >3h continuous infusion), 3) Known pregnancy, 4) Currently receiving extracorporeal membrane oxygenation therapy, 5) Chronic respiratory failure defined as PaCO₂ >60 mmHg in the outpatient setting, 6) Home mechanical ventilation (non-invasive or via tracheotomy) except for continuous or bilevel positive airway pressure support used solely for sleep-disordered breathing, 7) Actual body weight exceeding 1 kg per centimeter of height, 8) Severe chronic liver disease defined as a Child-Pugh score of 12-15, 9) Bone marrow transplantation within the last year, 10) Expected duration of mechanical ventilation <48 hours, 11) Decision to withhold life-sustaining treatment, not including those patients committed to full support except cardiopulmonary resuscitation, 12) Moribund patient not expected to survive 24 hours; if cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) provided, assess for moribund status ≥6 hours from CPR conclusion, 13) Diffuse alveolar hemorrhage from vasculitis, 14) Burns >70% of total body surface, 15) Unwillingness to utilize the NHLBI Acute Respiratory Distress Network (ARDS) Network 6 ml/kg, ideal body weight ventilation protocol,</p>	All-cause mortality day 90	<p>1. ICU acquired weakness a. Manual muscle strength testing will be attempted at 96 hours, 7 days, and then every 7 days thereafter, until hospital discharge or day 28 (whichever comes first). Patients will be defined as having ICU acquired weakness if their Medical Research Council (MRC) score is < 48.19 b. AM-PAC “6 clicks” inpatient basic mobility short forms: This validated six question inpatient survey determines the functional status of inpatients. The AM-PAC will be determined at 96 hours, 7 days, and then every 7 days thereafter, until hospital discharge or day 28 (whichever comes first). 20 2. IL-6 levels (plasma) We will measure interleukin-6 (IL-6) at study entry and at 48 hours. A proposed mechanism of benefit of neuromuscular blockade is decreased ventilator-induced lung injury. Interleukin-6 is a pro-inflammatory cytokine that decreased in patients treated with a lung-protective low tidal volume ventilation strategy compared to control patients.²¹</p>
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16) Previous hypersensitivity or anaphylactic reaction to cisatracurium, 17) Neuromuscular conditions that may potentiate NMB or impair spontaneous ventilation (study protocol, appendix A2), 18) Neurologic conditions undergoing treatment for intracranial hypertension, 19) Enrollment in an interventional ARDS trial with direct impact on neuromuscular blockade and PEEP, 20) Pa O₂/FIO₂ (if available) >200 mmHg after meeting inclusion criteria and before randomization, 21) Endotracheal ventilation for greater than 120 hours (5 days), 22) Patient has completed lung transplant evaluation and has been officially listed for lung transplant by the United Network for Organ Sharing organization

Furthermore, in pilot studies neuromuscular blockade was associated with decreased levels of IL-6.¹⁴ Here, we hypothesize that compared to control subjects, subjects receiving neuromuscular blockade for 48 hours will have lower levels of IL-6, reflecting decreased ventilator-induced lung injury. As in the ARDS Network trials, analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) will be used to examine the impact of treatment with neuromuscular blockade on biomarker levels at 48 hours.

3. Hospital mortality to day 28

4. Ventilator free days to day 28

Ventilator free days to day 28 are defined as the number of days from the time of initiating unassisted breathing to day 28 after randomization, assuming survival for at least two consecutive calendar days after initiating unassisted breathing and continued unassisted breathing to day 28. If a patient returns to assisted breathing and subsequently achieves unassisted breathing to day 28, VFDs will be counted from the end of the last period of

assisted breathing to day 28. A period of assisted breathing lasting less than 24 hours and for the purpose of a surgical procedure will not count against the VFD calculation. If a patient was receiving assisted breathing at day 27 or dies prior to day 28, VFDs will be zero. Patients transferred to another hospital or other health care facility will be followed to day 28 to assess this endpoint.

5. Organ failure free days to day 28
Organ failure is defined as present on any date when the most abnormal vital signs or clinically available lab value meets the definition of clinically significant organ failure according to SOFA scores (Appendix K).²² Patients will be followed for development of organ failures to death, hospital discharge or study day 28, whichever comes first. Each day a patient is alive and free of a given organ failure will be scored as a failure-free day. Any day that a patient is alive and free of all organ failures will represent days alive and free of all organ failure.

6. ICU-free days at day 28

7. Hospital-free days at day 28

8. Physiologic measures to include:

- a) Oxygenation Index on study days 1-4,7
- b) PaO₂ / FiO₂ ratio on study days 1-4, 7
- c) Level of PEEP on study days 1-4, 7
- d) Plateau pressure on study day 1-4, 7
- e) Development of pneumothorax through day 7

9. Long term outcome assessments

We will assess seven measures after hospitalization:

- a) Impact Event Scale-Revised (IES-R)
- b) EuroQol (EQ5D) health questionnaire
- c) Katz Activities of Daily Living (ADL)/Lawton Instrumental Activities of Daily Living Scale (IADL)
- d) Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)
- e) Medical Outcomes Study Short Form-36 Health Survey (SF-36)
- f) Paralysis recall assessment, using a modified Brice questionnaire
- g) Return to work status: Improving Care of ALI Patients (ICAP) study questionnaire

These measures will be obtained at 3 (MoCA, IADL, ADL, and EQ5D only), 6 and

12 months, and collected through telephone interviews with patients or their LARs. (see 6.4 Assessments After Hospitalization).

10. Use of rescue procedures
Rescue procedures will be chosen according to the practice at the clinical site. We will record the use of the following rescue procedures (yes/no) through study day 28: prone positioning, nitric oxide, epoprostenol sodium, high frequency ventilation, and ECMO.

11. Paralysis recall, in-hospital
Paralysis recall assessment, will be monitored once during hospitalization in all patients, using a modified Brice questionnaire.^{23;24}

12. Supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) or new onset atrial fibrillation (the occurrence of one or more episodes during the ICU stay will be recorded)

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Parke, 2021	Protocol-guided strategy utilizing stroke volume variation to guide administration of bolus fluid administration until desedation or up to 24 hours	Usual care	1) 16 years old or older, 2) Having elective cardiac surgery with planned use of cardiopulmonary bypass and 3) A preoperative EuroSCORE II of 0.9 or more	1) Emergency procedure; 2) Contraindication to SVV monitoring, 3) Atrial fibrillation, 4) Intra-aortic balloon pump in situ or anticipated, 5) Open chest, 6) Critical post-operative condition (patient not expected to survive > 24 hours after post-operative admission to ICU); 7) Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation or ventricular assist device in situ or anticipated; 8) Indication for specific fluid management strategy after surgery, 9) Adult congenital heart surgery, 10) End-stage renal failure requiring dialysis; 11) Enrolment not considered to be in the patient's best interest	ICU length of stay day 28	Incidence of wound infections, Development of organ dysfunction using the SOFA score, All-cause mortality to Day 180, Quality of life at Days 90 and 180 using the EQ-5D-5L instrument, Disability-free survival at Days 90 and 180 using WHODAS 2.021, Development of AKI according to KDIGO criteria, Amount of fluid administered (mL) up to Day 3 if still in ICU, Overall fluid balance (mL) for Days 1–3 (if in ICU), Requirement for red blood cell, platelet, fresh frozen plasma or cryoprecipitate transfusion, Duration of mechanical ventilation (hours), Requirement for vasopressor therapy in ICU, Requirement for diuretic therapy in hospital, Hospital length of stay (days)	Lowest haemoglobin level measured in hospital, Creatinine measures, Greatest change in creatinine level from baseline to hospital discharge, Daily creatinine levels (if measured) for first 72 hours after surgery, Fluid balance-adjusted serum creatinine level ²² , Highest and lowest base excess (if measured) for first 72 hours after surgery, Daily mean arterial pressure, heart rate and respiratory rate recorded to Day 3, Incidence of arrhythmias (eg, atrial fibrillation) to hospital discharge, Requirement for renal replacement therapy up to 6 month, Return to theatre due to bleeding

Pickkers, 2018	Recombinant Alkaline Phosphatase (recAP)	Placebo	1) Informed consent, 2) Aged 18-85 inclusive, 3) Admitted to ICU or intermediate care unit, 4) Sepsis, 5) AKI	1) Woman of childbearing potential with a positive pregnancy test (blood or urine), pregnant or breast feeding, 2) Weighs more than 115 kg (253 lb), 3) Has life-support limitations (eg, do not intubate, do not dialyse, do not resuscitate), 4) Is known to be HIV-positive, 5) Has urosepsis, 6) Is already on renal replacement therapy (RRT) or a decision has been made to initiate RRT within 24, 7) Hours after planned start of study drug administration, 8) Is receiving immunosuppressant treatment or is on chronic high doses (high-dose therapy exceeding 2 weeks of treatment) of steroids equivalent to prednisone/prednisolone 0.5 mg/kg/day, including solid organ transplant patients. Patients with septic shock treated with hydrocortisone (eg, 3x100 mg) can be included, 9) Is expected to have rapidly fatal outcome (within 24 hours), 10) Has known, confirmed fungal sepsis, 11) Has advanced chronic liver disease, confirmed by a Child-Pugh score of 10–15 (Class C), 12) Has acute pancreatitis with no established source of infection, 13) Has participated in another investigational study within 30 days prior to enrolment into the study, 14) Is not expected to survive for 28 days due to medical conditions other than SA-AKI, including cancer (previous haematological malignancies that are not actively treated allowable), end-stage cardiac disease, cardiac arrest requiring	The Effect of recAP on renal function in patients with SA-AKI, To determine effective therapeutic dose(s) of recAP	RRT incidence during the period Day 1 (after first treatment) 1597 to Day 28, inclusive; ? Renal endpoints include the following: 1604 ? Volume of urine (daily from Day 1 to Day 7, inclusive, and on subsequent visit days if 1605 reliable urine collection is possible) 1606 ? Serum creatinine and BUN (daily from Day 1 to Day 7, inclusive, and on subsequent visit 1607 days if reliable urine collection is possible) 1608 ? BUN clearance (daily from Day 1 to Day 7, inclusive, and on subsequent visit days if 1609 reliable urine collection is possible) 1610 ? Peak value of serum creatinine and BUN (during the period Day 1 to Day 7, inclusive) 1611 ? RRT-free days (during the period Day 1 to Day 28 excluding patients who died or 1612 withdrew from the study prior to the end of this period); ? Total number of days on RRT (during the period Day 1 to Day 28, inclusive). A day on 1624 RRT is defined as a day on which a patient did receive any form of RRT for any
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	<p>cardiopulmonary resuscitation or with pulseless electrical activity or asystole within the past 30 days, end-stage lung disease and end-stage liver disease, 15) Has known prior history of CKD with a documented eGFR <60 ml/min by a commonly used formula such as MDRD or CKD-EPI, known GFR <60 ml/min or a known history of persistent creatinine level $\geq 150 \mu\text{mol/l}$ (1.70 mg/dl) prior to entry for reasons other than the current sepsis condition, 16) Has diagnosis of malaria or other parasite infections, 17) Has burns on >20% of body surface, 18) Has had AKI diagnosis according to the AKI inclusion criteria for a period longer than 24 hours prior to study drug administration, 18) Is anticipated to be treated with non-continuous RRT from day 1 to day 7, 19) During day 1 to day 7, continuous RRT is anticipated to be started or stopped not according to per protocol criteria, 20) The AKI is most likely attributable to other causes than sepsis, such as nephrotoxic drugs (NSAIDs, contrast, aminoglycosides) and renal perfusion-related (acute abdominal aortic aneurysm, dissection, renal artery stenosis), 21) Improvement in serum creatinine of at least $26.2 \mu\text{mol/l}$ (0.30 mg/dl) prior to administration of the study drug, 22) Patients who use nephrotoxic medication and who fulfil the SA-AKI inclusion criteria at screening are not eligible if the use of this nephrotoxic medication is planned to continue (eg, NSAIDs,</p>	<p>period of 1625 time on that day. 1626 ? Reasons for initiation of RRT (during the period Day 1 to Day 28, inclusive) 1627 ? Kidney function at Day 28 as assessed by measured creatinine clearance if available, 1628 1629 1630 otherwise as assessed by eGFR (estimated by the CKD-EPI formula based on serum creatinine). Patients who die prior to Day 28 will be excluded from this endpoint, with any other missing assessments (including early withdrawals) imputed using LOCF. 1631 ? Kidney function at Day 60 and Day 90 as assessed by eGFR (estimated by the CKD-EPI 1632 1633 1634 formula based on serum creatinine). Patients who die prior to Day 60 or Day 90, respectively, will be excluded from this endpoint, with any other missing assessments (including early withdrawals) imputed using LOCF. 1635 ? Sustained loss of kidney function at Day 60 and Day 90, defined by eGFR < 60 mL/min 1636 1637 1638 1639 (with eGFR estimated by</p>
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ACE inhibitors, gentamycin, tobramycin) when alternative, medically appropriate non-nephrotoxic medication is available, 23) Has a history of known intravenous drug abuse, 24) Is an employee or family member of the investigator or study site personnel, 25) Has active hematological malignancy

the CKD-EPI formula based on serum creatinine). Patients who die prior to Day 60 or Day 90, respectively, will be excluded from this endpoint, with any other missing assessments (including early withdrawals) at Day 60 or Day 90 imputed using LOCF; ? Incidence of dialysis dependency at Day 60 and Day 90. Patients who die or withdraw
1641
from the study prior to Day 60 or Day 90, respectively, without recording incidence of
1642
dialysis dependency will be counted as not having required dialysis dependency.
Page; ? Liver enzymes (AST, ALT, GGT, LDH, bilirubin but excluding AP). 1646 ? Lung function as assessed by arterial PaO₂, FiO₂, P/F ratio, PEEP, and tidal volume in
1647
mechanically ventilated patients.
1648 ? Ventilator-free days (from Day 1 to Day 28, inclusive), i.e., 28 days minus the number of
1649
days a patient is on ventilator during this period. Should a patient die or withdraw prior to
1650 1651

Day 28, the days remaining in this period will be counted as per the status of the patient at time of death or withdrawal.

1652 ? Time from start of first administration of study drug to being off-ventilator (from Day 1

1653 1654 to Day 28, inclusive) for those patients who are on ventilator at the start of this period. Patients who remain on ventilator will be censored at the earliest of Day 28 or withdrawal

1655 from the study for any reason.

1656 ? Shock-free days (during the period Day 1 to Day 28, inclusive), i.e., 28 days minus the

1657 1658 number of days a patient is on inotropic or vasopressor therapy during this period. Should a patient die or withdraw prior to Day 28, the days remaining in this period will be

1659 1660 1661 1662 counted as per the status of the patient at time of death or withdrawal. A patient is considered to be shock free if he or she is not on vasopressors or inotropic agents (including but not limited to noradrenaline, adrenaline, dobutamine, dopamine, vasopressin, and enoximone); ? Time from

start of first administration of treatment to being shock free (from Day 1 to 1664 1665 1666 Day 28, inclusive) for those patients who are not shock free at the start of this period. Patients who do not become shock free will be censored at the earliest of Day 28 or withdrawal from the study for any reason. 1667 ? SOFA scores during ICU or intermediate care unit stay. 1668 ? Number of dysfunctional organs as assessed by SOFA scores. 1669 ? Deaths during the 90-day study period (by recording date). Page; 7.3.3 Biomarkers Recombinant alkaline phosphatase Protocol Version 3.0 1671 Biomarker endpoints include the following: 1672 ? Kidney function markers (e.g., urine and serum creatinine, BUN/urea clearance, sodium, 1673 proteinuria, fractional excretion of sodium, urea, and urine output). 1674 ? Tubular injury biomarkers (e.g., KIM-1, IL 18, GST-alpha). 1675 ? Biomarkers for systemic inflammation (e.g., IL-6, CRP, LBP). 1676 ? Pharmacokinetics of recAP in all 3 active treatment groups in the first 120 patients from 1677

Part 1 only
1678 ? In addition to recAP
PK concentration
measurements, baseline
(pre-dose) AP will be
1679
measured by activity
(central laboratory)
1680 7.3.4 Other Endpoints
1681 Additional endpoints
include the following: 1682
? Composite endpoints –
patients that meet, or do
not meet, at least one of
the following
1683
criteria:
1684 1685
1686 1687
1688 1689
a. Received RRT or died
(prior to Day 28 [inclusive])
b. eGFR < 60 mL/min (at
Day 60, estimated by a
commonly used formula
such as MDRD or CKD-EPI),
or requiring chronic RRT, or
died (prior to Day 60)
c.; ? Serology as assessed
by IgG, IgE, and total
immunoglobulin 1691 ?
Safety parameters including
(S)AEs, laboratory
assessments (clinical
chemistry,
1692 1693
hematology, and urinalysis
parameters not considered
in the efficacy analysis),
vital
signs, and ECG data
1694 ? Quality of life,
assessed by the EQ-5D
questionnaire at baseline,
ICU or intermediate

1695
care unit discharge, and
Day 90
1696 ? Time from start of
first administration of
treatment to discharge
from ICU or intermediate
1697
care unit (during the period
Day 1 to Day 28, inclusive,
for patients in ICU or
P; intermediate care unit at
the start of this period)
where discharge is defined
as the time when the
decision was made to
transfer the patient (as
opposed to the time of
actual transfer)
1701 ? Total time in ICU or
intermediate care unit from
the start of first
administration of study
1702 1703
drug (during the period Day
1 to Day 90, inclusive) using
the times when the
decision is made to admit
or discharge the patient as
appropriate
1704 ? Time from start of
first administration of
treatment to discharge
from hospital (during the
1705
period Day 1 to Day 90,
inclusive) where discharge
is defined as the time when
the
1706
decision was made to
transfer the patient (as
opposed to the time of
actual transfer)
1707 ? Total time in

hospital from the start of
first administration of study
drug (during the
1708 1709
period Day 1 to Day 90,
inclusive) using the times
when the decision is made
to admit or discharge the
patient as appropriate
1710

Ridley, 2018	Supplemental parenteral nutrition	Usual care	<p>1) Admitted to intensive care between 48 hours and 72 hours previously, 2) Mechanically ventilated at the time of enrolment and expected to remain ventilated until the day after tomorrow, 3) At least 16 years of age, 4) Have central venous access suitable for PN solution administration, 5) Have one or more organ system failure related to their acute illness defined as: a) PaO₂/FiO₂ ≤ 300 mmHg, b) Currently on one or more continuous vasopressor infusions which were started at least 4 hours ago at a minimum dose of: Dopamine ≥ 5 mcg/kg/min, Noradrenaline ≥ 0.1 mcg/kg/min, Adrenaline ≥ 0.1 mcg/kg/min, Any dose of vasopressin, Milrinone > 0.25 mcg/kg/min), 6) Renal dysfunction defined as In</p>	<p>1) Both EN and PN cannot be delivered at enrolment (that is, either an enteral tube or a central venous catheter cannot be placed or clinicians feel that EN or PN cannot be safely administered due to any other reason), 2) Currently receiving PN, 3) Standard PN solutions cannot be delivered at enrolment (that is, clinicians believe that a patient definitely needs a specific parenteral nutrition formulation (for example, glutamine supplementation or specific lipid formulation), 4) Death is imminent or deemed highly likely in the next 96 hours, 5) There is a current treatment limitation in place or the patient is unlikely to survive to 6 months due to underlying illness 6) More than 80 % of energy requirements have been satisfactorily delivered via the enteral route in the last 24 hours, 7) Are known to be pregnant, 8) The treating clinician does not believe the study to be in the best interest of the patient.</p>	Mean energy delivered through the first 7 days	<p>1) Total protein delivered in the first 7 days of the study period; 2) Total energy and protein delivered in the ICU stay (up to 28 days); 3) Number of new antibiotics commenced while in ICU to day 28; (4) SOFA scores; (5) duration of MV to day 28; (6) duration of ICU and hospital stay; (7) mortality to 180 days post randomization; (8) assessment of physical function using the ICU mobility scale (or 6-minute walk test where possible) at hospital discharge (D/C), hand grip strength (HGS) at ICU and hospital D/C and (9) quality of life with the EuroQuol-5 Dimension 3 Level (EQ-5D-3L) at hospital D/C, 90 and 180 days post randomization</p>
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patients without known renal disease: a) Serum creatinine > 171 mmol/L OR b) Currently receiving renal replacement therapy, In patients with known renal disease: a) An absolute increase of > 50 % in serum creatinine from baseline OR b) Currently receiving renal replacement therapy, 7) Currently has an intracranial pressure monitor or ventricular drain in situ, 8) Currently receiving extracorporeal membrane oxygenation, 9) Currently has a ventricular assist device.

Roquilly, 2021	Continuous hypertonic saline solution	Standard care	1) Aged 18 to 80 years, 2) Admitted to the participating ICUs for moderate to severe traumatic brain injury (TBI)	1) Pregnancy; 2) Dependence on daily activity before trauma, 3) Association with a cervical spinal cord injury that would have affected the Extended Glasgow Outcome Scale (GOS-E), 4) Imminent death or fixed dilated pupils with a score of 3 on the Glasgow Coma Scale (considered moribund), 5) Fluid retention.	Glasgow Outcome Scale Extended (GOS-E) at 6 months	1) Mortality at 6 months after the trauma, 2) GOS-E at 3 months, 3) Duration of post-traumatic amnesia, 4) Exit from postcritical amnesia will be defined as obtaining a score > 75/100 on the G.O.A.T. (described in appendix) at 3 and 6 months, 5) Measurement of autonomy in activities of daily living, 6) Katz ADL at 3 and 6 months, 7) Quality of life estimated by the SF-36 score at 3 months and 6 months, Place of residence at 3 months and 6 months, Evolution of natremia, chloremia, kalaemia, pH, and plasma osmolarity, 8) Evolution of intracranial pressure (if measured), 9) Intensity of the management of intracranial hypertension, 10) Frequency of renal failure, 11) Severe thromboembolic accident (pulmonary embolism) without compulsory paraclinical systematic screening, 12) Incidence of centro-pontine myelinolysis without an imposed paraclinical approach.
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Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Shehabi, 2019	Dexmedetomidine as primary sedative agent	Usual care	1) Mechanical ventilation through an endotracheal tube, 2) Expected to continue to receive ventilatory support beyond the next full calendar day, 3) Receiving sedatives for safety and comfort.	1) Age less than 18 years 2. Has been intubated (excluding time spent intubated within an operating theatre or transport) for greater than 12 hours in an intensive care unit, 2) Proven or suspected acute primary brain lesion such as traumatic brain injury, intracranial haemorrhage, stroke, or hypoxic brain injury, 3) Proven or suspected spinal cord injury or other pathology that may result in permanent or prolonged weakness, 4) Admission as a consequence of a suspected or proven drug overdose or burns, 5) Administration of ongoing neuromuscular blockade, 6) A mean arterial blood (MAP) pressure that is less than 50 mmHg, 7) Heart rate less than 55 beats per minute unless the patient is being treated with a beta- blocker or a high grade atrio-ventricular block in the absence of a functioning pacemaker, 8) Acute fulminant hepatic failure, 9) Patient requires full time residential nursing care, 10) Death is deemed to be imminent or inevitable during this admission.	All causes mortality at day 90 after randomisation	1) Ventilation free days, 2) Proportion of RASS measurements in target range, 3) Incidence and duration of delirium measured by delirium free days, 4) Length of ICU stay, 5) Proportion of patients who receive a tracheostomy Proportion of patients who require: re-intubation, physical restraints, or unplanned extubation, 6) Cumulative dose of midazolam, propofol, dexmedetomidine, fentanyl, and morphine, 7) Duration of treatment with midazolam, propofol, dexmedetomidine, fentanyl, and morphine, 8) Mortality at hospital discharge, 9) Length of hospital stay, 10) Readmission to ICU, 11) EQ-5D questionnaire, 12) Cognitive function, 13) Mortality at ICU discharge, 14) Full time institutional dependency at 180 days, 15) Discharge destination	-

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Wade, 2019	Nurse-Led preventive psychological intervention	Usual care	1) Adult (≥ 18 years of age), 2) At least 48 hours in the ICU, 3) Receipt of level 3 (intensive) care, between a score of +1 and -1 on the Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale, 3) Glasgow Coma Scale score of 15, 4) English speaking and 5) able to communicate orally	1) Pre-existing chronic cognitive impairment, 2) Pre-existing psychotic illness, 3) Pre-existing chronic PTSD, 4) Receiving end-of-life-care, 5) Previously recruited into POPPI	PTSD symptom severity measured using the PTSD Symptom Scale (Self-report version) (PSS-SR) 6 month	Days alive and free from sedation to day 30, Duration of critical care unit stay, PSS-SR greater than 18 points at six months, Depression at six months, measured using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), Anxiety at six months, measured using the HADS, Health-related quality of life (HRQoL) at six months, Measured by the EuroQol (EQ-5D-5L) questionnaire	-

<p>Laterre, 2021</p>	<p>Adrecizumab 2 or 4mg/kg</p>	<p>Placebo</p>	<p>1) Written informed consent by patient or legal representative, 2) Male and female patient, 3) Age \geq 18 years, 4) Body weight 50 kg - 120 kg, 5) Bio-ADM concentration > 70 pg/ml, 6) Patient with early septic shock (start of vasopressor therapy < 12 hours), 7) Women of childbearing potential must have a negative serum or urine pregnancy test before randomization, 8) Highly effective method of contraception must be maintained for 6 months after study start by women of childbearing potential and sexually active men, 9) No care limitation</p>	<p>1) Moribund, 2) Pre-existing unstable condition, 3) Congestive heart failure - New York Heart Association (NYHA) Class IV, 4) Patients that required cardiopulmonary resuscitation in the last 4 weeks prior to evaluation for enrollment, 5) Severe Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) with chronic oxygen need at home (GOLD IV), 6) Any organ or bone marrow transplant within the past 24 weeks, 7) Uncontrolled serious hemorrhage (\geq 2 units of blood / platelets in the previous 24 hrs.), 8) Patients may be considered for enrollment if bleeding has stopped and patient is otherwise qualified, 9) Uncontrolled hematological / oncological malignancies, 10) Absolute neutropenia < 500 per μL, 11) Severe chronic liver disease (Child-Pugh C), 12) Systemic fungal infection or active tuberculosis, 13) Neuromuscular disorders that impact breathing / spontaneous ventilation, 14) Burns > 30% of body surface, 15) Plasmapheresis, 16) Breastfeeding women, 17) Participation in a clinical trial involving another investigational drug within 4 weeks prior to inclusion, 18) Unwilling or unable to be fully evaluated for all follow-up visits</p>	<p>Mortality day 90, Interruption of infusion day 90, Frequency of TEAEs day 90, Severity and frequency of TEAEs - mild/moderate/severe severity day 90,</p>	<p>Efficacy to be determined by sepsis support index (SSI) day 14, SSI day 28, Penalized sepsis support index (pSSI) day 14 follow-up, Persistent organ dysfunction or death at day 14 and 28 follow-up, Mortality day 28, SSI and pSSI excluding the renal component day 14 and 28, SSI weighted for mortality day 14, Individual SSI components day 14 and 28, SOFA score day 28, Change in creatinine day 1, 3, and 7, Duration of stay at icu/hospital day 90, Changes of MAP during stay at ICU day 28, Changes of Creatinine during stay at ICU day 28, Changes of PaO₂/FiO₂ during -, lactate -, fluid balance -, MR-proADM -, PCT -, IL-6 -, DPP3 - stay at ICU day 28, Vasopressor use day 28, Quality of life (EQ-5D) day 28 and 90, Vital signs day 7</p>	<p>Endpoints for Pharmacokinetics: In sub-study to determine key PK parameters, including: • peak plasma concentrations (C_{max}) • time to C_{max} (t_{max}) • systemic exposure (AUC) • volume of distribution (V) • systemic clearance (CL) • elimination half-life (t_{1/2})</p>
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Granholm, 2022 (Munch)	Dexamethasone 12mg	Dexamethasone 6mg	1) Aged 18 years or above 2) Confirmed SARS-CoV-2 requiring hospitalisation 3) Use of one of the following: a) Invasive mechanical ventilation, b) Non-invasive ventilation or continuous use of continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) for hypoxia, c) Oxygen supplementation with an oxygen flow of at least 10 L/min independent of delivery system	1) Use of systemic corticosteroids for other indications than COVID-19 in doses higher than 6 mg dexamethasone equivalents, 2) Use of systemic corticosteroids for COVID-19 for 5 consecutive days or more, 6) Invasive fungal infection, 7) Active tuberculosis Fertile woman (<60 years of age) with positive urine human gonadotropin (hCG) or plasma-hCG, 8) Known hypersensitivity to dexamethasone, 9) Previously randomised in the COVID STEROID 2 trial, 10) Informed consent not obtainable	Days alive without life support to day 28	Number of participants with one or more serious adverse re-actions (SARs) to dexamethasone from randomisation to day 28, All- cause mortality at day 28, All- cause mortality at day 90, Days alive without life support at day 90, Days alive and out of hospital at day 90, All- cause mortality at day 180, HRQoL at day 180 using EQ-5D- 5L and EQ-VAS	-
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<p>Silversides, 2022</p>	<p>Conservative fluid administration and active deresuscitation</p>	<p>Usual care</p>	<p>1) Receiving invasive mechanical ventilation, 2) Between 24 and 48 hours of ICU admission, 3) Admission at the time of randomisation, 4) The treating intensive care doctor expects treatment in an ICU to be required beyond the next calendar day</p>	<p>1) Age < 16 years 2) Weight < 40 kg, 3) Known pregnancy, 4) Expectation of death within 72 hours, 5) Refusal of consent, 6) Inability to measure fluid balance, 7) Inability of the personal consultee to understand written or verbal information, 8) Active treatment for diabetic ketoacidosis, hyperosmolar hyperglycaemic state, non-traumatic subarachnoid haemorrhage, acute cardiac failure, cardiogenic shock, endstage renal failure, or active diabetes insipidus.</p>	<p>Day 3 fluid balance</p>	<p>Cumulative fluid balance day 3, 5 and at ICU discharge, Incidence of significant protocol violations up to day 5, Rates of recruitment, Change in overall and organ SOFA scores from baseline to beginning of day 3 and end of day 5, Mortality (28-day and 180 day), Duration of mechanical ventilation in survivors and non-survivors, from initiation of mechanical ventilatory support until unassisted breathing, censored at 28 days) Length of ICU stay (number of days or part thereof from admission to an ICU or being under the care of a critical care team or consultant until ICU discharge, censored at 28 days), Cardiovascular stability (highest and mean dose of vasopressors; highest and mean heart rate and, serum lactate), Volume of fluid bolus administration until the beginning of study day 3 and to end of day 5, Incidence of new AKI defined as Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) Stage 3, before and after correction for fluid balance, up to end of day 5, Cognitive function score at 180 days, HRQoL at 180 days, Incidence of anxiety and depression, absolute number (defined as</p>	<p>1. Endothelial function and injury (plasma levels of Angiotensin II and Ang-1/2, Syndecan-1, total protein, plasma albumin, and protein permeability (albumin:α2-macroglobulin ratio), absolute levels and change from baseline. 2. Inflammatory mediators (plasma levels of CRP, TNFα, IL6, IL8 and other biomarkers), absolute levels and change from baseline. 3. Cardiac function (echocardiographic measures including left ventricular ejection fraction, E/E' ratio), change from baseline. 4. Renal function and injury (plasma and urine levels of Cystatin C and NGAL), absolute levels and change from baseline. 5. Cerebral oximetry (NIRS measurement of regional cerebral oxygen saturation), mean and minimum rScO2 level, proportion of time spent with rScO2 below thresholds of 50%, 65%, and 75%. 6. Tissue oxygenation (NIRS measurement of muscle tissue oxygen saturation), mean and minimum rScO2 level</p>
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Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) score > 11), Incidence of post-traumatic stress disorder (defined as Impact of Events Scores-Revised (IES-R) score > 33

Crescioli, 2022 (Schjørring)	Lower oxygenation target (8 kPa)	Higher oxygenation target (12 kPa)	<p>1) Acute admission to the ICU, 2) Age \geq 18 years, 3) Supplemental oxygen therapy fulfilling one of the following criteria:</p> <p>a) Flow of oxygen \geq 10 litres/minute in an open system irrespective of any flow of atmospheric air, including high-flow systems, b) Fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂) \geq 0.50 in a closed system (invasive or non-invasive (mask or helmet) ventilation, or continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) systems (mask or helmet)), 4) Expected duration of supplemental oxygen \geq 24 hours in the ICU, 5) Arterial line in place for monitoring partial pressure of arterial oxygen (PaO₂)</p>	<p>1) Cannot be randomised within 12 hours of ICU admission, 2) Chronic mechanical ventilation (invasive mechanical ventilation, continuous non-invasive ventilation, or continuous mask-CPAP) for any reason except nocturnally for sleep apnoea and/or obesity, hypoventilation syndrome, 3) Use of home supplementary oxygen, 4) Previous bleomycin treatment, 5) Solid organ transplant planned or performed during current hospitalisation, 6) Withdrawal from active therapy or brain death deemed imminent, 7) Pregnancy (positive urine or plasma human chorionic gonadotropin), 8) Carbon monoxide poisoning, 9) Cyanide poisoning, 10) Methaemoglobinaemia, 11) Paraquat poisoning Any condition expected to involve the use of hyperbaric oxygen (HBO), 12) Sickle cell disease, 13) Consent not obtainable according to national regulations, 14) Previously randomised into the HOT-ICU trial</p>	90-day all cause mortality	Days alive without organ support, Days alive out of hospital, Number of patients with one or more serious adverse events, 1-year mortality, HRQoL 1-year, Cognitive function 1-year, Health economic analysis 90 days	-
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<p>Bellingan, 2022</p>	<p>intravenous multipotent adult progenitor cells</p>	<p>Placebo</p>	<p>1) Male or female age 18-90, 2) Informed consent (subject or legally authorized representative), 3) ARDS (a) PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio of <200 mmHg (27 kPa) on positive end-expiratory airway pressure (PEEP) of ≥5 cm H₂O; b) Bilateral opacities on a chest radiograph or CT scan; c) Respiratory failure not fully explained by cardiac failure or fluid overload, 4) Able to receive investigational medicinal product within 96 hours, 5) Female subjects who are either: a) Not pregnant, not breastfeeding, and are not planning on becoming pregnant for 3 months from IMP administration; b) Not of childbearing potential, defined as one who has been postmenopausal for at least 1 year, or has been surgically sterilized, or has had a total hysterectomy at least</p>	<p>1) Moribund subject not expected to survive up to 48 hours; 2) Concurrent illness that shortens life expectancy to less than 6 months; 3) Home mechanical ventilation for chronic respiratory failure (Non-invasive ventilation (NIV) or via tracheostomy) except for Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (CPAP)/Bilevel positive airway pressure (BiPAP) used solely for sleep-disordered breathing; 4) Diffuse alveolar hemorrhage with or without vasculitis; 5) Severe ILD needing supplemental oxygen; 6) Severe COPD with recent FEV₁/FVC ratio <0.3 (if available) or the use of home oxygen; 7) History of chronic pulmonary hypertension (WHO Class III or IV); 8. History of lung transplantation; 9) ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) within the last 6 months; 10) Mean arterial pressure (MAP) <60 mmHg while on 2 or more vasopressors with or without cardiovascular inotropic support; 11) Severe chronic liver disease (Childs-Pugh Score >10); 12) Known anaphylaxis or religious objection to bovine or porcine products; 13) Previous autologous, allogeneic bone marrow or peripheral stem cell transplant to treat conditions other than hematologic malignancies; 14) Any history of malignancy within the last 2 years, with the exception of adequately treated basal or squamous cell carcinoma of the skin or hematologic malignancy treated with bone</p>	<p>1. Safety and tolerability within 4 hours of MultiStem therapy administration; 2. Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reactions (SUSARs) within 24 hours of MultiStem therapy administration</p>	<p>1) Frequency of adverse events 2) Changes in vital signs 3) Changes in blood safety laboratories 4) Ventilator-free days 5) ICU-free days 6) Total length of hospital stay 7) All-cause mortality 8) Changes in levels of oxygenation 9) Changes in positive end-expiratory airway pressure 10) Changes in respiratory physiologic measures including lung compliance and airway resistance (peak and plateau pressures) 11) All-cause mortality</p>	<p>Changes in circulating biomarkers of inflammation and lung injury between baseline and Days 1, 2, 3 and 7; and health-related quality of life (EQ-5D-3L) at Days 28, 90 and 365</p>
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	<p>3 months prior to the start of this trial; c) If of childbearing potential, must agree to use an effective method of contraception for 3 months from IMP administration, 6) Male subjects with female partners of childbearing potential must agree to use adequate contraceptive methods (see Section Error! Reference source not found.) for 3 months from IMP administration.</p>	<p>marrow or peripheral stem cell transplantation; 15) History of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection with the most recent CD4 T lymphocyte count, measured within the prior 6 months, being less than 200 cells/mm³ (testing of CD4 T lymphocyte count should be performed at screening for those subjects whose series of prior counts have been considered borderline for progressive disease, those for whom a count has not been performed within the prior 6 months, or on the recommendation of the Medical Monitor after consultation with the Investigator); 16) Clinical findings that, in the opinion of the Investigator, raise significant doubt that ARDS is the primary etiology of the subject's hypoxemia and chest radiography criteria; 17) Other serious medical or psychiatric illness that, in the Investigator's opinion, would not permit the subject to be managed according to the protocol; 18) Prior participation in any other clinical trial involving administration of a novel (unapproved) investigational pharmacological agent(s) within 30 days prior to enrollment. Concurrent enrollment in observational and device trials and trials involving administration of approved pharmacological agent(s) will be considered on a case by case basis and in consultation with the Medical Monitor; and 19. Significant sustained improvement in oxygenation</p>
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following initial diagnosis of ARDS (meeting inclusion #3), suggesting resolving ARDS (P/F ratio > 300 mmHg (40 kPa)).
P/F ratio should be confirmed ≤ 300 mmHg (40 kPa) within the 6 hours prior to randomization.

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Campos, 2022	Early mobilisation and neuro-muscular electrical stimulation	Early mobilisation	1) Age above 18 years, 2) Less than 48 hours of ICU admission, 3) An expected stay on mechanical ventilation for longer than 48 hours.	1) Inability to walk without assistance before ICU admission, 2) Previous neuromuscular diseases, 3) Spinal cord injury, 4) Epilepsy as a diagnosis that led to hospitalization or uncontrolled seizures, 5) Risk of death in the next 24 hours, 6) Suspected or confirmed brain death, 7) Abnormal musculoskeletal and skin conditions or situations that could interfere with electrical stimulation, (for example, hip or femur fracture, use of an external fixator, wound in the lower limbs, skin disease, burn in the anterior thigh or presence of a pacemaker)	Functional status at ICU discharge	Muscle strength, functional status through other scales, Global muscle strenght and physical function test at first day awake and ICU and hospital dishcharge, Barthel index at ICU admission	HRQoL at ICU and hospital discharge - står mere som bare en variabel end outcome

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Bisset, 2022	Inspiratory Muscle Training	Control group	1) Invasively mechanically ventilated (via endotracheal tube or tracheostomy) for at least 7 days, 2) Aged 16 years, 3) Sufficiently alert to provide informed consent and participate actively in training (Riker Sedation Agitation Scale score ≥ 19), 4) haemodynamically stable and requiring minimal ventilatory support (ie, PEEP ≤ 10).	1) Pregnancy, 2) Significant pain or distress affecting breathing, 3) Medical instability (e.g., new cardiac arrhythmia, acutely septic) where the treating team considered that interference with ventilatory support could compromise the patient's recovery, 4) Anticipated death within weeks	Fatigue resistance index (24h and 7 days postweaning)	Maximum inspiratory pressure Quality of life/functional assessments ; (Short Form-36, EQ-5D, Acute Care Index of Function) Rate of perceived exertion at rest and during training; Duration of mechanical ventilation (days) and duration of weaning (from commencement of pressure-support only to 24 h ventilator-free); ICU length of stay (days) U NA Post-ICU discharge length of hospital stay UU (days) and hospital discharge destination (including in-hospital mortality) ICU readmission rates and reintubation UU rates (%)(defined as reintubation required within 48 h of extubation) Urinary cortisol, creatinine and urea levels	

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	Trial intervention	Trial Comparator	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Primary outcome	Secondary outcome	Tertiary outcome
Lamontagne, 2022	Infusion Vitamin C (at a dose of 50 mg per kilogram of body weight)	Placebo	1) Patients ≥ 18 years old; 2) Admitted to the ICU with proven or suspected infection as the main diagnosis; 3) Currently treated with a continuous intravenous infusion of vasopressors (norepinephrine, epinephrine, vasopressin, dopamine, phenylephrine).	1) > 24 hours of intensive care unit (ICU) admission; 2) Known Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency; 3) Expected death or withdrawal of life-sustaining treatments within 48 hours; 4) Previously enrolled in this study; 5) Previously enrolled in a trial with which co-enrolment is not allowed (co-enrolment to be determined case by case).	Death or persistent organ dysfunction (defined as continued dependency on mechanical ventilation, renal replacement therapy, or vasopressors) at 28 days	Persistent organ dysfunction-free days in ICU, up to day 28; Mortality and health-related quality of life at 6 months; Organ function (including renal function) assessed by the SOFA score, Global tissue dysoxia, Inflammation assessed by interleukin-1 beta (IL-1β), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-α), Creactiveprotein (CRP), Infection assessed by procalcitonin (PCT), and endothelial injury	

<p>Boyle, 2022 (McNamee)</p>	<p>Lower tidal volume ventilation, facilitated by vv-ECCO2R</p>	<p>Ventilation alone</p>	<p>1) Invasive mechanical ventilation using PEEP \geq 5cmH2O, 2) Acute and potentially reversible cause of acute respiratory failure as determined by the treating physician, 3) Within 48 hours of the onset of hypoxaemia as defined by PaO2/FiO2 \leq 20kPa</p>	<p>1) Age <16 years old, 2) Intubated and mechanically ventilated via an endotracheal or tracheostomy tube \geq 7 Days (168 hours) up to the time of randomisation, 3) Ability to maintain Vt to \leq 3ml/kg PBW while maintaining pH \geq 7.2 as determined by the treating physician, 4) Receiving, or decision to commence, ECMO in the next 24 hours, 5) Mechanical ventilation using High Frequency Oscillatory Ventilation (HFOV) or Airway Pressure Release Ventilation (APRV), 6) Untreated pulmonary embolism, pleural effusion or pneumothorax as the primary cause of acute respiratory failure, 7) Acute respiratory failure fully explained by left ventricular failure or fluid overload (May be determined by clinical assessment or echocardiography/cardiac output monitoring), 8) Left ventricular failure requiring mechanical support, 9) Contra-indication to limited systemic anticoagulation with heparin, 10) Unable to obtain vascular access to a central vein (internal jugular or femoral vein), 11) Inferior vena cava filter (if using femoral vein catheter), 12) Consent declined, 13) Treatment withdrawal imminent within 24 hours, 14) Patients not expected to survive 90 days on basis of pre-morbid health status, 15) Do Not Attempt Resuscitation (DNAR) order (excluding advance directives) in place, 16) Severe chronic respiratory disease requiring domiciliary ventilation (except for sleep disordered</p>	<p>1) All cause mortality day 90</p>	<p>1) Tidal volume day 2 and 3, 2) Ventilator free days - day 28, 3) Duration of ventilation day 28, 4) Need for Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation day 7, 5) Mortality rate day 28, 6m and 1y, 6) HRQoL at 6 m and 1y, 7) Adverse event rate day 28, 8) Health and social care service costs 6m and 1y, 9) St George Respiratory questionnaire 1y, 10) Need for home oxygen 6m and 1y, 11) Post traumatic stress syndrome questionnaire 1y, 12) Montreal cognitive assessment or AD8 Dementia screening interview 1y</p>	<p>Right ventricular function baseline and day 2+3</p>
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breathing), 17) Severe chronic liver disease (Child Pugh >11) Platelet count < 40,000 mm³ (Prior to catheter insertion), 18) Previously enrolled in the REST trial, 19) Prisoners

Table S3. Trial Characteristics

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	No. of patients per arm (the study population from the original trial)	Female (%)	Age (mean or median)	Age	Age variation (IQR, Range or SD)	Age variation	SAPS (mean or median)	SAPS	SAPS variation (IQR, range or SD)	SAPS variation	APACHE score (mean or median)	APACHE score	APACHE score variation (IQR, range or SD)	APACHE score variation	SOFA score (mean or median)	SOFA score	SOFA score variation (IQR, range or SD)	SOFA score variation	Patients with invasive mechanical ventilation (%)	Patients with dialysis (%)	Patients with vasopressor (%)	Patient with sepsis/severe sepsis (as defined by author) (%)	Patients with septic shock (%)
Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
Hodgson, 2016	29	41	Mean	64	SD	12	NA	NA	Mean	19.8	SD	9.8	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	65	NA				
	21	38	Mean	53	SD	15	NA	NA	Mean	15.9	SD	6.9	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	66	NA				
Sosnowski, 2018	15	40	Mean	54.9	SD	15.9	NA	NA	Mean	14.9	SD	5.9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	27	NA				
	15	73	Mean	60.6	SD	11.0	NA	NA	Mean	13.7	SD	5.0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	47	NA				
Harvey, 2016	1191	42	Mean	63.3	SD	15,1	NA	NA	Mean	19.6	SD	6.9	Mean	9.5	SD	3.4	82	NA	NA	82	NA		
	1197	39	Mean	62.9	SD	15.4	NA	NA	Mean	19.6	SD	7.0	Mean	9.6	SD	3.3	83	NA	NA	83	NA		
Messika, 2019	36	50	Median	68	IQR	61-76	Median	35.5	IQR	27-47	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	38	45	Median	64	IQR	57-72	Median	32	IQR	24-40	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	39	41	Median	66	IQR	58.5-71	Median	35	IQR	27-41	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Lall, 2015	398	36		NA		NA	NA	NA	Mean	21.7	SD	6.0	NA	NA	100	22	NA	NA	NA	NA			
	397	40		NA		NA	NA	NA	Mean	22.0	SD	6.1	NA	NA	99	18	NA	NA	NA				
Gates, 2013	162	36	Mean	55.8	SD	17.2	NA	NA	Mean	19.5	SD	6.2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	24	NA				
	164	33	Mean	54.2	SD	17.5	NA	NA	Mean	18.9	SD	6.7	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	29	NA				
Allingstrup, 2017	100	35	Median	63	IQR	51-72	Median	48	IQR	37-54	NA	NA	Median	8	IQR	6-11	100	6	NA	47	NA		
	99	40	Median	68	IQR	52-75	Median	47	IQR	39-59	NA	NA	Median	8	IQR	5-10	100	5	NA	47	NA		

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
Doig, 2013	682	41	Mean	68.4	SD	15.1	NA	NA	Mean	20.5	SD	7.4	NA	NA	84	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	681	38	Mean	68.6	SD	14.3	NA	NA	Mean	21.5	SD	7.8	NA	NA	81	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Trouillet, 2011	109	29	Mean	64.1	SD	13.3	Mean	47.2	SD	12.4	NA	NA	Mean	11.6	SD	3.5	100	38	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	107	42	Mean	66.0	SD	12.4	Mean	45.8	SD	11.4	NA	NA	Mean	10.9	SD	3.6	100	17	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Kayambu, 2015	26	31	Median	62.5	IQR	30-83	NA	NA	Mean	28.0	SD	7.6	Mean	11.1	SD	3.2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	24	42	Median	65.5	IQR	37-85	NA	NA	Mean	27.0	SD	6.8	Mean	10.5	SD	2.5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Schaller, 2016	104	38	Median	66	IQR	48-73	NA	NA	Median	16	IQR	12-22	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	1	NA	NA	0	NA	
	96	36	Median	64	IQR	45-76	NA	NA	Median	17	IQR	11-22	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	0	NA	
Fossat, 2018	158	35	Mean	65	SD	13	Mean	47	SD	19	NA	NA	Median	9	IQR	6-12	77	10	NA	41	28	28	
	154	36	Mean	66	SD	15	Mean	46	SD	17	NA	NA	Median	8.5	IQR	6-12	79	7	NA	34	24	24	
Denehy, 2013	74	42	Mean	61.4	SD	15.9	NA	NA	Mean	19.0	SD	6	NA	NA	55	NA	NA	14	NA	NA	14	NA	
	76	32	Mean	60.1	SD	15.8	NA	NA	Mean	20.7	SD	7.7	NA	NA	55	NA	NA	9	NA	NA	9	NA	
Brummel, 2014	22	41	Median	62	IQR	48-67	NA	NA	Median	21.5	IQR	20.0-28.8	Median	8	IQR	6-10	78	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	43	35	Median	62	IQR	54-69	NA	NA	Median	25	IQR	19.5-29.5	Median	9	IQR	6-11	77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
	22	64	Median	60	IQR	51-69	NA	NA	Median	27	IQR	17.5-31.0	Median	10	IQR	8.0-11.8	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Angus, 2006 (Taylor)	192	48	Mean	50	SD	17	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	0	NA		
	193	46	Mean	50	SD	17	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	0	NA		
Schädler, 2017	150	31	Median	67	IQR	55-75	NA	NA	Median	16	IQR	12-19	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	150	29	Median	69	IQR	60-74	NA	NA	Median	16	IQR	11-19	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Taylor, 2016 (Myburgh)	3358	40	Mean	63.1	SD	17.0	NA	NA	Median	17.0	IQR	12.0-22.0	NA	NA	63	NA	45	29	NA	NA	NA		
	3384	40	Mean	62.9	SD	16.9	NA	NA	Median	17.0	IQR	12.0-23.0	NA	NA	64	NA	46	28	NA	NA	NA		
Madsen, 2017	50	40	Median	59	IQR	50-69	Median	43	IQR	34-54	NA	NA	Median	8	IQR	5-10	96	NA	NA	NA	40		
	50	36	Median	61	IQR	50-71	Median	42	IQR	33-54	NA	NA	Median	7	IQR	4-9	94	NA	NA	NA	36		
Jones, 2015	28	36	Median	64	SD	18	NA	NA	Median	18	SD	6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	21	NA		
-	23	52	Median	62	SD	14	NA	NA	Median	14	SD	10	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	43	NA		
-	20	50	Median	60	SD	12	NA	NA	Median	14	SD	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	50	NA		
-	22	36	Median	64	SD	13	NA	NA	Median	17	SD	10	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	45	NA		
Noguchi, 2017 (Matsuoka)	52	17	Mean	38.1	SD	13.5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
	57	19	Mean	40.9	SD	17.3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Jackson, 2010 (Girard)	89	46	Median	65	IQR	53-73	NA	NA	Median	28	IQR	22-34	Median	9	IQR	7-12	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	91	55	Median	68	IQR	56-76	NA	NA	Median	28	IQR	21-33	Median	9	IQR	6-12	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Rygård, 2016 (Holst)	502	46	Median	67	IQR	57-73	Median	51	IQR	42-62	NA	NA	Median	10	IQR	8-12	69	14	100	NA	100	NA	100
	496	48	Median	67	IQR	58-75	Median	52	IQR	44-64	NA	NA	Median	10	IQR	8-12	71	11	100	NA	100	NA	100
Gallagher, 2014 (Bellomo)	722	34	Mean	64.7	SD	14.5	NA	NA	Mean	102.5	SD	25.9	NA	NA	74	100	NA	50	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	743	36	Mean	64.4	SD	15.3	NA	NA	Mean	102.3	SD	25.5	NA	NA	74	100	NA	49	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Cronberg, 2015 (Nielsen)	473	17	Mean	64	SD	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	466	21	Mean	64	SD	13	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Dinglas, 2016 (Truwit)	379	51	Mean	54.2	SD	17.1	NA	NA	Mean	92.1	SD	28.4	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	100	46	46
	366	51	Mean	54.1	SD	15.6	NA	NA	Mean	94.8	SD	27.9	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	100	45	45
Azevedo, 2019	57	40	Mean	65.0	SD	18.8	NA	NA	Mean	81.1	SD	32.4	Mean	9.8	SD	14.6	100	NA	NA	21	NA	NA	NA
	63	49	Mean	67.4	SD	18.9	NA	NA	Mean	77.2	SD	30.7	Mean	6.8	SD	4.0	100	NA	NA	24	NA	NA	NA

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
Antonelli, 2005	67	39	Mean	63	SD	1	Mean	43	SD	14	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	10	NA		
	72	42	Mean	64	SD	17	Mean	44	SD	11	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	7	NA		
Marasco, 2013	23	13	Mean	57.8	SD	17.1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	23	13	Mean	59.3	SD	10.4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA		
Wittbrodt, 2013 (Perner)	398	40	Median	66	IQR	56-75	Median	50	IQR	40-60	NA	NA	Median	7	IQR	5-9	60	NA	NA	100	84		
	400	39	Median	67	IQR	56-76	Median	51	IQR	39-62	NA	NA	Median	7	IQR	5-9	61	NA	NA	100	84		
Freeman-Sanderson, 2016	15	27	Mean	53	SD	21	NA	NA	Mean	19	SD	4	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	15	60	Mean	67	SD	11	NA	NA	Mean	18	SD	5	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
Van Maastrigt, 2006	298	21	Mean	62.7	SD	9.30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	299	20	Mean	62.6	SD	9.42	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
Agus, 2017 (McAuley)	259	47	Mean	53.2	SD	16.1	NA	NA	Mean	19.4	SD	6.9	Mean	8.6	SD	3.2	100	NA	65	73	NA		
	280	39	Mean	54.4	SD	16.7	NA	NA	Mean	18.3	SD	6.2	Mean	9.0	SD	2.9	100	NA	67	78	NA		
Dubois, 2017	777	36	Mean	66	SD	14	NA	NA	Mean	21	SD	9	NA	NA	85	1	NA	17	NA	NA	NA		

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
	773	38	Mean	66	SD	15	NA	NA	NA	Mean	20	SD	9	NA	NA	86	2	NA	13	NA			
Ingels, 2006 (Van den Berghe)	765	29	Mean	63.4	SD	13.6	NA	NA	Median	9	IQR	7-13	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	783	29	Mean	62.2	SD	13.9	NA	NA	Median	9	IQR	7-13	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Walsh, 2017 (Lacroix)	1206	43	Mean	61.3	SD	16.7	NA	NA	Mean	21.9	SD	7.7	NA	NA	98	27	62	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	1206	47	Mean	61.0	SD	16.7	NA	NA	Mean	21.6	SD	7.6	NA	NA	97	29	63	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Zhu, 2018 (Doig)	239	34	Mean	63.3	SD	15.4	NA	NA	Mean	21.7	SD	7.6	NA	NA	82	NA	NA	15	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	235	37	Mean	62.7	SD	16.6	NA	NA	Mean	20.2	SD	6.8	NA	NA	83	NA	NA	11	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Kurtoglu, 2015	15	7	Mean	66.1	SD	13.9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	15	7	Mean	69.9	SD	11.0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Wright, 2017	150	46	Mean	60	SD	16	NA	NA	Mean	19	SD	7	NA	NA	99	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	158	37	Mean	64	SD	16	NA	NA	Mean	19	SD	7	NA	NA	97	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Wischmeyer, 2017	52	60	Mean	55.8	SD	19.8	NA	NA	Mean	20.5	SD	6.4	Mean	6.2	SD	3.5	100	NA	NA	29	NA	NA	
	73	47	Mean	55.1	SD	16.2	NA	NA	Mean	20.8	SD	7.2	Mean	5.9	SD	3.6	100	NA	NA	25	NA	NA	
Giraud, 2016	115	24	Mean	77.4	SD	4.8	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	108	23	Mean	77.0	SD	4.9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
Amundadottir, 2019	29	34	Median	62	IQR	50-70	NA	NA	Mean	23.5	SD	19.7-27.2	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	21	33	Median	64	IQR	58-74	NA	NA	Mean	22.0	SD	18.2-25.8	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Deane, 2020 (Chapman)	1971	38	Mean	57.2	SD	16.6	NA	NA	Mean	22.0	SD	8.3	NA	NA	100	9	63	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	1986	36	Mean	57.5	SD	16.5	NA	NA	Mean	22.1	SD	8.5	NA	NA	99.8	9	63	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
de Azevedo, 2021	87	39	Mean	67.6	SD	17.8	Median	55	IQR	44-66	NA	NA	Median	5	IQR	3-9	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	94	51	Mean	65.3	SD	19.7	Median	50	IQR	48.7-68	NA	NA	Median	6	IQR	3.7-8	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fan, 2021	58	45	Mean	50.9	SD	8.41	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	58	47	Mean	50.3	SD	8.66	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Hammond, 2020 (Venkatesh)	1971	43	Mean	62.3	SD	14.9	NA	NA	Median	24.0	IQR	19.0-29.0	NA	NA	99.8	12	100	0	100	0	100	0	100
	1986	43	Mean	62.7	SD	15.2	NA	NA	Median	23.0	IQR	18.0-29.0	NA	NA	99.9	13	100	0	100	0	100	0	100
Irving, 2019 (Cooper)	2457	47	Mean	62.5	SD	16.8	NA	NA	Mean	72.6	SD	29.2	Median	7	IQR	4-10	50	14	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	2462	49	Mean	61.4	SD	17.3	NA	NA	Mean	73.2	SD	29.6	Median	7	IQR	5-10	51	15	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Liu, 2021	223	38	Mean	67.9	SD	16.07	NA	NA	Mean	24.65	SD	5.89	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	325	30	Mean	57.6	SD	16,72	NA	NA	Mean	20.65	SD	6.37	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
Mao, 2020	43	51	Mean	44.0	SD	5.1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	43	42	Mean	43.5	SD	4.2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Martin, 2021	10	60	Median	40	IQR	35-74	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA
	10	50	Median	48	IQR	38-64	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA
Mou, 2020	53	51	Mean	57.8	SD	5.4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	53	45	Mean	58.2	SD	5.9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Nickels, 2020	36	36	Mean	56	SD	18	NA	NA	Median	67	IQR	48-82	Median	9	IQR	8-12	100	NA	NA	NA	19	NA	NA
	36	28	Mean	57	SD	16	NA	NA	Median	65	IQR	49-81	Median	9	IQR	7-11	100	NA	NA	NA	17	NA	NA
Nielsen, 2020	36	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	39	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Olsen, 2021	349	36	Median	72.0	IQR	63.0-80.0	Median	49	IQR	39-60	Median	26	IQR	22-30	Median	7	IQR	5-10	100	NA	NA	24	NA
	351	42	Median	70.0	IQR	62.8-78.0	Median	49	IQR	40-59	Median	25	IQR	21-30	Median	8	IQR	6-11	100	NA	NA	21	NA
Pandian, 2020	25	60	Mean	50.7	SD	17.5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Mean	6.12	SD	2.09	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	25	40	Mean	57.9	SD	14.9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Mean	5.44	SD	1.56	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Perkins, 2019	182	51	Mean	64.3	SD	13.6	NA	NA	Mean	18.9	SD	6.6	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
	182	48	Mean	61.8	SD	15.8	NA	NA	Mean	18.8	SD	6.2	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	71	NA	NA	31	NA	
Rood, 2019 (van den Boogaard)	350	41	Mean	66.1	SD	12.6	NA	NA	Mean	20.1	SD	7.1	NA	NA	71	NA	NA	71	NA	NA	31	NA	
	732	37	Mean	66.7	SD	12.7	NA	NA	Mean	19.2	SD	6.9	NA	NA	68	NA	NA	68	NA	NA	37	NA	
	707	39	Mean	67.0	SD	12.6	NA	NA	Mean	19.0	SD	6.8	NA	NA	65	NA	NA	65	NA	NA	33	NA	
Viana, 2021	15	20	Mean	61.3	SD	18.3	Mean	48.5	SD	10.9	Mean	21.3	SD	6.7	Mean	9.33	SD	2.64	100	NA	NA	NA	NA
	15	27	Mean	68.9	SD	14.3	Mean	47.1	SD	12.5	Mean	23.7	SD	6.2	Mean	8.45	SD	2.25	100	NA	NA	NA	NA
Waldauf, 2021	75	29	Mean	59.9	SD	15.1	NA	NA	Mean	22.1	SD	5.2	Mean	8.8	SD	2.6	100	NA	NA	25	11		
	75	24	Mean	62.3	SD	15.4	NA	NA	Mean	22.2	SD	7.7	Mean	8.8	SD	3.2	100	NA	NA	24	13		
Xu, 2021	55	47	Mean	53.63	SD	4.28	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	55	44	Mean	53.67	SD	4.32	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	NA	NA		
Zeng, 2021	70	40	Mean	43.96	SD	7.41	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	64	38	Mean	44.21	SD	7.17	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Morris, 2016	150	56	Mean	55	SD	17	NA	NA	Mean	76	SD	26	NA	NA	93	NA	NA	93	NA	NA	NA	24	
	150	55	Mean	58	SD	14	NA	NA	Mean	76	SD	27	NA	NA	93	NA	NA	93	NA	NA	NA	22	
Ruble, 2002 (Warren)	1157	3	Mean	57	SD	17	Mean	49	SD	17	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	49	
	1157	3	Mean	58	SD	17	Mean	49	SD	16	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	47	

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, Year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	No. of patients per arm (the study population from the original trial)	Female (%)	Age (mean or median)	Age	Age variation (IQR, Range or SD)	Age variation	SAPS (mean or median)	SAPS	SAPS variation (IQR, range or SD)	SAPS variation	APACHE score (mean or median)	APACHE score	APACHE score variation (IQR, range or SD)	APACHE score variation	SOFA score (mean or median)	SOFA score	SOFA score variation (IQR, range or SD)	SOFA score variation	Patients with invasive mechanical ventilation (%)	Patients with dialysis (%)	Patients with vasopressor (%)	Patient with sepsis/severe sepsis (as defined by author) (%)	Patients with septic shock (%)
Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
Lemkes, 2020	273	18	Mean	65.7	SD	12.7	NA	NA	Mean	107	SD	28	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	265	24	Mean	64.9	SD	12.5	NA	NA	Mean	105	SD	32	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Mackle, 2020	484	38.8	Mean	58.1	SD	16.2	NA	NA	Mean	23.6	SD	9.3	NA	NA	100	NA	53.7	10.5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	481	37.2	Mean	57.5	SD	16.1	NA	NA	Mean	23.3	SD	9.4	NA	NA	100	NA	55.1	9.4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Bagshaw, 2020	1465	32.1	Mean	64.6	SD	14.3	Mean	58.1	SD	17.4	NA	NA	Mean	11.6	SD	3.6	75.3	NA	68.8	58.4	43.7	NA	NA
	1462	31.9	Mean	64.7	SD	13.4	Mean	59.4	SD	17.4	NA	NA	Mean	11.8	SD	3.6	78.5	NA	72.0	57.0	44.0	NA	NA
Dixon, 2021	128	35	Mean	58	SD	15	NA	NA	Mean	23	SD	7	NA	NA	100	12	81	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	124	40	Mean	59	SD	15	NA	NA	Mean	24	SD	7	NA	NA	100	10	75	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Ginde, 2019	538	42.6	Mean	56.5	SD	15.9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Mean	5.6	SD	3.6	32.2	NA	31.4	34.4	35.7	NA	NA
	540	44.1	Mean	54.6	SD	16.7	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Mean	5.4	SD	3.7	34.1	NA	32.8	32.2	36.5	NA	NA
Hughes, 2021	214	43	Median	59	IQR	48-68	NA	NA	Median	27	IQR	21-32	Median	10	IQR	8-13	100	NA	56	NA	56	NA	NA
	208	42	Median	60	IQR	50-68	NA	NA	Median	27	IQR	22-32	Median	10	IQR	8-12	100	NA	49	NA	49	NA	NA
Lamontagne, 2020	1291	42.8	Median	75.2	IQR	70.4-80.5	NA	NA	Mean	20.9	SD	6.5	NA	NA	58.1	24.8	98.8	29.9	48.4	NA	NA	NA	NA
	1307	44.1	Median	74.8	IQR	70.1-80.8	NA	NA	Mean	20.6	SD	6.1	NA	NA	55.8	24.7	98.0	29.8	48.0	NA	NA	NA	NA

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, Year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	No. of patients per arm (the study population from the original trial)	Female (%)	Age (mean or median)	Age	Age variation (IQR, Range or SD)	Age variation	SAPS (mean or median)	SAPS	SAPS variation (IQR, range or SD)	SAPS variation	APACHE score (mean or median)	APACHE score	APACHE score variation (IQR, range or SD)	APACHE score variation	SOFA score (mean or median)	SOFA score	SOFA score variation (IQR, range or SD)	SOFA score variation	Patients with invasive mechanical ventilation (%)	Patients with dialysis (%)	Patients with vasopressor (%)	Patient with sepsis/severe sepsis (as defined by author) (%)	Patients with septic shock (%)
Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
Laterre, 2019	562	40.9	Mean	62.1	SD	15.7	NA	NA	Mean	14.5	SD	6.0	NA	NA	16.4	5.5	60.9	NA	NA				
	266	36.1	Mean	62.6	SD	14.5	NA	NA	Mean	14.6	SD	6.9	NA	NA	14.8	3.7	63.0	NA	NA				
Litton, 2021	110	40.9	Mean	62.1	SD	15.7	NA	NA	Mean	14.5	SD	6.0	NA	NA	16.4	5.5	60.9	NA	NA				
	108	36.1	Mean	62.6	SD	14.5	NA	NA	Mean	14.6	SD	6.9	NA	NA	14.8	3.7	63.0	NA	NA				
Amrein, 2014	237	35.0	Mean	63.9	SD	15.5	Mean	32.4	SD	15.0	NA	NA	NA	NA	63.7	NA	55.3	NA	NA				
	238	34.9	Mean	65.3	SD	14.0	Mean	34.2	SD	15.7	NA	NA	NA	NA	64.7	NA	52.9	NA	NA				
Moss, 2019	501	41.9	Mean	56.6	SD	14.7	NA	NA	Mean	103.9	SD	30.1	Mean	8.7	SD	3.6	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	55.1	
	505	46.7	Mean	55.1	SD	15.9	NA	NA	Mean	104.9	SD	30.1	Mean	8.8	SD	3.6	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	61.2	
Parke, 2021	358	28.5	Median	70	IQR	59-74	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Median	5	IQR	4-6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	357	24.4	Median	68	IQR	59-74	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Median	5	IQR	4-6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Pickkers, 2018	111	26.1	Median	65.0	IQR	57-73	Median	50.0	IQR	42-61	Median	25.0	IQR	19-31	Median	10.0	IQR	8-12	63.1	NA	91.9	100	NA
	116	27.6	Median	68.0	IQR	61-75	Median	47.0	IQR	39-60	Median	26.0	IQR	20-33.5	Median	10.0	IQR	8-12	58.6	NA	88.8	100	NA
Ridley, 2018	51	31	Mean	59	SD	17	NA	NA	Mean	18	SD	7	Mean	10	SD	4	100	NA	NA	14	NA		
	48	27	Mean	60	SD	17	NA	NA	Mean	19	SD	7	Mean	10	SD	3	100	NA	NA	2	NA		
Roquilly, 2021	185	21.2	Median	46	IQR	27-60	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	185	19.1	Median	43	IQR	27-59	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Author for reporting the HRQoL data, Year (Author of original trial, if applicable)	No. of patients per arm (the study population from the original trial)	Female (%)	Age (mean or median)	Age	Age variation (IQR, Range or SD)	Age variation	SAPS (mean or median)	SAPS	SAPS variation (IQR, range or SD)	SAPS variation	APACHE score (mean or median)	APACHE score	APACHE score variation (IQR, range or SD)	APACHE score variation	SOFA score (mean or median)	SOFA score	SOFA score variation (IQR, range or SD)	SOFA score variation	Patients with invasive mechanical ventilation (%)	Patients with dialysis (%)	Patients with vasopressor (%)	Patient with sepsis/severe sepsis (as defined by author) (%)	Patients with septic shock (%)
Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
Shehabi, 2019	1954	39.4	Mean	61.2	SD	15.5	NA	NA	Mean	22.1	SD	7.7	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	63.9	NA	
	1964	37.3	Mean	61.4	SD	15.3	NA	NA	Mean	21.9	SD	7.7	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	100	NA	NA	64.0	NA	
Wade, 2019	283	40.6	Mean	59.5	SD	16.0	NA	NA	Mean	16.9	SD	6.5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	340	45.0	Mean	60.4	SD	15.0	NA	NA	Mean	17.7	SD	6.4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	284	37.0	Mean	57.2	SD	16.2	NA	NA	Mean	16.7	SD	5.8	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	446	39.9	Mean	57.2	SD	15.6	NA	NA	Mean	16.9	SD	6.2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Laterre, 2021	72	37.5	Median	68	IQR	59-75	NA	NA	Median	32	IQR	29-34	Median	11	IQR	7-11	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	100	
	77	31.2	Median	71	IQR	65-77	NA	NA	Median	33	IQR	28-36	Median	10	IQR	7-11	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	100	
	152	43.4	Median	71	IQR	60-78	NA	NA	Median	33	IQR	29-36	Median	9	IQR	7.75-11.25	NA	NA	NA	NA	100	100	
Granhölm, 2022 (Munch)	497	30	Median	65	IQR	56-74	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	22	2	16	NA	NA		
	485	32	Median	64	IQR	54-72	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	20	3	14	NA	NA		
Silversides, 2022	89	38.2	Mean	57	SD	17.2	NA	NA	Mean	17.5	SD	6.9	Mean	8.4	SD	3.3	100	16.9	16.9	56.2	45		
	90	34.4	Mean	57.1	SD	16.9	NA	NA	Mean	16.8	SD	6.4	Mean	7.7	SD	2.9	100	6.7	6.7	45.6	35.6		
Crescioli, 2022 (Schjørring)	1453	36.3	Median	70	IQR	60-77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Median	8	IQR	5-10	57.4	NA	55.1	NA	NA			

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Study details		Baseline characteristics																					
	1457	35,1	Median	70	IQR	60-77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Median	8	IQR	5-10	59.7	NA	54.3	NA	NA	
Bellingan, 2022	20	35	Mean	51	SD	14	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Mean	10.9	SD	2.2	100	NA	45	15	NA	
	10	40	Mean	59	SD	18	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Mean	12.2	SD	4.2	100	NA	30	10	NA	
Campos, 2022	34	30	Mean	42.5	SD	14.9	Mean	66.1	SD	13.2	NA	NA	NA	Mean	8.79	SD	2.95	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	40	35	Mean	46.7	SD	17.9	Mean	67.3	SD	15.5	NA	NA	NA	Mean	9.35	SD	2.71	100	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Bisset, 2022	33	45.5	Mean	60	SD	17	NA	NA	Median	19	IQR	16-25	Median	8	IQR	5-10	100	NA	NA	15	NA		
	37	37.8	Mean	59	SD	15	NA	NA	Median	18	IQR	14-24	Median	8	IQR	5-10	100	NA	NA	14	NA		
Lamontagne, 2022	429	35.2	Mean	65.0	SD	14.0	NA	NA	Mean	24.2	SD	7.4	Mean	3.8	SD	1.4	68.5	10.7	99.8	59.6	59.6		
	433	40.0	Mean	65.2	SD	13.8	NA	NA	Mean	24.1	SD	7.9	Mean	3.9	SD	1.4	65.4	9.7	100	56.1	56.1		
Boyle, 2022 (McNamee)	202	32	Median	60.2	IQR	50.6-69.0	NA	NA	Median	19	IQR	15-23	Median	10	IQR	7-12	100	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	210	38	Median	61.8	IQR	50.2-69.7	NA	NA	Median	20	IQR	16-23	Median	10	IQR	7-12	100	NA	NA	NA	NA		

Table S4. Primary and secondary objectives for all HRQoL assessments in included trials

Trial (year)	Missing data (primary objective)									Missing data (secondary objective)		
	Follo w-up time point (s)	HRQoL tool	Dead			Nonrespondents			Reported nonrespo ndents in quantity	Discus sion of poten tial attriti on bias	Baseline characteri stic compared between respondents and non- respondents	Method(s) used to handle missing data ^a
	Days	Tool ^b	n	N	%	n	N	%	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
Agus, 2017 ⁶	NA	EQ-5D-3L	0	539	0.0	282	539	52.3	Y	Y	N	MI
Agus, 2017 ⁶	90	EQ-5D-3L	172	539	31.9	163	365	44.7	Y	Y	N	MI
Agus, 2017 ⁶	180	EQ-5D-3L	180	539	33.4	167	359	46.5	Y	Y	N	MI
Agus, 2017 ⁶	365	EQ-5D-3L	190	539	35.3	179	349	51.3	Y	Y	N	MI
Allingstrup, 2017 ⁷	180	SF-36	73	199	36.7	23	126	18.3	Y	Y	N	MI
Amrein, 2014 ⁸	180	SF-12	185	475	38.9	1	290	0.3	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Amundadottir, 2019 ⁹	NA	SF-36	0	50	0.0	6	50	12.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Amundadottir, 2019 ⁹	90	SF-36	4	50	8.0	3	46	6.5	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Amundadottir, 2019 ⁹	180	SF-36	5	50	10.0	3	45	6.7	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Amundadottir, 2019 ⁹	365	SF-36	5	50	10.0	4	45	8.9	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Angus, 2006 ¹⁰	180	QWB	111	368	30.2	NA	257	NA	Y	N	Y	Assumed CCA
Angus, 2006 ¹⁰	365	QWB	142	368	38.6	NA	226	NA	Y	N	Y	Assumed CCA
Antonelli, 2005 ¹¹	365	SF-12	72	139	51.8	36	67	53.7	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Azevedo, 2019 ¹²	90	SF-36	60	120	50.0	6	60	10.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Azevedo, 2019 ¹²	180	SF-36	61	120	50.8	10	59	16.9	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bagshaw, 2020 ¹³	90	EQ-5D-5L	1282	2,927	43.8	542	1,645	32.9	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bagshaw, 2020 ¹³	90	EQ-VAS	1282	2,927	43.8	494	1,645	30.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bellingan, 2022 ¹⁴	28	EQ-VAS	9	30	30	6	21	28.6	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bellingan, 2022 ¹⁴	28	EQ-5D-3L	9	30	30	6	21	28.6	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bellingan, 2022 ¹⁴	90	EQ-VAS	NA	30	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bellingan, 2022 ¹⁴	90	EQ-5D-3L	NA	30	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bellingan, 2022 ¹⁴	365	EQ-VAS	13	30	43,3	2	17	11.8	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bellingan, 2022 ¹⁴	365	EQ-5D-3L	13	30	43,3	2	17	11.8	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Bissett, 2022 ¹⁵	0	SF-36	0	70	0	NA	70	NA	N	N	N ^f	Assumed CCA
Bissett, 2022 ¹⁵	0	EQ-5D-3L	0	70	0	NA	70	NA	N	N	N ^f	Assumed CCA
Bissett, 2022 ¹⁵	0	EQ-VAS	0	70	0	NA	70	NA	N	N	N ^f	Assumed CCA

Trial (year)	Missing data (primary objective)									Missing data (secondary objective)		
	Follow-up time point (s)	HRQoL tool	Dead			Nonrespondents			Reported nonrespondents in quantity	Discussion of potential attrition bias	Baseline characteristics compared between respondents and non-respondents	Method(s) used to handle missing data ^a
			n	N	%	n	N	%				
Bissett, 2022 ¹⁵	NA	SF-36	NA	70	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N ^f	Assumed CCA
Bissett, 2022 ¹⁵	NA	EQ-5D-3L	NA	70	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N ^f	Assumed CCA
Bissett, 2022 ¹⁵	NA	EQ-VAS	NA	70	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N ^f	Assumed CCA
Boyle, 2022 ¹⁶	180	EQ-5D-5L	170	412	41.3	NA	242	NA	Y	N	Y	Assumed CCA
Boyle, 2022 ¹⁶	180	EQ-VAS	170	412	41.3	NA	242	NA	Y	N	Y	Assumed CCA
Boyle, 2022 ¹⁶	365	EQ-5D-5L	174	412	42.2	108	238	45.4	Y	N	Y	Assumed CCA
Boyle, 2022 ¹⁶	365	EQ-VAS	174	412	42.2	105	238	44.1	Y	N	Y	Assumed CCA
Brummel, 2014 ¹⁷	90	EQ-5D	32	87	36.8	11	55	20.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Campos, 2022 ¹⁸	NA	EQ-VAS	48	139	34,5	48	91	52.7	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Campos, 2022 ¹⁸	NA	EQ-5D-3L	48	139	34,5	48	91	52.7	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Campos, 2022 ¹⁸	NA	EQ-VAS	56	139	40,3	36	83	43.4	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Campos, 2022 ¹⁸	NA	EQ-5D-3L	56	139	40,3	36	83	43.4	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Crescioli, 2022 ¹⁹	365	EQ-5D-5L	1,411	2,887	48,9	287	1,476	19.4	Y	Y	Y	MI, Sensitivity, BWCS ^e
Crescioli, 2022 ¹⁹	365	EQ-VAS	1,411	2,887	48,9	287	1,476	19.4	Y	Y	Y	MI, Sensitivity, BWCS ^e
Cronberg, 2015 ²⁰	180	SF-36	448	939	47.7	36	491	7.3	Y	N	N	MI
de Azevedo, 2021 ²¹	90	SF-36	73	181	40.3	0	108	0.0	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
de Azevedo, 2021 ²¹	180	SF-36	80	181	44.2	1	101	1.0	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Deane, 2020 ²²	180	EQ-5D-5L	1,099	3,957	27.8	366	2,858	12.8	Y	N	Y	CCA
Denehy, 2013 ²³	90	SF-36	23	150	15.3	25	127	19.7	Y	N	N	CCA
Denehy, 2013 ²³	180	SF-36	24	150	16.0	29	126	23.0	Y	N	N	CCA
Denehy, 2013 ²³	365	SF-36	32	150	21.3	36	118	30.5	Y	N	N	CCA
Dinglas, 2016 ²⁴	180	SF-36	26	272	9.6	13	246	5.3	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Dinglas, 2016 ²⁴	365	SF-36	35	272	12.9	30	237	12.7	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Dinglas, 2016 ²⁴	180	EQ-5D	26	272	9.6	13	246	5.3	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Dinglas, 2016 ²⁴	365	EQ-5D	35	272	12.9	30	237	12.7	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Dixon, 2021 ²⁵	60	SF-36	41	252	16.3	20	211	9.5	Y	Y	N	CCA
Dixon, 2021 ²⁵	60	EQ-5D-3L	41	252	16.3	18	211	8.5	Y	Y	N	CCA

Trial (year)	Missing data (primary objective)									Missing data (secondary objective)		
	Follow-up time point (s)	HRQoL tool	Dead			Nonrespondents			Reported nonrespondents in quantity	Discussion of potential attrition bias	Baseline characteristics compared between respondents and non-respondents	Method(s) used to handle missing data ^a
			n	N	%	n	N	%				
	Days	Tool ^b	n	N	%	n	N	%	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
Dixon, 2021 ²⁵	180	SF-36	52	252	20.6	16	200	8.0	Y	Y	N	CCA
Dixon, 2021 ²⁵	180	EQ-5D-3L	52	252	20.6	16	200	8.0	Y	Y	N	CCA
Doig, 2013 ²⁶	60	RAND-36	301	1,363	22.1	30	1,062	2.8	Y	Y	N	CCA
Dubois, 2017 ²⁷	NA	EQ-5D-3L	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Dubois, 2017 ²⁷	90	EQ-5D-3L	180	1,55	11.6	NA	1,37	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Fan, 2021 ²⁸	NA	SF-36	0	116	0.0	0	116	0.0	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Fossat, 2018 ²⁹	180	SF-36	96	312	30.8	34	216	15.7	Y	Y	N	CCA
Freeman-Sanderson, 2016 ³⁰	NA	EQ-5D	5	30	16.7	NA	25	NA	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Freeman-Sanderson, 2016 ³⁰	NA	EQ-VAS	5	30	16.7	NA	25	NA	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Gallagher, 2014 ³¹	1,138	EQ-5D	258	810	31.9	202	552	36.6	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Gallagher, 2014 ³¹	1,138	SF-12	258	810	31.9	202	552	36.6	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Gates, 2013 ³²	180	SF-12	120	326	36.8	132	206	64.1	Y	Y	N	CCA
Gates, 2013 ³²	180	EQ-5D	120	326	36.8	130	206	63.1	Y	Y	N	CCA
Gates, 2013 ³²	365	SF-12	126	326	38.7	126	200	63.0	Y	Y	N	CCA
Gates, 2013 ³²	365	EQ-5D	126	326	38.7	123	200	61.5	Y	Y	N	CCA
Ginde, 2019 ³³	NA	EQ-5D-5L	0	1,078	0.0	67	1,078	6.2	Y	N	N	CCA
Ginde, 2019 ³³	90	EQ-5D-5L	296	1,358	21.8	201	1,062	18.9	Y	N	N	CCA
Giraud, 2016 ³⁴	84	EQ-5D	NA	223	NA	28	NA	NA	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Giraud, 2016 ³⁴	84	EQ-VAS	NA	223	NA	28	NA	NA	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Granholt, 2022 ³⁵	180	EQ-5D-5L	348	971	35.8	49	623	7.9	Y	Y	Y	MI, Sensitivity, BWCS ^e
Granholt, 2022 ³⁵	180	EQ-VAS	348	971	35.8	49	623	7.9	Y	Y	Y	MI, Sensitivity, BWCS ^e
Hammond, 2020 ³⁶	180	EQ-5D-5L	1,143	3,686	31.0	392	2,543	15.4	Y	Y	Y	CCA
Hammond, 2020 ³⁶	180	EQ-VAS	1,143	3,686	31.0	418	2,543	16.4	Y	Y	Y	CCA
Harvey, 2016 ³⁷	90	EQ-5D-5L	918	2,388	38.4	305	1,47	20.7	Y	Y	N	MI
Harvey, 2016 ³⁷	365	EQ-5D-5L	1,054	2,388	44.1	339	1,334	25.4	Y	Y	N	MI
Hodgson, 2016 ³⁸	180	EQ-5D-5L	3	50	6.0	10	47	21.3	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Hughes, 2021 ³⁹	180	EQ-5D	175	422	41.5	59	268	22.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Ingels, 2006 ⁴⁰	1,461	NHP	162	970	16.7	205	808	25.4	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA

Trial (year)	Missing data (primary objective)									Missing data (secondary objective)		
	Follow-up time point (s)	HRQoL tool	Dead			Nonrespondents			Reported nonrespondents in quantity	Discussion of potential attrition bias	Baseline characteristics compared between respondents and non-respondents	Method(s) used to handle missing data ^a
			n	N	%	n	N	%				
Irving, 2019 ⁴¹	180	EQ-5D-3L	1,365	4,919	27.7	415	3,554	11.7	Y	Y	N	CCA, MI
Jackson, 2010 ⁴²	90	SF-36	81	180	45.0	26	99	26.3	Y	Y	N	CCA
Jackson, 2010 ⁴²	365	SF-36	94	180	52.2	30	86	34.9	Y	Y	N	CCA
Jones, 2015 ⁴³	90	SF-36	4	93	4.3	17	89	19.1	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Jones, 2015 ⁴³	90	EQ-5D	4	93	4.3	17	89	19.1	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Kayambu, 2015 ⁴⁴	180	SF-36	16	50	32.0	4	34	11.8	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Kurtoglu, 2015 ⁴⁵	0	SF-36	NA	30	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Kurtoglu, 2015 ⁴⁵	30	SF-36	NA	30	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Lall, 2015 ⁴⁶	180	SF-12	395	795	49.7	185	400	46.3	Y	Y	N	CCA, MI
Lall, 2015 ⁴⁶	180	EQ-5D-3L	395	795	49.7	185	400	46.3	Y	Y	N	CCA, MI
Lall, 2015 ⁴⁶	365	SF-12	405	795	50.9	211	390	54.1	Y	Y	N	CCA, MI
Lall, 2015 ⁴⁶	365	EQ-5D-3L	405	795	50.9	211	390	54.1	Y	Y	N	CCA, MI
Lamontagne, 2020 ⁴⁷	90	EQ-5D-5L	1,044	2,568	40.7	224	1,524	14.7	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Lamontagne, 2020 ⁴⁷	365	EQ-5D-5L	NA	2,568	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Lamontagne, 2022 ⁴⁸	180	EQ-5D-5L	376	872	43.1	32	496	6.5	Y	N	N	CCA
Lamontagne, 2022 ⁴⁸	180	EQ-VAS	376	872	43.1	32	496	6.5	Y	N	N	CCA
Laterre, 2019 ⁴⁹	30	EQ-5D-5L	284	828	34.3	NA	544	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Laterre, 2019 ⁴⁹	60	EQ-5D-5L	NA	828	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Laterre, 2019 ⁴⁹	90	EQ-5D-5L	336	828	40.6	NA	492	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Laterre, 2019 ⁴⁹	180	EQ-5D-5L	357	828	43.1	83	471	17.6	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Laterre, 2019 ⁴⁹	180	EQ-VAS	357	828	43.1	83	471	17.6	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Laterre, 2021 ⁵⁰	NA	EQ-VAS	NA	301	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	CCA
Laterre, 2021 ⁵⁰	28	EQ-VAS	77	301	25.6	NA	224	NA	N	N	N	CCA
Laterre, 2021 ⁵⁰	90	EQ-VAS	103	301	34.2	31	198	15.7	Y	N	N	CCA
Lemkes, 2020 ⁵¹	365	RAND-36	195	538	36.2	108	343	31.5	Y	Y	Y	Assumed CCA
Litton, 2021 ⁵²	60	EQ-5D-5L	11	218	5.0	12	207	5.8	Y	N	N	CCA
Litton, 2021 ⁵²	60	EQ-VAS	11	218	5.0	12	207	5.8	Y	N	N	CCA
Liu, 2021 ⁵³	7	QoL2	0	548	0.0	135	548	24.6	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Mackle, 2020 ⁵⁴	100	EQ-5D-5L	334	965	34.6	132	631	20.9	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA

Trial (year)	Missing data (primary objective)									Missing data (secondary objective)		
	Follow-up time point (s)	HRQoL tool	Dead			Nonrespondents			Reported nonrespondents in quantity	Discussion of potential attrition bias	Baseline characteristics compared between respondents and non-respondents	Method(s) used to handle missing data ^a
			n	N	%	n	N	%				
Madsen, 2017 ⁵⁵	180	SF-36	25	100	25.0	13	75	17.3	Y	Y	N	MI
Mao, 2020 ⁵⁶	42	SF-36	NA	86	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Marasco, 2013 ⁵⁷	180	SF-36	1	46	2.2	8	45	17.8	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Martin, 2021 ⁵⁸	NA	QOL-MV	0	20	0.0	0	20	0.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Martin, 2021 ⁵⁸	NA	QOL-MV	0	20	0.0	0	20	0.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Martin, 2021 ⁵⁸	NA	QOL-MV	4	20	20.0	3	16	18.8	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Messika, 2019 ⁵⁹	90	SF-36	18	113	15.9	32	95	33.7	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Morris, 2016 ⁶⁰	NA	SF-36	36	300	12.0	56	264	21.2	Y	Y	Y	MI
Morris, 2016 ⁶⁰	60	SF-36	NA	300	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Y	MI
Morris, 2016 ⁶⁰	120	SF-36	NA	300	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Y	MI
Morris, 2016 ⁶⁰	180	SF-36	66	300	22.0	73	234	31.2	Y	Y	Y	MI
Moss, 2019 ⁶¹	90	EQ-5D-5L	429	1,006	42.6	176	577	30.5	Y	N	N	CCA
Moss, 2019 ⁶¹	180	EQ-5D-5L	NA	1,006	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	CCA
Moss, 2019 ⁶¹	365	EQ-5D-5L	NA	1,006	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	CCA
Mou, 2020 ⁶²	NA	SF-36	4	106	3.8	0	102	0.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Nickels, 2020 ⁶³	10	EQ-5D-5L	2	72	2.8	NA	70	NA	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Nickels, 2020 ⁶³	90	EQ-5D-5L	6	72	8.3	4	66	6.1	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Nickels, 2020 ⁶³	180	EQ-5D-5L	6	72	8.3	6	66	9.1	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Nickels, 2020 ⁶³	10	EQ-VAS	2	72	2.8	NA	70	NA	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Nickels, 2020 ⁶³	90	EQ-VAS	6	72	8.3	4	66	6.1	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Nickels, 2020 ⁶³	180	EQ-VAS	6	72	8.3	6	66	9.1	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Nielsen, 2020 ⁶⁴	NA	SF-36	3	75	4.0	20	72	27.8	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Noguchi, 2017 ⁶⁵	90	SF-36	1	109	0.9	10	108	9.3	Y	N	N	Assumed CCAS
Olsen, 2021 ⁶⁶	90	SF-36	306	700	43.7	50	394	12.7	Y	N	Y	CCA, BWCS ^e
Pandian, 2020 ⁶⁷	1	QOL-MV	0	50	0.0	0	50	0.0	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Pandian, 2020 ⁶⁷	5	QOL-MV	0	50	0.0	3	50	6.0	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Parke, 2021 ⁶⁸	90	EQ-5D-5L	18	715	2.5	NA	697	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA

Trial (year)	Missing data (primary objective)									Missing data (secondary objective)		
	Follow-up time point (s)	HRQoL tool	Dead			Nonrespondents			Reported nonrespondents in quantity	Discussion of potential attrition bias	Baseline characteristics compared between respondents and non-respondents	Method(s) used to handle missing data ^a
			n	N	%	n	N	%				
	Days	Tool ^b	n	N	%	n	N	%	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
Parke, 2021 ⁶⁸	180	EQ-5D-5L	19	715	2.7	NA	686	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	NA	EQ-5D-3L	67	364	18.4	57	297	19.2	Y	Y	N	CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	90	EQ-5D-3L	81	364	22.3	121	283	42.8	Y	Y	N	CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	180	EQ-5D-3L	85	364	23.4	63	279	22.6	Y	Y	N	CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	NA	SF-12	67	364	18.4	80	297	26.9	Y	Y	N	CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	90	SF-12	81	364	22.3	121	283	42.8	Y	Y	N	CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	180	SF-12	85	364	23.4	120	279	43.0	Y	Y	N	CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	NA	EQ-VAS	67	364	18.4	63	297	21.2	Y	Y	N	CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	90	EQ-VAS	81	364	22.3	100	283	35.3	Y	Y	N	CCA
Perkins, 2019 ⁶⁹	180	EQ-VAS	85	364	23.4	106	279	38.0	Y	Y	N	CCA
Pickkers, 2018 ⁷⁰	NA	EQ-5D-5L	NA	227	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Pickkers, 2018 ⁷⁰	NA	EQ-VAS	NA	227	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Pickkers, 2018 ⁷⁰	90	EQ-5D-5L	53	227	23,3	5	174	2.9	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Pickkers, 2018 ⁷⁰	90	EQ-VAS	53	227	23,3	5	174	2.9	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Ridley, 2018 ⁷¹	NA	EQ-5D-3L	27	99	27,3	28	72	38.9	Y	N	N	CCA
Ridley, 2018 ⁷¹	90	EQ-5D-3L	32	99	32,3	6	67	9.0	Y	N	N	CCA
Ridley, 2018 ⁷¹	180	EQ-5D-3L	32	99	32,3	6	67	9.0	Y	N	N	CCA
Rood, 2019 ⁷²	NA	SF-12	0	1,245	0.0	358	1,245	28.8	Y	Y	Y	Assumed CCA
Rood, 2019 ⁷²	30	SF-12	NA	887	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Y	Assumed CCA
Rood, 2019 ⁷²	180	SF-12	NA	887	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Y	Assumed CCA
Roquilly, 2021 ⁷³	90	SF-36	64	370	17,3	104	306	34.0	Y	N	N	CCA
Roquilly, 2021 ⁷³	180	SF-36	66	370	17,8	67	304	22.0	Y	N	N	CCA
Rublee, 2002 ⁷⁴	28	Karnofsky	898	2,314	38.8	0	1,416	0.0	N	N	N	Simple imputation
Rublee, 2002 ⁷⁴	56	Karnofsky	NA	2,314	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Simple imputation
Rublee, 2002 ⁷⁴	90	Karnofsky	897	2,314	38.8	NA	1,417	NA	N	N	N	Simple imputation
Rygård, 2016 ⁷⁵	365	SF-36	447	777	57.5	148	330	44.8	Y	Y	Y	CCA ^d
Schaller, 2016 ⁷⁶	90	SF-36	32	193	16.6	77	161	47.8	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA

Trial (year)	Missing data (primary objective)										Missing data (secondary objective)	
	Follow-up time point (s)	HRQoL tool	Dead			Nonrespondents			Reported nonrespondents in quantity	Discussion of potential attrition bias	Baseline characteristics compared between respondents and non-respondents	Method(s) used to handle missing data ^a
			n	N	%	n	N	%				
Schädler, 2017 ⁷⁷	365	EORTC-QLQ-C30	92	300	30.7	125	208	60.1	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Shehabi, 2019 ⁷⁸	180	EQ-5D-3L	1,219	3,904	31.2	364	2,685	13.6	Y	Y	M	MI
Silversides, 2022 ⁷⁹	180	EQ-5D-5L	46	178	25.8	94	132	71.2	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Silversides, 2022 ⁷⁹	180	EQ-VAS	46	178	25.8	94	132	71.2	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Sosnowski, 2018 ⁸⁰	90	SF-36	5	30	16.7	2	25	8.0	Y	Y	N	CCA
Taylor, 2016 ⁸¹	180	EQ-5D-3L	779	3,450	22.6	60	2,671	2.2	Y	Y	N	CCA
Trouillet, 2011 ⁸²	90	SF-36	97	216	44.9	3	116	2.6	Y	Y	N	Assumed CCA
Van Mastrigt, 2006 ⁸³	NA	EQ-5D-3L	0	597	0.0	2	597	0.3	Y	Y	N	MI
Van Mastrigt, 2006 ⁸³	30	EQ-5D-3L	4	597	0.7	44	593	7.4	Y	Y	N	MI
Viana, 2021 ⁸⁴	30	SF-12	NA	30	NA	1	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Viana, 2021 ⁸⁴	60	SF-12	NA	30	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Wade, 2019 ⁸⁵	180	EQ-5D-5L	120	1,353	8.9	302	1,233	24.5	Y	Y	N	MI, Sensitivity ^c
Waldauf, 2021 ⁸⁶	180	SF-36	62	150	41.3	0	88	0.0	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA
Walsh, 2017 ⁸⁷	180	EQ-5D-3L	132	359	36.8	88	227	38.8	Y	Y	N	MI
Walsh, 2017 ⁸⁷	180	EQ-5D-5L	132	359	36.8	88	227	38.8	Y	Y	N	MI
Walsh, 2017 ⁸⁷	365	EQ-5D-3L	138	359	38.4	93	221	42.1	Y	Y	N	MI
Walsh, 2017 ⁸⁷	365	EQ-5D-5L	138	359	38.4	93	221	42.1	Y	Y	N	MI
Wischmeyer, 2017 ⁸⁸	90	SF-36	NA	125	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	N	CCA
Wischmeyer, 2017 ⁸⁸	180	SF-36	NA	125	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	N	CCA
Wittbrodt, 2013 ⁸⁹	365	SF-36	407	705	57.7	116	298	38.9	Y	Y	Y	Assumed CCA
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	NA	EQ-5D	79	308	25.6	77	229	33.6	Y	Y	Y	MI
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	NA	SF-36	79	308	25.6	77	229	33.6	Y	Y	Y	MI
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	NA	SF-6D	79	308	25.6	77	229	33.6	Y	Y	Y	MI
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	90	SF-36	84	308	27.3	86	224	38.4	Y	Y	Y	MI
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	90	SF-6D	84	308	27.3	86	224	38.4	Y	Y	Y	MI
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	90	EQ-5D	84	308	27.3	86	224	38.4	Y	Y	Y	MI
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	180	SF-36	99	308	32.1	93	209	44.5	Y	Y	Y	MI

Trial (year)	Missing data (primary objective)									Missing data (secondary objective)		
	Follow-up time point (s)	HRQoL tool	Dead			Nonrespondents			Reported nonrespondents in quantity	Discussion of potential attrition bias	Baseline characteristics compared between respondents and non-respondents	Method(s) used to handle missing data ^a
	Days	Tool ^b	n	N	%	n	N	%	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N	
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	180	SF-6D	99	308	32.1	93	209	44.5	Y	Y	Y	MI
Wright, 2017 ⁹⁰	180	EQ-5D	99	308	32.1	93	209	44.5	Y	Y	Y	MI
Xu, 2021 ⁹¹	NA	SF-36	NA	110	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Zeng, 2021 ⁹²	14	SF-36	NA	130	NA	NA	NA	NA	N	N	N	Assumed CCA
Zhu, 2018 ⁹³	90	RAND-36	89	474	18.8	13	385	3.4	Y	N	N	Assumed CCA

^a Complete case analysis (CCA), Assumed CCA: assigned if no wording regarding analysis method, Multiple imputation (MI): imputation of patients lost to follow up/nonrespondents, Simple imputation: carrying last assessment forward to the next time-point, Sensitivity analysis (sensitivity), Best/worst case scenario (BWCS).

^b Tool used at timepoint; EuroQol-5-dimension-5-level (EQ-5D-5L), EuroQol-5-dimension-3-level (EQ-5D-3L), EuroQol Visual Analogue Scale (EQ-VAS), Quality of Well-Being scale (QWB), European Organisation for the Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life Questionnaire (EORTC-QLQ-C30), Short Form 36 items (SF-36), Short Form 12 items (SF-12), Short Form 6 items (SF-6), Nottingham Health Profile (NHP), Quality of Life scale for terminal cancer patients (QoL2), Quality Of Life in Mechanically Ventilated patients (QOL-MV), Research And Development 36-Item Health Survey (RAND-36), Karnofsky performance scale index (Karnofsky).

^c Sensitivity by experts conducting elicitation and converting it into a range of priors. This to modelling missing not at random data with a fully Bayesian pattern-mixture models.

^d Little's test indicating missing completely at random.

^e Best-worst and worst-best case scenarios or the other way around.

^f In table 1, Bisset 2022, no. of patients lost to follow-up is presented with baseline characteristics, but data does not show non survivors vs. the nonrespondents, why "N" was assigned.

Table S5. Risk of Bias tool 2 – detailed summary of bias assessment

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
TEAM (Hodgson, 2016) ³⁸		Low	Low	High	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
Difference in baseline characteristics, probably by chance due to small population. Participants and personnel were likely aware of the intervention as it included early mobilisation/exercise in the ICU. Patients as HRQoL assessor might have been aware of intervention, resulting in “some concerns”. No protocol or SAP available.							
(Sosnowski, 2018) ⁸⁰		Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
Analyses were based on intention-to-treat principle. Participants and personnel were likely aware of the intervention as it included early mobilisation/exercise in the ICU. Patients as HRQoL assessor could have been aware of the received intervention. No protocol or SAP available.							
CALORIES (Harvey, 2016) ³⁷		Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
Patients and HRQoL assessor unblinded, though knowledge of the intervention (nutrition via enteral or parenteral route) seems unlikely to affect the outcome after 1 year, why only some concerns for bias.							
Mus-IRA (Messika, 2019) ⁵⁹		Low	Low	High	High	Low	High
Missing was >30%. Recommended analyses (multiple imputation + sensitivity analyses) done. Patients unblinded and likely to be aware of intervention; music therapy while being awake and non-invasive ventilated. Assessment after 90 days. This awareness could affect the outcome.							
OSCAR (Lall, 2015) ⁴⁶		Low	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
Missing 54%. Recommended analyses done and a table comparing respondents vs non-respondents included. Nonrespondents were most likely not missing at random resulting in “some concerns”. Patients were unblinded, but the intervention was technical (high frequency oscillatory ventilation vs. standard care) that patients and relatives probably do not have an opinion about and thereby might influence the outcome. No protocol or SAP available.							
BALTI-2 (Gates, 2013) ³²		Low	Low	High	Low	Low	High
Missing was >37% handled with assumed complete case analysis without further exploration of possible attrition bias even though possible attrition was considered in the protocol. Patients unaware of allocation due to double-blinded design							

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
EAT-ICU (Allingstrup, 2017) ⁷		Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
		Patients unblinded and HRQoL assessor, though knowledge of the intervention (early goal nutrition vs standard care) seems unlikely to affect the outcome after 6 months, why only some concerns for bias.					
EPaNIC (Doig, 2013) ²⁶		Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
		Patients unblinded and HRQoL assessor, though the intervention (nutrition) seems unlikely to affect the outcome. Anticipated complete case analysis. According to protocol intention-to-treat was used although non-respondents were not a part of the HRQoL analysis, resulting in "some concerns".					
(Trouillet, 2011) ⁸²		Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
		Patients and relatives unblinded to intervention (early tracheotomy vs standard care). Awake and aware of intervention with possible influence of the outcome, though assumed not likely. No protocol and no information regarding ITT or per protocol analysis, no consort diagram.					
(Kayambu, 2015) ⁴⁴		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Patients blinded to the intervention (early physical rehabilitation vs. standard care), resulting in "low risk of bias".					
(Schaller, 2016) ⁷⁶		Low	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	Low	High
		Patients and caregivers might be aware of allocation during intervention (early goal directed mobilisation). Per-protocol analysis. High number of missing with multiple imputation (MI), but no sensitivity analysis.					
(Fossat, 2018) ²⁹		Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
		Modified intention-to-treat analysis. Patients unblinded to intervention (muscle stimulation and leg cycling exercise vs. standard rehabilitation program); could have affected outcome assessed by patient, though not likely.					
(Denehy, 2013) ²³		Low	Some concerns	High	High	Low	High
		Unable to recruit participants in accordance with the sample size calculation. Unknown to what extent the control group received exercise. High missing without clarifying attrition by statistical analyses. As patients unblinded and aware of intervention (intensive exercise in the ICU, ward and as outpatients vs. usual care), this could have affected the HRQoL assessed.					

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
ACT-ICU (Brummel, 2014) ¹⁷		Low	Low	High	High	Low	High
Intention-to-treat. High missing (20%) without compensating statistical analyses. Patients unblinded to intervention (multi component program through hospitalisation vs. usual care).							
(Taylor, 2004) ⁹⁴	(Angus, 2006) ¹⁰	Low	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns
No comments on analysis and non-respondents not included in the analysis resulting in "some concerns". No protocol or SAP available (author replied that protocol and SAP were not routine practice at the time of the trial).							
ASOPI (Schädler, 2012) ⁹⁵	(Schädler, 2017) ⁷⁷	Low	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
Anticipated complete case analysis resulting in "some concerns". High missing (60%), no compensating statistical analyses. Patients unblinded to intervention (automated weaning group vs. control group); this knowledge could influence assessment though not likely. No protocol or SAP.							
CHEST (Myburgh, 2012) ⁹⁶	(Taylor, 2016) ⁸¹	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Intention-to-treat. Patients blinded to the intervention							
INSTINCT (Madsen, 2017) ⁵⁵		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Patients and carers blinded to the intervention. Intention-to-treat with MI for non-respondents.							
(Jones, 2015) ⁴³		Low	High	Low	High	Some concerns	High
Patients unblinded to physical intervention for 6 weeks, no information regarding intention-to-treat analysis or per protocol.							
(Matsuoka, 2015) ⁹⁷	(Noguchi, 2017) ⁶⁵	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Patients and carers blinded to the intervention.							
ABC (Girard, 2008) ⁹⁸	(Jackson, 2010) ⁴²	Low	Low	High	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
High missing (35%), patients and carers unblinded to intervention (daily spontaneous breathing), though not likely to affect the assessment. No protocol or SAP.							
TRISS (Holst, 2014) ⁹⁹	(Rygård, 2016) ⁷⁵	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
Patients unblinded (lower vs higher transfusion target), but not likely to affect the assessment.							

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
RENAL (Bellomo, 2009) ¹⁰⁰	POST-RENAL (Gallagher, 2014) ³¹	Low	High	High	Low	Low	High
		No info regarding whether deviations in intervention occurred and no information regarding intention-to-treat analysis for HRQoL. High missing (37%), patients unblinded to lower or higher haemofiltration, though unlikely to affect the assessment.					
TTM (Nielsen, 2013) ¹⁰¹	(Cronberg, 2015) ²⁰	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Patients and relatives were unblinded to intervention (higher vs lower temperature targets) while sedated. Research personal instructed the staff not to discuss allocation with relatives as they did not blind the intervention, and thereby not likely to affect the assessment.					
SAILS (Truwit, 2014) ¹⁰²	(Dinglas, 2016) ²⁴	Low	Some concerns	High	Low	Low	High
		Not described whether intention-to-treat analysis is used, but this is assumed. Patients declining or withdrawing before obtaining HRQoL follow-up were excluded leaving 272 respondents out of 745 randomised (including nonsurvivors, why no calculation in percentages of these). So, excluding those declining/withdrawing before follow-up left the 13% missing falsely 'few' missing HRQoL data.					
(Azevedo, 2019) ¹²		Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
		Patients unblinded, but on mechanical ventilation during the intervention, and did presumably not affect the assessment. No protocol or SAP.					
(Antonelli, 2005) ¹¹		Low	High	High	Low	Some concerns	High
		Not clear whether intention-to-treat or per-protocol, no consort diagram to conclude from. High missing (54%).					
(Marasco, 2013) ⁵⁷		Low	Low	Low	High	Some concerns	High
		Patients aware of allocation. Intervention was operative or conservative fixation of rib fractures, so the patient felt the surgery and thereby likely to have affected the assessment. No SAP or protocol.					
6S (Perner, 2012) ¹⁰³	(Wittbrodt, 2013) ⁸⁹	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns
		High missing (40%), though probably not depending on its true value supported by multiple imputation and best/worst case analyses and worst/best case analysis interpreted not to influence the results.					
Freeman-Sanderson, 2016) ³⁰		High	Low	High	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
		Difference in age and gender (small trial). Number of missing NA. Patients awake while receiving intervention (cuff-deflation vs. control received) – they could be aware of the allocation but presumably unlikely to affect the assessment. No protocol or SAP.					

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
(Van Mastrigt, 2006) ⁸³		Low	High	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
		Deviation from intended intervention – not possible to transfer patients as intended. Patients unblinded towards short stay (8h) vs stay overnight. Likely to know the allocation though unlikely to affect the assessment. No protocol or SAP.					
HARP-2 (McAuley, 2014) ¹⁰⁴	(Agus, 2017) ⁶	Low	Low	High	Low	Low	High
		High missing (51%)					
LOGIC-2 (Dubois, 2017) ²⁷		Low	Low	High	Low	Low	High
		Number of missing NA and thereby unclear what to answer for domain 3. Patients unblinded to intervention (blood-glucose control) – probably not affecting the assessment.					
(Van den Berghe, 2001) ¹⁰⁵	(Ingels, 2006) ⁴⁰	Low	Low	High	Low	Some concerns	High
		High missing (25%) without any strategy for further analyses. Patients unblinded to intervention (intensive vs. conventional insulin treatment). No protocol or SAP.					
ABLE (Lacroix, 2015) ¹⁰⁶	(Walsh, 2017) ⁸⁷	Low	Low	High	Low	Some concerns	High
		High missing with MI, but no sensitivity analysis. No protocol or SAP.					
Nephro-Protective (Doig, 2015) ¹⁰⁷	(Zhu, 2018) ⁹³	Low	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns
		The patients were unblinded, but probably not aware of their allocation. No comments on handling of trial medication. In the SAP a sensitivity analysis was planned if more than 1% HRQoL was missing. These data are not found in the paper or supplements.					
(Kurtoglu, 2015) ⁴⁵		High	High	High	High	Some concerns	High
		Sequence not random and not clear how they secure concealment of the sequence. Unclear whether intention-to-treat or per-protocol and no consort diagram to conclude from. Number of missing NA. Non blinded assessment and patient consent obtained before intervention (neuromuscular stimulation vs. control group in 10 days) – so patients were probably aware of intervention. No protocol or SAP.					
EPICC (Wright, 2017) ⁹⁰		Low	Low	High	High	Low	High
		High missing (34-45% depending on timepoint), but efforts done to limit bias (MI) and comparing respondents vs. nonrespondents), but it is still unlikely that nonrespondents were MAR. Patients unblinded to intervention (intensive vs. standard rehabilitation at ICU) and assessment at discharge, day 90 and 180 so may possibly affect the assessment.					

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
TOP-Up (Wischmeyer, 2017) ⁸⁸		Low	Low	High	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
		Missing NA (tried contact with author). Patients unblinded though not likely that it would affect the assessment. No protocol or SAP.					
(Giraud, 2016) ³⁴		Low	Low	Low	High	Low	High
		Participant gave consent to the trial before intervention (structured mirrors intervention vs. usual care), so likely aware of allocation and follow-up assessment at 12 weeks – so shortly after ICU.					
(Amundadottir, 2019) ⁹		Low	Some concerns	Low	High	Some concerns	High
		No information about deviation from intended intervention or information regarding intention-to-treat, but likely ITT according to consort and tables. Patients unblinded and probably aware of group allocation. Intervention was mobilisation twice daily compared with just daily mobilisation. High risk as the patients assessed HRQoL at day 90, 180 and 365. No protocol or SAP.					
(Deane, 2020) ²²		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Low number of nonrespondents, intention-to-treat and patients blinded to the intervention.					
(de Azevedo, 2021) ²¹		Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
		“No intention-to-treat due to many exclusions after randomisation”, though it seems like they used ITT. Patients not blinded to intervention. No protocol or SAP.					
(Fan, 2021) ²⁸		Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	High	Some concerns	High
		No wording regarding sequence concealment or randomisation, author asked – also regarding protocol/SAP and consort diagram – assume no missing. Patients and carers? Blinded to the intervention with psychological preparation – aware of intervention received with assessment of HRQoL after intervention.					
ADRENAL (Venkatesh, 2018) ¹⁰⁸	(Hammond, 2020) ³⁶	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Assessor (patient) of HRQoL was blinded to the intervention. Missing less than 20%.					
TRANSFUSE (Cooper, 2017) ¹⁰⁹	(Irving, 2019) ⁴¹	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Assessor (patient) of HRQoL was blinded to the intervention. Missing less than 20%.					

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
(Liu, 2021) ⁵³		High	Some concerns	High	High	Low	High
		Significant difference in baseline characteristics; could be due to small sample size. Refusal rate high at 1- and 3-month surveys; in the paper hence, they only analysed baseline and 1-week post intervention surveys were analysed. Patients aware of intervention (family-clinician shared decision-making vs standard care) and assessed HRQoL day 7, which likely affected assessment of outcome.					
(Mao, 2020) ⁵⁶		Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	High	Some concerns	High
		Only two baseline characteristics presented, and randomisation was performed according to a random number table. No consort diagram/transparency in the patient flow, but according to table 2 no missing. Patients likely aware of intervention (empowerment nursing for 1 month) with HRQoL assessment day 42. No protocol or SAP.					
(Martin, 2021) ⁵⁸		Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
		Deviations of intervention not clear. Patients could be aware of the intervention (speaking valve or not) as they gave consent before intervention and the assessment could be close to the intervention (not known), though unlikely to affect the assessment, resulting in "some concerns".					
(Mou, 2020) ⁶²		Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
		Patients randomly divided, but no other details regarding the sequence or method. No transparency in patient flow or blinding. Patients were allocated to systematic vs routine nursing and assessment at hospital discharge could influence assessment, though not likely.					
CYCLIST (Nickels, 2020) ⁶³		Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
		Patients gave consent before randomisation to in-bed cycling in addition to usual care vs. usual care. Assessment at hospital discharge could influence assessment though unlikely.					
DRIP-study (Nielsen, 2020) ⁶⁴		Low	High	High	High	Low	High
		Not intention-to-treat, high missing (28%) without transparency in the analyses, likely aware of intervention (diary written by relatives vs. none) which were to be shared with the patient after discharge.					
NONSEDA (Olsen, 2020) ¹¹⁰	(Olsen, 2021) ⁶⁶	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
		Likely deviation in intended intervention (non-sedation), where patients received more sedation than intended. HRQoL not addressed as an outcome in the protocol, no information regarding analyses.					

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
(Pandian, 2020) ⁶⁷		Low	Some concerns	Low	High	Some concerns	High
No transparency in whether intention-to-treat or not. Patients likely aware of intervention (either early tracheostomy with speech language pathologist consultations or tracheostomy one week later), and assessment after 1 and 5 days. Deviation in primary outcome between clinicaltrials.gov and manuscript. No SAP or protocol.							
(Perkins, 2019) ⁶⁹		Low	Low	High	Some concerns	Low	High
High missing (19-43%) with multiple imputation, but only for QALYs. Outcome assessor (patient) not blinded to NIV weaning or invasive weaning, so they could be aware of allocation, though unlikely.							
REDUCE (van den Boogaard, 2018) ¹¹¹	(Rood, 2019) ⁷²	Low	Low	High	Low	Low	High
Transparency in high missing (29%), but complete case analysis.							
(Viana, 2021) ⁸⁴		Low	High	High	Low	Some concerns	High
No information regarding analysis in domain 2. No transparency in missing data including death.							
(Waldauf, 2021) ⁸⁶		Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
Patients not blinded to intervention (progressive mobility program vs. routine practice for 28 days or discharge), which could affect the assessment, though not likely as the patients likely did not remember the allocation after 180 days.							
(Xu, 2021) ⁹¹		Some concerns	High	High	Some concerns	Some concerns	High
No transparency in sequence concealment. No transparency in analysis used and only complete cases included in the trial. No transparency in missing. Patients aware of intervention as consent given before allocation. This could have affected the assessment, although not likely. No SAP or protocol.							
(Zeng, 2021) ⁹²		Some concerns	High	High	High	Some concerns	High
No transparency in sequence concealment. No consort diagram and number of patients increases in the follow-up – unlikely intention-to-treat analysis. No transparency in missing – 120% of patients replied. Intervention either humanised care or routine care, which could affect the assessment, and likely would, due to assessment at day 14.							
(Morris, 2016) ¹¹²		Low	Low	High	High	Low	High
High missing (21-31%). Patients aware of intervention (standardised rehabilitation therapy for 7 weeks through hospital discharge vs. usual care).							

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
KyberSept (Warren, 2001) ¹¹³	(Ruble, 2002) ⁷⁴	Some concerns	Low	High	Low	Some concerns	High
		No wording regarding sequence concealment or intention-to-treat and no consort diagram, resulting in “some concerns”. No transparency in missing. No protocol or SAP.					
COACT (Lemkes, 2019) ¹¹⁴	(Lemkes, 2020) ⁵¹	Low	Low	High	High	Low	High
		High missing and patients likely aware of intervention (angiography either immediate at the ICU or delayed at the general ward), which could affect the assessment.					
ICU-ROX (Mackle, 2020) ⁵⁴		Low	Low	High	Some concerns	Low	High
		High missing (21%) with no clarifying analyses. Patient unblinded and assessor, although unlikely to influence outcome.					
STARRT-AKI (Bagshaw, 2020) ¹³		Low	Low	High	Some concerns	Low	High
		High missing (30-33%) with no clarifying analyses. Patient unblinded and assessor, although unlikely to influence outcome.					
CHARLI (Dixon, 2021) ²⁵		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Double-blinded trial and with rather low missing (6-8.5%)					
VIOLET (Ginde, 2019) ³³		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Double-blinded trial. Missing 18.9%, i.e., below the arbitrary limit.					
MENDS2 (Hughes, 2021) ³⁹		Low	Low	High	Low	Low	High
		Double-blinded. High missing (22%). Stated MI though not able to locate where this was conducted why some concerns.					
65-trial (Lamontagne, 2020) ⁴⁷		Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns
		Lack of transparency in missing; could be either 15 or 20%, resulting in “some concerns”. Non-blinded assessors though knowledge of allocation seems unlikely to have influenced the outcome.					
SEPSIS-ACT (Laterre, 2019) ⁴⁹		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Double-blinded trial. Missing 19%.					
ROCIT (Litton, 2021) ⁵²		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Double blinded with 6% missing.					

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
VITdAL-ICU (Amrein, 2014) ⁸		Low	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns
		Double-blinded. Some concerns as no words about outcomes to obtain at 6 months follow-up in wither protocol or SAP, only mentioned in main manuscript.					
ROSE (Moss, 2019) ⁶¹		Low	Some concerns	High	Low	Low	High
		High missing (31%) and only reported missing for one timepoint out of 3. No further analyses. Non-blinded trial could affect the assessment of the outcome, though not likely as the intervention was Cisatracurium infusion, which is not a prominent intervention directly to the patient.					
(Parke, 2021) ⁶⁸		Low	Some concerns	High	Low	Low	High
		No information regarding deviations from intended intervention. No transparency in missing. Participants blinded.					
STOP-AKI (Pickkers, 2018) ⁷⁰		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Low missing (3%), though no transparency in how many relatives assessed HRQoL. Double-blinded.					
(Ridley, 2018) ⁷¹		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Seems like low number of missing though not transparent and discrepancy between number of respondents + dead vs. number of participants. Patients unblinded, but knowledge of the intervention (early goal nutrition vs standard care) seems unlikely to affect the outcome after 6 months, why only some concerns for bias.					
COBI (Roquilly, 2021) ⁷³		Low	Low	High	Low	Low	High
		High missing (22-34%) without any comments or further analyses. Patient unblinded to intervention (hyperton fluids vs. placebo), which seems unlikely to have influenced the outcome.					
SPICE III (Shehabi, 2019) ⁷⁸		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
		Double-blinded. Missing 16.6%, i.e., though below the arbitrary limit.					
POPPI (Wade, 2019) ⁸⁵		Low	Some concerns	High	High	Low	High
		Randomised at site level (cluster RCT), high missing (>20%). They did multiple imputation and sensitivity analysis and interpreted missing as MAR. The high number of missing results in "high ROB". Only patients with GCS 15, able to give consent and well cognitive functioning were included to either a nurse-led preventive psychological intervention or usual care, resulting in "high ROB" due to awareness of allocation.					

Trial acronym (author)	Secondary analysis (author)	1. Randomisation process	2. Deviations from the intended intervention	3. Missing outcome data	4. Measurement of the outcome	5. Selection of the reported result	Overall risk of bias
AdrenOSS-2 (Laterre, 2021) ⁵⁰		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
No wording regarding the randomisation process or concealment. Missing 16%. Double-blinded.							
COVID STEROID 2 (Munch, 2021) ¹¹⁵	(Granholm, 2022) ³⁵	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Missing 6%. Double-blinded. N=73 relatives answered HRQoL, but the distribution between the groups were not transparent.							
RADAR-2 (Silversides, 2022) ⁷⁹		Low	Low	High	Some concerns	Low	High
Missing >20% without further clarification or considerations. Patients unblinded to fluid therapy which could affect the outcome, but not likely.							
HOT-ICU (Schjørring, 2021) ¹¹⁶	(Crescioli, 2022) ¹⁹	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns
Missing 19.8%. Patients unblinded to oxygenation target, which could affect the assessment, although not likely.							
MUST-ARDS (Bellingan, 2022) ¹⁴		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Double-blinded. High missing (29%) day 28, but for long-term follow-up only 12% missing, resulting in "low ROB" as patients partly could not assess their HRQoL at day 28.							
(Campos, 2022) ¹⁸		Some concerns	High	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	High
Unblinded trial, unclear if allocation sequence was concealed. Primary analysis was per-protocol. No transparency in number of non-respondents or non-survivors. Knowledge of allocation could have affected the assessment as the intervention was rehabilitation, i.e. the allocation was likely known. The assessment was done at ICU and hospital discharge, so patients were likely to have remembered allocation.							
IMPROVE (Bisset, 2022) ¹⁵		Low	Low	High	Low	Low	High
Intention-to-treat analysis. Number of non-respondents is not transparent, resulting in "NI" and thereby "high ROB" for domain 3. Patients unblinded to either inspiratory muscle training vs control group while intubated. Assessment at baseline and day 7 after extubation, why it seems unlikely that the patient was aware of allocation. No SAP.							
LOVIT (Lamontagne, 2022) ⁴⁸		Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Double blinded. Intention-to-treat analysis and low missing 6.5%.							
REST trial (McNamee, 2021) ¹¹⁷	(Boyle, 2022) ¹⁶	Low	Low	High	Some concerns	Low	High
High missing at 1-year follow-up (44%), no data for 6 months follow-up. Patients unblinded to lower tidal volume vs standard care, which could have affected the outcome, but unlikely.							

Checklist (PRISMA 2020)

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Page 1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Page 3
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Page 3
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Page 4
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Page 4
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Supplement page 5
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 4-5
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 5
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Page 5

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Page 5
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 5 and supplement page 19
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Not relevant
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item 5)).	Page 4
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Page 6
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Supplement page 5 and 19
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Page 6
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Page 6
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Not relevant
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Page 5 and supplement page 179
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Not relevant
RESULTS			

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Page 8 and supplement page 3
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	Page 8 and supplement page 3
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Supplement page 7
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Supplement page 179
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Not relevant
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	Not relevant
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Page 7 and 8
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Table 3
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Not relevant
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Figure 2 and Table S5
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Not relevant
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Page 9
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Page 9
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Page 10

Topic	No.	Item	Location where item is reported
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Page 10 and 11
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	Page 4
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	Page 4
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	Supplement page 2
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Page 11
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Page 1
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Supplement

Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, Shamseer L, Tetzlaff JM, Akl EA, Brennan SE, Chou R, Glanville J, Grimshaw JM, Hróbjartsson A, Lalu MM, Li T, Loder EW, Mayo-Wilson E, McDonald S, McGuinness LA, Stewart LA, Thomas J, Tricco AC, Welch VA, Whiting P, Moher D. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021; 372: n71.²

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PAPER III

Long-term patient-important outcomes after septic shock: A protocol for 1-year follow-up of the CLASSIC trial

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Long-term patient-important outcomes after septic shock: A protocol for 1-year follow-up of the CLASSIC trial

Maj-Brit N. Kjær^{1,2}

¹Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

²Centre for Research in Intensive Care (CRIC), Copenhagen, Denmark

³Copenhagen Trial Unit, Centre for Clinical Intervention Research, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

⁴Section of Biostatistics, Department of Public Health, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

⁵Section of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Department of Clinical Science and Education, Södersjukhuset, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

⁶Division of Emergencies and Critical Care, Department of Anaesthesiology, Oslo University Hospital, Rikshospitalet, Oslo, Norway

⁷Department of Intensive Care Medicine, University Hospital Bern (Inselspital), University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland

⁸Medical Intensive Care Unit, 1. Interni klinika, Fakultni Nemocnice, Plzen, Czech Republic

⁹Division of Intensive Care Medicine, Department of Anaesthesiology, Intensive Care and Pain Medicine, Helsinki University Hospital, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

¹⁰Department of Intensive Care, Maastricht University Medical Center+, University Maastricht, Maastricht, The Netherlands

¹¹Department of Intensive Care, Guy's and St Thomas' Hospital, London, UK

¹²Clinical Trial Unit, Intensive Care National Audit & Research Centre (ICNARC), London, UK

¹³Department of Intensive Care Medicine, Humanitas Research Hospital, Milan, Italy

¹⁴Department of Intensive Care, Hospital Vall d'Hebron, Barcelona, Spain

¹⁵Department of Intensive Care Medicine, University Hospital Brussels (UZB), Jette, Belgium

¹⁶Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Brussels, Belgium

¹⁷Department of Perioperative Medicine and Intensive Care, Karolinska University Hospital Huddinge, Stockholm, Sweden

¹⁸Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Bispebjerg, Copenhagen, Denmark

¹⁹Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Nordsjællands Hospital, University Hospital of Copenhagen, Hillerød, Denmark

²⁰Department of Clinical Medicine, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

²¹Department of Intensive Care, Gentofte Hospital, Gentofte, Denmark

²²Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Zealand University Hospital, Køge, Denmark

²³Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Zealand University Hospital, Roskilde, Denmark

²⁴Copenhagen Academy for Medical Education and Simulation, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

²⁵Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Randers Hospital, Randers, Denmark

²⁶Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Viborg Hospital, Viborg, Denmark

²⁷Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Lillebælt Hospital, Kolding, Denmark

²⁸Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark

Correspondence

Maj-Brit N. Kjær, Department of Intensive Care 4131, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Blegdamsvej 9, DK-2100 Copenhagen, Denmark.
Email: maj-brit.noerregaard.kjaer@regionh.dk

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Background: In patients with septic shock, mortality is high, and survivors experience long-term physical, mental and social impairments. The ongoing Conservative vs Liberal Approach to fluid therapy of Septic Shock in Intensive Care (CLASSIC) trial assesses the benefits and harms of a restrictive vs standard-care intravenous (IV) fluid therapy. The hypothesis is that IV fluid restriction improves patient-important long-term outcomes.

Aim: To assess the predefined patient-important long-term outcomes in patients randomised into the CLASSIC trial.

Methods: In this pre-planned follow-up study of the CLASSIC trial, we will assess all-cause mortality, health-related quality of life (HRQoL) and cognitive function 1 year after randomisation in the two intervention groups. The 1-year mortality will be collected from electronic patient records or central national registries in most participating countries. We will contact survivors and assess EuroQol 5-Dimension, -5-Level (EQ-5D-5L) and EuroQol-Visual Analogue Scale and Montreal Cognitive Assessment 5-minute protocol score. We will analyse mortality by logistic regression and use general linear models to assess HRQoL and cognitive function.

Discussion: With this pre-planned follow-up study of the CLASSIC trial, we will provide patient-important data on long-term survival, HRQoL and cognitive function of restrictive vs standard-care IV fluid therapy in patients with septic shock.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Sepsis is a syndrome with a dysregulated host response to an infection; in the most severe cases, septic shock, multiple organ failure and death are frequent.¹ Sepsis contributes to every third hospital death.² Patients surviving septic shock often have long-term physical, psychological and cognitive disabilities with health-related and social implications.³⁻⁷ Any improvement in the treatment of septic shock is estimated to have a significant impact on public health and health economy.³

Intravenous (IV) fluid therapy is a recommend key intervention in septic shock; however, the evidence on how to manage fluids in these intensive care unit (ICU) setting is of low quality.^{6,8,9} Therefore, the ongoing multi-centre, randomised clinical trial (RCT) 'The Conservative vs Liberal Approach to fluid therapy of Septic Shock in Intensive Care' (CLASSIC) assesses the benefits and harms of IV fluid restriction vs standard-care in adult ICU patients with septic shock.¹⁰

1.1 | Health-related quality of life

Health-related quality of life (HRQoL) is the most frequently used patient-reported outcome measure (PROM) for patients surviving critical illness in ICU.¹¹⁻¹³ HRQoL instruments offer a comprehensive multidimensional approach assessing physical, mental and social domains and an overall perceived health state.^{14,15} The HRQoL measure is, therefore, an important outcome measure in addition to survival.¹⁵

Most often HRQoL is assessed in ICU survivors using generic, non-disease-specific instruments, most frequently, the Short Form 36-item questionnaire or the EuroQol 5 dimension scale (EQ-5D).¹³ The EQ-5D is a short HRQoL questionnaire including domains on mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression.¹⁶ The EQ-5D is considered validated to be used for follow-up in ICU trials to assess self-perceived HRQoL,¹⁷⁻²⁰ and is recommended as a core outcome measure in this setting.²¹ The EQ-5D comes in two versions: a 3-level and a 5-level version. The EQ-5D in five levels (EQ-5D-5L) is to be answered together with an EQ-Visual Analogue Scale (EQ-VAS), the latter being a range for worst to best imaginable health state.¹⁶

1.2 | Cognitive function

Long-term cognitive impairment after critical illness is defined as the neuropsychological changes that tend to persist and cause deficits of a magnitude that impair daily function.²² The incidence of cognitive impairment after sepsis has been reported to range from 4% to 62%.^{23,24} Both physical and cognitive impairment after intensive care are likely modifiable outcomes²⁵ as well as being outcomes reported as important to patients who survived acute respiratory failure.²⁶

The Montreal Outcome Assessment (MoCA) is a validated tool to assess cognitive function.²⁷ The full MoCA score is based on face-to-face interviews, but these are challenging to perform in large trials. The Mini MoCA refers to the MoCA 5-minute protocol,²⁸ previously validated in stroke patients, consisting of five cognitive domains

from the full MoCA for assessing mild cognitive impairment.²⁸ The five domains are attention, verbal learning and memory, executive function/language and orientation covered by four subtests.²⁸

1.3 | Fluid trials for patients with septic shock measuring 1-year follow-up

A systematic review and meta-analysis, assessing lower vs higher fluid volumes in patients with septic shock, including nine trials, are in review.²⁹ None of these nine trials assessed long-term patient-important outcomes like HRQoL or cognitive function.

In the Fluid and Catheters Treatment Trial (FACTT), patients with acute lunge injury were randomised to conservative vs standard fluid therapy after the initial management.³⁰ In an adjunct study to the FACTT trial, a potential association between the conservative fluid-management strategy and long-term cognitive impairment was found in survivors²⁵ when assessed after 12 months by a validated neurocognitive telephone test.^{25,31} The authors could not explain the result by reduced cerebral perfusion (eg cardiac index, systolic blood pressure) and encouraged further research to validate this result.²⁵

There are at least two ongoing restricted vs standard IV fluid trials in patients with sepsis/septic shock; the Crystalloid Liberal Or Vasopressor Early Resuscitation in Sepsis (CLOVERS) trial follows patients until day 90 with in-hospital mortality as primary outcome,³² and the CLASSIC trial follows patients until 1 year, assessing mortality, HRQoL and cognitive function.¹⁰ The CLASSIC trial seems to be the only trial measuring long-term patient-important outcomes.¹⁰

1.4 | Aim

To assess the predefined patient-important, long-term outcomes in patients randomised in the CLASSIC trial.

1.5 | Hypothesis

The hypothesis is that IV fluid restriction will improve survival, HRQoL and cognitive function after septic shock.

2 | METHOD

2.1 | The CLASSIC trial

CLASSIC is an ongoing investigator-initiated, international, parallel-grouped, randomised 1:1 by a computer-generated allocation sequence list, stratified, analyst-blinded trial (NCT03668236). In the CLASSIC trial, we assess the benefits and harms of restricted vs standard-care IV fluid therapy in adult ICU patients with septic shock, stratified for haematological or metastatic cancer (yes/

no) and trial site.¹⁰ The protocol and statistical analysis plan (SAP) for the 90-day follow-up have been published.¹⁰ The planned sample size is 1554 patients. The first patient was enrolled on 27 November 2018, and the last patient is expected on 27 November 2020, with 1-year follow-up of the last patient by 27 November 2021.

The primary outcome is mortality at day 90 and secondary outcomes are serious adverse events, serious adverse reactions, days alive at day 90 without life support, days alive and out of hospital at day 90, and mortality, HRQoL and cognitive function at 1 year.

2.2 | Study design

This is a pre-planned long-term follow-up study assessing secondary outcomes of the CLASSIC trial. The staff assessing HRQoL and cognitive function and the statistician will be blinded to the trial allocation.

2.3 | Study population

All patients randomised in the CLASSIC trial for whom there is obtained consent to carry out 1-year follow-up.

2.3.1 | Inclusion criteria

All the following criteria must be met:

- Aged 18 years or above
- Admitted to the ICU or plan to be admitted to the ICU regardless of trial participation
- Septic shock defined according to the Sepsis-3 criteria¹:
 - Suspected or confirmed site of infection or positive blood culture AND
 - Ongoing infusion of vasopressor/inotrope agent to maintain a mean arterial blood pressure of 65 mmHg or above AND
 - Lactate of 2 mmol/L or above in any plasma sample performed within the last 3 hours
- Have received at least 1 L of IV fluid (crystalloids, colloids or blood products) in the last 24 hours prior to screening.

2.3.2 | Exclusion criteria

Patients who meet any of the following criteria will be excluded:

- Septic shock for more than 12 hours at the time of screening
- Life-threatening bleeding
- Acute burn injury of more than 10% of the body surface area
- Known pregnancy
- Consent not obtainable

2.4 | Outcomes at 1-year follow-up

- All-cause mortality
- HRQoL measured by the EQ-5D-5L and EQ-VAS
- Cognitive function as assessed by the Mini MoCA

2.5 | Ethical approval

The CLASSIC trial is registered at the European Clinical Trials Database (2018-000404-42) and www.clinicaltrials.gov (NCT03668236), is approved by the Danish Medicines Agency (2018020596), the Ethics Committee of the Capital Region (H-18006255) and the Danish Data Protection Agency (VD-2018-392) and by the relevant authorities for all participating sites. Written informed consent will be obtained for all patients when regained mental capacity.

2.6 | Protection of data

At enrolment, each patient receives a unique trial identification number in the electronic case report form (eCRF). All data will be obtained from patient files and national registers and recorded in a secured web-based eCRF. Data are managed electronically in the eCRF by trained trial personnel and will be handled according to the National Data Protection Agency and protected by the Danish national laws.^{33,34}

2.7 | Workflow

We will introduce a standard operating procedure (SOP) to be followed for all patients to motivate a high response rate and uniform data collection.^{35,36} Patients withdrawn from the intervention who have accepted further data registration will be contacted for the 1-year follow-up.

2.7.1 | Obtaining survival status

We will obtain 1-year survival status for all patients. One-year mortality post-randomisation will be obtained by registry for all Danish patients. At the sites in other countries, it will be obtained as most feasible for the country. If the patient has deceased, date of death will be registered.

2.7.2 | Telephone interviews

Each site will conduct telephone interviews with all survivors at 1-year post-randomisation (allowing four additional weeks to increase the likelihood of response). Each site must secure that the personnel, who contacts the patients, is blinded to the trial allocation.

2.7.3 | Obtaining Mini MoCA

Every site will receive a version of the Mini MoCA in their language and the SOP on how to obtain the Mini MoCA. To increase consistency, all assessors will obtain training and certification according to the recommendations of MoCA Clinic & Institute. It is important to start the interview with the Mini MoCA to ensure this is completed, in case the patient gets tired. Also, it is important that the patient is placed in a quiet room with no other people (to avoid noise and help) and not facing a calendar due to a question concerning orientation in the cognitive function score.³⁷ The Mini MoCA²⁸ can only be answered by the patient directly by phone and not by proxy. If the Mini MoCA has not been released for use at the time of the first assessment (1 year after randomisation of the first patient), we will adapt the Mini MoCA from the MoCA full v. 7.1 with acceptance from the author.

2.7.4 | Obtaining EQ-5D-5L

Every participating site will receive a version of the questionnaire in their language and the SOP on how to obtain the EQ-5D-5L. The EQ-5D-5L and the EQ-VAS scores can be obtained by phone, as we recommend, or by mail, if the patient prefers this. If the patient is not cognitively able to participate, we will ask a relevant proxy to answer.¹⁵ There is a proxy version of the EQ-5D-5L in all languages needed for the trial. In this version, the proxy is asked to rate the patients' HRQoL in their (the proxies) opinion.

2.8 | Statistical analyses

We will conduct all analyses in the intention-to-treat (ITT) population defined as all randomised patients for whom there is consent for the use of data. If the distribution of HRQoL and Mini MoCA deviates substantially from the normal distribution, the primary analysis will be adjusted for the stratification variable of sites using Van Elteren test for differences of medians between groups. If the distribution of HRQoL and Mini MoCA comes close to a normal distribution or if the distribution of the log-transformed data comes close to a normal distribution, we perform multiple linear regression adjusted for both the stratification variable of sites and haematological malignancy.

In the two intervention groups, we will assess any differences in:

- One-year mortality using two-tailed logistic regression adjusted for the stratification variables. Odds ratio will be converted to relative risks (computed using generalised linear model (GLM) with appropriate link functions and binomial error distribution), to consistently report the latter. We will present a Kaplan-Meier curve for the crude data.
- EQ-5D-5L, EQ-VAS and Mini MoCA scores using a GLM or non-parametric test stratified for site (rating and calculation are described in the Supplemental File S1). We have considered the challenge of handling patients 'truncated due to death' when analysing functional

outcomes in trials.³⁸ In consensus, we decided to assume that death is worse than a low HRQoL or low cognitive function score. Patients who are dead at 1-year follow-up will therefore be assigned the worst possible value (a value of zero). This will make these data non-normally distributed. We will, therefore, compare the groups using the method of Lange and Kryger Jensen; the probability of having a zero will be modelled using a logistic regression while the mean value among the non-zero values will be modelled using linear regression.³⁹ A joint test for no treatment effect will be reported.

- The scores of the single sub-domains of the EQ-5D-5L and the Mini MoCA will be presented in a supplement.

With 2×777 patients and a control event rate of 55% for the mortality at 1-year,^{40,41} we will have an 80% statistical power to detect a 15% relative risk reduction in the fluid restriction group vs the standard-care group with a type 1 error level of 1%. The estimates of the control event rates originate from data of previous septic shock trials.^{40,41} We expect HRQoL and cognitive function at 1-year to be highly skewed (non-normally distributed). As we lack knowledge on the details of the distribution, no realistic power analysis can be provided. We therefore refrain from this to avoid creating a false impression of precision. We will also conduct sensitivity analyses of EQ-5D-5L and Mini MoCA in the survivors only.

2.8.1 | Significance

We will provide 99% confidence intervals (CI) between means (if data are nearly normally distributed) or otherwise between medians (by bootstrapping). We will present the results as adjusted absolute and relative risk differences, computed using GLMs with appropriate link functions and binomial error distribution, using 99% CIs for the secondary outcomes (P -value .01) due to the multiplicity of these as stated in the CLASSIC protocol.¹⁰

2.8.2 | Patients with missing data

Patients who die before 1-year follow-up will not create missingness. The following are the reasons for having missing data:

- Lost to follow-up (missing vital status and the EQ-5D-5L, EQ-VAS and the Mini MoCA data)
- Patients known to be alive who cannot be contacted or do not respond (missing EQ-5D-5L and Mini MoCA data).

We will obtain the reasons for missing data (Supplemental File S2); these will be described in the main manuscript and presented in Supporting Information. If data in the completed questionnaires are missing exclusively for the outcome of EQ-5D-5L and the Mini MoCA in less than 5% or more than 40% of patients, or data are missing completely at random (MCAR) with a negative Little's test ($P > .05$), we will not impute missing data.⁴²

If data are missing for outcomes in more than 5% and less than 40% of the patients, data will be imputed using multiple imputation (MI) assuming data missing at random (MAR); 50 imputed data sets will be generated. If MI is considered necessary, aggregated analyses of the imputed data sets will be calculated. However, assuming data missing not at random (MNAR), we will conduct analyses as best-worse and worse-best scenarios where data from missing response from survivors will be imputed using the mean ± 1 standard deviation of the EQ-5D-5L and Mini MoCA in patients with complete data.⁴²

3 | DISCUSSION

With this long-term follow-up study, we aim to establish how restrictive vs standard-care IV fluid therapy affects long-term patient-important outcomes in adult patients with septic shock. The strength of our study includes being based on a large international RCT, which aims to provide us with high-quality evidence and with lowest possible risk of bias. The protocol for the CLASSIC trial, including the long-term follow-up after 1 year, and SAP was defined and published prior to the end of the trial.¹⁰

The limitations of our long-term follow-up include lack of a baseline EQ-5D-5L or MoCA score, which can lead to a potential baseline imbalance in HRQoL and cognitive function, which may be present but undetected. The Mini MoCA is not validated for critically ill patients and it only detects mild cognitive impairment. Patients surviving sepsis may have long-term moderate to severe cognitive impairment.⁴ Therefore, cognitive impairment could potentially be underestimated with the Mini MoCA score. We will evaluate the use of the Mini MoCA tool, which, to our knowledge, has not previously been used in a RCT as long-term outcome in critically ill patients. Furthermore, evaluation of a simple and short tool measuring an important patient outcome will add significant value for future research.

4 | CONCLUSION

We will assess HRQoL and cognitive function 1 year after patients with septic shock have been included in the CLASSIC trial. This will provide us with essential knowledge of long-term benefits and/or harms of restrictive IV fluid therapy vs standard-care.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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PUBLICATION

The results of the long-term follow-up of the CLASSIC trial will be published in a peer-reviewed journal.

ORCID

Maj-Brit N. Kjær <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6536-0504>

Tine S. Meyhoff <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1840-1596>

Martin B. Madsen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5832-2262>

Morten Hylander Møller <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6378-9673>

[org/0000-0002-6378-9673](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6378-9673)

Jon H. Laake <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6157-5359>

Ville Pettilä <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3921-4423>

Lene Russell <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7352-8728>

Anders Perner <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4668-0123>

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section.

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Supplemental file S1. Description of the Mini MoCA and the EQ-5D-5L

Mini MoCA

The Mini MoCA refers to MoCA 5 minute protocol and has been validated for telephone interview in stroke patients.³⁷ The Mini MoCA score ranges from 0-30. There are 4 subtests examining 5 cognitive domains:

1. Attention: Immediate recall of 5 words, 1 point for each word (0-5 points).
2. Executive function/language. 1-minute verbal fluency, 0.5 point for each correct input (0-9 points)
3. Orientation. 6-item date and geographic orientation, 1 point for each correct response (0-6 points)
4. Memory. Delayed recall and recognition of 5 words learned in item 1; 2 points for each of the word spontaneously recalled and 1 point for each word by cued recall or recognition but not spontaneously recalled (0-10 points).³⁷

The questionnaire also obtains age and years of education as these are important covariates for the score.^{42,43} Among patients with stroke age is negatively correlated with the total cognitive function score by the Mini MoCA -and positively correlated with years of education, but not with gender.²⁸

The MoCA Institute and Clinic's definition of years of education implies all years of formal education including primary school. The number of years does not refer to an education level; for example, it does not refer to individuals that have or have not completed high school. Years of home schooling are included if the governmental program was followed. Work trainings and courses are not included in the count.

If the patient has less than 12 years of education and scores less than 30 points, an extra point will be added to the final score. The results will be presented in means +/- standard deviation.

EQ-5D-5L

The EQ-5D-5L consists of 5 domains and the EQ-VAS. Each domain has 5 levels and for each domain the patient will be given a score from 1-5; 1. No problems, 2. Slight problems, 3. Moderate problems, 4. Severe problems, and 5. Extreme problems. The response will end up as a 5-digit code that can be converted to an index value. The index value reflects how good or bad the health state is compared to the preferences of the general population of a country.⁴⁴ EQ-5D-5L index ranges from 0-1.00 and EQ-VAS ranges from 0-100, where 100 equals the best imaginable health state.¹⁶ The minimal clinically important difference is not known for ICU survivors at 1-year follow-up as this has not yet been investigated.⁴⁵

Supplemental file S2. Reasons for lost to follow-up

	n=	Restrictive IV fluid therapy n=	Standard IV fluid therapy n=
Consent withdrawn/Not given			
Unable to get hold of the patient			
Patient did not wish to participate			
Other*			

*will be summarised in text.

CONSORT 2010 checklist of information to include when reporting a randomised trial*

Section/Topic	Item No	Checklist item	Reported on page No
Title and abstract			
	1a	Identification as a randomised trial in the title	8.1
	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstracts)	8.1
Introduction			
Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	5
	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	7
Methods			
Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	8
	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	not relevant
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	8
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	8
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	8
	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	9
Sample size	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	not relevant
	7a	How sample size was determined	12
Randomisation:	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	not relevant
	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	8
Sequence generation	8b	Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	8
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	N.R.
	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	8
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those	8

	assessing outcomes) and how		N.R
11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions		N.R
12a	Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes		10
12b	Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses		10
Results			
13a	Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)	For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	N.R
13b	Recruitment	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	N.R
14a		Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	8
14b		Why the trial ended or was stopped	N.R.
15	Baseline data	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	Protocol
16	Numbers analysed	For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups	N.R
17a	Outcomes and estimation	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)	N.R
17b		For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended	N.R
18	Ancillary analyses	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	N.R
19	Harms	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	N.R
Discussion			
20	Limitations	Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses	13
21	Generalisability	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	13
22	Interpretation	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	N.R.
Other information			
23	Registration	Registration number and name of trial registry	8
24	Protocol	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available	8
25	Funding	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	15

*We strongly recommend reading this statement in conjunction with the CONSORT 2010 Explanation and Elaboration for important clarifications on all the items. If relevant, we also recommend reading CONSORT extensions for cluster randomised trials, non-inferiority and equivalence trials, non-pharmacological treatments, herbal interventions, and pragmatic trials. Additional extensions are forthcoming: for those and for up to date references relevant to this checklist, see www.consort-statement.org.

PAPER IV

Long-term effects of restriction of intravenous fluid in adult ICU patients with septic shock

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ORIGINAL

Long-term effects of restriction of intravenous fluid in adult ICU patients with septic shock

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær^{1,2*}

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Abstract

Purpose: To assess long-term outcomes of restrictive versus standard intravenous (IV) fluid therapy in adult intensive care unit (ICU) patients with septic shock included in the European Conservative versus Liberal Approach to Fluid Therapy in Septic Shock in Intensive Care (CLASSIC) trial.

Methods: We conducted the pre-planned analyses of mortality, health-related quality of life (HRQoL) using EuroQol (EQ)-5D-5L index values and EQ visual analogue scale (VAS), and cognitive function using Mini Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Mini MoCA) test at 1 year. Deceased patients were assigned numerical zero for HRQoL as a state equal to death and zero for cognitive function outcomes as worst possible score, and we used multiple imputation for missing data on HRQoL and cognitive function.

Results: Among 1554 randomized patients, we obtained 1-year data on mortality in 97.9% of patients, HRQoL in 91.3%, and cognitive function in 86.3%. One-year mortality was 385/746 (51.3%) in the restrictive-fluid group versus 383/767 (49.9%) in the standard-fluid group, absolute risk difference 1.5%-points [99% confidence interval (CI) – 4.8 to

*Correspondence: maj-brit.noerregaard.kjaer@regionh.dk

¹ Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Blegdamsvej 9, 2100 Copenhagen, Denmark

¹⁷ First Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Therapy, Medical University Lublin, Lublin, Poland

Full author information is available at the end of the article

7.8]. Mean differences were 0.00 (99% CI – 0.06 to 0.05) for EQ-5D-5L index values, – 0.65 for EQ VAS (– 5.40 to 4.08), and – 0.14 for Mini MoCA (– 1.59 to 1.14) for the restrictive-fluid group versus the standard-fluid group. The results for survivors only were similar in both groups.

Conclusions: Among adult ICU patients with septic shock, restrictive versus standard IV fluid therapy resulted in similar survival, HRQoL, and cognitive function at 1 year, but clinically important differences could not be ruled out.

Keywords: Septic shock, Sepsis, Intravenous fluid, Critical illness, Long-term outcomes, Quality of life, Cognitive function

Background

Septic shock results in millions of deaths every year [1, 2], and the survivors often have long-term sequelae with physical, psychological, cognitive, and social implications [3–5].

Intravenous (IV) fluid is a first-line treatment, as suggested in the Surviving Sepsis Campaign guideline [1]. While short-term outcomes of lower vs. higher fluid volumes may be similar in patients with septic shock [6–8], no randomized trial of different IV fluid volumes has reported on long-term health-related quality of life (HRQoL) or any outcomes beyond 90 days for patients with septic shock [9].

In patients with acute lung injury, 1-year follow-up of the Fluid and Catheter Treatment Trial (FACTT) allocation to the conservative vs. liberal fluid management was potentially associated with long-term cognitive impairment and reduced executive function, but a similar quality of life was found [10]. However, only 75 of 439 survivors were eligible for 1-year follow-up assessments [11].

The Conservative vs. Liberal Approach to Fluid Therapy of Septic Shock in Intensive Care (CLASSIC) trial assessed IV fluid restriction vs. standard IV fluid therapy and found similar mortality and other outcomes in the two intervention groups at 90 days [6]. In this report, we present the results of the pre-planned assessment of mortality, HRQoL, and cognitive function at 1 year in the CLASSIC trial [12]. We hypothesized that fluid restriction would improve long-term outcomes.

Methods

Trial design

The CLASSIC trial was a European, investigator-initiated, stratified, parallel-group, open-labeled randomized trial. The trial protocol was approved by the relevant medicine agencies and ethics committees [6]. The trial protocol, statistical analysis plan, and primary results have been published elsewhere [6, 13]; so has the statistical analysis plan for the 1-year outcomes [12]. Some deviations from

Take-home message

In adult ICU patients with septic shock, restrictive vs. standard intravenous fluid therapy resulted in similar survival, health-related quality of life, and cognitive function at 1 year.

the protocol and analysis plan were necessary; these are outlined with rationales in the Electronic Supplementary Material (ESM1). We report this manuscript according to the CONSORT 2010 Statement (checklist in ESM2).

Trial sites and patients

Patients were enrolled from November 2018 to November 2021, in 31 intensive care units (ICUs) in Denmark, Sweden, Norway, Switzerland, Italy, the Czech Republic, the United Kingdom, and Belgium after written informed consent from patients or their legal surrogates according to national regulations [13].

We enrolled adult ICU patients with septic shock according to the SEPSIS-3 criteria [14], who had received at least 1L of IV fluid in the last 24 h, and onset of shock no longer than 12 h before screening. Further details regarding the inclusion and exclusion criteria are presented in the ESM1 and elsewhere [6, 13].

Outcomes

The pre-specified secondary outcomes assessed 1 year after randomization were all-cause mortality, HRQoL, and cognitive function [12]. To increase follow-up rate and uniform data collection, we made a standard operating procedure (in the ESM1) for all patients [15]. Trial staff made several attempts to obtain follow-up data for at least 4 weeks after the 1-year date. The process was centrally monitored by the coordinating center in Denmark to support sites in obtaining responses. Data were obtained from medical records (i.e., survival status) and by phone interviews with survivors in their native language. Survivors were interviewed over the telephone by certified trial staff (ESM1) who were masked for the intervention using EuroQol 5 dimension 5 levels (EQ-5D-5L) questionnaire and EQ visual analogue scale (EQ

VAS) [16, 17] and Mini Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) test [18]. In some cases, relatives provided data on survival status or, if necessary, performed the HRQoL on behalf of the patient (using the proxy version of the tool). Relatives could not perform the cognitive test.

The EQ-5D-5L is a generic instrument to describe and value health and has 5 dimensions: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort, and anxiety/depression. Each dimension has 5 response levels: no, slight, moderate, severe, or extreme problems [16, 17]. It also includes EQ VAS, for which respondents are asked to mark on a visual analogue scale how good or bad their health is on the day of the questionnaire on a scale from 100 ('the best health you can imagine') to 0 ('the worst health you can imagine'). When EQ VAS was performed by phone, respondents were asked to picture a scale like a thermometer as per recommendations in the EuroQol interview guide.

The HRQoL outcome measures were EQ-5D-5L index values, a summary score based on the 5 domains reflecting health states according to the preference of a general population ranging from 1.0 (perfect health) to values below 0 (health states valued worse than death, with 0 defined as a state equal to death) and EQ VAS [17]. We used country-specific value sets to calculate the index values for Denmark [19], Sweden [20], England [21], and Italy [22]. The lowest index value depends on the value set, and for Denmark, the lowest index value is -0.76 [19]. For countries with no specific value set, we contacted the national investigator and agreed on a value set close to that country as for culture and healthcare system. For Switzerland, we used the German value set [23]; for Norway, the Danish value set [19]; and for Czech Republic, the Polish value set [24]. As recommended, we conducted an additional analysis with index values calculated using the Danish value set [19] for all patients (most patients were enrolled in Denmark) [25].

The Mini MoCA is a short version of the MoCA test [18] validated for telephone use [26]. The Mini MoCA consists of 4 cognitive dimensions: attention (immediate recall of 5 words), executive functions and language (1-min verbal fluency), orientation (6 items on date and geographic orientation), and memory (delayed recall and recognition of 5 previously learned words). The total score ranges from 0 to 30, with lower values indicating worse cognitive function. To correct for any educational effect on the cognitive test, 1 point is added for participants with 12 years of education or less (scores were truncated at the maximum upper value of 30 points) [27]. Further details on the Mini MoCA are presented in the ESM1.

Statistical analyses

We deviated from the predefined analysis plan in the following ways [12]: (1) HRQoL and Mini MoCA were non-normally distributed, hence why we used Kryger Jensen and Lange test only [28], (2) statistical handling of mortality was not clearly specified; we primarily used adjusted logistic regression models with G-computation and non-parametric bootstrapping, (3) we added secondary analyses in survivors only, (4) we added best-worst and worst-best case scenario sensitivity analyses for missing data despite Little's test rejected data being missing completely at random (described in detail, with reasoning, in ESM1).

The analysis population consisted of all randomized patients ($n=1554$) except 5, who withdrew consent for the use of all data. We present descriptive baseline data stratified by treatment allocation and survival/respondence status for HRQoL and cognitive outcomes. Numerical data were summarized using medians with interquartile ranges (IQRs) and categorical data were summarized using numbers with percentages.

As more than 5% of the patients had missing outcome data (8.8% for EQ-5D-5L index values, 9.2% for EQ VAS, and 13.8% for Mini MoCA), we conducted Little's test, which indicated that data were not missing completely at random ($P<0.001$). Consequently, we conducted the primary analyses of these outcomes after multiple imputation of missing data [29]. We used the predictive mean matching method with 50 datasets imputed separately in each treatment group, with the imputation model including the stratification variables (trial site and metastatic or hematologic cancer), baseline values, and all outcomes (ESM1). Analysis was conducted in each imputed dataset with results pooled as appropriate [30]. Additionally, we conducted best-worst and worst-best case imputations of missing data using the mean ± 1 standard deviation (SD) of EQ-5D-5L index, EQ VAS, and Mini MoCA using the means and SDs estimated in survivors with complete responses for survivors with missing data, and in all patients with available data for patients with missing survival status, and complete case analyses, which we also used for the mortality outcome due to limited missing data (2.1%).

The primary analysis of all outcomes was adjusted for stratification variables, whereas secondary analysis was unadjusted. We analyzed mortality at 1 year using a G-computation procedure based on an adjusted logistic regression model, and 50,000 bootstrap resamples (for the primary analysis), and generalized linear models with binomial error distributions and log/identity links for the unadjusted, secondary analysis. Results are presented as average (unconditional) risk differences (RDs) and relative risks (RRs) with 99% confidence intervals

(CIs), supplemented with a Kaplan–Meier survival curve. The continuous outcomes were clearly non-normally distributed, as expected. For the continuous outcomes, we used the Kryger Jensen and Lange test [28] to calculate *P* values and linear regression models with a similar procedure as for the primary analysis of mortality and presented average (unconditional) mean differences (MDs) and ratios of means with 99% CIs. For the primary analyses of the numerical outcomes, patients who had died at 1 year were included in the analyses with scores of zero. This corresponds to a health state equivalent to death for EQ-5D-5L index values or the worst possible perceived health state value for EQ VAS or the worst cognitive function score [17]. We also analyzed EQ-5D-5L index values, EQ VAS, and Mini MoCA in survivors only. Finally, we analyzed EQ-5D-5L index values for all patients using the Danish value set in secondary analyses of all patients and survivors only, respectively.

Analyses were performed using R (R Core Team, Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria), versions 4.2.0 and 4.2.1. *P* values below 0.01 were considered statistically significant due to multiple testing [12].

Results

A total of 1549 patients were included in 1-year follow-up analysis (Fig. 1). There were no major differences in baseline characteristics between the allocation groups (Table 1). Some differences were present between vital/response status strata: 1-year nonsurvivors had more coexisting conditions, were more frequently admitted from in-hospital wards, had higher median predicted 90-day mortality [31], more frequently had sepsis due to gastrointestinal infection, and more frequently received life-supportive interventions than survivors (respondents and nonrespondents). Nonrespondents appeared less ill (more had admissions from emergency department/pre-hospital or operation/recovery room and more had urinary tract infection) than respondents.

1-Year mortality

We obtained 1-year mortality data for 97.9% of the 1554 randomized patients. One year after randomization, 385 of 767 (51.3%) in the restrictive-fluid group had died compared with 383 of 782 (49.9%) in the standard-fluid group, leading to an absolute difference of 1.5%-points (99% CI – 4.8 to 7.8; *P*=0.55) (Table 2 and Table S1). The Kaplan–Meier survival curve is presented in Fig. 2A.

Health-related quality of life

We obtained 1-year HRQoL for 91.3% of the 1554 randomized patients. The time from the 1-year follow-up date to complete HRQoL assessment was a median 6 days

(IQR 3–14) in the restrictive-fluid group and median 5 days (IQR 3–17) in the standard-fluid group. The proportions of relatives answering the HRQoL questionnaire were 24 of 365 (6.6%) in the restrictive-fluid group and 21 of 384 (5.5%) in the standard-fluid group.

Patients in the restrictive-fluid group had a median EQ-5D-5L index value of 0 (IQR 0–0.82) compared with 0 (IQR 0–0.81) in the standard-fluid group, leading to an MD of 0 (99% CI – 0.06–0.05; *P*=0.81, Table 2 and Fig. 2B). The median EQ VAS was 0 (IQR 0–70) in both groups with an MD of – 0.65 (99% CI – 5.4 to 4.08; *P*=0.8, Table 2 and Fig. 2B). Results for survivors only are presented in Table 2 and Table S1 in the ESM1. EQ-5D-5L index values were 0.83 (IQR 0.58–0.93) vs. 0.81 (IQR 0.58–0.93) for the restrictive- vs. the standard-fluid groups, respectively, with an MD of 0.01 (99% CI – 0.05 to 0.07; *P*=0.61). One-year data for the survivors for each EQ-5D-5L domain are presented in Fig. 3 and Table S2 in the ESM1.

Cognitive function

We obtained 1-year cognitive function for 86.3% of the 1554 randomized patients. The median time from the 1-year follow-up date to complete cognitive function assessment was 6 days (IQR 3–14.5) in the restrictive-fluid group and 6 days (IQR 3–17) in the standard-fluid group. The length of education was median 11 years (IQR 9–14) for both groups.

The median Mini MoCA scores were 0 (IQR 0–22) in both groups leading to an MD of -0.14 (99% CI – 1.59 to 1.31; *P*=0.82) (Table 2). Similar MDs were found in the analyses of survivors only (Table S1 in the ESM1). The four domains of cognitive function for survivors only are presented in Table S3 in ESM1.

Sensitivity analyses

The results from the complete case analyses and unadjusted analyses were similar to the primary results except the best–worst, worst–best case scenarios due to moderate proportions of missing data (Table S1, ESM1).

Discussion

In this 1-year follow-up study of the CLASSIC trial, we found that adult ICU patients with septic shock randomized to restrictive-fluid therapy vs. standard-fluid therapy had similar survival, HRQoL, and cognitive function at 1 year. However, we cannot exclude a clinical important difference in mortality as the 99% CI ranged from – 4.8 to 7.8.

Our results are in line with those from the previously mentioned systematic review with meta-analysis in patients with sepsis or septic shock, where the RR for

all-cause mortality was 0.99 (97% CI 0.89–1.1) closest to day 90 after randomization being the longest follow-up in eight low risk of bias trials [9].

We are not aware of any studies assessing HRQoL on patients with septic shock defined by the Sepsis-3 criteria [14]. The early goal-directed therapy trial, Australasian Resuscitation In Sepsis Evaluation (ARISE), included patients with early septic shock in the emergency department [32] using the sepsis criteria from 1992 [33]. The 90-day mortality was 18.6% in the early goal-directed therapy (EGDT) group and 18.8% in the usual-care group, which can likely be explained by a younger population and fewer patients receiving vasopressor and mechanical ventilation [32]. The 1-year HRQoL assessed with EQ-5D-3L in survivors only was lower than in our cohort, which could be due to the three-level instrument with a ceiling effect [33, 34] or our population with low scores being the nonsurvivors; however, EQ VAS results were similar to ours. The ongoing ARISE FLUIDS trial (ClinicalTrials.gov identifier: NCT04569942) compares restricted fluids and early vasopressors to larger initial IV fluid volumes with later vasopressor administration in patients with sepsis, hypotension, and elevated lactate in emergency

departments and will provide further data on HRQoL after 1 year using EQ-5D-5L.

The only fluid trial we are aware of assessing cognitive function is the previously mentioned FACTT trial where patients with acute lung injury who received conservative vs. liberal fluid management had worse cognitive impairment after 2 months and 1 year, respectively [11]. We did not find similar results which can possibly be explained by the small population that was much younger and only 20–25% had sepsis [11]. Anyway, cognitive function is an important outcome, especially as sepsis is associated with deterioration of the cognitive performance [35]. Overall, our patients scored a median 22 points out of 30 on the Mini MoCA test. For the original MoCA test, the cut-off for mild cognitive impairment is <26. Our results do appear to confirm findings in observational studies of cognitive deterioration in survivors of septic shock [5, 35].

Strengths and limitations

Our study has several strengths. First, we had almost complete data for mortality and only moderate missingness for HRQoL. Second, cognitive function was assessed by certified staff to increase interrater reliability by adhering to a uniform standard operating procedure. Third,

Table 1 Baseline characteristics in all 1549 patients analyzed in the CLASSIC trial stratified by allocation and status at follow-up

	Dead at 1-year follow-up		Alive with complete long-term follow-up		Any missing outcome data	
	Restrictive-fluid group (n = 385)	Standard-fluid group (n = 383)	Restrictive-fluid group (n = 276)	Standard-fluid group (n = 282)	Restrictive-fluid group (n = 106)	Standard-fluid group (n = 117)
Age	73 (66–79)	71 (64–78.5)	67 (59–75)	65.5 (56–74)	67 (55–76)	70 (59–76)
Male sex	236 (61.5%)	223 (58.2%)	169 (61.2%)	167 (59.2%)	54 (52.4%)	64 (56.6%)
Coexisting conditions						
Hematologic or metastatic cancer	97 (25.2%)	96 (25.1%)	24 (8.7%)	35 (12.4%)	8 (7.5%)	9 (7.7%)
Ischemic heart disease or heart failure	65 (16.9%)	80 (20.9%)	41 (14.9%)	51 (18.1%)	11 (10.7%)	21 (18.6%)
Chronic hypertension	189 (49.2%)	183 (47.8%)	125 (45.3%)	135 (47.9%)	33 (32%)	42 (37.2%)
Long-term dialysis	8 (2.1%)	9 (2.3%)	1 (0.4%)	2 (0.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.9%)
Time from ICU admission to randomization	3.4 (1.6–7.9)	3.8 (1.7–8.6)	3.0 (1.2–6.8)	2.9 (1.3–7.9)	2.8 (1.4–6.9)	2.9 (1.4–6.7)
Predicted 90-day mortality (SMS-ICU [31])	24 (21–27)	24 (20–27)	22 (18.8–24)	20 (17–23)	22 (19–24)	21 (17–24)
Admission from						
Emergency department or prehospital	144 (37.5%)	142 (37.1%)	110 (39.9%)	113 (40.1%)	45 (43.7%)	45 (39.8%)
Hospital ward	154 (40.1%)	161 (42%)	77 (27.9%)	103 (36.5%)	32 (31.1%)	36 (31.9%)
Operating or recovery room	76 (19.8%)	68 (17.8%)	75 (27.2%)	60 (21.3%)	23 (22.3%)	26 (23%)
Another ICU	10 (2.6%)	12 (3.1%)	14 (5.1%)	6 (2.1%)	3 (2.9%)	6 (5.3%)
Focus of infection						
Gastrointestinal	150 (39.1%)	160 (41.8%)	103 (37.3%)	99 (35.1%)	29 (28.2%)	39 (34.5%)
Pulmonary	121 (31.5%)	117 (30.5%)	63 (22.8%)	57 (20.2%)	26 (25.2%)	32 (28.3%)
Urinary tract	33 (8.6%)	40 (10.4%)	57 (20.7%)	71 (25.2%)	31 (30.1%)	23 (20.4%)
Skin or soft tissue	33 (8.6%)	26 (6.8%)	22 (8%)	30 (10.6%)	8 (7.8%)	8 (7.1%)
Other	47 (12.2%)	40 (10.4%)	31 (11.2%)	25 (8.9%)	9 (8.7%)	11 (9.7%)
Body weight, blood values, and interventions						
Body weight (kg)	76 (67–86)	76 (65–90)	82.5 (70–96)	81 (70–96.8)	73 (61.5–85)	76 (65–88)
Highest plasma lactate (mmol/liter)	4 (2.8–7.1)	4.3 (2.8–7.3)	3.5 (2.6–5.1)	3.5 (2.6–5.4)	3.5 (2.7–5.8)	3.6 (2.8–4.9)
Highest dose of norepinephrine (µg/kg/min)	0.3 (0.1–0.5)	0.3 (0.1–0.5)	0.2 (0.1–0.4)	0.2 (0.1–0.3)	0.2 (0.1–0.4)	0.2 (0.1–0.4)
Volume of intravenous fluid 24 h before randomization (ml)	3000 (1995–4367)	3000 (1969–5000)	3273.5 (2000–5000)	3000 (2000–4782.5)	3725 (2711–5186.5)	3150 (2225–4400)
Systemic glucocorticoid	119 (31%)	121 (31.6%)	79 (28.6%)	81 (28.7%)	21 (20.4%)	25 (22.1%)
Highest plasma creatinine (µmol/liter)	150 (97–247)	156 (101.5–231.8)	132 (93–208)	140 (95–219)	126 (79–193)	134 (89.8–224)
Respiratory support	213 (55.5%)	213 (55.6%)	137 (49.6%)	115 (40.8%)	52 (50.5%)	51 (45.1%)

SMS: simplified mortality score

Numeric data are presented as medians with interquartile ranges, and categorical data as number and percentages

The analysis population consisted of all randomized patients except 5, who withdrew consent for the use of all data (n = 1549). Baseline characteristics are stratified by

Table 1 (continued)

allocation, vital status, and response status at 1 year. There were 8 patients with missing data (0.5%) for all variables except for the highest plasma creatinine with 17 patients with missing data (1.1%). There are 10 more patients with available baseline data compared to the CLASSIC primary publication [6] as we obtained consent to use the baseline data in anonymised form without further follow-up

Table 2 Outcomes at 1-year follow-up

Variable	Restrictive-fluid group (n = 767)	Standard-fluid group (n = 782)	Adjusted risk difference or adjusted mean difference (99% CI)	Adjusted relative risk or adjusted ratio of means (99% CI)	P value ^a	Missing values
Mortality						
Death by 1 year	385 (51.3%)	383 (49.9%)	1.5% (− 4.8% to 7.8%)	1.03 (0.91–1.17)	0.55	32 (2.1%)
Health-related quality of life						
EQ-5D-5L index values ^b	0 (0–0.82)	0 (0–0.81)	0 (− 0.06 to 0.05)	0.99 (0.85–1.16)	0.81	135 (8.7%)
Survivors only ^c	0.83 (0.58–0.93)	0.81 (0.58–0.93)	0.01 (− 0.05 to 0.07)	1.01 (0.93–1.1)	0.61	102 (13.6%)
EQ VAS	0 (0–70)	0 (0–70)	− 0.65 (− 5.4 to 4.08)	0.98 (0.84–1.14)	0.80	140 (9%)
Survivors only ^c	70 (50–80)	70 (50–80)	− 0.05 (− 5.29 to 5.25)	1 (0.92–1.09)	0.63	108 (14.4%)
Cognitive test^d						
Mini MoCA	0 (0–22)	0 (0–22)	− 0.14 (− 1.59 to 1.31)	0.99 (0.86–1.14)	0.82	212 (13.7%)
Survivors only ^c	22 (17.5–25)	22 (18–24.5)	0.16 (− 0.96 to 1.39)	1.01 (0.95–1.07)	0.59	180 (24%)

CI confidence interval, EQ-5D-5L: EuroQol 5 domains 5 levels, VAS visual analogue scale, MoCA Montreal cognitive assessment

Numeric data are presented as medians with interquartile ranges, and categorical data as numbers and percentages

The analysis population consisted of all randomized patients except 5, who withdrew consent for the use of all data (n = 1549). Patients with missing values include patients lost to follow-up and patients who withdraw consent (n = 43)

^a All analyses were adjusted for the stratification variables, which were trial site and hematologic or metastatic cancer at baseline. Results are presented as adjusted, unconditional, average treatment effects

^b Index values calculated using country-specific value sets, as described in the Methods section

^c Post hoc analyses

^d Nonsurvivors at 1 year after randomization were assigned the value zero corresponding to a health state as bad as being dead for EQ-5D-5L index values and the worst possible score for EQ VAS and Mini MoCA. Missing data were multiply imputed and all HRQoL and cognitive function results in this table (including descriptive data) were calculated using the multiply imputed datasets. We collected data for EQ-5D-5L index values for 1,414 (91.3%) patients, for EQ VAS scores for 1,409 (91%) patients, and for Mini MoCA for 1,337 (86.3%) patients

outcome assessors interviewing patients were masked to the allocation. Finally, CLASSIC was a large European trial involving 31 ICUs in 8 countries, which increases external validity.

Our study also has limitations. First, the proportion of missing data for HRQoL and cognitive function was more than 5%. However, we handled this using multiple imputations, supplemented with best–worst and worst–best case scenarios, which showed that missing data potentially could affect the results in both directions [12, 36]. Second, the trial allocation was not masked for patients and relatives, which may have affected the assessment of HRQoL and cognitive function. Third, the Mini MoCA is a cognitive test developed to detect mild cognitive impairment [18] and has not been validated in critically ill patients, and we cannot assure the mentioned cut-off is reasonable for our population due to the use of the shortened version of the tool by telephone. However the full MoCA has been preliminary validated for patients with septic shock [37]. Further, we may have

underestimated the cognitive function as patients surviving sepsis have been described to have moderate-to-severe impairment of cognitive function [5], but Mini MoCA detects only mild cognitive function. We found that the Mini MoCA was feasible to use by telephone but posed some challenges in patients with impaired hearing and those too ill to comply. Fourth, as relatives were not able to assess the cognitive function as proxy for the patient, we had a higher proportion of missing data for this outcome. Fifth, the assignment of the value zero to deceased patients may be discussed. We expected that the population would have high mortality and planned this assignment in both HRQoL and cognitive function. We hypothesized that the intervention may affect mortality which is the reason, hence why a survivors-only analysis would have been misleading, as discussed in a recent scoping review [38] and by Colantuoni and colleagues [39]. EuroQol recommends to use zero as index value for deceased patients, because this has been valued as a health state equal to death [17]. Also including survivors

A One-year survival curve

Number at risk

	766	460	421	404	388	380	371	366
Restrictive group	766	460	421	404	388	380	371	366
Standard group	781	475	429	418	405	401	393	386

B Stacked heat map

Fig. 2 One-year survival curves in the two interventions groups (A). One patient in each group had died at day 90, but dates of death were unknown due to lack of consent. This resulted in 766 patients in the restrictive group and 781 patients in the standard group to be presented in the survival curves. The four patients who were lost to follow-up at day 90 [4] were included in the survival curves until the last day they were known to be alive. B Stacked heat maps for EQ VAS, EQ-5D-5L index, and Mini MoCA values in all patients after imputations (nonsurvivors assigned zero and multiple imputation of missing data) in the restrictive (Res.) vs standard (Std.) groups. Red represents worse outcomes and blue better outcomes. The horizontal axes represent the cumulated proportion of the patients scoring at or below the value on the secondary axes which represents the score ranges of the tools used; EQ VAS from 0 to 100, EQ-5D-5L index value from below 0 (corresponding to health states valued worse than death) to 1 and Mini MoCA from 0 to 30. In total, 1.5% (restricted-fluid group) and 1.6% (standard-fluid group) of the EQ-5D-5L index values were below zero; these were included as zero in heat map. The plots were done by calculating the proportions after stacking all 50 imputed datasets. Heat maps for survivors only are presented in the ESM1

Fig. 3 Distribution of the health state levels in the 5 HRQoL domains from all respondents being alive at 1-year ($n = 749$) in the restrictive (Res.) vs. standard (Std.) groups. Relatives responded on behalf of 55/749 (7.3%) of the surviving patients. The numeric data corresponding to the Figure are presented in Table S3 in the ESM1

only would have excluded the contribution of half of our population, which would lead to loss of important information and decrease power [28, 39]. Thus, we found it most appropriate to include the deceased cohort in our primary analyses. Sixth, more patients had gastrointestinal focus of infection than respiratory focus [6]. Finally, different results may be obtained in settings where higher IV fluid volumes are given as standard care [6, 40].

Conclusions

In conclusion, restrictive IV fluid therapy resulted in similar survival, HRQoL, and cognitive function at 1 year in adult ICU patients with septic shock compared with standard-fluid therapy, but clinically important differences could not be excluded.

Supplementary Information

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Author details

¹ Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Blegdamsvej 9, 2100 Copenhagen, Denmark. ² Collaboration for Research in Intensive Care (CRIC), Copenhagen, Denmark. ³ Department of Cardiothoracic Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Denmark. ⁴ Copenhagen Trial Unit, Centre for Clinical Intervention Research, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark. ⁵ Section of Biostatistics, Department of Public Health, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark. ⁶ Section of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Department of Clinical Science and Education, Karolinska Institutet, Södersjukhuset, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁷ Division of Emergencies and Critical Care, Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care Medicine, Oslo University Hospital, Rikshospitalet, Oslo, Norway. ⁸ Division of Emergencies and Critical Care, Department of Research and Development, Oslo University Hospital, Rikshospitalet, Oslo, Norway. ⁹ Department of Intensive Care Medicine, University Hospital Bern (Inselspital), University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland. ¹⁰ Medical Intensive Care Unit, First Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Teaching Hospital and Biomedical Center in Pilsen, Charles University, Pilsen, Czech Republic. ¹¹ Department of Intensive Care, Guy's and St Thomas' Hospital, London, UK. ¹² Clinical Trial Unit, Intensive Care National Audit & Research Centre (ICNARC), London, UK. ¹³ Department of Biomedical Sciences, Humanitas University Pieve Emanuele, Milan, Italy. ¹⁴ Anaesthesia and Intensive Care Medicine IRCCS, Humanitas Research Hospital, Rozzano, Milan, Italy. ¹⁵ Department of Intensive Care Medicine, University Hospital Brussels (UZB), Jette, Belgium. ¹⁶ Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Brussels, Belgium. ¹⁷ First Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Therapy, Medical University Lublin, Lublin, Poland. ¹⁸ Department of Perioperative Medicine and Intensive Care, Karolinska University Hospital Huddinge, Stockholm, Sweden. ¹⁹ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital, Bispebjerg, Copenhagen, Denmark. ²⁰ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital-North Zealand, Hilleroed, Denmark. ²¹ Department of Clinical Medicine, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark. ²² Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Zealand University Hospital, Køge, Denmark. ²³ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Zealand University Hospital, Roskilde, Denmark. ²⁴ Copenhagen Academy for Medical Education and Simulation, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark. ²⁵ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Randers Hospital, Randers, Denmark. ²⁶ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Herning Hospital, Herning, Denmark. ²⁷ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Viborg Hospital, Viborg, Denmark. ²⁸ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Kolding, University Hospital of Southern Denmark, Odense, Denmark. ²⁹ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Holbæk Hospital, Holbæk, Denmark. ³⁰ Intensive Care Unit, Basel University Hospital, Basel, Switzerland. ³¹ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Humanitas Gavazzeni Hospital Bergamo, Bergamo, Italy. ³² Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark. ³³ Department of Intensive Care, Hospital Innland Hamar, Hamar, Norway. ³⁴ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care Medicine, Hospital Østfold Kalnes, Grålum, Norway. ³⁵ Department of Intensive Care Medicine, Stavanger University Hospital, Stavanger, Norway. ³⁶ Department of Perioperative Medicine and Intensive Care, Karolinska University Hospital, Solna, Sweden. ³⁷ Department of Clinical Science and Education, Södersjukhuset, Medical Intensive Care Unit, Center for Resuscitation Science, Karolinska Institutet, Solna, Sweden. ³⁸ Department of Emergency Medicine, Capio St Görans Hospital, Stockholm, Sweden. ³⁹ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Capio St Görans Hospital, Stockholm, Sweden. ⁴⁰ Department of Biomedical Sciences and Public Health, Università Politecnica Delle Marche, Ancona, Italy. ⁴¹ Anaesthesia and Intensive Care Unit, Humanitas Research Hospital, Castellanza, Italy. ⁴² Anaesthesia and Intensive Care Unit, Azienda Ospedaliera Universitaria Delle Marche, Ancona, Italy. ⁴³ Division of Nephrology, Faculty of Medicine, Excellence Centre in Critical Care Nephrology, King Chulalongkorn Memorial Hospital, Bangkok, Thailand. ⁴⁴ Division of Emergencies and Critical Care, Department of Research and Development, Oslo University Hospital, Oslo, Norway. ⁴⁵ Institute of Clinical Medicine, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway. ⁴⁶ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Oslo University Hospital Ullevål, Oslo, Norway.

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Author contributions

MBNK coordinated the follow-up and wrote the first draft, which was critically revised by all authors. TSM and PS were coordinating investigators of the CLASSIC trial. AG conducted all analyses presented in this manuscript. Author contributions to the design and conduct of the CLASSIC trial together with complete trial were presented in the CLASSIC primary publication [6].

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Data availability

De-identified trial patient data set will be shared. Data will be available to researchers who provide a methodologically sound proposal.

Declarations

Conflicts of interest

MBNK, TSM, PS, AG, PBH, MBM, MHM, GVK, and AP are affiliated with the Department of Intensive Care at Rigshospitalet, which has received funding for other projects from The Novo Nordisk Foundation, Pfizer, and Fresenius Kabi, Sygeforsikringen "danmark", and has conducted contract research for AM-Pharma (the REVIVAL trial). AP has received an honorarium from Novartis for the participation in an advisory board. MHB and SW are affiliated with the Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care at Copenhagen University Hospital – North Zealand, which has received funding for other research projects from The Novo Nordisk Foundation, Sygeforsikringen "danmark", Toyota Foundation, A.P. Moeller Foundation, Frimodt-Heineke Foundation, Svend Andersen Foundation, Ehrenreich Foundation, and Olga Bryde Nielsen Foundation, and has conducted contract research for AM-Pharma (the REVIVAL trial) and Inotrem (ASTONISH trial). MHB has received an honorarium from AM-Pharma for participation in an advisory board. All other authors have no conflicts to disclose.

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Long-term effects of restriction of intravenous fluid in adult ICU patients with septic shock

Electronic Supplementary Material (ESM)

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Tine Sylvest Meyhoff, Praleene Sivapalan, Anders Granholm, Peter Buhl Hjortrup, Martin Bruun Madsen, Morten Hylander Møller, Ingrid Egerod, Jørn Wetterslev, Theis Lange, Maria Cronhjort, Jon Henrik Laake, Stephan M. Jakob, Marek Nalos, Marlies Ostermann, Doug Gould, Maurizio Cecconi, Manu L.N.G. Malbrain, Christian Ahlstedt, Louise Bendix Kiel, Morten H. Bestle, Lars Nebrich, Thomas Hildebrandt, Lene Russell, Marianne Vang, Michael Lindhart Rasmussen, Christoffer Sølling, Anne Craveiro Brøchner, Mette Krag, Carmen Pfortmueller, Martin Siegemund, Giovanni Albano, Søren Rosborg Aagaard, Helle Bundgaard, Vera Elisabeth Crone, Sine Wichmann, Bror Johnstad, Yvonne Karin Martin, Philipp Seidel, Johan Mårtensson, Jacob Hollenberg, Mats Wistrand, Abele Donati, Enrico Barbara, Thomas Karvunidis, Alexa Hollinger, Andrea Carsetti, Nuttha Lumlertgul, Eva Joelsson-Alm, Nikolas Lambiris, Tayyba Naz Aslam, Fredrik Femtehjell Friberg, Gitte Kingo Vesterlund, Camilla Bekker Mortensen, Stine Rom Vestergaard, Sidsel Fjordbak Caspersen, Diana Bertelsen Jensen, Morten Borup, Bodil Steen Rasmussen, and Anders Perner

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Protocol deviations and rationales

We deviated from the published statistical analysis in several aspects [1].

First, in the analysis plan, we had erroneously included two analysis strategies for the handling of the numerical outcomes (HRQoL using EQ-5D-5L index values and EQ-VAS and Mini MoCA) if their distributions were non-normal (as was the case): the van Elteren test adjusted for site only and the Kryger Jensen and Lange test [2], adjusted for both stratification variables (sites and the presence of haematological malignancy or metastatic cancer). As the Kryger Jensen and Lange test allows adjustment for both stratification variables [2], we used this test and omitted the van Elteren test.

Second, for non-normally distributed values we planned to present (unadjusted) differences between medians with 99% confidence intervals (CIs) estimated using bootstrapping. However, as >50% of the values for all continuous outcomes were 0 in the primary analysis set (due to the assignment of 0 to non-survivors, as specified in the protocol), this analysis approach was omitted because it produced estimates of the difference of 0 with CIs ranging from 0 to 0 in most cases, incorrectly applying absolute certainty of effects due to the large proportion of similar values in the dataset. Instead, we present adjusted mean differences and ratios of means with 99% CIs, calculated from linear regression models adjusted for the stratification variables, using non-parametric bootstrapping (with 50,000 resamples in each multiply imputed dataset and the percentile method on the pooled bootstrap samples) and G-computation [3]. This approach allowed us to estimate both adjusted absolute and relative differences, it is robust to the skewed distributions, and it matches previous reports [4].

Third, the published statistical analysis plan [1] specified that one-year mortality would be analysed using both adjusted logistic regression and generalized linear models with binomial error distributions and appropriate link functions, with results presented as relative risks. As this strategy was somewhat unclear, the primary, adjusted analyses of mortality used adjusted logistic regression models, with results presented as relative risks and risk differences with 99% CIs using G-computation and non-parametric bootstrapping (with 50,000 resamples and the percentile method), as done in the analyses of shorter-term outcomes in the trial [5] and elsewhere previously [4, 6]. Unadjusted analyses of this outcome were conducted using generalized linear models with binomial error distributions and log- and identity links, to present similar results (these models did not converge for the adjusted analyses).

Fourth, the published statistical analysis plan only mentioned that adjusted analyses would be conducted in all patients (assigning non-survivors the value 0 for the numerical outcomes); we supplemented this with post-hoc unadjusted and adjusted analyses conducted in survivors only.

Finally, according to the published statistical analysis plan, substantial missing data would be handled using multiple imputations if Little's test rejected the null hypothesis of data being missing completely at random (as was the case) and if missing data could be assumed to be missing at random; if data were assumed to be missing not at random, best-worst and worst-best case scenario analyses would be conducted instead. We consider the missing at random assumption most plausible but opted to present both analyses conducted on multiply imputed data as the primary while supplementing this with both best-worst and worst-best case scenario analyses and analyses conducted using complete cases only.

Baseline values and outcomes included in the multiple imputation models

SMS-ICU [7], site of infection, comorbidities (ischemic heart disease or heart failure and chronic hypertension or chronic renal replacement therapy (RRT), use of corticosteroids, mechanical ventilation, highest p-creatinine 24 hours prior to randomisation, habitual plasma creatinine, plasma lactate, participant weight, and volume of intravenous (IV) fluids given prior to randomisation were included in the imputation models together with shorter-term outcomes reported at day 90 (serious adverse events, serious adverse reactions, days alive and out of hospital and days alive without life support; 90-day mortality was omitted from the models due to high correlation with 1-year mortality) and all long-term outcomes.

Enrolment criteria

All patients who were admitted or planned to be admitted to an active trial site were considered for participation. Patients were eligible if they fulfilled all inclusion criteria and no exclusion criteria as stated below.

Trial inclusion criteria [5]

- Age: the age of the patient in whole years at the time of randomization. The age was calculated from the date of birth.
- Admitted to the ICU or planned to be admitted to the ICU: We only recruited sites that had the status as an ICU. These could have overseen beds defined as high-dependency, step-up or step-down beds. We considered these as being part of the trial site ICU if staff trained in the protocol looking after the patients in these beds. The medical doctors at the site ICUs could enrol patients from other locations in the hospital (e.g. emergency departments, general wards or the recovery room) if the patient for clinical reasons was planned to be admitted to the ICU.
- Septic shock: We defined septic shock at the time of screening according to the Sepsis-3 criteria [8] i.e.:
 - Suspected or confirmed site of infection or positive blood culture **AND**
 - Ongoing infusion of vasopressor/inotrope agent (norepinephrine, epinephrine, phenylephrine, vasopressin analogues, angiotensin, dopamine, dobutamine, milrinone or levosimendan) to maintain a mean arterial blood pressure of 65 mmHg or above **AND**
 - Lactate of 18 mg/dL [2 mmol/L] or above in any plasma sample performed within the last 3-hours prior to screening.
- Have received at least 1 L of IV fluid in the last 24 hours prior to screening: we counted all crystalloids (isotonic saline, Ringer's and Plasmalyte™ solutions) colloids (albumin 4, 5 or 20%, gelatine, hydroxyethyl starch, and dextran solutions) and blood products (units or red cells, plasma or platelets) the patient has received according to the source data within the last 24 hours independent of location (in- or pre-hospital) including fluids with IV medication and IV nutrition. Intraosseous fluid will be counted as IV.

Trial exclusion criteria [5]

- Septic shock for more than 12 hours at the time of screening: septic shock according to the Sepsis-3 criteria [8] (definition given in inclusion criteria) for more than 12 hours at the time of screening. We used infection and infusion of vasopressor/inotrope agent for more than 12 hours as a cut off, as the plasma lactate value may change during the course of treatment.
- Life-threatening bleeding: clinical bleeding needed transfusion of blood products as defined by the clinicians.
- Acute burn injury of more than 10% of the body surface area: burn injury leading to the present intensive care unit (ICU) admission. Patients with burn injury who were readmitted to the ICU or were initially cared for in a general ward and admitted to the ICU for infection may have been screened to enrolment. The latest documented estimate of the burn area we used as those may have been downgraded after the initial assessments.
- Known pregnancy: women with known pregnancy based on clinical examination, the history or human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG).
We did not demand negative hCG-status in all eligible fertile women, because
(i) screening for enrolment was to be done within the time window (waiting for the hCG result will delay screening and result in fewer fertile women included),
(ii) the pregnancy rate was very low in ICU patients with septic shock and
(iii) trial participation did not endanger the woman or the fetus.
The same procedure was approved by the Danish Medicines Agency in the TARTARE 2S trial (EudraCT no. 2015-005112-15), which has many similarities to the CLASSIC trial (ICU patients with septic shock randomized to protocolized titration of an approved medicine (norepinephrine).
- Consent not obtainable according to national regulations: patients where the clinician or investigator was unable to obtain the necessary consent before inclusion of the patient according to the national regulations.

Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for long-term follow-up in the CLASSIC trial

V-2019-12-19

SOP for obtaining the long-term outcomes for the CLASSIC trial

These are the three secondary outcomes that should be obtained at 1-year follow-up: Mortality, cognitive function and Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL).

Retention strategies

- When obtaining patient consent, please assure that the patients are informed about the 1-year contact
- Similarly, inform the relatives about the 1-year follow-up when obtaining their consent
- If the patients cannot be reached at 1-year follow-up, aim to contact the patient daily during the following 4 weeks until 1-year follow-up is obtained
- If the patient is assumed to be at work, then try to make contact during the late afternoon
- If the patient chooses to answer by e-mail (or post) the time for obtaining answers is extended by another 4 weeks, with a reminder 2 weeks after the e-mail/letter has been posted. Remark that cognitive function can only be assessed by telephone.

We cannot contact any participants who rejected to be contacted or were withdrawn with the demand of no further data registration.

Procedure at 1-year follow-up:

By personnel **blinded** to the trial allocation.

- 1 • Assure patient is alive
- 2 • Contact the patient first weekday after randomisation
- 3 • Ask the patient to sit in an undisturbed room **without a clock or calendar.**
- 4 • 1st obtain Mini MoCA
- 5 • 2nd obtain EQ-5D-5L + EQ-VAS
- 6 • Not obtainable -> register cause in eCRF

Paper questionnaires are used for the telephone interview. The interviewer enters ID number; date for interview and a signature on the paper after the interview. Then enter data into the e-CRF

in Open Clinica. The paper questionnaires are to be filed in folders. Please read the instructions for both questionnaires beforehand, in order to obtain as objective answers as possible.

Cognitive function is assessed with a 4-items questionnaire. The Mini MoCA is a shorter version than the full MoCA. Mini MoCA covers test #5, #8, #10 and #11 described in the main Instructions. We have made an un-official short guide for the relevant parts for the Mini MoCA. The Mini MoCA takes 5 minutes and you will need the instructions (short guide) together with the questionnaire. MoCA requires certification to conduct the cognitive function assessment, which covers the full MoCA. Mini MoCA can only be assessed by telephone or face to face and not by mail.

HRQoL is assessed with EQ-5D-5L. It is a 5-item questionnaire together with a VAS scale score and takes 5 minutes. We recommend conducting the interview by phone, but it is also possible to answer the questionnaire by mail. If the patient is too frail or cognitively impaired to consistently complete EQ-5D-5L, try to obtain the patients HRQoL from relatives (there is a specific questionnaire for relatives). The relative assesses the HRQoL from the relative's point of view.

Mini MoCA certification: This is done here: <https://www.mocatest.org/training-certification/> and takes 1 hour. The full MoCA instructions are very helpful. The certificate is valid for two years. The certification for conducting a cognitive score with the Mini MoCA is charged USD 125 per site and will be refunded by the foundation for the CLASSIC trial. E-mail an invoice to contact@cric.nu.

Charges: case money contains coverage of long-term follow-up. If there is a central person conducting all following-up in a country, we kindly ask you to solve this internally. The payment for conducting 1-year follow-up for another site is Euro 100 per patient and will be paid by the including sites case-money.

Co-enrolment: patients might be co-enrolled in another CRIC trial (HOT-ICU and/or AID-ICU) who also obtain EQ-5D-5L. If so, you still obtain EQ-5D-5L unless the form in the eCRF are already done or you are being notified by the coordinating investigator from the other trials.

Coordinator: Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, RN, MSc (Health Science), PhD student will coordinate and report 1-year follow-up of the CLASSIC trial.

Contact details: maj-brit.noerregaard.kjaer@regionh.dk or phone +45 3545 7236.

Mini MoCA – modified version

We used a modified Mini MoCA version as the validated MoCA 5 minute was not official when we started the CLASSIC 1-year follow-up, and as the MoCA Institute recommended us to draft our own modified version of the Mini MoCA. The Mini MoCA test was back-and forth translated and approved by MoCA Institute for all participating countries by native speaking colleagues. The scoring system was similar to the validated MoCA 5-minute protocol [9], but not similar to the final version, which has since been launched by the MoCA Institute (<https://mocacognition.com/paper/>). However, the content is similar. The official validation of the tool by MoCA Institute, has not yet been published.

The Mini MoCA consists of 4 cognitive dimensions; attention (immediate recall of 5 words) with score 0 to 5 (best), executive functions/language (1-minute verbal fluency) with score 0 to 9 (best), orientation (6-item date and geographic orientation) with score 0 to 6 (best) and memory (delayed recall and recognition of 5 words learned) with score 0 to 10 (best).

Table S1 Secondary analyses and sensitivity analyses

Variable	Restrictive-Fluid group (n = 767)	Standard-Fluid group (n = 782)	Absolute difference	Relative difference	P-value
Mortality at 1-year	Number (%)	Number (%)	Risk difference (99% CI)	Relative risk (99% CI)	P-value
Adjusted (primary analysis)	51.3%	49.9%	1.5% (-4.8 to 7.8)	1.03 (0.91 to 1.17)	0.55
Unadjusted	51.3%	49.9%	1.4% (-5.2 to 8.0)	1.03 (0.90 to 1.17)	0.59
EQ-5D-5L index values^a	Medians (IQRs)	Medians (IQRs)	Mean difference (99% CI)	Ratio of means (99% CI)	P-value
Multiple imputed data, adjusted (primary analysis)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.82)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.81)	0.00 (-0.06 to 0.05)	0.99 (0.85 to 1.16)	0.81
Unadjusted ^b	0.00 (0.00 to 0.82)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.81)	0.00 (-0.06 to 0.05)	0.99 (0.85 to 1.16)	0.81
Complete case analysis	0.00 (0.00 to 0.80)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.78)	0.01 (-0.05 to 0.06)	1.02 (0.86 to 1.19)	0.78
Best-worst case analysis ^c	0.00 (0.00 to 0.86)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.74)	0.05 (0.00 to 0.10)	1.16 (1.00 to 1.34)	<0.01
Worst-best case analysis ^c	0.00 (0.00 to 0.76)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.86)	-0.06 (-0.11 to -0.00)	0.85 (0.74 to 0.99)	<0.01
EQ-5D-5L index value based on Danish value set for all countries^c					
Multiple imputed data, adjusted (primary analysis)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.80)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.81)	0.00 (-0.06 to 0.05)	1.00 (0.85 to 1.17)	0.80
Survivors only	0.81 (0.54 to 0.93)	0.81 (0.52 to 0.92)	0.01 (-0.05 to 0.07)	1.01 (0.93 to 1.11)	0.61
Unadjusted ^b	0.00 (0.00 to 0.80)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.81)	0.00 (-0.06 to 0.05)	1.00 (0.85 to 1.17)	0.77
Complete case analysis	0.00 (0.00 to 0.78)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.77)	0.01 (-0.05 to 0.06)	1.03 (0.87 to 1.21)	0.68
Best-worst case analysis ^c	0.00 (0.00 to 0.84)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.72)	0.06 (0.00 to 0.11)	1.17 (1.01 to 1.36)	<0.01
Worst-best case analysis ^c	0.00 (0.00 to 0.75)	0.00 (0.00 to 0.86)	-0.06 (-0.11 to 0.00)	0.85 (0.73 to 0.99)	<0.01
EQ VAS					
Multiple imputed data, adjusted (primary analysis)	0.0 (0.0 to 70.0)	0.0 (0.0 to 70.0)	-0.65 (-5.40 to 4.08)	0.98 (0.84 to 1.14)	0.80
Unadjusted ^b	0.0 (0.0 to 70.0)	0.0 (0.0 to 70.0)	-0.64 (-5.51 to 4.23)	0.98 (0.84 to 1.15)	0.84
Complete case analysis	0.0 (0.0 to 65.0)	0.0 (0.0 to 65.0)	0.08 (-4.78 to 4.89)	1.00 (0.85 to 1.18)	>0.99
Best-worst case analysis ^c	0.0 (0.0 to 75.0)	0.0 (0.0 to 60.0)	4.07 (-0.57 to 8.61)	1.14 (0.98 to 1.32)	<0.01
Worst-best case analysis ^c	0.0 (0.0 to 60.0)	2.5 (0.0 to 75.0)	-5.58 (-10.24 to -0.91)	0.84 (0.72 to 0.97)	<0.01
Mini MoCA					
Multiple imputed data, adjusted (primary analysis)	0.0 (0.0 to 22.0)	0.0 (0.0 to 22.0)	-0.14 (-1.59 to 1.31)	0.98 (0.86 to 1.14)	0.82
Unadjusted ^b	0.0 (0.0 to 22.0)	0.0 (0.0 to 22.0)	-0.12 (-1.61 to 1.38)	0.98 (0.85 to 1.14)	0.83
Complete case analysis	0.0 (0.0 to 21.0)	0.0 (0.0 to 20.5)	0.15 (-1.30 to 1.63)	1.02 (0.86 to 1.20)	0.86
Best-worst case analysis ^c	0.0 (0.0 to 23.5)	0.0 (0.0 to 19.0)	1.46 (0.07 to 2.86)	1.15 (1.01 to 1.32)	<0.01
Worst-best case analysis ^c	0.0 (0.0 to 19.5)	9.8 (0.0 to 24.0)	-1.78 (-3.18 to -0.36)	0.84 (0.74 to 0.97)	<0.01

Abbreviations: *CI*: confidence interval; *EQ-5D-5L*: EuroQol 5 domains 5 levels; *VAS*: visual analogue scale, *MoCA*: Montreal cognitive assessment.

The analyses were adjusted for the stratification variables being trials site and hematologic or metastatic cancer at baseline.

^a Index value based on country specific value sets except for the three countries with no value set, where we chose the most comparable (defined in the methods section of the main text).

^b The unadjusted analyses consists of the descriptive data of the multiple imputation and therefore similar to the adjusted multiple imputed data as the descriptive data are not affected by the adjusted analyses.

^c Best-worst worst-best case analyses were conducted as described in the methods section of the main text.

^d Adjusted mean difference using the Danish value set for all patients. These analyses use multiply imputed data.

Table S2 Responses for each level within the five domains of EQ-5D-5L

Variable	Restrictive-Fluid group (n = 365)	Standard-Fluid group (n = 384)	Missing values
Mobility			104 (13.9%)
I have no problems in walking around	126 (39.3%)	112 (34.6%)	
I have slight problems with walking around	77 (24.0%)	76 (23.5%)	
I have moderate problems with walking around	57 (17.8%)	75 (23.1%)	
I have severe problems with walking around	41 (12.8%)	36 (11.1%)	
I am unable to walk around	20 (6.2%)	25 (7.7%)	
Self-care			104 (13.9%)
I have no problems with washing and dressing myself	214 (66.7%)	210 (64.8%)	
I have slight problems with washing and dressing myself	49 (15.3%)	47 (14.5%)	
I have moderate problems with washing and dressing myself	26 (8.1%)	35 (10.8%)	
I have severe problems with washing and dressing myself	14 (4.4%)	12 (3.7%)	
I am unable to wash and dress myself	18 (5.6%)	20 (6.2%)	
Usual activities			104 (13.9%)
I have no problems doing my usual activities	132 (41.2%)	112 (34.5%)	
I have slight problems doing my usual activities	71 (22.2%)	73 (22.5%)	
I have moderate problems doing my usual activities	61 (19.1%)	76 (23.4%)	
I have severe problems doing my usual activities	30 (9.4%)	33 (10.2%)	
I am unable to do my usual activities	26 (8.1%)	31 (9.5%)	
Pain/discomfort			106 (14.2%)
I have no pain or discomfort	107 (33.6%)	119 (36.6%)	
I have slight pain or discomfort	94 (29.6%)	95 (29.2%)	
I have moderate pain or discomfort	78 (24.5%)	65 (20.0%)	
I have severe pain or discomfort	29 (9.1%)	41 (12.6%)	
I have extreme pain or discomfort	10 (3.1%)	5 (1.5%)	
Anxiety/depression			104 (13.9%)
I am not anxious or depressed	184 (57.5%)	174 (53.5%)	
I am slightly anxious or depressed	83 (25.9%)	83 (25.5%)	
I am moderately anxious or depressed	36 (11.2%)	51 (15.7%)	
I am severely anxious or depressed	14 (4.4%)	12 (3.7%)	
I am extremely anxious or depressed	3 (0.9%)	5 (1.5%)	
Relatives responding on behalf of surviving patients	24/365 (6.6%)	21/384 (5.5%)	

Results are presented as numbers and percentages. Data from survivors only with complete EQ-5D-5L scores included.

Table S3 Responses for each level within the 4 domains of Mini MoCA

Variable	Restrictive-Fluid group (n = 365)	Standard-Fluid group (n = 384)	Missing values
Attention	4.0 (3.0 - 5.0)	4.0 (3.0 - 5.0)	183 (24.4%)
Executive functions and language	4.5 (3.0 - 6.0)	4.5 (3.0 - 6.0)	186 (24.8%)
Orientation	6.0 (6.0 - 6.0)	6.0 (6.0 - 6.0)	183 (24.4%)
Memory	7.0 (5.0 - 9.0)	7.0 (5.0 - 8.0)	184 (24.6%)
Length of education (years)	11.0 (9.0 - 14.0)	11.0 (9.0 - 14.0)	200 (26.7%)

Numeric data are presented as medians with interquartile ranges. Data from survivors only with complete Mini MoCA test data.

Figure S1 Heatmap survivors only

In this heat map, we included survivors only after multiply imputing missing data for EQ VAS, EQ-5D-5L index values based on country specific value sets, and Mini MoCA. The horizontal-axis represents the score ranges of the tools used; EQ VAS from 0 to 100, EQ-5D-5L index value from below 0.0 (corresponding to health states valued worse than death) to 1.00 and Mini MoCA from 0 to 30. For EQ-5D-5L index-values below 0 in the survivors were 2.8% in the restrictive-fluid group vs. 3.1% in the standard-fluid group.

Table S4 Reasons for loss to follow-up for nonrespondents

Variable	Restrictive-Fluid group (n=80)	Standard-Fluid group (n=96)
Cognitive function by Mini MoCA		
Unable to get hold of the patient	19	37
Did not wish to participate	17	20
Withdrew consent	5	3
Had other reasons	39	36
HRQoL by EQ-5D-5L and EQ VAS	(n=41)	(n=55)
Unable to get hold of the patient	18	31
Did not wish to participate	9	8
Withdrew consent	5	4
Had other reasons	9	12

Table S5 Synthesized comments to 'other reasons' in Table S4

Comments	Mini MoCA	EQ-5D-5L and EQ VAS
Bad hearing	5	None
Lack of speech	5	None
Too ill/cognitive impaired to participate	21	7
Difficulties with the language	10	2
Lack of resources due to COVID	5	6
Patients irritated to the test	4	None
Too emotional affected by the test	None	2

Most comments were explaining why the score was low or why patients were withdrawn or lost to follow-up.

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CONSORT 2010 checklist of information to include when reporting a randomised trial*

Section/Topic	Item No	Checklist item	Reported on page No
Title and abstract			
	1a	Identification as a randomised trial in the title	5
	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstracts)	5
Introduction			
Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	6
	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	6
Methods			
Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	7
	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	7
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	ESM p.4
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	7
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	7
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	7-8
	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	7 and ESM p.2
Sample size	7a	How sample size was determined	7 and in the protocol [1].

	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	In the primary publication [5].
Randomisation:			
Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	In the primary publication [5].
	8b	Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	In the primary publication [5].
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	In the primary publication [5].
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	In the primary publication [5].
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how	7
	11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	Not relevant
Statistical methods	12a	Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	8-9
	12b	Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses	8-9
Results			
Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	Fig.1 and table 2
	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	Fig 1, and ESM p.13
Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	7
	14b	Why the trial ended or was stopped	Not relevant
Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	Table 1

Numbers analysed	16	For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups	Table 2
Outcomes and estimation	17a	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)	Table 2
	17b	For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended	Table 2 and ESM Table S1
Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	ESM Table S1
Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	None
Discussion			
Limitations	20	Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses	12-13
Generalisability	21	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	12-13
Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	12
Other information			
Registration	23	Registration number and name of trial registry	4
Protocol	24	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available	5
Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	14

*We strongly recommend reading this statement in conjunction with the CONSORT 2010 Explanation and Elaboration for important clarifications on all the items. If relevant, we also recommend reading CONSORT extensions for cluster randomised trials, non-inferiority and equivalence trials, non-pharmacological treatments, herbal interventions, and pragmatic trials. Additional extensions are forthcoming: for those and for up-to-date references relevant to this checklist, see www.consort-statement.org

PAPER V

Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients – A protocol

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients—A protocol

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær¹ |
 Stine Estrup² | Praleene Sivapalan¹ | Camilla Rahbek Lysholm Bruun¹ |
 Camilla Bekker Mortensen² |
 Steffen Christensen³ | Thomas Strøm^{4,5} | Eva Laerkner⁴ | Anne Craveiro Brøchner⁶ |
 Bodil Steen Rasmussen⁷ | Stine Rom Vestergaard⁷ | Emily Barot¹ |
 Martin Bruun Madsen¹

¹Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital—Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

²Department of Anaesthesiology, Zealand University Hospital, Køge, Denmark

³Department of Intensive Care, Aarhus University Hospital, Aarhus, Denmark

⁴Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care, Odense University Hospital, Odense, Denmark

⁵Department of Anaesthesia and Critical Care Medicine, Hospital Sønderjylland, University Hospital of Southern Denmark, Kolding, Denmark

⁶Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Lillebælt Hospital, Kolding, Denmark

⁷Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark

Correspondence

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Department of Intensive Care 4131, Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, Blegdamsvej 9, DK-2100, Copenhagen, Denmark.

Email: maj-brit.noerregaard.kjaer@regionh.dk

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Abstract

Introduction: Different outcomes are reported in randomised clinical trials (RCTs) in intensive care unit (ICU) patients, and no core outcome set (COS) is available for ICU patients in general. Accordingly, we aim to develop a COS for ICU patients in general.

Methods: The COS will be developed in accordance with the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) Handbook, using a modified Delphi consensus process and semi-structured interviews involving adults who have survived acute admission to an ICU, family members, clinicians, researchers and other stakeholders. The modified Delphi process will include two steps. Step 1: conduction of a modified Delphi survey, developed and informed by combining the outputs of a literature search of outcomes in previous COSs and semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders. We plan at least two survey rounds to obtain consensus and refine the COS. Step 2: a consensus process regarding instruments or definitions to be recommended for the measurements of the outcomes selected in Step 1. A 'patient and public involvement panel' consisting of a smaller group of patients, family members, clinicians and researchers will be included in the development, analysis and interpretation of the COS.

Discussion: The outlined multiple method studies will establish a COS for ICU patients in general, which may be used to increase the standardisation and comparability of results of RCTs conducted in patients in the ICU setting.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Outcome selection and prioritisation are an important part in the planning of randomised clinical trials (RCTs).¹ Variability in the selection and definition of outcomes² in the intensive care unit (ICU) population makes it difficult to compare and synthesise results across studies.³ The development of core outcome sets (COSs) is generally encouraged, and several have been developed for subpopulations of critically ill patients based on the primary reason for admission including those with acute respiratory failure.⁴ However, a COS for the general ICU population is lacking.⁵

Patient and public involvement (PPI) is increasingly recommended and used^{6,7} as it increases the likelihood that research is relevant to the target population.^{3,8}

In the ICU setting, the involvement of patients and family members, together with clinicians and other stakeholders, is important since patients are vulnerable⁹ and rarely have the opportunity to interact during an ICU stay due to impaired consciousness and cognitive function and the stress of critical illness. Furthermore, ICU survivors often have long-term physical, psychological and cognitive impairments resulting in health and social implications.¹⁰⁻¹² Finally, the involvement of patients and relatives in the research process increases the focus on patient-important outcomes.^{6,7}

1.1 | Aims

We aim to develop a non-disease-specific COS for ICU patients in general. We also aim to establish a consensus on how the identified outcomes could be measured.

2 | METHODS

We have prepared this protocol in accordance with the Core Outcome Set-STandardised Protocol (COS-STAP) statement (completed checklist available in Supplement)¹³ and in accordance with the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) initiative including the COMET Handbook.³ This study has been registered in the COMET database (<https://comet-initiative.org/Studies/Details/1882>).

This COS will be developed using a multiple methods design including a modified Delphi process with surveys and consensus meetings and semi-structured interviews, as shown in Figure 1. The modified Delphi process approach aims to establish consensus amongst stakeholders while avoiding influential individuals to markedly affect the results. Participants are only presented with aggregated responses during survey rounds.³ The process consists of two steps described in further detail below:

- Step 1: item development including conceptualisation of domains item identification and consensus meeting with a finalised COS as the product, which will be reported using the Core Outcome Set-STAndards for Reporting (COS-STAR) statement.¹⁴

- Step 2: identification of how to measure the COS informed by step 1. This includes identifying existing instruments, quality assessment of instruments and a consensus process for selecting instruments or definitions to be included in a core outcome measurement set (COMS).

2.1 | The scope of the core outcome set:

- Health condition: critical illness requiring treatment in an ICU
- Population: adult patients (≥18 years of age) acutely admitted to an ICU
- Interventions: any form of treatment or care performed in the ICU, including pharmacological or non-pharmacological interventions or care protocols used in the ICU

2.2 | Stakeholders

- Adult patients who survived acute admission to an ICU
- Adult family members (including, but not limited to, spouses, friends, close or informal caregivers or next of kin) to ICU patients regardless of patients' survival
- Clinicians (including, but not limited to, doctors and nurses) with any involvement in the care of ICU patients
- Researchers (including clinicians and researchers) conducting research in the ICU setting or in adjacent populations of critically ill patients
- Other stakeholders including grant funders, patient organisations and political and legal partners (examples included in the supplement)

We have established a *patient and public involvement panel (PPI panel)* currently consisting of two patients, two family members, two nurses and three physicians (all clinicians with research experience, four of which are co-authors of this protocol) who will be included in the development, analysis and establishment of the COS. This PPI panel is planned to be expanded by members from all regions in Denmark. We intend to use the established PPI panels local in their home region and together as one large PPI panel in future research projects including the prioritisation of research questions.

2.2.1 | Recruitment of participants

- Invitation for participation in the COS development study will be promoted in the outpatient clinics of the participating hospitals and ICUs.
- Information and invitation to the COS development study will be given to patients and family members when delayed consent is obtained for participation in RCTs or at long-term follow-up in RCTs originating from the Collaboration of Research in Intensive Care (CRIC; www.cric.nu) in Denmark.

FIGURE 1 Flow diagram outlining the core outcome set (COS) development. Steps required for consensus for the COS and core outcome measurement set (COMS) instruments are summarised. Dashed lines (---) indicate specific requirements for a consensus meeting determined on completion of the modified Delphi consensus process

- Patients not participating in these RCTs will be visited in the general ward before discharge for information and invitation or when participating in ICU patient cafes.
- Information and invitation to participate will be available as hand-outs in the participating hospitals and relevant charities and support organisations.

- Clinicians will be identified in the authors' affiliations and invited by e-mail, interdisciplinary meetings and by phone calls.
- Researchers will be identified by the authors' affiliations and research networks (e.g. CRIC) and invited by e-mail.

In Table 1, we have listed participants' characteristics to be obtained; we will strive for a balanced distribution of these amongst the participating stakeholders.

We plan to start the modified Delphi process and semi-structured interviews at the end of 2021, and we expect to finalise the first Delphi round in the summer of 2022, the second round at the end of 2022 and to obtain final consensus in the spring of 2023. The final version of the COS is estimated to be completed at the end of 2023.

2.2.2 | Step 1, part 1: Developing the COS

We are developing a survey by condensation of the existing literature, complemented with knowledge gained from semi-structured interviews. The survey will be distributed and answered online using the DelphiManager software (COMET Initiative). We will ensure internal validity of the survey prior to commencing the formal modified Delphi process with a pilot test in accordance with the COMET Handbook.³

Existing literature will be summarised according to a systematic literature review, using a search string from a previous systematic review of COS for critical illness and recovery, developed by a librarian (Supplement).⁵

We searched PubMed and Embase on 1 May 2021 without any filters. We also searched the COMET database for relevant COS with assistance from the COMET group. Two authors independently and in duplicate screened results for COS (MNK and SED).

Subsequently, two research teams (MNK, PS, MOC, GKV and SED, LMP, CBM) independently followed the recommended process described in the COMET Handbook³ and classified outcomes in categories describing similar outcomes, followed by division into sub-domains, where all categories were placed and reconsidered before deciding on the final number of domains. These domains will be discussed with the involved stakeholders and serve as the fundamental for the Delphi survey along with the additional knowledge gained from the semi-structured interviews.

We will invite relevant stakeholders to the semi-structured interviews, in parallel with the modified Delphi process, by quota sampling to ensure balanced distributions of the characteristics shown in Table 2. Interviewed respondents will be invited to the modified Delphi process.

The semi-structured interviews will provide us with experiential knowledge of what constitutes patient-important outcomes. We will construct an interview guide based on the domains identified from the literature and from the categorisation of outcomes to ensure rigorous interviews and to elaborate thoughts and considerations regarding admission to an ICU with critical illness and sequelae.

The survey will be pilot tested by the PPI panel and revised as necessary (Supplement).

2.2.3 | Step 1, part 2: Delphi round 1: consensus on core outcomes

At the start of Delphi round 1, we will collect baseline variables for the included stakeholders (variables listed in Table 1). Other stakeholders will answer on behalf of their organisations and not individually, and the results will be tabulated separately.

Round 1 survey will be structured so outcomes common to all stages of the ICU admission will be listed first, followed by outcomes that are specific to specific time points during the ICU admission. Within this structure, the order of outcomes will initially be randomised individually for all participants. For each outcome, participants will be able to provide free-text comments and suggest additional outcomes.

Participants will score the importance of each outcome as outlined in the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) approach,¹⁵ using a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 9 in terms of importance for inclusion in the final COS. The same rating for multiple outcomes is allowed. Scores of 1–3 are defined as 'not important' for inclusion, 4–6 as 'important but not critical' and 7–9 as 'critical' for inclusion. The survey will also include an item 'unable to score' to reduce the number of incomplete answers.

We will also explore the outcomes with semi-structured interviews in parallel with the first survey round. Additional outcomes identified in the interviews will be included in the second round. Further details regarding the semi-structured interviews (including the pre-planned framework analysis) are presented in the Supplement.

2.2.4 | Step 1, part 3: Consensus process after the first survey round

In-person or online consensus meetings will be held to confirm the final COS contents or undertake any additional voting if the number of included outcomes in the COS is perceived as excessive and to ensure that participants of the meetings do not disregard the results from the first survey round. The COS Management Committee (MC; consisting of all authors of this protocol) will review the findings of the first survey to determine the structure, format and content of the consensus meeting. For the consensus meeting, the PPI panel will take part, representing relevant stakeholders.³

2.2.4.1 | Modified Delphi consensus definition

Consensus for inclusion of an outcome is defined for every particular group of stakeholders as $\geq 70\%$ of responses rating the outcome as 'critical' (a score ≥ 7 and $\leq 15\%$ of responses rating the outcome 'not important', i.e. a score ≤ 3).³ Participants will be asked to complete survey rounds within 7 days of receipt; non-respondents will receive

TABLE 1 Characteristics of all stakeholders who accepted to participate in the Delphi survey round 1.

	Patients	Family members	Clinicians	Researchers ¹
Characteristics				
Age (years) ^a	# (# to #)	# (# to #)	# (# to #)	# (# to #)
Sex (female) ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Region of residence				
Capital Region ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Region Zealand ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Central Region ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Northern Region ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Southern Region ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Origins				
Danish ^c	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Other than Danish ^d	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Admission type				
Surgical ^b	# (#%)			
Medical ^b	# (#%)			
SMS-ICU^d at ICU admission^a				
Low <17 point ^{b,f}	# (#%)			
High ≥17 point ^{b,f}	# (#%)			
Self-reported critical illness severity^{a,g}				
ICU length of stay (days) ^a	# (# to #)			
Time since ICU admission (months)^{a,h}				
Family to a deceased patient ^b		# (#%)		
Clinical experience (years)^a				
Employed in ICU (experience in years) ^a			# (# to #)	# (# to #)
Professional group				
Doctor ^b			# (#%)	
Nurse ^b			# (#%)	
Physiotherapist ^b			# (#%)	
Occupational therapist ^b			# (#%)	
Other ^{b,j}			# (#%)	
Research experience (years)^a				
Doctor ^b			# (# to #)	# (# to #)
Nurse ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Physiotherapist ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Occupational therapist ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Other ^{b,k}			# (#%)	# (#%)
Time doing research				
Full-time ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Part-time ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Free-time ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Highest obtained academic degree				
Bachelor			# (#%)	# (#%)
Master ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
PhD or higher ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)

(Continues)

TABLE 1 (Continued)

	Patients	Family members	Clinicians	Researchers ⁱ
Employment				
University hospital ^b				# (#%)
Non-university hospital ^b				# (#%)
University ^b				# (#%)
Other ^b				# (#%)

^a Median (Interquartile (IQR) range).

^b N (%).

^c Danish origin has at least one parent born in Denmark with Danish citizenship (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk).

^d Other than Danish origins covers 'immigrants' born abroad and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark and 'descendants' born in Denmark and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk).

^e The Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit (SMS-ICU)²⁸ is a severity score that predicts 90-day mortality with higher points meaning a higher risk of mortality. The range of points is 0–42.

^f To assure a balanced distribution of patients with higher mortality risk ≥ 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 25.3% and above) vs. lower risk < 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 22.8% and below).²⁸

^g Self-reported severity of illness assessed on a numeric score (0–10 where 0 is non-critical and 10 is most critical).

^h From either the patients' view or from the view of family members to ICU patients.

ⁱ Researchers (including clinicians and researchers) conducting research in the ICU setting or in adjacent populations of critically ill patients.

^j Other professional backgrounds will be specified in the footnote.

^k Other research experience than listed will be described.

reminders for survey completion during an overall survey window of 3 weeks from the original e-mail.

2.2.5 | Step 1, part 4: Additional Delphi rounds

Outcomes from round 1 which have reached consensus on 'not important for inclusion' will be removed to maximise efficiency by avoiding re-scoring of redundant outcomes. Remaining outcomes and new outcomes identified from round 1 will be carried forward to round 2.

Participants will be shown their own scores from round 1 and summarised scores from each of the three participant groups when re-scoring the outcomes.¹⁶ Participants can report reasons to change any scores.

Participants will repeat scoring for three planned rounds, with the possible addition of further rounds, if consensus is not reached but seems obtainable with further rounds.¹⁵

2.2.6 | Step 2, part 1: Establishing the COMS

To determine how to measure the outcomes, we will follow the guideline from the Classroom Observation Schedule to Measure Intentional Communication (COSMIC) initiative for selecting instruments for a COS.¹⁷ We also aim to narrow down a suggested measurement time point/period.

The COSMIC guideline contains four steps independent from the modified Delphi process. In the first step, a COS for the target population will be defined. In the second step, all existing outcome measurement instruments will be sought by a systematic literature search for all core outcomes. In the third step, the quality of measurement instruments will be measured. In the fourth step, a generic

COMS with suggestions for one primary instrument/definition for each outcome will be established.¹⁷

There is an ongoing scoping review concerning patient-important outcomes other than mortality¹⁸ which will provide us with insight into the most used instruments and the methodological issues around these. Decisions on suggested instruments will be based on methodological quality assessments using the Consensus-based Standards for the selection of health Measurement Instrument (COSMIN).¹⁹ We do not expect patients and family members to possess academic skills for the COSMIN assessment, and this assessment will thus be conducted by the MC.

2.2.7 | Step 2, part 2: Modified Delphi Consensus process

Findings of the consensus process for determining measurement instruments will be similarly reviewed by the PPI panel and the MC. Consensus meetings may be conducted as described in Step 1. Involvement of the PPI panel is important for the consensus process when deciding between instruments with equal COSMIN assessment to agree on instruments that are manageable.

2.3 | Analysis

2.3.1 | Attrition bias between rounds

Attrition bias between rounds may occur if non-respondents have different views from those continuing to participate and may lead to missed outcomes or overstated importance of certain outcomes.²⁰ We aim to limit attrition by pilot testing the survey

TABLE 2 Characteristics of all stakeholders who accepted to participate in the semi-structured interviews.

	Patients	Family members	Clinicians	Researchers ¹
Characteristics				
Age (years) ^a	# (# to #)	# (# to #)	# (# to #)	# (# to #)
Sex (female) ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Region of residence				
Capital Region ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Region Zealand ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Central Region ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Northern Region ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Southern Region ^b	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Origins				
Danish ^c	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Other than Danish ^d	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)	# (#%)
Admission type				
Surgical ^b	# (#%)			
Medical ^b	# (#%)			
SMS-ICU^d at ICU admission^a				
Low <17 point ^{b,f}	# (#%)			
High ≥17 point ^{b,f}	# (#%)			
Self-reported critical illness severity^{a,g}				
ICU length of stay (days) ^a	# (# to #)			
Time since ICU admission (months)^{a,h}				
Family to a deceased patient ^b		# (#%)		
Clinical experience (years)^a				
Employed in ICU (experience in years) ^a			# (# to #)	# (# to #)
Professional group				
Doctor ^b			# (#%)	
Nurse ^b			# (#%)	
Physiotherapist ^b			# (#%)	
Occupational therapist ^b			# (#%)	
Other ^{b,j}			# (#%)	
Research experience (years)^a				
Doctor ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Nurse ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Physiotherapist ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Occupational therapist ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Other ^{b,k}			# (#%)	# (#%)
Time doing research				
Full-time ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Part-time ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Free-time ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
Highest obtained academic degree				
Bachelor			# (#%)	# (#%)
Master ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)
PhD or higher ^b			# (#%)	# (#%)

(Continues)

TABLE 2 (Continued)

	Patients	Family members	Clinicians	Researchers ⁱ
Employment				
University hospital ^b				# (#%)
Non-university hospital ^b				# (#%)
University ^b				# (#%)
Other ^b				# (#%)

^a Median (Interquartile (IQR) range).

^b N (%).

^c Danish origin has at least one parent born in Denmark with Danish citizenship (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk).

^d Other than Danish origins covers 'immigrants' born abroad and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark and 'descendants' born in Denmark and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk).

^e The Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit (SMS-ICU)²⁸ is a severity score that predicts 90-day mortality with higher points meaning a higher risk of mortality. The range of points is 0–42.

^f To assure a balanced distribution of patients with higher mortality risk ≥ 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 25.3% and above) vs. lower risk < 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 22.8% and below).²⁸

^g Self-reported severity of illness assessed on a numeric score (0–10 where 0 is non-critical and 10 is most critical).

^h From either the patients' view or from the view of family members to ICU patients.

ⁱ Researchers (including clinician-researchers) conducting research in the ICU setting or in adjacent populations of critically ill patients.

^j Other professional backgrounds will be specified in the footnote.

^k Other research experience than listed will be described.

for intelligibility and face validity by observing how the survey is received. We will display the number of respondents in the completed rounds to ensure transparency as outlined in Table S1 (Supplement).

In case of more than 5% attrition, we will use simple imputation for patients not responding in round 2 (or 3) by 'Last Observation Carried Forward' (LOCF) of the previously rated items. We will display both results including imputed values (considered the primary results) and results including completed cases only.

In case of more than 20% attrition in any round but the first for each stakeholder group, we will pragmatically assess whether attrition may introduce bias³ by calculating medians with interquartile ranges (IQR) for each outcome in the previous round for all non-respondents and compare those responses with the medians and IQRs calculated for participants responding to the current round. If median values appear substantially different (assessed without formal statistical comparison), attrition bias will be considered likely. Regardless of whether attrition bias is considered likely, we will consider the imputed analyses as the primary with the complete case analyses presented in the supplementary material.

2.3.2 | Retention strategy

During the modified Delphi survey rounds, strategies for facilitating retention of participants will be implemented including personal invitations and reminders about the survey completion, provision of contact details for the research team, regular checks to verify and update contact details and optimising elements of the online survey including interface, conciseness and speed of completion. One

author will be assigned to each group of stakeholders to facilitate survey completion.

2.3.3 | Sample size

We will include a sample of 30 interviews with patients, family members and other stakeholders each (i.e. 90 interviews in total). The planned sample size for the semi-structured interviews was selected using the concept of information power considering a varied aim, not use of theory, small population, weak dialogue, and transverse analysis.²¹ The interviews will be conducted by phone and analysis strategy with the ambition of investigating the ICU admission trajectory for acutely admitted patients.²¹

The optimal sample size to achieve valid consensus in studies using modified Delphi methods is undetermined and influenced by aspects of practicality and the scope of the question.³ We estimate that 100 patients, 100 family members and 200 clinicians, researchers and other stakeholders are needed. To minimize attrition bias, which may lead to overestimations of the degree of consensus in the final results, only participants responding favourably to the primary invitation to participate will be recruited.²²

2.3.4 | Statistics

We will use simple descriptive statistics to describe the populations and Delphi responses, that is number of respondents, the number and percentages for categorical data and medians with IQRs for numeric data for the characteristics of participants. Attrition bias will be assessed according to the COMET Handbook as described above.

2.3.5 | Software used

All Delphi survey rounds will be delivered electronically using the web-based COMET DelphiManager (COMET Initiative, Liverpool, UK) (www.comet-initiative.org/delphimanager).

To support qualitative analysis of the semi-structured interviews, we will use NVivo computer software version 12 (QSR International, Melbourne, Australia). For statistics, we will use R (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria) and SAS (SAS Institute).

We will send the survey link to all eligible patients through a digitally secure electronic mail system (e-Boks) and for other stakeholders, including family members, via e-mail after obtaining their consent. For patients or family members not able to enter data in the web-based survey system, we will invite them to receive a conventional letter containing a hard copy of the survey and a pre-paid envelope to return the survey.

2.4 | Ethics and dissemination

Participants being interviewed will provide written informed consent, survey participants will consent by ticking 'confirming consent' in the survey, after being advised that participation is voluntary and before any additional responses are collected. Data will be handled confidentially and anonymously, and all participants will be able to withdraw their consent to participate at any time. We seek approval for all participating hospitals and the Danish Data Protection Agency and ensure compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The Ethical Committee for the Capital Region of Denmark has waived the need for ethical approval (H-21010116).

Subject confidentiality is secured by the participating investigators, research staff and the sponsoring institution. No information concerning the study of the data will be released to any unauthorized third party without the prior written approval of the MC.

For the COMET Delphi Manager tool, the anonymity of all participants will be ensured by individual unique identifiers and data will be stored at a secure location.

We will report the COS in accordance with the COS-STAR checklist.¹⁴ All results will be published in peer-reviewed journals and presented at international conferences.

3 | DISCUSSION

The outlined multiple method studies will develop a general COS for ICU patients.

Strengths of the study include the planned inclusion of a high number of stakeholders in the modified Delphi process and the use of semi-structured interviews. Furthermore, we will adhere

to the recommendations by the COMET Handbook and have prepared this protocol in accordance with relevant recommendations (COS-STAP).³

The outlined study comes with limitations too. Primarily, we plan to only include Danish-speaking stakeholders in our modified Delphi process and semi-structured interviews. However, we expect the Danish population, health care system and society to be generally comparable to other Scandinavian countries²³⁻²⁶ and probably also other European countries with caution for cultural diversity. Our literature search for outcomes might not be fully comprehensive as we only use two databases, but it was done pragmatically with an existing search used previously for a review.⁵ In spite of only acutely admitted ICU patients being included, we assume that outcomes in the final COS will be relevant for elective ICU patients.²⁷

4 | CONCLUSION

The outlined multiple method studies will develop a COS for general ICU patients which will help outcome selection and prioritisation in future trials conducted in the ICU and simplify comparison and pooling of individual trial results.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The Department of Intensive Care at Rigshospitalet (MNK, AG, GVK, PS, CRLB, MHM, EB, MBM, IE, AP and MOC) has received funding for other projects from the Novo Nordisk Foundation, Pfizer, Ferring Pharmaceuticals and Fresenius Kabi and conducts contract research for AM-Pharma (the REVIVAL trial). The Department of Anaesthesiology, Zealand University Hospital in Køge (SE, CBM and LMK) has received funding for other projects from the Novo Nordisk Foundation and conducts contract research for AM-Pharma (the REVIVAL trial). The Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care at Aalborg University Hospital (BSR and SRV) have received funding for other projects from the Novo Nordisk Foundation, Ministry of Higher Education and Science and conducts contract research for AM-Pharma (the REVIVAL trial). Aarhus University Hospital, Department of Intensive Care (SC) conducts contract research for AM-Pharma (the REVIVAL trial).

ORCID

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6536-0504>

Gitte Kingo Vesterlund <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5221-3938>

Camilla Bekker Mortensen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5202-3552>

Morten Hylander Møller <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6378-9673>

Bodil Steen Rasmussen <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2190-145X>

Martin Bruun Madsen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5832-2262>

Marie Oxenbøll Collet <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8387-3960>

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of the article at the publisher's website.

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Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients – a protocol.

Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients – a protocol.

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Anders Granholm, Gitte Kingo Vesterlund, Stine Estrup Damby, Praleene Sivapalan, Camilla Rahbek Lysholm Bruun, Camilla Bekker Mortensen, Lone Musaeus Poulsen, Morten Hylander Møller, Steffen Christensen, Thomas Strøm, Eva Lærkner, Anne Craveiro Brøchner, Bodil Steen Rasmussen, Stine Rom Vestergaard, Emily Barot, Martin Bruun Madsen, Ingrid Egerod, Anders Perner and Marie Oxenbøll Collet

Supplement

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Search strategy

Search strategies for publications on critical care-related core outcome sets from the systematic review conducted by Dinglas et al.¹ The search was conducted 1 May 2021.

Search strategy for PubMed:

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("acute care"[tw] OR "asystole"[tw] OR "brain injuries, traumatic"[mesh] OR "burn unit"[tw] OR "burn units"[mesh] OR "burn units"[tw] OR "cardiac arrest"[tw] OR "cardiac arrests"[tw] OR "cardiac death"[tw] OR "cardiac surgeries"[tw] OR "cardiac surgical procedures"[mesh] OR "cardiac surgery"[tw] OR "cardiopulmonary arrest"[tw] OR "cardiopulmonary arrests"[tw] OR "cardiopulmonary death"[tw] OR "coma"[mesh] OR "coma"[tw] OR "comas"[tw] OR "comatose"[tw] OR "coronary care unit"[tw] OR "coronary care units"[mesh] OR "coronary care units"[tw] OR "critical care"[mesh] OR "critical care"[tw] OR "H D U "[tw] OR "HDU"[tw] OR "HDUs"[tw] OR "heart arrest"[mesh] OR "heart arrest"[tw] OR "heart arrests"[tw] OR "heart death"[tw] OR "heart surgeries"[tw] OR "heart surgery"[tw] OR "high dependency unit"[tw] OR "high dependency units"[tw] OR "I C U "[tw] OR "I T U"[tw] OR "ICU"[tw] OR "ICUs"[tw] OR "intensive care units"[mesh] OR "intensive care units, neonatal"[mesh] OR "intensive care units, pediatric"[mesh] OR "intensive care"[tw] OR "intensive therapy unit"[tw] OR "intensive therapy units"[tw] OR "ITU"[tw] OR "ITUs"[tw] OR "mechanical ventilation"[tw] OR "PICU"[tw] OR "PICUs"[tw] OR "P I C U "[tw] OR "recovery room"[mesh] OR "respiratory care unit"[tw] OR "respiratory care units"[mesh] OR "respiratory care units"[tw] OR "sepsis"[mesh] OR "sepsis"[tw] OR "septic"[tw] OR "TBI"[tw] OR "TBIs"[tw] OR "traumatic brain injuries"[tw] OR "traumatic brain injury"[tw] OR "ventilated"[tw] OR "ventilator"[tw] OR "ventilators"[tw]) AND ("critical care outcomes"[mesh] OR "critical care outcome"[tw] OR "critical care outcomes"[tw] OR "core outcome"[tw] OR "core outcomes"[tw] OR "core set"[tw] OR "core sets"[tw] OR "core measure"[tw] OR "core measures"[tw] OR "core domain"[tw] OR "core domains"[tw])
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Search strategy for Embase:

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('acute care':ti,ab,kw OR 'asystole':ti,ab,kw OR 'traumatic brain injury'/exp OR 'burn unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'burn unit'/exp OR 'burn units':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac arrest':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac arrests':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac death':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac surgeries':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart surgery':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac surgery':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiopulmonary arrest':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiopulmonary arrests':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiopulmonary death':ti,ab,kw OR 'coma'/exp OR 'coma':ti,ab,kw OR 'comas':ti,ab,kw OR 'comatose':ti,ab,kw OR 'coronary care unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'coronary care unit'/exp OR 'coronary care units':ti,ab,kw OR 'critical care':ti,ab,kw OR 'H D U ':ti,ab,kw OR 'HDU':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart arrest'/exp OR 'heart arrest':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart arrests':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart death':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart surgeries':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart surgery':ti,ab,kw OR 'high dependency unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'high dependency units':ti,ab,kw OR 'I C U ':ti,ab,kw OR 'I T U':ti,ab,kw OR 'ICU':ti,ab,kw OR 'ICUs':ti,ab,kw OR 'intensive care'/exp OR 'intensive care unit'/exp OR 'neonatal intensive care unit'/exp OR 'pediatric intensive care unit'/exp OR 'intensive care':ti,ab,kw OR 'intensive therapy unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'intensive therapy units':ti,ab,kw OR 'ITU':ti,ab,kw OR 'ITUs':ti,ab,kw OR 'mechanical ventilation':ti,ab,kw OR 'PICU':ti,ab,kw OR 'PICUs':ti,ab,kw OR 'P I C U ':ti,ab,kw OR 'recovery room'/exp OR 'respiratory care unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'respiratory care units':ti,ab,kw OR 'sepsis'/exp OR 'sepsis':ti,ab,kw OR 'septic':ti,ab,kw OR 'TBI':ti,ab,kw OR 'TBIs':ti,ab,kw OR 'traumatic brain injuries':ti,ab,kw OR 'traumatic brain injury':ti,ab,kw OR 'ventilated':ti,ab,kw OR 'ventilator':ti,ab,kw OR 'ventilators':ti,ab,kw) AND ('critical care outcome'/exp OR 'critical care outcome':ti,ab,kw OR 'critical care outcomes':ti,ab,kw OR 'core outcome':ti,ab,kw OR 'core outcomes':ti,ab,kw OR 'core set':ti,ab,kw OR 'core sets':ti,ab,kw OR 'core measure':ti,ab,kw OR 'core measures':ti,ab,kw OR 'core domain':ti,ab,kw OR 'core domains':ti,ab,kw)
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Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients – a protocol.

Semi-structured interview (methods)

We will include patients, family members, clinicians, researchers, and other stakeholders that are adults, defined as ≥ 18 years of age. We will use purposive sampling^{2,3}, to ensure maximum variation, to reflect a range of age, sex, ethnicity, admission type (medical/surgical), Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit (SMS-ICU)⁴ (low < 17 points or high ≥ 17 points), intensive care unit (ICU) length of stay and time since patient was in the ICU; ICU length of stay for patients in the ICU and time since the patient was in the ICU for family members; and for stakeholders the number of years stakeholders have been affiliated with the ICU. All characteristics are shown in Table 1. We will include participants who are able to participate in an interview in Danish. Recruitment is expected to start at the end of 2021 and interviewing is expected to start in the spring or summer of 2022.

Recruitment of participants

Patients: all participating hospitals (Copenhagen University Hospital – Rigshospitalet, Zealand University Hospital - Køge, Odense University Hospital, Kolding Hospital, and Aalborg University Hospital) will recruit patients for interviews: 1) before they are discharged from the hospital or 2) through the outpatient clinics or 3) during follow-up for research approximately 1 year after ICU stay, including patients already in contact with the hospital as they are participating in other research project such as the Agents Intervening against Delirium in the Intensive Care Unit (AID-ICU) trial⁵ and the Conservative vs Liberal Approach to fluid therapy in Septic Shock in Intensive Care (CLASSIC) trial.⁶

Family members: include, but are not limited to spouses, friends, close or informal caregivers or next of kin, to ICU patients regardless of patient's survival. All participating hospitals will recruit family members: 1) during patients' ICU stay or 2) during follow-up on other clinical studies (as described above) or 3) from outpatient clinics or wards before hospital discharge.

Clinicians: all clinicians (including, but not limited to, doctors, nurses, physiotherapists and occupational therapists) that are involved in the treatment and care of ICU patients.

Researchers: full time/part time researchers with or without clinical work besides (clinician-researchers) who have an attentiveness and interest in improving the care and treatment in the ICU.

Other stakeholders: major funders of Danish ICU trials (including the Novo Nordisk Foundation, the Lundbeck Foundation, the Regions in Denmark, Sygeforsikringen "danmark", Innovation Fund Denmark), patient organisations (Danish Patients) and researchers from known networks in Denmark (including the

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Danish Society of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care Medicine (DASAIM) and Dansk Selskab For Sygeplejeforskning (a Danish society of nursing in research)).

Construction of interview guide

The interview guide will be developed by the research team according to the literature and adapted throughout the study. All major adaptations will be logged. The interview guide aims to elaborate thoughts and considerations regarding admission to an ICU with critical illness and sequelae and resolve what is important to the participants and how best to describe or assess health (mentally and physically). Finally, we will elaborate on which outcomes other than survival are assumed most important, i.e., what could otherwise be of importance and what could contribute enhance the patient's current situation/quality of life.

Data collection

The interviews will be conducted by phone. Different data collection strategies will ensure wider geographical and socioeconomic distribution of participants. Interviews will be digitally recorded and transcribed verbatim.

Data analysis

Data will be investigated using framework analysis consisting of familiarization, generating initial categories, construction of matrix, defining and naming themes.⁷ The analysis will follow five stages with inductive line by line coding followed by initial coding matrix construction:

- 1) We will categorise data from patients, family members, and other stakeholders, line by line with inductive coding
- 2) Construction of the initial matrix
- 3) Data arrangement in the initial matrix, condensation of matrix
- 4) Categorising data in groups, and creating meta text
- 5) Mapping stage, with construction of the final matrix and finalising themes

Analysis will be done using NVivo computer software version 12 (QSR International, Melbourne, Australia).

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Pilot test of the survey

To pilot test the survey, we invite our Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) panel (described in the main text) for cognitive interviews using the think aloud technique,¹⁴ to hear their interpretation of the drafted items, which will help us to refine the outcomes and explanations. We (the Management Committee consisting of all authors) will present the online survey and observe PPI-panel members who are not involved stakeholders while they answer the survey to ensure it is manageable. If the survey is extensively revised, the need for a second pilot test will be considered.

Tables and figures

Table S1. Distribution of stakeholders invited to the modified Delphi process (mock table)

Stakeholders outside hospital	Accepted to participate	Respondents round X ^c
	n	n (%)
Patients	#	#
Family members	#	#
Clinicians and researchers with affiliation to ICU		
Doctors	#	# (%)
Nurses	#	# (%)
Other clinicians ^a	#	# (%)
Researchers ^b	#	# (%)

^a Other professional groups and affiliations will be listed in this annotation.

^b Researchers (including clinician-researchers) conducting research in the ICU setting or in adjacent populations of critically ill patients. Those without clinical affiliation will be calculated in numbers (%) and will be listed in this annotation.

^c The list of respondents will be presented for every round repeated in the modified Delphi process.

Raw list of outcomes obtained from the search

- Abnormal time of temperature during infection
- Accidental extubation
- Acute physiology and chronic health evaluation (APACHE II) score
- Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS)
- Additional medication for agitation
- Adverse events
- Adverse events
- Alanine aminotransferase (ALT)
- All-cause mortality
- Anaemia
- Antibiotic therapy
- Antipyretic rate
- Anxiety
- Any return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC)
- Acute physiology and chronic health evaluation (APACHE IV) score
- Appetite
- At hospital discharge is independence in functional level established matching home environment
- Biochemical outcomes
- Blood gas analysis
- Blood oxygen saturation
- Blood pressure
- Blood routine test
- Body composition
- Body composition tests (ultrasound/anthropometry)
- Boredom
- Brain function
- Calcitonin
- Cardiovascular disease
- Catecholamine infusion
- Change in activities of daily living
- Change in downstream marker (e.g. interleukin-6),
- Changes in relationships
- Chest computed tomography (CT)
- Chest pain
- Chest x-ray examination
- Chloroquine blood concentration
- Circulatory function
- Clearance time of fatigue
- Clinical workload
- Cluster of differentiation (CD)-4 and CD8 T-cells count
- Coagulation function
- Coagulation outcomes
- Cognition

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- Cognition
- Cognitive function and symptoms
- Complete blood count (CBC)
- Confusion, uraemia, respiratory rate, blood pressure, age ≥ 65 years (CURB-65) pneumonia severity score
- Consciousness
- Constipation
- Contamination of packs and glass bottles
- Cost-effectiveness
- Costs (cost-effectiveness)
- Cough
- C-reactive protein (CRP)
- CT of hip
- Curative effects of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) syndrome
- Days of immobility (bed-bound)
- Days of sedation
- D-dimer
- Decreased quality of life
- Decreased walking distance
- Delirium duration*
- Delirium incidence*
- Delirium prevalence*
- Delirium resolution*
- Delirium severity*
- Delirium type*
- Delirium*
- Delivery of care
- Demand for first aid measurement
- Diabetes
- Diarrhoea
- Difficulties concentrating
- Difficulties in activity of daily living (ADL)
- Difficulties returning to work/employment
- Disability
- Discharge location
- Disease severity
- Disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) score
- Dizziness
- Duration (d) of extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO)
- Duration (d) of oxygen inhalation
- Duration (d) of supplemental oxygenation
- Duration (d)/frequency of medical ventilation
- Duration of antibiotics treatment
- Duration of hospital stay
- Duration of ICU stay

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- Duration of intubation
- Duration of weaning from mechanical ventilation?
- Dysphagia
- Electrocardiogram (ECG)
- Emotional well-being
- Endurance
- Erythrocyte sedimentation rate
- Exercise capacity and intensity
- Fatigue
- Feeding intolerance
- Feeling isolated
- Fever
- Financial impact on patient
- Financial impact on the individual
- Financial impact on the patient
- Finger oxygen improvement rate
- Flexion contractures and heterotopic ossification
- Frequency of clinical improvement (turning to ordinary or recovery)
- Frequency of hospital discharge
- Frequency of ICU admission
- Frequency of interstitial pneumonia
- Frequency of multi organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS)
- Frequency of other sequelae
- Frequency of shock
- Gas production
- Gastrointestinal discomfort
- Gastrointestinal function and symptoms
- Genetic factors/biomarkers
- Global Organ Dysfunction/Multi-organ failure
- Gratitude
- Headache
- Health care resource use
- Healthcare resource utilization (e.g., doctors' visits, need for further intervention)
- Health-related quality of life
- Health-related quality of life
- Hearing impairment
- Heart function
- Heart rate
- Hobbies
- Hospital/ICU-free survival
- Hospital-acquired infection
- Hospitalisation cost
- Hospitalisation/length of stay
- Human leukocyte antigen – DR isotype (HLA-DR)

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- ICU free days
- Interleukin (Il-10)
- Interleukin (Il-4)
- Interleukin (Il-6)
- Interleukin (Il-8)
- Immunity and antibodies
- Immunoglobulin
- Impact on family and/or caregivers
- Impact on family, caregivers or both
- Improvement of aerobic capacity
- Improvement of functional exercise capacity
- Improvement of physical function
- Improvement of respiratory muscle strength
- Improvement of skeletal muscle strength
- Incidence of antibiotic treatment
- Incidence of hypoxia
- Incidence of intensive care unit admission
- Incidence of medical complications during hospitalisation
- Incidence of shock
- Incidence of Ventilator associated pneumonia
- Incontinence
- Infections
- Intensive care unit acquired weakness
- Intensive care unit length of stay
- Interferon γ
- Interleukin (Il)-2
- Intracranial haemorrhage
- Jaw thrust manoeuvre
- Joint pain
- Kidney function
- Lack of physical strength
- Length of hospital stay
- Length of hospital stay
- Less independence
- Level of virus antibodies in blood sample
- Life participation
- Liquid balance
- Liver function
- Loneliness/isolation
- Long-term mortality rate
- Loss of taste
- Lowest oxygen saturation (SpO₂) during intubation
- Lung scarring (fibrosis)
- Lymphocyte count

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- Lymphocyte count
- Major bleeding
- Major organ failure
- Management of complex medication regimens
- Mechanical ventilation
- Mechanical ventilation duration
- Memory loss
- Mental health/emotional functioning
- Metabolic complications
- Mobility
- Mortality
- Move to nursing home
- MRI of hip
- Muscle and/or nerve function
- Muscle function, nerve function or both
- Muscle pain
- Myocardial enzymes
- Myoglobin
- National Early Warning Score (NEWS)2 score
- Nausea/vomiting
- Neurologic recovery
- Neuromuscular function
- Nightmares
- Nutrition
- Organ failure
- Other infection
- Outcomes; respiratory, thoracic and mediastinal outcomes
- Overall muscle strength
- Oxygen saturation
- Pain
- Pressure of arterial oxygen to fractional inspired oxygen concentration (PaO₂/FiO₂)-ratio
- Participation
- Patient-centred morbidity rate (health related quality of life (HRQoL), time course of return to pre-morbid function)
- Percentage of cases returning to critical care
- Percentage of cases turning to severe or critical
- Physical function
- Physical symptoms
- Physiologic consequences (extent or time to resolution of study entry criteria etc., alterations in individual physiologic variables – e.g., pressure of arterial oxygen to fractional inspired oxygen concentration (PO₂/FiO₂)-ratio, mean arterial pressure (MAP))
- Physiological or clinical (e.g., cardiac outcomes; nervous system-related outcomes)
- Physiological response to exercise
- Post-intensive care syndrome (PICS) screening at hospital discharge
- Pneumonia
- Pneumonia severity index (PSI) score

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- Pneumothorax
- Post intensive care syndrome (PICS) for family (PICS-F) before hospital discharge (PICS for family)
- Post-traumatic stress disorder
- Presence of delirium* while in hospital
- Progressing to the critical stage
- Progressing to the severe stage
- Proinflammatory cytokines
- Proportion of patient without cough
- Proportion of patient without wheezing
- Proportion of patients without fatigue
- Proportion of patients without fever
- Proportion of patients without sputum
- Proportion of pt. with negative SARS-CoV-2
- Psychological state
- Pulmonary function and symptoms
- Pulmonary function; lung function
- Pulmonary rehabilitation
- Rate of ALT recovery
- Rate of creatine kinase (CK) recovery
- Rate of mycobacteria (MB) recovery
- Rate of no requiring supplemental oxygen
- Rate of patient receiving systematic corticosteroids
- Rate of preventing mild to moderate patients from shifting to severe patients
- Rate of progressing to final stage
- Readmission/control visits
- Reintubation
- Remission rate of respiratory symptoms
- Renal function
- Resilience
- Respiratory function
- Respiratory muscle function
- Respiratory muscle function
- Respiratory muscle strength
- Respiratory rate
- Respiratory rate
- Respiratory support
- Return to work or prior activities
- Routine urine culture test
- Sadness/depression
- Satisfaction with life or personal enjoyment
- Score of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) symptoms
- Self-efficacy/management
- Sepsis/septic shock
- Sequential organ failure assessment (SOFA) score

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- Sexual function
- Sexual function and symptoms
- Short tempered
- Shortness of breath
- Shortness of breath
- Short-term morbidity rate
- Short-term mortality rate
- Single organ dysfunction/single organ failure
- Sleep
- Sleep function and symptoms
- Social roles
- Social roles, activities or relationships
- Successful extubation
- Survival
- Survival after leaving ICU
- Survived event
- Susceptibility to repeated infections
- Sustained return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC)
- Swallowing function and symptoms
- Temperature
- The proportion of inpatients
- The rate of discontinuations due to adverse events
- The time when the condition became worse
- Therapeutic target (alteration in target (e.g. reduced tumour necrosis factor (TNF)))
- Time delirium and coma free days
- Time delirium free
- Time of ALT recovery
- Time of Mb recovery
- Time of Mb recovery
- Time of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 ribonucleic acid (SARS-CoV-2 RNA) turns to negative
- Time of using assisted breathing
- Time to 2019-nCoV real time – polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) negativity
- Time to CD4 t cell recovery
- Time to CD8 cell recovery
- Time to clinical improvement (TTCI)
- Time to cough disappearance
- Time to cough reported as mild
- Time to CRP recovery
- Time to defervescence (the subsidence of a fever)
- Time to delirium onset
- Time to dyspnoea reported as absent
- Time to gastrointestinal symptoms reported as absent
- Time to hospital discharge
- Time to national early warning score (NEWS2) of lower or equal to 2 maintained for 24 hours

Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients – a protocol.

- Time to release for isolation
- Time to resolution
- Time to treatment failure
- Tinnitus
- Total costs
- Tracheostomy
- Troponin
- Tube placement (time needed or success)
- Tumour necrosis factor (TNF)-alfa
- Type of residence
- Type of residence
- Use of antipsychotic medications
- Use of non-invasive ventilation (NIV)
- Ventilator free days
- Ventilators parameters
- Viral load or clearance
- Vision impairment
- Walking distance
- Weakness
- Weight loss
- Wishing to have died

*Delirium occurs several times, but with different definitions assessing different perspectives.

All outcomes listed are from core outcome sets or essential outcomes defined by researchers in a similar process as development of a core outcome set obtained during the systematic search.⁸⁻²⁴

Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients – a protocol.

Core Outcome Set-Standards Protocol Items: The COS-STAP Statement Checklist

SECTION/TOPIC	ITEM No.	CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE NUMBER
TITLE/ABSTRACT			
Title	1a	Identify in the title that the paper describes the protocol for the planned development of a COS	1
Abstract	1b	Provide a structured abstract	2
INTRODUCTION			
Background and objectives	2a	Describe the background and explain the rationale for developing the COS, and identify the reasons why a COS is needed and the potential barriers to its implementation	3
	2b	Describe the specific objectives with reference to developing a COS	3
Scope	3a	Describe the health condition(s) and population(s) that will be covered by the COS	4
	3b	Describe the intervention(s) that will be covered by the COS	4
	3c	Describe the context of use for which the COS is to be applied	4
METHODS			
Stakeholders	4	Describe the stakeholder groups to be involved in the COS development process, the nature of and rationale for their involvement and also how the individuals will be identified; this should cover involvement both as members of the research team and as participants in the study	4-5
Information sources	5a	Describe the information sources that will be used to identify the list of outcomes. Outline the methods or reference other protocols/papers	5-6
	5b	Describe how outcomes may be dropped/combined, with reasons	6-7
Consensus process	6	Describe the plans for how the consensus process will be undertaken	6-7
Consensus definition	7a	Describe the consensus definition	6-7
	7b	Describe the procedure for determining how outcomes will be added/combined/dropped from consideration during the consensus process	7
ANALYSIS			
Outcome scoring/feedback	8	Describe how outcomes will be scored and summarised, describe how participants will receive feedback during the consensus process	7
Missing data	9	Describe how missing data will be handled during the consensus process	9
ETHICS and DISSEMINATION			
Ethics approval/informed consent	10	Describe any plans for obtaining research ethics committee/institutional review board approval in relation to the consensus process and describe	11

Development of a core outcome set for general intensive care unit patients – a protocol.

		how informed consent will be obtained (if relevant)	
Dissemination	11	Describe any plans to communicate the results to study participants and COS users, inclusive of methods and timing of dissemination	11
ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION			
Funders	12	Describe sources of funding, role of funders	13
Conflicts of interest	13	Describe any potential con	13

From: Kirkham JJ, Gorst S, Altman DG, et al. (2019) Core Outcome Set-STANDARDISED Protocol Items: the COS-STAP Statement. *Trials* 20, 116. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-019-3230-x>²⁵

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PAPER VI

External validation of a core outcome set developed in Denmark for the general ICU patient – protocol amendment to an ongoing modified Delphi consensus process

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External validation of a core outcome set developed in Denmark for the general ICU patient – protocol amendment to an ongoing modified Delphi consensus process

Contributors:

Maj-Brit N Kjær, Camilla R L Bruun, Anders Granholm, Morten Hylander Møller, Bodil S Rasmussen, Camilla Bekker Mortensen, Lone Musaeus Poulsen, Thomas Strøm, Eva Laerkner, Anne Craveiro Brøchner, Trine Haberlandt, Patricia Angel, Stine Rom Vestergaard, Anne-Marie Gellert Bunzel, Louise Stenbryggen Herløv, Anna Holm, Anders Perner, Maria Cronhjort, Anna Schandl, Jon Henrik Laake, Kristin Hofsf, Frederik Keus, Fredrike Blokzijl, Carmen Pfortmüller, Marlies Ostermann, Jade M Cole, Matt P Wise, Wojciech Szczeklik, Ania Wludarczyk, Tomas Jovaiša, Maurizio Cecconi, Martin Ingi Sigurdsson, Marek Nalos, Johanna Hästbacka, Naomi Hammond, Edward Litton, Kimberley Haines, Sheila N Myatra, Vivekanand Jha, Bharath Kumar Tirupakuzhi Vijayaraghavan, Balasubramanian Venkatesh, Ingrid Egerod and Marie O Collet

Corresponding author:

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær
RN, MSc (Health Science), PhD student
Department of Intensive Care
Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet
Blegdamsvej 9, DK-2100, Copenhagen, Denmark
E-mail: maj-brit.noerregaard.kjaer@regionh.dk

Background

Core outcome sets (COS) are essential for ensuring consistent reporting of patient-important outcome measures across clinical trials (1–3), and may also be used for quality improvement, benchmarking, and for informing practice and policy. To the best of our knowledge, there is no COS applicable to general intensive care unit (ICU) patients, but there are disease-specific COS including acute respiratory failure, Covid-19, and delirium (4). For critical care burns, and aneurysmal subarachnoid haemorrhage systematic reviews evaluating core outcomes have been conducted, but COS has not yet been developed (5,6).

In Denmark, we are currently developing a COS for the general ICU patient using a modified Delphi consensus process involving 380 invited stakeholders for the survey rounds (7). We invited 100 patients, 100 family members, 180 multi-professional clinicians (doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, occupational therapists, amongst others) and researchers. Of the 380 invited persons, 264 took part in the development.

External validation of a COS in other countries (8–10), may enhance the COS's applicability in healthcare systems characterised by different population cultures, socioeconomic composition, and funding models (e.g. private vs public funded health care). This amendment describes an external validation process, which was not originally planned when we began developing the primary COS in Denmark (7). Through an external validation process, we aim to explore whether the primary COS can be applied to other settings, and therefore represent a wider range of perspectives on what is important to patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers.

Methods

We approached collaborators in other countries through the Collaboration for Research in Intensive Care (CRIC) – www.cric.nu.

We invited clinicians and researchers in the following countries: Australia, Czech Republic, Finland, Iceland, India, Italy, Lithuania, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America. Participants in each country were asked to set up one or more research panels (described below) to discuss the primary COS and its applicability in their national context. We plan to present the primary COS in November 2023 for the CRIC collaborators and all participating countries, with the goal of external validation and dissemination in the spring of 2024.

Consensus on external validation

Our understanding of how to externally validate a COS is currently limited. We discussed the concept of external validation with the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) initiative and decided on a pragmatic, and comprehensive approach. The overall process is to share the primary COS with participants in other countries and work towards achieving consensus on an internationally validated COS.

We will assess the applicability of the COS in other countries and determine if the primary COS or single outcomes, can be adopted as it is, or if adaptations are needed to align with the national context, with the goal of reaching broad consensus (11) (Figure 1).

If a national research panel finds the COS applicable and decides to adopt it, it will be considered as externally validated for that specific country. If a national research panel rejects the COS, it will not be considered externally validated in that specific country, and this decision will be transparently documented.

If a national research panel agrees that the COS is applicable but requires adaptations, it will be transparently documented. The core outcomes will finally be discussed across countries with the aim to reaching agreement on whether the COS can be externally validated or if further adjustments are needed to reach consensus.

Figure 1. The process to reaching consensus on the external validation of the COS

Preparation and research panels

Each participating country will assemble one or more research panel(s) consisting of ICU survivors, family members, clinicians, and researchers involved in the treatment and care of ICU patients. The number of research panels in each country depends on health system differences and socio-cultural variations within the country. The decision to have one or more research panels in each country depends on the presence of differences across the country that could potentially impact values and preferences regarding outcomes, as well as resource considerations. National investigators will make this decision.

The composition of the panel will be determined by what is feasible. The number of research panels and distribution of panel members will be documented in the minutes template (Appendix 1). Patients and family members can be approached either at the time of discharge or at follow-up in outpatient clinics or other legally accessible settings, as mandated by relevant legislation. We suggest maintaining a balanced composition of approximately 10 individuals in each research panel, ensuring representation of both patient/family members and clinicians/researchers.

We will provide guidance on how to establish and manage research panels in an ICU setting.

Planning the external validation

Researchers from the countries listed above convened online in August 2023 to discuss how to initiate research panels and how to proceed with the external validation meetings. Following the discussion, participants were requested to appoint a national contact responsible for organising the research panels within their respective country, ensuring that invitations and recruitment is done well in advance and that external validation meetings has been conducted before the final consensus meeting across all countries (Figure 1).

Prior to the external validation meeting, all participants will receive an English translation of the primary COS developed in Denmark, including the underlying rationale. In addition, participating countries will receive all outcomes considered in the survey in the modified Danish Delphi consensus process (Figure 2).

These outcomes served as the basis for the final consensus process and the final primary COS (Figure 1). These documents will provide transparent insight into which outcomes were deemed important during the survey rounds.

Each country will be responsible for translating the COS back-and-forth into their local language to ensure accurate comprehension when making comparisons with the primary COS. We recommend that the translators are native speakers of the local language with a solid command of the English language.

Conducting the external validation

We recommend discussing the primary COS in a meeting of up to three hours duration conducted in the research panel members' native language (Figure 2).

Figure 2. A diagram showing the process of the external validation meeting with the research panel. The meeting agenda is informed by the left column, and the possibility of additional knowledge to inform the panels is provided by the right column. Together, this information will assist the research panel in reaching a conclusion to either adopt, adapt, or reject.

We recommend that the meetings begin with an introduction to the purpose of the meeting and all participants, with the aim of creating a safe environment for sharing thoughts and perspectives.

The research panel will be trained to understand the principles of randomised clinical trials, the importance of outcomes in trials and in general, and the validity of a COS repeated across trials. The teaching material will be based on a video developed by the COMET Initiative

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D0Q9vypSYeE>.

The research panel will be engaged in a dialogue to assess whether they can adopt the primary COS in their own country, whether it is not applicable and thereby to be rejected. This decision will not be reached

through voting, but through discussion and consensus-building. If there are any adaptations from the COS, these should be outlined in the minutes, along with whether the consensus is that the primary COS can be validated with some adaptations or restrictions.

Minutes are crucial as they serve as field notes for the content of the discussion. The minutes will be translated into English for sharing with the author group and will serve as documentation for participating research panels' perspective on the primary COS.

Synthesising the external validation

Following the completion of the external validation meetings by all research panels, a consensus meeting involving all participating countries is set to take place in January 2024.

In this meeting, each country will present their conclusions and minutes, serving as documentation for any adaptations or adjustments required to arrive at a consensus on a COS or rejection. This information is integral to the subsequent discussion, with the aim of achieving consensus on an externally validated COS. We expect that participants from each country will be able to reach an agreement (consensus) on which core outcomes can be externally validated and which ones require adjustments (adaptation) before being incorporated into the externally validated COS.

Other countries to be included in the future

In the future more countries are welcome to use or possibly validate the externally validated final COS. We would then recommend that they get in touch with the corresponding author and proceed to establish a research panel in their country, following the same process as described above, but without the final consensus meeting across countries. The discussion with the research panel will mainly focus on whether the specific country can adopt the final COS. All countries, as well as additional countries that have validated the use of the externally validated COS with a research panel will be listed on the intensive care platform trials website, www.incept.dk.

Ethics

All participants involved in the research panels do so voluntarily and may opt to leave the panel at their discretion without any explanation or obligations. Although meetings will be confidential, minutes will be documented, including the composition of the panel (patient, family, clinician, or researcher), without collecting other demographic details. If the meeting is to be recorded, panel members must provide their consent prior to the recording. All participating countries must comply with national and international ethical obligations.

Evaluation of patient and public involvement

We intend to evaluate the output of the patient and public involvement (PPI) (12). We will report the extent of PPI, adhering to the short form of the Guidance for Reporting Involvement of Patients and the

Public (GRIPP2) checklist (13). We will report both the positive and negative output of PPI and summarise successful aspects and areas that presented challenges. This will be evaluated in the minutes (Appendix 1).

Authorship

Those who take responsibility for the research panels and who actively engage in the external validation process will be credited with authorship; otherwise, they will be acknowledged for their contribution in the design phase.

Perspectives

With the outlined external validation of the ongoing COS in general ICU patients, our goal is to investigate the applicability of the primary COS in diverse settings and other countries. This effort will help us capture a broader spectrum of perspectives regarding what outcomes are important to patients and their family members.

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External validation COS minutes

Country:

Number of research panels:

Number of participants	
Patients	
Relatives	
Nurses	
Doctors	
Physiotherapists	
Occupational therapists	
Researchers	
Others (describe)	

Introduction (How did you do?)

Evaluation of the meeting (what worked well and what did not?)

PAPER VII

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

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A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Abstract

Purpose Randomised clinical trials should ideally use harmonised outcomes that are important to patients and to facilitate meta-analyses and ensuring generalisability. Core outcome sets for specific subsets of ICU patients exist, e.g., respiratory failure, delirium, and COVID-19, but not for ICU patients in general. Accordingly, we aimed to develop a core outcome set for adult general ICU patients.

Methods We developed a core outcome set in Denmark following the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) Handbook. We used a modified Delphi consensus process with multiple methods design, including literature review, survey, semi-structured interviews, and discussions with initially five Danish research panels, involving adult ICU survivors, family members, clinicians, and researchers. The core outcome set was internationally validated in local panels in 14 countries and revised accordingly.

Results We identified 329 published outcomes, of which 50 were included in the 264 participant Delphi survey. After 82 semi-structured survey participant interviews no additional outcomes were added. The first survey round was completed by 249 (94%) participants, and 202 (82%) contributed to the final third round. The initial core outcome set comprised six core outcomes. International validation involved 217 research panel members and resulted in the final core outcome set of survival, free of life support, free of delirium, out of hospital, health-related quality of life, and cognitive function.

Conclusions We developed and internationally validated a core outcome set with six core outcomes to be used in research, specifically clinical trials involving adult general ICU patients.

Keywords: intensive care, intensive care unit, critical care, core outcome set, patient and public involvement, patient-important outcomes

Authors

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær^{1,2}, Camilla Rahbek Lysholm Bruun¹, Anders Granholm^{1,2}, Morten Hylander Møller^{1,2,3}, Bodil Steen Rasmussen^{2,4}, Camilla Bekker Mortensen⁵, Lone Musaeus Poulsen^{2,5}, Thomas Strøm^{2,6}, Eva Laerkner⁶, Anne Craveiro Brøchner^{2,7}, Trine Haberlandt⁷, Anne-Marie Gellert Bunzel⁴, Louise Stenbryggen Herløv⁵, Anna Holm⁸, Praleene Sivapalan¹, Stine Estrup¹, Maria Cronhjort^{2,9,10}, Anna Schandl^{9,11}, Jon Henrik Laake^{2,12}, Kristin Hofsvold^{2,13,14}, Fredrike Blokzijl¹⁵, Frederic Keus¹⁵, Carmen Andrea Pfortmueller^{2,16}, Marlies Ostermann^{2,17}, Jade M Cole¹⁸, Matt P Wise^{2,18}, Wojciech Szczeklik^{2,19}, Anna Wludarczyk¹⁹, Tomas Jovaiša²⁰, Maurizio Cecconi^{21,22}, Martin Ingi Sigurdsson^{2,23,24}, Marek Nalos^{2,25}, Johanna Hästbacka^{2,26}, Marja Mäkinen²⁷, Naomi Hammond^{28,29}, Edward Litton^{30,31}, Kimberley Haines^{32,33}, Sheila Nainan Myatra³⁴, Bharath Kumar Tirupakuzhi Vijayaraghavan^{35,36}, Kavita Yadav³⁶, Vivekanand Jha^{29,36,37,38}, Balasubramanian Venkatesh^{28,39}, Ingrid Egerod¹, Anders Perner^{1,2,3}, and Marie O Collet¹

¹ Department of Intensive Care, Copenhagen University Hospital - Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

² Collaboration for Research in Intensive Care (CRIC), Copenhagen, Denmark

³ Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Science, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

⁴ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg

⁵ Department of Anaesthesiology, Zealand University Hospital, Denmark

⁶ Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care, Odense University Hospital, Odense

⁷ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Lillebælt Hospital, Kolding, Denmark

⁸ Department of Intensive Care, Aarhus University Hospital, Aarhus

⁹ Department of Clinical Science and Education, Södersjukhuset, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

¹⁰ Department of Clinical Sciences, Danderyd Hospital, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

¹¹ Department of Perioperative and intensive care, Södersjukhuset, Stockholm, Sweden

¹² Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care Medicine and Department of Research and Development, Division of Emergencies and Critical Care, Rikshospitalet, Oslo University Hospital, Norway

¹³ Department of Postoperative and Intensive Care Nursing, Division of Emergencies and Critical Care, Oslo University Hospital, Oslo, Norway

¹⁴ Lovisenberg Diaconal University College, Oslo, Norway

¹⁵ Department of Critical Care, University Medical Center Groningen, University of Groningen, The Netherlands

¹⁶ Department of Intensive Care Medicine, Inselspital, University Hospital Bern, Bern, Switzerland

¹⁷ Department of Intensive Care, Guy's and St Thomas' Hospital, London, The United Kingdom

¹⁸ Adult Critical Care, University Hospital of Wales, Cardiff

¹⁹ Jagiellonian University Medical College - Centre for Intensive Care and Perioperative Medicine

²⁰ Vilnius University, Faculty of Medicine, Clinic of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care

²¹ Department of Biomedical Sciences, Humanitas University, 20072 Pieve Emanuele, Milan, Italy

²² Department of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care, IRCCS Humanitas Research Hospital, 20089 Rozzano, Milan, Italy

²³ Faculty of Medicine, University of Iceland, Reykjavik Iceland

²⁴ Landspítali – the National University Hospital of Reykjavik, Iceland

²⁵ Medical Intensive Care Unit, 1st Department of Internal Medicine, Charles University, Faculty of Medicine, Teaching Hospital and Biomedical Center in Pilsen, Pilsen, Czech Republic

²⁶ Tampere University Hospital, Wellbeing Services County of Pirkanmaa and Tampere University, Faculty of Medicine and Health Technology, Tampere, Finland

²⁷ Department of Emergency Medicine and Services, Helsinki University and Helsinki University Hospital, Helsinki, Finland

²⁸ The George Institute for Global Health, University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia

²⁹ Malcolm Fisher Department of Intensive Care, Royal North Shore Hospital, Sydney, Australia

³⁰ Intensive Care Unit, Fiona Stanley Hospital, Robin Warren Drive, Murdoch, Western Australia

³¹ School of Medicine, University of Western Australia, Crawley, Western Australia

³² Department of Physiotherapy, Western Health

³³ Department of Critical Care, Melbourne Medical School, The University of Melbourne

³⁴ Department of Anaesthesiology, Critical Care and Pain, Tata Memorial Hospital, Homi Bhabha National Institute, Mumbai, India

³⁵ Apollo Hospitals, Chennai, India

³⁶ The George Institute for Global Health, New Delhi, India

³⁷ Prasanna School of Public Health, Manipal Academy of Medical Sciences, India

³⁸ School of Public Health, Imperial College, London, UK

³⁹ Department of Intensive Care, Gold Coast University Hospital, Australia.

Corresponding author:

Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær

RN, MSc (Health Science), PhD student

Department of Intensive Care

Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet

Blegdamsvej 9, DK-2100, Copenhagen, Denmark

E-mail: maj-brit.noerregaard.kjaer@regionh.dk

Introduction

Outcomes assessed in randomised clinical trials (RCTs) should ideally be important to patients and used consistently across trials to facilitate comparisons, generalisability, and valid meta-analyses to inform clinical guidelines [1, 2]. Acutely admitted intensive care unit (ICU) patients have a high mortality [3–5], hence this outcome is frequently used and often hypothesised to be affected by the interventions assessed in clinical trials in the ICU setting [6]. However, ICU survivors often report experiencing persistent physical, cognitive, and mental impairments [7–9], aspects that are not covered by survival alone.

Outcome choices and definitions in critical care RCTs vary substantially, as illustrated by a recent scoping review revealing 103 distinct outcomes for assessing functional, neurological, and cognitive aspects and 29 distinct outcomes for health-related quality of life (HRQoL) [10]. The inconsistency in choices of outcomes and the definitions across RCTs involving ICU populations presents a challenge for comparison of trial results and evidence synthesis [10–13]. Therefore, it is important to establish a standardised approach to outcomes and measurements in [11, 14–16]. Involvement of patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers adds substantial value to discussions and prioritisation of outcomes [17–19].

Several core outcomes set (COS) have been developed for specific subsets of the ICU population, such as acute respiratory failure, delirium, or COVID-19, or for interventions, e.g., rehabilitation. However, there is no COS for the broad population of adult general ICU patients [7, 20–23], who do not fit into specific subsets, and may have a range of impairments.

The Intensive Care Platform Trial (INCEPT, www.incept.dk) will focus on assessing frequently used interventions in acutely ill ICU patients and has a need for a COS for the general ICU patient.

The aim of this study was to develop and internationally validate a generic COS for adult general ICU patients, regardless of the intervention assessed in the trials and involving a diversity of patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers with lived ICU experience.

Methods

We conducted a study using multiple methods design to develop a COS. Our approach incorporated a modified Delphi consensus process, and integrated a literature review, surveys, semi-structured interviews, and international external validation. The work took place between February 2021 and February 2024; the study was registered in the Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials (COMET) database (<https://comet-initiative.org/Studies/Details/1882>), and conducted following a published protocol [24]. The COS was developed in accordance with the COMET initiative [11] and reported according to the Core Outcome Set-STAndards for Reporting (COS-STAR) Statement [25], and Guidance for Reporting Involvement of Patients and the Public short form [26] (checklists in the electronic supplementary material (ESM)).

In line with the publicly registered protocol amendment [27], we conducted an international (external) validation of the initial COS. This involved international sites from the Collaboration for Research in Intensive Care (CRIC) network and its collaborators. The international validation process was initiated in November 2023 and completed in February 2024.

Participants

Stakeholder involvement

The steering committee (listed in author contributions) established research panels in Denmark to facilitate the involvement of persons with lived experience being adult ICU survivors (patients), family members, multi professional health care workers (clinicians), and researchers. The Danish research panels actively participated in condensing outcomes identified in the literature review. They were involved in developing survey questions, ensuring their cognitive validity through initial and inter-survey evaluations. Additionally, international research panels were established for the international validation (Table S1, ESM).

Survey and interview

We invited patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers from Denmark to participate in the Delphi survey and/or interviews. We aimed to include 400 participants: 100 patients, 100 family members and 200 multi professional ICU clinicians and researchers in the survey [24]. In addition, we targeted a total of 90 individual interviews: 30 patients, 30 family members, and 30 ICU clinicians or researchers. We recruited ICU survivors and family members directly in ICUs and via other ongoing research projects [24]. Clinicians and researchers were recruited via the steering committees' clinical- and research network. The sampling of participants aimed at balancing the distribution considering age, sex, ethnicities, admission type, risk of

mortality above and below 25% (defined by the Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit (SMS-ICU) score [28]), ICU length of stay, and time since ICU stay (details in ESM). We collected demographic and clinical data for the survey participants and interviewees (Table S2-S3, ESM) [24].

Process

Figure 1 illustrates the process for developing a COS involving a modified Delphi consensus process (step 1-4) and an additional internationally validation of the COS (step 5-6).

Step 1

Two authors (MNK and SE) independently and in duplicate conducted an initial literature review to identify relevant outcomes, results were compared and merged to one list of outcomes (search string and full list of outcomes in the ESM, Table S4) [24].

We conducted multiple meetings in Danish research panels to identify important outcomes, using the nominal group technique with face-to-face discussion in small groups aiming for immediate consensus [29]. These meetings helped to identify the most essential outcomes to inform the survey [29].

Step 2

Meetings were held between survey rounds to reach consensus on removal and inclusion of outcomes suggested in the first survey round. Participants in the Delphi survey rated the importance of an outcome on a Likert scale from 1-9 [11]. Ratings were categorised as follows: 1-3 the outcome was considered 'not important', 4-6 'important, but not critical', and 7-9 'critical' [24].

Consensus definition

Within each stakeholder group (patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers) consensus for an outcome was achieved when two criteria were met: 1) $\geq 70\%$ of the participants rated the outcome as 'critical' (a score ≥ 7), and 2) no more than $\leq 15\%$ of the participants rated the outcome 'not important' (≤ 3) [11, 24]. In the second and third survey rounds, participants were provided with their own score, the score from all four groups, and a summary score.

Step 3

Following the final survey round, four research panels (the fifth research panel withdrew due to no patients in the panel at the time) met to reach consensus on the most important outcomes.

Step 4

Subsequently, the steering committee convened to obtain consensus on the initial COS following review of comments on several suggested outcomes from the research panels.

Step 5

The international steering committee (listed in author contributions) familiarised themselves with the modified Delphi consensus process. This involved studying the condensed outcomes in the survey, reviewing the survey results, and understanding the rationale behind the initial COS (ESM, page 23). Investigators from each country established local research panels (Figure 1, Step 5). International research panels were briefed on the initial COS and its underlying rationale. Utilising the nominal group technique with face-to-face discussion in smaller groups [29], all countries discussed each single core outcome and reached a consensus on whether to adopt them as they were, adapt them (i.e., accept with changes), or reject them. Minutes from the meetings are presented in the ESM Table S5. Two online meetings, due to time zones, including the international steering committee, was convened on January 30, 2024, to address all issues raised during the international validation process.

Consensus definition

For the international validation, a predefined cut-off value for consensus was not established. However, the protocol amendment outlined, a transparent process for all participating countries, ensuring that any issues raised during the consensus process discussions were documented [27].

Step 6

The steering committee considered the feedback from the international research panels and revised the wording of the COS accordingly. The revised COS was then reassessed by the Danish and international research panels and approved.

Analysis

For the qualitative analysis, the semi-structured interviews were transcribed (Microsoft Word 2016, Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington), and were then reviewed by the research team (MNK, CRLB, AMGB, AH, MOC) who identified potentially new outcomes. All survey rounds in the Delphi consensus process were delivered electronically using the web based DelphiManager software version 5.0 (COMET, University of Liverpool, Liverpool; www.comet-initiative.org/delphimanager). For statistical analyses, we used R (R Core Team, Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria) version 4.2.2, and Microsoft Excel 2016 (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington).

We used descriptive statistics to report the population, ratings, and responses of survey rounds with frequencies and proportions for categorical data and medians and interquartile ranges for numeric data. Less than 20% of data were missing. As per protocol, missing data were handled by carrying the last observation forward (further details in the ESM, Table S6) [24].

Ethics and consent

All Danish participants in the survey and interviews provided written informed consent either by signature (interviews) or ticking confirmed consent in the survey registration. All data were handled confidentially, and participants could withdraw their consent anytime. The Danish Data Protection Agency and Ethical Committee for the Capital Region waived the need for ethical committee assessment (H-21010116).

Results

Participants

A total of 380 participants took part in the Delphi survey, of whom 90 were invited for interviews by quota sampling [30]; 82 completed the interviews. The inclusion flow and response rate are presented in Figure 2 and characteristics of the survey participants are presented in Table 1 (all characteristics are presented in ESM, Table S2-S3).

A total of 217 research panel members participated in the development of the COS (ESM, Table S1). The 4 research panels in Denmark had a total of 39 members (47 in the 5 initial panels) consisting of 8 patients, 5 family members, 17 clinicians, and 9 researchers. The 17 international research panels had a total of 178 members consisting of 46 patients, 26 family members, 60 clinicians, and 46 researchers (ESM, Table S4).

Step 1

First, the 329 outcomes from the literature review were screened for duplicates by MNK, CBM, PS, SE, LMP, EL, and MOC and with thematic analysis the outcomes were condensed in categories and translated to Danish. The Danish research panels reached consensus on condensing the outcomes 50 outcomes, more details in the ESM.

Step 2

The 82 interviews provided 9 additional outcomes to be considered (ESM, Table S7), but the Danish research panels concluded that they were already covered by the initial 50 outcomes.

In response to comments received during the first survey round and uncertainties raised by our Danish research panels, we adjusted the second survey round while maintaining the same set of 50 outcomes (ESM, Table S8). For all three rounds, we generated graphs depicting the scores on the Likert scale from 1-9 for each outcome and distributed them to all survey participants (Figure S1-S150, ESM).

Overall, the 50 outcomes were all considered important for inclusion (Figure S151, ESM). There was more variation among clinicians compared with patients and family members (Figure S152, ESM). The largest decline in response rates from the first to the final round was among family members and clinicians (Table S6, ESM).

Step 3

Informed by the survey findings, the Danish research panels convened at separate consensus meetings. Each panel, prioritized between 9 and 13 outcomes for inclusion in the COS (Figure 1 and ESM, Table S8). After removing overlaps, a total of 19 unique outcomes emerged. One additional outcome, suggested by one research panel, was included to be assessed by the steering committee for the initial COS.

Step 4

From the 19 outcomes, the steering committee agreed on six core outcomes, including the four that were deemed 'critical' by all Danish panels, thus defining the initial, Danish COS (Figure 3). Other outcomes were discussed, such as 'health-economic consequences of a treatment in ICU', 'discharge location after hospitalisation', and particularly 'overall well-being'. 'Well-being' may be considered part of HRQoL after ICU, and there was consensus not to include the additional discussed outcomes in the COS (ESM, Table S9).

Step 5

Seventeen research panels in 13 countries (excluding Denmark) validated the initial COS (ESM, Table S1 and Table S10). Detailed minutes from all international research panels are provided in ESM, Table S5.

Three core outcomes were generally accepted: 'survival', 'free of life support', and 'HRQoL'. During the international validation process, discussions were centred on the other initial core outcomes. It was considered for 'days alive without coma or delirium' that coma and delirium could not reasonably be amalgamated into a single outcome measure, and it was difficult to define coma and assess delirium, with delirium being a fluctuating mental state. 'Days alive out of hospital', and 'cognitive function' were rejected by one panel (5%), while three panels (14%) suggested that both outcomes should be adapted. 'Days alive out of hospital' should incorporate returning to home or previous level of function and 'cognitive function' could be considered as a domain of the HRQoL outcome.

The initial COS was revised based on the minutes from the international consensus meeting. An updated COS was then presented for feedback from the Danish and international research panels (Table 2, Figure 3).

Step 6

The final internationally validated COS included survival, free of life support, free of delirium, out of hospital, HRQoL, and cognitive function. The COS reached unanimous consensus on 'survival', 'free of life support', and 'health-related quality of life'. The remaining three outcomes had at least 90% consensus. For 'out of hospital', two panels (10%) recommended adapting it to include 'returning to pre-ICU condition'.

One panel (5%) rejected 'free of delirium' because of practicalities and tools around assessing delirium (ESM, Page 228). Regarding 'cognitive function', two panels (10%) recommended adaptation to include this measure in HRQoL (Table 2, Figure 3).

Discussion

We employed a multiple methods study incorporating a 3-round modified Delphi survey and an international validation process. This resulted in consensus of 6 core outcomes for adult, general ICU patients being: ‘survival’, ‘free of life support’, ‘free of delirium’, ‘out of hospital’, ‘HRQoL’, and ‘cognitive function’.

The inclusion of ‘survival’, ‘HRQoL’, and ‘cognitive function’ align with the COS for acute respiratory failure developed by Needham and colleagues [23, 31, 32]. However, our COS diverges by not including ‘muscle and/or nerve function’ and ‘pulmonary function’, likely relevant for patients with acute respiratory failure [32]. Conversely, our COS includes ‘free of life support’, ‘free of delirium’, and ‘out of hospital’, which were not included by Needham et al. Other core outcomes, including pain, mental health, and physical function, were all discussed during our consensus meetings. Although, ultimately not included in our COS, these will be considered when developing the subsequent core outcome measurement set.

Delirium was a critical outcome during all three rounds of the Delphi survey involving various stakeholders. In the international validation, it was highlighted due to its frequent occurrence and its burdensome nature for ICU patients, family members, and clinicians. It was acknowledged that delirium is a fluctuating state that can be challenging to detect [33]. Rose and colleagues developed a COS specifically for research interventions that aim to treat or prevent delirium in critically ill patients, underscoring the importance of this outcome [34].

The usability of our COS is somewhat constrained until the next step, which involves exact definitions, including the selection of appropriate instruments for their measurement and the timing of their assessments [11, 24]. Our future development of a standardised core outcome measurement set will also adhere to the COMET Handbook and COnsensus-based Standards for the selection of health status Measurement Instruments (COSMIN) initiatives [11, 35] and will involve the established research panels.

Strengths and limitations

The strengths of this study. First, a diverse stakeholder involvement, which includes patients, family, and clinicians and researchers. Second, we actively involved stakeholders throughout the entire process and ensured well-balanced consensus meetings using nominal group technique [29]. Third, from the outset, we proactively planned for stakeholder inclusion within the modified Delphi process [24]. Fourth, the semi-structured interviews represented an opportunity to potentially reveal outcomes that had not been

identified in our literature search. Fifth, we adhered rigorously to the modified Delphi process as described in the COMET Handbook. We also published the protocol before study commencement, following relevant COS-STAR recommendations [11]. Sixth, the Delphi process exhibited a high response rate without the necessity for response imputation. However, distinguishing between COS and the core outcome measurement set (instruments) posed a challenge during the consensus discussions, as some core outcomes definitions are influenced by how they are assessed. Seventh, we opted to enhance the COS relevance by an international validation process, encouraged by commenting on the published protocol to incorporate a broader context [27, 36]. This additional step aimed to strengthen the applicability of the initial COS. Consensus discussions in native languages further improved the applicability and generalisability of the COS. Furthermore, we anticipate that the international research panels will continue contributing to research in intensive care, as proven successful in other medical specialties [37].

Limitations of this study. First, the modified Delphi consensus process was confined to Denmark. Second, the decision to involve international collaborators in the validation process was made *post hoc*, following the completion of the Danish COS as outlined in the protocol [24]. We subsequently, registered the amendment to the protocol before conducting the international validation [27]. This approach offered a practical way of involving multiple international sites in the consensus development of a COS even though the panels may not have been fully representative of their countries. Third, convincing colleagues in other countries to the use of the COS may be challenged based on what is considered important in clinical practice and practise variations. In the context of randomised trials, random allocation will reduce this challenge. Additionally, we collaborated with a diverse array of countries, each with its unique case mix and economic circumstances, enhancing the generalisability of our findings. Despite varied perspectives and robust discussions during the consensus process, the final COS emerged consistently across all countries, underscoring the rigor of its development.

Conclusions

We have developed and internationally validated a COS for ICU patients in general with six core outcomes. These are ‘survival’, ‘free of life support’, ‘free of delirium’, ‘out of hospital’, ‘health-related quality of life’, and ‘cognitive function’, and we encourage its use in future research, specifically clinical trials in the ICU setting.

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Author contributions

Conceptualisation: MNK, AG, MHM, AP, and MOC.

Data curation: MNK, CRLB, AG, MHM, BSR, CBM, TS, EL, ACB, TH, AMGB, LSH, AH, PS, SE, MC, AS, JHL, KH, FB, CP, MO, JMC, MPW, WS, AW, TJ, MC, MIS, MN, JH, MM, NH, EL, KH, SNM, BKTU, VJ, and MOC.

Formal analysis: MNK, and AG.

Funding acquisition: AG, MHM, AP, and MOC.

Investigation: all authors.

Methodology: MNK, AG, MHM, and MOC.

Project administration: in Denmark: MNK, CLRB, and MOC; internationally: MNK and CLRB.

Resources: MNK, CRLB, AG, MHM, BSR, CBM, TS, EL, ACB, TH, AMGB, LSH, AH, MC, AS, JHL, KH, FB, CP, MO, JMC, MPW, WS, AW, TJ, MC, MIS, MN, JH, MM, NH, EL, KH, SNM, BKTU, KY, VJ, and MOC.

Supervision: AG, MHM, AP, and MOC.

Validation: MNK, CRLB, AG, MHM, BSR, CBM, TS, EL, ACB, TH, AMGB, LSH, AH, PS, SE, MC, AS, JHL, KH, FB, CP, MO, JMC, MPW, WS, AW, TJ, MC, MIS, MN, JH, MM, NH, EL, KH, SNM, BKTU, KY, VJ, and MOC.

Visualization: MNK, and AG.

Writing – first draft: MNK.

Writing – reviewing & editing: all authors.

Steering committee, authors: MNK, CRLB, AG, BSR, CBM, LMP, TS, EL, ACB, TH, AMGB, LSH, IE, and MOC.

International CRIC partners, authors: MC, AS, JHL, KH, FB, CP, MO, JMC, MPW, WS, AW, TJ, MC, MIS, MN, JH, MM, NM, EL, KH, SNM, VH, BV, and BKTV.

International steering committee, authors: MNK, CRLB, AG, BSR, CBM, LMP, TS, EL, ACB, TH, AMGB, LSH, IE, MOC, MC, AS, JHL, KH, FB, CP, MO, JMC, MPW, WS, AW, TJ, MC, MIS, MN, JH, MM, NM, EL, KH, SNM, VH, BV, KY, and BKTV.

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Conflicts of interest

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Figures, tables, and legends

Figure 1.

COS: core outcome set, CRIC: Collaboration of Research in Intensive Care

The 329 outcomes were condensed to 50 outcomes by the steering committee and the 5 Danish research panels. Semi-structured interviews were initiated during the preparation of the Delphi survey and ran concurrently with the first survey round. These interviews were used to identify additional outcomes for potential inclusion. Nine outcomes (ESM) were identified and discussed with the 5 Danish research panels but was unanimously decided against inclusion because they were adjudicated irrelevant.

During the process, one panel left the process due to withdrawal of patients and family members from that panel. After the development of the initial Danish COS the international CRIC partners and 17 international research panels were involved in the following consensus process.

^a There were 9 outcomes considered from the 82 interviews (ESM, Table S7), however, a consensus was reached across the national research panels that they were already covered by the 50 outcomes in the survey. Therefore, there were no additional outcomes revealed from the interviews.

Figure 2. Flow diagram for the participants being interviewed and registered for the Delphi survey

Attrition between the rounds is calculated from the number of completion from the first round as defined in the protocol [27]. Distributions of panel members in all rounds are shown in ESM, Table S6.

Figure 3. The initial Danish COS and the adjusted international COS

COS: core outcome set, HRQoL: health-related quality of life.

The suggested outcomes covered by HRQoL are to be found in ESM, Table S9.

Wording of the initial Danish COS was considered and agreed to be changed for three outcomes (grey arrows). The changes entailed in highlighting the essential outcome, more than how to measure the outcome, which will be clarified when the core outcome measurement set is defined.

Table 1. Characteristics of stakeholders in the Delphi survey and the semi-structured interviews

Characteristics of stakeholders for the first round of the Delphi survey (n=264)				
	Patients n=65	Family members n=49	Clinicians ^e n=136	Researchers ^f n=14
Age (years)	62 (50 to 70)	59 (47 to 65)	46 (39 to 52)	41 (37 to 48)
Sex (female)	21 (32%)	34 (69%)	93 (68%)	9 (64%)
Other ethnicity than Danish ^a	4 (6%)	1 (2%)	5 (4%)	3 (21%)
Admission type				
- Surgical	29 (47%)	-	-	-
- Medical	33 (53%)	-	-	-
SMS-ICU ^b at ICU admission ^c	20 (13.5 to 22.0)	-	-	-
- <17 point	23 (37%)	-	-	-
- ≥17 point	40 (63%)	-	-	-
Self-reported critical illness severity ^d	10.0 (8.5 to 10.0)	-	-	-
ICU length of stay (days) ^c	9.0 (6.0 to 22.5)	-	-	-
Time since ICU stay (months) ^c	14 (3 to 20)	-	-	-
Assistance to fill in the survey	11 (17%)	-	-	-
Family to a deceased patient	-	5 (10%)	-	-
Characteristics of stakeholders participating in the semi-structured interviews (n=82)				
	Patients n=27	Family members n=25	Clinicians ^e n=26	Researchers ^f n=4
Age (years)	60 (50 to 68)	54 (41 to 60)	45 (43 to 48)	43 (38 to 48)
Sex (female)	13 (48%)	18 (72%)	21 (81%)	4 (100%)
Other ethnicity than Danish ^{a,g}	1 (4%)	1 (4%)	3 (10%)	0 (0%)
Admission type				
- Surgical ^b	13 (48%)	-	-	-
- Medical ^b	14 (52%)	-	-	-
SMS-ICU ^b at ICU admission ^c	19 (15 to 22)	-	-	-
- <17 points	10 (37%)	-	-	-
- ≥17 points	17 (63%)	-	-	-
Self-reported critical illness severity ^d	9 (8 to 10)	-	-	-
ICU length of stay (days) ^c	9 (7 to 25)	-	-	-
Time since ICU admission (months) ^c	11 (4 to 17)	-	-	-
Family to a deceased patient	-	3 (12%)	-	-

ICU: intensive care unit, SMS-ICU: The Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit [28].

Numeric data are presented as medians with interquartile ranges, categorical data as counts with percentages.

^a Other than Danish origins covers both 'immigrants' (born abroad and neither parent being a Danish citizen or born in Denmark) and 'descendants' (born in Denmark and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark) (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk). Danish origin means at least one parent born in Denmark with Danish citizenship (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk).

^b We aimed for a balanced distribution of patients with higher mortality risk ≥17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 25.3% and above) vs. lower risk <17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 22.8% and below) [24, 28]. Further details in the methods section.

^c These variables were obtained from the patients' medical records. For the survey there were two patients with missing medical record data. One withdrew consent, one where there were only paper medical records, which couldn't be located. No missing data for patients interviewed.

^d A numeric score (0-10 where 0 is non-critical and 10 is most critical). From either the patients' view or from the view of family members to ICU patients.

^e Multi professional clinicians cover doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, occupational therapists, and others (ESM, Table S2 and S3).

^f Multi professional researchers (ESM, Table S2 and S3).

^g Missing data for 2 patients, 1 family member, and 1 clinician.

Table 2. International validation of the core outcome set across the participating countries

Country	Adjusted core outcome set					
	Survival	Free of life support	Free of delirium	Out of hospital	HRQoL	Cognitive function
Australia ^b General ICU patient	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt ^h	Adopt	Adapt ^h
Australia ^b Sepsis survivors	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt ^h	Adopt	Adapt ^h
Czech Republic	Adopt ^h	Adopt ^h	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Denmark (Copenhagen) ^c	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Denmark (Køge) ^d	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Denmark (Kolding) ^e	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Denmark (Aalborg) ^f	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Finland (Helsinki)	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Finland (Tampere)	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Iceland	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
India (Chennai) ^g	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
India (Mumbai)	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Italy	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Lithuania	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt ^h
Norway	Adopt	Adopt	Reject ^h	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Netherlands	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Poland	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Sweden	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Switzerland	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt ^h	Adopt	Adopt
United Kingdom (Cardiff)	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
United Kingdom (London)	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt
Total adopted	21 (100%)	21 (100%)	20 (95%)	19 (90%)	21 (100%)	19 (90%)
Total adapted	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)
Total rejected	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

HRQoL: Health-related quality of life

Colour interpretation: green/Adopt=adopting the outcome, yellow/Adapt=adapting the outcome, and red/Reject=rejecting the outcome.

Numbers (percentages) of panels.

^a Detailed minutes in ESM, Table S5

^b Number of participants from different areas of Australia: 1 Aboriginal, 11 Western Australia, 5 New South Wales, 4 Victoria, 3 Queensland, and 1 Northern Territory.

^c The Capital Region of Denmark

^d Region Zealand

^e The Region of Southern Denmark

^f The North Denmark Region

^g Indian areas represented: Chennai, Bangalore, Vellore, Pune, and New Delhi.

^h Remarks to the core outcome (ESM, Page 228-229).

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Maj-Brit Nørregaard Kjær, Camilla Rahbek Lysholm Bruun, Anders Granholm, Morten Hylander Møller, Bodil Steen Rasmussen, Camilla Bekker Mortensen, Lone Musaeus Poulsen, Thomas Strøm, Eva Laerkner, Anne Craveiro Brøchner, Trine Haberlandt, Anne-Marie Gellert Bunzel, Louise Stenbryggen Herløv, Anna Holm, Praleene Sivapalan, Stine Estrup, Maria Cronhjort, Anna Schandl, Jon Henrik Laake, Kristin Hofsfø, Fredrike Blokzijl, Frederik Keus, Carmen Andrea Pfortmueller, Marlies Ostermann, Jade M Cole, Matt P Wise, Wojciech Szczeklik, Ania Wludarczyk, Tomas Jovaiša, Maurizio Cecconi, Martin Ingi Sigurdsson, Marek Nalos, Johanna Hästbacka, Marja Mäkinen, Naomi Hammond, Edward Litton, Kimberley Haines, Sheila Nainan Myatra, Bharath Kumar Tirupakuzhi Vijayaraghavan, Kavita Yadav, Vivekanand Jha, Balasubramanian Venkatesh, Ingrid Egerod , Anders Perner, and Marie O Collet

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Additional methodological details

Stakeholder involvement

The steering committee (composed of authors MNK, CRLB, AG, BSR, CBM, LMP, TS, EL, ACB, TH, AMGB, LSH, IE, and MOC) for the initial core outcome set (COS) covers multi professional clinicians and researchers with knowledge of the intensive care unit (ICU) environment and critically ill patients. The steering committee established initially 5 research panels in 4 out of 5 regions in Denmark [1, 2], consisting of 10 patients, 5 family members, 19 multi professional clinicians, and 9 researchers in total. The research panels functioned as advisory boards in relation to the process with developing the COS. Thus, the research panels were involved in several research stages with a nominal group technique: the design, recruitment strategy, consensus, and dissemination in a broad sense from, e.g., information materials, interview guides, and wording in the survey [2].

Developing the initial core outcome set

Identification of outcomes

First step was a literature review obtaining outcomes from COS developed to the critically ill patient (Figure 1 in the manuscript, Step 1). This step was conducted to obtain initial knowledge of outcomes relevant for the critically ill population. The search string and all listed outcomes are to be found in the end of the Supplemental Digital Content (SDC) (Figure 1).

Interviews

Interviews were conducted concurrently with the design of the survey and the first survey round. Semi-structured individual interviews were carried out with patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers to identify any outcomes overlooked in the literature search [1]. Quota sampling was employed to ensure a balanced distribution of characteristics and especially for patients we ensured distribution of patients with predicted mortality above and below 25%, and furthermore we used a matrix with variables important to consider, with the goal of achieving a diverse distribution of [1, 3]:

- Age (young: 18 to 50 years old, middle: 51 to 75 years old, and old: >75 years old)
- Time after ICU discharge (1-2 weeks, 6 weeks or in a follow up clinic, or 1 year)
- Sex (female, male)
- Ethnicities (other than Danish origins covers 'immigrants' born abroad and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark and 'descendants' born in Denmark and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark)

- Admission type (surgical or medical)
- SMS-ICU (low <17 point or high mortality risk ≥ 17). The Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit (SMS-ICU) is a severity score that predicts 90-day mortality with higher points meaning higher risk of mortality [4]. The range of points is 0-42. SMS-ICU assesses the severity of illness, which could influence the perspective of the importance of outcomes for a COS. Therefore, we aimed for a balanced distribution of patients with higher mortality risk ≥ 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 25.3% and above) vs. lower risk <17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 22.8% and below) [4]
- ICU length of stay (<7 days or ≥ 7 days)

Interviews were conducted either by phone or through physical attendance, based on the preferences of the informants. Three interview guides were developed to encompass all stakeholders invited for interviews: one for patients, one for family members, and one for clinicians and researchers [1]. These guides underwent cognitive validation by Danish research panels, focusing on the structure, the directness of questions considering potential emotional stress, and whether they addressed the intended research questions.

Although all interviews were reviewed for outcomes not covered in our literature search, the framework analysis of the interviews will not be included in this study. The interviews were carried out by MNK, CRLB, EL, SRV, CBM, AH, MOC, and three former members of the steering committee using validated interview guides published in the protocol [1].

Construction of survey

The first step involved a literature review, utilizing a search string (in this SDC) from a previous systematic review regarding COS for critical illness and recovery (Figure 1, Step 1) [1, 5]. From this search, we obtained a raw list of outcomes considered for developing a COS. We independently and in duplicate (MNK and SE) obtained 329 outcomes listed alphabetically in the protocol and in page 9 in this SDC [1]. MNK, CBM, PS, SE, LMP, EL, and MOC removed duplicates and used thematic analysis to condense the outcomes in categories. Then MNK, CRLB, PS, and MOC translated all outcomes to Danish and made mind maps with a central category in the middle and associated outcomes around it. Some categories contained overlapping outcomes to break up all outcomes into smaller pieces to be presented for the Danish research panels.

The second step was to present all the categories for the Danish research panels. We used the nominal group technique, with face-to-face discussion in small groups aiming for an instant result [6], to discuss,

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reallocate and further condense to essential outcomes as many were overlapping ending up with 50 outcomes (Figure 1, Step 2).

The third step was determining how to formulate survey questions that covered the essential outcomes and to construct the survey in DelphiManager (COMET, University of Liverpool, Liverpool) using their default layouts and graphics.

The fourth step was for the research panels to pilot test the survey to ensure intelligibility and face validity, aiming to prevent attrition resulting from a lack of understanding. This was achieved through the use of the think aloud technique, testing the DelphiManager software [7].

Recruitment for the survey

We aimed to recruit 400 participants for the survey, 100 patients, 100 family members, and 200 clinicians and researchers [1]. We used convenience sampling recruiting both patients and family members via long-term follow-up of trial participants, outpatient clinics, the general ward, ICU patient cafés, and hand out invitations (flyers). Clinicians and researchers were identified in the authors affiliations by the research network, Collaboration of Research in Intensive Care (CRIC), and comprised multi professional participants. Informants were also invited for the survey.

We aimed for a comprehensive representation of patients in the survey as well following the same matrix as for the interview covering the following variables obtained and shown in the table illustrating characteristics of the patients in the Delphi survey [1]:

- Age (young: 18 to 50 years old, middle-aged: 51 to 75 years old, and old: >75 years old)
- Time after ICU discharge (1-2 weeks, 6 weeks or in a follow up clinic, or 1 year)
- Sex (female, male)
- Ethnicities as described above
- Admission type (surgical or medical)
- SMS-ICU as described above
- ICU length of stay (<7 days or ≥7 days)

Survey round 1

In round 1, we recorded demographic data according to the protocol [1], and assigned all consenting registrations a unique identifier.

After the first survey round, the research panels held a consensus meeting where the results from the first round was summarized and the survey participants suggested additional outcomes, and participants'

comments were reviewed. There was unanimous agreement not to add any additional outcomes, but the comments added by survey participants required revision of the questions and revision of parts of the help text provided. Also, there was consensus not to remove any outcomes from the survey, as outlined in the 'consensus process' section.

Additional two survey rounds

We performed two additional rounds as the survey was revised. For precision, we included the wording 'assessing' or 'investigating' as an introduction of 31 outcomes. Additionally, for six questions related to health economics, well-being, blood samples, delirium, thirst, and dyspneic conditions, we included examples or provided more details to clarify the inquiries. Furthermore, we expanded the help text in six outcomes. Predefined, only those registered for the first survey round were able to participate in the following two round(s) [1]. No changes were made between round 2 and 3. One national research panel were convened between the rounds 2 and 3 to review the scores of the outcomes, determining whether there was consensus to remove any from the survey.

Retention strategy

We supplied all invited participants with an e-mail address and a hot line for any questions related to the survey. Each round defaulted to a three-week duration, with weekly notifications sent out to remind participants to complete the survey. The final round was extended to four weeks when feasible. Patients and family members received phone calls to inquire if they required assistance in using the DelphiManager software. Additional information on the retention strategy can be found in the protocol [1].

Consensus process

After the completion of the survey rounds, four research panels individually conducted a consensus meeting to review the findings and reach consensus on their final proposal for a COS. MNK and CRLB visited all four panels to ensure a consistent consensus process starting with a summarization of the results (MNK) and maintained consistent minutes (CRLB). The research panels were tasked with discussing the survey results and determining which outcomes should be considered core outcomes, thereby defining their perspective on a COS. The research panels identified between 9 and 13 outcomes, with some overlap, ultimately resulting in a total of 19 outcomes (Figure 1).

The summaries from all 4 meetings, the survey results, and the 19 outcomes were presented to the steering committee informing their consensus meeting across Denmark, with the goal of reaching

consensus on an initial COS with an accessible number of outcomes [7]. The detailed description of the meeting and the rationale behind the revealed 6 outcomes are to be found in this SDC page 23.

The additional international validation

The countries within the Collaboration of Research in Intensive Care (CRIC) network were informed about the pragmatic international validation of the initial COS and agreed to participate in this study. The participating countries included Australia, the Czech Republic, Finland, Iceland, India, Italy, Lithuania, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America.

International validation necessitated at least one research panel from each participating country. Using the nominal group technique, these panels deliberated on the initial COS and its applicability in their national context. The protocol amendment for this process was written and registered before the first international validation meeting was convened [8]. During the validation meetings, each country provided insights on whether they could adopt the outcome(s) as they were, whether adaptations were needed for their country, or whether they rejected the outcome(s). Meeting facilitators were briefed on the process behind the initial COS, the rationale for it, and were equipped with a slideshow to ensure a consistent presentation of the meeting's purpose. All necessary information was provided to guide the facilitators in discussions involving new outcomes that may have suggested or previously discussed. Detailed minutes were documented to ensure a transparent process and discussion.

Following completion of all international validation meetings, all authors gathered online for a consensus meeting. They deliberated and tried to reach an agreement on whether the initial COS could be universally applicable for all participating countries, whether adaptation was necessary, or if new outcomes should be added, akin to the extended version as demonstrated by Fink et al. [9].

Analysis and reporting

Characteristics were recorded from informants who consented to be interviewed and from survey participants who consented for registration in the DelphiManager software for the first survey round. Few characteristics were acquired from patients' medical journals following consent (for further information see the protocol) [1].

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Attrition between rounds

We had more than 5% attrition, which prompted the utilization of the *last observation carried forward* approach for rounds 2 and 3 in cases where patients did not respond to previously rated items. The attrition was 19% between round 1 and 2, as well as round 1 and 3 as attrition was calculated from those completing the first round. Consequently, we present the complete cases with last observation carried forward as planned [1].

Statistics

We used descriptive statistics to report the populations and responses of the survey rounds, presenting numbers and percentages of respondents. Regarding the characteristics of the participants, categorical data were expressed using numbers and percentages, while the numeric data were represented by medians with interquartile ranges (IQRs). Missing data were handled with last observation carried forward and with percentages for missingness presented as previously described [1].

Ethics

Participants who underwent interviews provided written informed consent, while survey participants indicated their consent by ticking the 'confirming consent' box in the survey. They were informed of the voluntary nature of participation before any additional responses were collected. Data were handled confidentially and anonymously without using their names, and participants had the option to withdraw their consent at any time. We sought approval for all participating hospitals and the Danish Data Protection Agency to ensure compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The Ethical Committee for the Capital Region of Denmark waived the need for ethical approval (H-21010116). For the international validation, Iceland was obliged to obtain the Ethics Board Permission with informed consent from participants, and the United Kingdom (London) obtained institutional approval from the Guy's & St Thomas' Hospital London.

Subject confidentiality was rigorously upheld by participating investigators, research staff, and the sponsoring institution. No information concerning the study, or the data will be released to any unauthorized third party without prior written approval from the steering committee.

In the case of the DelphiManager software, anonymity for all participants was ensured through individual unique identifiers, and data were stored in a secure location.

Table S1. Distribution of panel members in categories and professions across countries for the research panels

Country	Number of panels ^a	Patients	Family members	Doctors	Nurses	Other ^f	Researchers	Total
Australia	2	5	5	(5)	3 (5)	(2)	11	24
Czech Republic	1	2	2	2	0	0	2	8
Denmark	4	8	5	6 (4)	6 (5)	5	9	39
Finland ^c	2	7	3	3(1)	0	0	6	19
Iceland	1	1	1	(2)	2 (1)	0	3	7
India ^d	2	4	4	10 (1)	2	2	2	24
Italy	1	3	2	2(3)	1	1	3	12
Lithuania	1	1	1	3	2	0	3	10
Norway	1	2	0	1 (3)	(1)	(1)	6	9
Netherlands	1	4	2	2	2	0	2	12
Poland	1	1	1	2	1	0	2	7
Sweden	1	5	1	2	2	2	0	12
Switzerland	1	2	2	1 (1)	(2)	(1)	4	9
United Kingdom ^e	2	9	2	3 (1)	3 (1)	6	2	25
Total	21	54	31	37	24	16	55	217

All data entered are numeric. No missing data. Brackets refer to the proportion of researchers.

This table contains all the countries who have held a national or international validation meeting with a local research panel(s) contributing to the consensus of the core outcome set.

^a Number of research panels established in the single country.

^b Australian areas represented: Aboriginals, Western Australia, New South Wales, Victoria, Queensland, and Northern Territory. One panel was focused on the general intensive care unit patient and the other panel on sepsis survivors.

^c One panel from Tampere and one panel from Helsinki.

^d Indian areas represented: Chennai, Bangalore, Vellore, Pune, New Delhi, and Mumbai.

^e One panel from Wales and one from England.

^f Other consisted of multi professional stakeholders as e.g., physiotherapists, occupational therapists.

Table S2. Characteristics of stakeholders registered for the first round of the Delphi survey (n=264)

	Patients n=65	Family members n=49	Clinicians n=136	Researchers ^g n=14
Characteristics				
Age (years)	62 (50 to 70)	59 (47 to 65)	46 (39 to 52)	41 (37 to 48)
Sex (female)	21 (32%)	34 (69%)	93 (68%)	9 (64%)
Region of residence:				
-The Capital Region of Denmark	19 (29%)	13 (27%)	30 (22%)	6 (43%)
-Region Zealand	6 (9%)	6 (12%)	22 (16%)	2 (14%)
-Central Denmark Region	12 (19%)	9 (18%)	19 (14%)	2 (14%)
-The North Denmark Region	14 (22%)	10 (20%)	35 (26%)	4 (29%)
-The Region of Southern Denmark	14 (22%)	11 (22%)	30 (22%)	0 (0%)
Other ethnicity than Danish ^a	4 (6%)	1 (2%)	5 (4%)	3 (21%)
Admission type				
- Surgical	29 (47%) ^f	-	-	-
- Medical	33 (53%) ^f	-	-	-
SMS-ICU^b at ICU admission^c	20 (13.5 to 22.0) ^f	-	-	-
- <17 points	23 (37%) ^f	-	-	-
- ≥17 points	40 (63%) ^f	-	-	-
Self-reported critical illness severity^d	10.0 (8.5 to 10.0)	-	-	-
ICU length of stay (days)^c	9.0 (6.0 to 22.5) ^f	-	-	-
Time since ICU admission (months)^c	14 (3 to 20) ^f	-	-	-
Assistance to fill in the survey	11 (17%)	-	-	-
Family to a deceased patient	-	5 (10%)	-	-
Clinical experience (years)	-	-	18 (11 to 24)	12 (6 to 20)
Employed in ICU (experience in years)	-	-	10 (3 to 15)	5 (1 to 10)
Professional group				
- Medical doctors	-	-	64 (47%)	8 (57%)
- Nurses	-	-	52 (38%)	5 (36%)
- Physiotherapist	-	-	11 (8%)	1 (7%)
- Occupational therapist	-	-	8 (6%)	0 (0%)
- Other	-	-	1 (1%)	0 (0%)
Research experience (years)	-	-	0 (0 to 5)	7 (5 to 8)
- Medical doctors	-	-	4 (0 to 10)	5.5 (4.5 to 7.3) ^h
- Nurses	-	-	None	8 (5 to 8) ⁱ
- Physiotherapist	-	-	0 (0 to 1)	10 (10 to 10) ^j
- Occupational therapist	-	-	None	-
- Other ^e	-	-	-	-
Time doing research^f				
- Full time	-	-	-	9 (64%)
- Part time	-	-	12 (9%)	4 (29%)
- Free time	-	-	49 (37%)	1 (7%)
- No research	-	-	71 (54%)	-
Highest obtained academic degree				
- Not bachelor	-	-	11 (8%)	-
- Bachelor	-	-	48 (35%)	-
- Master	-	-	50 (37%)	7 (50%)
- PhD or higher degree	-	-	27 (20%)	7 (50%)
Employment				
- University hospital	-	-	118 (87%)	13 (93%)
- Non-university hospital	-	-	15 (11%)	1 (7%)
- Other	-	-	3 (2%)	-

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SMS-ICU: The Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit[4], ICU: intensive care unit.

Numeric data are presented as medians with interquartile ranges, categorical data as counts with percentages.

^a Danish origin has at least one parent born in Denmark with Danish citizenship (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk). Other than Danish origins covers both 'immigrants' born abroad and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark and 'descendants' born in Denmark and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk).

^b Patients with higher mortality risk ≥ 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 25.3% and above) vs. lower risk < 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 22.8% and below) [4].

^c These variables were obtained from the patients' medical records. For the survey there were two patients with missing medical record data. One withdrew consent, one where there were only paper medical records, which couldn't be located.

^d Self-reported severity of illness assessed on a numeric score (0-10 where 0 is non-critical and 10 is most critical). From either the patients' view or from the view of family members to ICU patients.

^e No other professions with research experience than listed.

^f There were 4 clinicians with missing data for the question concerning time doing research.

^g Researchers covers clinician-researchers and researchers from other professional groups

^h There were two missing among doctors.

ⁱ There were three missing among nurses.

^j There were two missing among physiotherapists.

Table S3. Characteristics of stakeholders participating in the semi-structured interviews (n=82)

	Patients (n=27)	Family members (n=25)	Clinicians (n=26)	Researchers(n=4) ^h
Characteristics				
Age (years)	60 (50 to 68)	54 (41 to 60)	45 (43 to 48)	43 (38 to 48)
Sex (female)	13 (48%)	18 (72%)	21 (81%)	4 (100%)
Region of residence:				
- The Capital Region of Denmark	6 (22%)	6 (24%)	5 (19%) ^j	2 (50%)
-Region Zealand	3 (11%)	3 (12%)	4 (15%) ^j	0 (0%)
-Central Denmark Region	6 (22%)	6 (24%)	4 (15%) ^j	1 (25%)
-The North Denmark Region	7 (26%)	6 (24%)	6 (23%) ^j	1 (25%)
-The Region of Southern Denmark	5 (19%)	4 (16%)	6 (23%) ^j	0 (0%)
Other ethnicity than Danish ^{a,b}	1 (4%)	1 (4%)	3 (12%)	0 (0%)
Admission type				
- Surgical	13 (48%)	-	-	-
- Medical	14 (52%)	-	-	-
SMS-ICU^c at ICU admission^c	19 (15 to 22)	-	-	-
- <17 points	10 (37%)	-	-	-
- ≥17 points	17 (63%)	-	-	-
Self-reported critical illness severity^e	9 (8 to 10)	-	-	-
ICU length of stay (days)^d	9 (7 to 25)	-	-	-
Time since ICU admission (months)^d	11 (4 to 17)	-	-	-
Family to a deceased patient	-	3 (12%)	-	-
Clinical experience (years)	-	-	19 (14 to 23)	13 (5 to 22)
Employed in ICU (experience in years)	-	-	12 (5 to 16)	7 (3 to 11)
Professional group				
- Medical doctors	-	-	12 (46%)	1 (25%)
- Nurses	-	-	9 (35%)	4 (75%)
- Physiotherapist	-	-	3 (12%)	0 (0%)
- Occupational therapist	-	-	2 (7%)	0 (0%)
- Other ^f	-	-	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Research experience (years)	-	-	0 (0 to 6) ^g	8 (3 to 12)
- Medical doctors	-	-	6 (0 to 10) ^g	4 (4 to 4)
- Nurses	-	-	0 (0 to 0) ^g	10 (7 to 13)
- Physiotherapist	-	-	0 (0 to 7) ^g	0 (0 to 0)
- Occupational therapist	-	-	0 (0 to 0) ^g	0 (0 to 0)
- Other ^f	-	-	0 (0 to 0) ^g	0 (0 to 0)
Time doing research				
- Full time	-	-	0 (0%) ^g	4 (100%)
- Part time	-	-	3 (81%) ^g	0 (0%)
- Free time	-	-	6 (23%) ^g	0 (0%)
- None	-	-	16 (62%) ^g	0 (0%)
Highest obtained academic degree				
- Bachelor	-	-	5 (19%)	0 (0%)
- Master	-	-	14 (54%)	3 (75%)
- PhD or higher	-	-	7 (27%)	1 (25%)
-	-	-	-	-
Employment				
- University hospital	-	-	26 (100%)	4 (100%)
- Non-university hospital	-	-	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
- University	-	-	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
- Other	-	-	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

SMS-ICU: The Simplified Mortality Score for the Intensive Care Unit[4], ICU: intensive care unit.

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Numeric data are presented as medians with interquartile ranges, categorical data as counts with percentages.

^a Danish origin has at least one parent born in Denmark with Danish citizenship (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk). Of missing data were 2 patients, 2 family member, and 1 clinician. Other than Danish origins covers 'immigrants' born abroad and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark and 'descendants' born in Denmark and neither of the parents is a Danish citizen or born in Denmark (Statistics Denmark, www.dst.dk).

^b Missing data for 2 patients, 1 family member, and 1 clinician.

^c Patients with higher mortality risk ≥ 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 25.3% and above) vs. lower risk < 17 (predicted 90-day mortality risk of 22.8% and below) [4].

^d These variables were obtained from the patients' medical records. No missing data.

^e Self-reported severity of illness assessed on a numeric score (0-10 where 0 is non-critical and 10 is most critical). From either the patients' view or from the view of family members to ICU patients.

^f No other professions than already listed.

^g There were 1 clinician with missing data for the question concerning region of residence, clinical experience, and time doing research.

^h Researchers covers clinician-researchers and researchers from other professional groups

Search strategy for the initial list of outcomes

Search strategies for publications on critical care-related core outcome sets from the systematic review conducted by Dinglas et al.[5] The search was conducted 1 May 2021.

Search strategy for PubMed:

```
("acute care"[tw] OR "asystole"[tw] OR "brain injuries, traumatic"[mesh] OR "burn unit"[tw] OR "burn units"[mesh] OR "burn units"[tw] OR "cardiac arrest"[tw] OR "cardiac arrests"[tw] OR "cardiac death"[tw] OR "cardiac surgeries"[tw] OR "cardiac surgical procedures"[mesh] OR "cardiac surgery"[tw] OR "cardiopulmonary arrest"[tw] OR "cardiopulmonary arrests"[tw] OR "cardiopulmonary death"[tw] OR "coma"[mesh] OR "coma"[tw] OR "comas"[tw] OR "comatose"[tw] OR "coronary care unit"[tw] OR "coronary care units"[mesh] OR "coronary care units"[tw] OR "critical care"[mesh] OR "critical care"[tw] OR "H D U "[tw] OR "HDU"[tw] OR "HDUs"[tw] OR "heart arrest"[mesh] OR "heart arrest"[tw] OR "heart arrests"[tw] OR "heart death"[tw] OR "heart surgeries"[tw] OR "heart surgery"[tw] OR "high dependency unit"[tw] OR "high dependency units"[tw] OR "I C U "[tw] OR "I T U"[tw] OR "ICU"[tw] OR "ICUs"[tw] OR "intensive care units"[mesh] OR "intensive care units, neonatal"[mesh] OR "intensive care units, pediatric"[mesh] OR "intensive care"[tw] OR "intensive therapy unit"[tw] OR "intensive therapy units"[tw] OR "ITU"[tw] OR "ITUs"[tw] OR "mechanical ventilation"[tw] OR "PICU"[tw] OR "PICUs"[tw] OR "P I C U "[tw] OR "recovery room"[mesh] OR "respiratory care unit"[tw] OR "respiratory care units"[mesh] OR "respiratory care units"[tw] OR "sepsis"[mesh] OR "sepsis"[tw] OR "septic"[tw] OR "TBI"[tw] OR "TBIs"[tw] OR "traumatic brain injuries"[tw] OR "traumatic brain injury"[tw] OR "ventilated"[tw] OR "ventilator"[tw] OR "ventilators"[tw]) AND ("critical care outcomes"[mesh] OR "critical care outcome"[tw] OR "critical care outcomes"[tw] OR "core outcome"[tw] OR "core outcomes"[tw] OR "core set"[tw] OR "core sets"[tw] OR "core measure"[tw] OR "core measures"[tw] OR "core domain"[tw] OR "core domains"[tw])
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Search strategy for Embase:

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('acute care':ti,ab,kw OR 'asystole':ti,ab,kw OR 'traumatic brain injury'/exp OR 'burn unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'burn unit'/exp OR 'burn units':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac arrest':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac arrests':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac death':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac surgeries':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart surgery':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiac surgery':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiopulmonary arrest':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiopulmonary arrests':ti,ab,kw OR 'cardiopulmonary death':ti,ab,kw OR 'coma'/exp OR 'coma':ti,ab,kw OR 'comas':ti,ab,kw OR 'comatose':ti,ab,kw OR 'coronary care unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'coronary care unit'/exp OR 'coronary care units':ti,ab,kw OR 'critical care':ti,ab,kw OR 'H D U ':ti,ab,kw OR 'HDU':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart arrest'/exp OR 'heart arrest':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart arrests':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart death':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart surgeries':ti,ab,kw OR 'heart surgery':ti,ab,kw OR 'high dependency unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'high dependency units':ti,ab,kw OR 'I C U ':ti,ab,kw OR 'I T U':ti,ab,kw OR 'ICU':ti,ab,kw OR 'ICUs':ti,ab,kw OR 'intensive care'/exp OR 'intensive care unit'/exp OR 'neonatal intensive care unit'/exp OR 'pediatric intensive care unit'/exp OR 'intensive care':ti,ab,kw OR 'intensive therapy unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'intensive therapy units':ti,ab,kw OR 'ITU':ti,ab,kw OR 'ITUs':ti,ab,kw OR 'mechanical ventilation':ti,ab,kw OR 'PICU':ti,ab,kw OR 'PICUs':ti,ab,kw OR 'P I C U ':ti,ab,kw OR 'recovery room'/exp OR 'respiratory care unit':ti,ab,kw OR 'respiratory care units':ti,ab,kw OR 'sepsis'/exp OR 'sepsis':ti,ab,kw OR 'septic':ti,ab,kw OR 'TBI':ti,ab,kw OR 'TBIs':ti,ab,kw OR 'traumatic brain injuries':ti,ab,kw OR 'traumatic brain injury':ti,ab,kw OR 'ventilated':ti,ab,kw OR 'ventilator':ti,ab,kw OR 'ventilators':ti,ab,kw) AND ('critical care outcome'/exp OR 'critical care outcome':ti,ab,kw OR 'critical care outcomes':ti,ab,kw OR 'core outcome':ti,ab,kw OR 'core outcomes':ti,ab,kw OR 'core set':ti,ab,kw OR 'core sets':ti,ab,kw OR 'core measure':ti,ab,kw OR 'core measures':ti,ab,kw OR 'core domain':ti,ab,kw OR 'core domains':ti,ab,kw)
```

Table S4. Raw list of outcomes obtained from the search string

- Abnormal time of temperature during infection
- Accidental extubation
- Acute physiology and chronic health evaluation (APACHE II) score
- Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS)
- Additional medication for agitation
- Adverse events
- Adverse events
- Alanine aminotransferase (ALT)
- All-cause mortality
- Anemia
- Antibiotic therapy
- Antipyretic rate
- Anxiety
- Any return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC)
- Acute physiology and chronic health evaluation (APACHE IV) score
- Appetite
- At hospital discharge is independence in functional level established matching home environment
- Biochemical outcomes
- Blood gas analysis
- Blood oxygen saturation
- Blood pressure
- Blood routine test
- Body composition
- Body composition tests (ultrasound/anthropometry)
- Boredom
- Brain function
- Calcitonin
- Cardiovascular disease
- Catecholamine infusion
- Change in activities of daily living
- Change in downstream marker (e.g. interleukin-6),
- Changes in relationships
- Chest computed tomography (CT)
- Chest pain
- Chest x-ray examination
- Chloroquine blood concentration
- Circulatory function
- Clearance time of fatigue
- Clinical workload
- Cluster of differentiation (CD)-4 and CD8 T-cells count
- Coagulation function
- Coagulation outcomes
- Cognition

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- Cognition
- Cognitive function and symptoms
- Complete blood count (CBC)
- Confusion, uremia, respiratory rate, blood pressure, age ≥ 65 years (CURB-65) pneumonia severity score
- Consciousness
- Constipation
- Contamination of packs and glass bottles
- Cost-effectiveness
- Costs (cost-effectiveness)
- Cough
- C-reactive protein (CRP)
- CT of hip
- Curative effects of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) syndrome
- Days of immobility (bed-bound)
- Days of sedation
- D-dimer
- Decreased quality of life
- Decreased walking distance
- Delirium duration*
- Delirium incidence*
- Delirium prevalence*
- Delirium resolution*
- Delirium severity*
- Delirium type*
- Delirium*
- Delivery of care
- Demand for first aid measurement
- Diabetes
- Diarrhea
- Difficulties concentrating
- Difficulties in activity of daily living (ADL)
- Difficulties returning to work/employment
- Disability
- Discharge location
- Disease severity
- Disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) score
- Dizziness
- Duration (d) of extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO)
- Duration (d) of oxygen inhalation
- Duration (d) of supplemental oxygenation
- Duration (d)/frequency of medical ventilation
- Duration of antibiotics treatment
- Duration of hospital stay
- Duration of ICU stay

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- Duration of intubation
- Duration of weaning from mechanical ventilation?
- Dysphagia
- Electrocardiogram (ECG)
- Emotional well-being
- Endurance
- Erythrocyte sedimentation rate
- Exercise capacity and intensity
- Fatigue
- Feeding intolerance
- Feeling isolated
- Fever
- Financial impact on patient
- Financial impact on the individual
- Financial impact on the patient
- Finger oxygen improvement rate
- Flexion contractures and heterotopic ossification
- Frequency of clinical improvement (turning to ordinary or recovery)
- Frequency of hospital discharge
- Frequency of ICU admission
- Frequency of interstitial pneumonia
- Frequency of multi organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS)
- Frequency of other sequelae
- Frequency of shock
- Gas production
- Gastrointestinal discomfort
- Gastrointestinal function and symptoms
- Genetic factors/biomarkers
- Global Organ Dysfunction/Multi-organ failure
- Gratitude
- Headache
- Health care resource use
- Healthcare resource utilization (e.g., doctors' visits, need for further intervention)
- Health-related quality of life
- Health-related quality of life
- Hearing impairment
- Heart function
- Heart rate
- Hobbies
- Hospital/ICU-free survival
- Hospital-acquired infection
- Hospitalisation cost
- Hospitalisation/length of stay
- Human leukocyte antigen – DR isotype (HLA-DR)

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- ICU free days
- Interleukin (II-10)
- Interleukin (II-4)
- Interleukin (II-6)
- Interleukin (II-8)
- Immunity and antibodies
- Immunoglobulin
- Impact on family and/or caregivers
- Impact on family, caregivers, or both
- Improvement of aerobic capacity
- Improvement of functional exercise capacity
- Improvement of physical function
- Improvement of respiratory muscle strength
- Improvement of skeletal muscle strength
- Incidence of antibiotic treatment
- Incidence of hypoxia
- Incidence of intensive care unit admission
- Incidence of medical complications during hospitalisation
- Incidence of shock
- Incidence of Ventilator associated pneumonia
- Incontinence
- Infections
- Intensive care unit acquired weakness
- Intensive care unit length of stay
- Interferon γ
- Interleukin (II)-2
- Intracranial hemorrhage
- Jaw thrust maneuver
- Joint pain
- Kidney function
- Lack of physical strength
- Length of hospital stay
- Length of hospital stay
- Less independence
- Level of virus antibodies in blood sample
- Life participation
- Liquid balance
- Liver function
- Loneliness/isolation
- Long-term mortality rate
- Loss of taste
- Lowest oxygen saturation (SpO₂) during intubation
- Lung scarring (fibrosis)
- Lymphocyte count

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

- Lymphocyte count
- Major bleeding
- Major organ failure
- Management of complex medication regimens
- Mechanical ventilation
- Mechanical ventilation duration
- Memory loss
- Mental health/emotional functioning
- Metabolic complications
- Mobility
- Mortality
- Move to nursing home
- MRI of hip
- Muscle and/or nerve function
- Muscle function, nerve function or both
- Muscle pain
- Myocardial enzymes
- Myoglobin
- National Early Warning Score (NEWS)2 score
- Nausea/vomiting
- Neurologic recovery
- Neuromuscular function
- Nightmares
- Nutrition
- Organ failure
- Other infection
- Outcomes; respiratory, thoracic and mediastinal outcomes
- Overall muscle strength
- Oxygen saturation
- Pain
- Pressure of arterial oxygen to fractional inspired oxygen concentration (PaO₂/FiO₂)-ratio
- Participation
- Patient-centered morbidity rate (health related quality of life (HRQoL), time course of return to pre-morbid function)
- Percentage of cases returning to critical care
- Percentage of cases turning to severe or critical
- Physical function
- Physical symptoms
- Physiologic consequences (extent or time to resolution of study entry criteria etc., alterations in individual physiologic variables – e.g., pressure of arterial oxygen to fractional inspired oxygen concentration (PO₂/FiO₂)-ratio, mean arterial pressure (MAP))
- Physiological or clinical (e.g., cardiac outcomes; nervous system-related outcomes)
- Physiological response to exercise
- Post-intensive care syndrome (PICS) screening at hospital discharge

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- Pneumonia
- Pneumonia severity index (PSI) score
- Pneumothorax
- Post intensive care syndrome (PICS) for family (PICS-F) before hospital discharge (PICS for family)
- Post-traumatic stress disorder
- Presence of delirium* while in hospital
- Progressing to the critical stage
- Progressing to the severe stage
- Proinflammatory cytokines
- Proportion of patient without cough
- Proportion of patient without wheezing
- Proportion of patients without fatigue
- Proportion of patients without fever
- Proportion of patients without sputum
- Proportion of pt. with negative SARS-CoV-2
- Psychological state
- Pulmonary function and symptoms
- Pulmonary function; lung function
- Pulmonary rehabilitation
- Rate of ALT recovery
- Rate of creatine kinase (CK) recovery
- Rate of mycobacteria (MB) recovery
- Rate of no requiring supplemental oxygen
- Rate of patient receiving systematic corticosteroids
- Rate of preventing mild to moderate patients from shifting to severe patients
- Rate of progressing to final stage
- Readmission/control visits
- Reintubation
- Remission rate of respiratory symptoms
- Renal function
- Resilience
- Respiratory function
- Respiratory muscle function
- Respiratory muscle function
- Respiratory muscle strength
- Respiratory rate
- Respiratory rate
- Respiratory support
- Return to work or prior activities
- Routine urine culture test
- Sadness/depression
- Satisfaction with life or personal enjoyment
- Score of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) symptoms
- Self-efficacy/management

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- Sepsis/septic shock
- Sequential organ failure assessment (SOFA) score
- Sexual function
- Sexual function and symptoms
- Short tempered
- Shortness of breath
- Shortness of breath
- Short-term morbidity rate
- Short-term mortality rate
- Single organ dysfunction/single organ failure
- Sleep
- Sleep function and symptoms
- Social roles
- Social roles, activities, or relationships
- Successful extubation
- Survival
- Survival after leaving ICU
- Survived event
- Susceptibility to repeated infections
- Sustained return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC)
- Swallowing function and symptoms
- Temperature
- The proportion of inpatients
- The rate of discontinuations due to adverse events
- The time when the condition became worse
- Therapeutic target (alteration in target (e.g. reduced tumor necrosis factor (TNF)))
- Time delirium and coma free days
- Time delirium free
- Time of ALT recovery
- Time of Mb recovery
- Time of Mb recovery
- Time of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 ribonucleic acid (SARS-CoV-2 RNA) turns to negative
- Time of using assisted breathing
- Time to 2019-nCoV real time – polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) negativity
- Time to CD4 t cell recovery
- Time to CD8 cell recovery
- Time to clinical improvement (TTCI)
- Time to cough disappearance
- Time to cough reported as mild
- Time to CRP recovery
- Time to defervescence (the subsidence of a fever)
- Time to delirium onset
- Time to dyspnea reported as absent
- Time to gastrointestinal symptoms reported as absent

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- Time to hospital discharge
- Time to national early warning score (NEWS2) of lower or equal to 2 maintained for 24 hours
- Time to release for isolation
- Time to resolution
- Time to treatment failure
- Tinnitus
- Total costs
- Tracheostomy
- Troponin
- Tube placement (time needed or success)
- Tumor necrosis factor (TNF)-alfa
- Type of residence
- Type of residence
- Use of antipsychotic medications
- Use of non-invasive ventilation (NIV)
- Ventilator free days
- Ventilators parameters
- Viral load or clearance
- Vision impairment
- Walking distance
- Weakness
- Weight loss
- Wishing to have died

Rationale behind the initial core outcome set

(This is the original and unedited text version shared with all collaborators)

The consensus process for developing the primary core outcome set (COS) in Denmark is depicted (Figure 1) and shortly explained below. Initially, 329 outcomes were identified from a literature search. Duplicates or overlapping outcomes were removed and remaining outcomes were aggregated in categories. From these categories 50 outcomes were found to be representative. We also performed 87 semi-structured interviews to ensure that the list covered all outcomes before creating the survey, which it did. The 50 outcomes informing the modified Delphi survey were narrowed to 19 by the four research panels. Additionally, our national stakeholder group further reduced the 19 outcomes to 6.

Figure 1. Consensus process for developing the primary COS

Survey

To determine which outcomes should be assessed across all clinical trials, patients, relatives, clinicians, and researchers were invited to participate in a survey consisting of three rounds. In each survey round, participants were required to grade the importance of 50 questions representing a specific

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outcome from 1-9, further categorized as *not important* (1-3), *important, but not critical* (4-6), and *critical* (7-9). Participants were instructed not to evaluate the questions in relation to one another, but to independently assess each question.

Each question was introduced with the phrase “How important is it to record or measure x?” Overall, the questions in the three survey rounds were the same. During the first round it was possible for participants to suggest unrevealed outcomes. These suggestions were presented to the research panels; however, no additions were made. We made a few changes in the wording of the questions and help-text between round 1 and 2 to clarify the understanding, and only minor changes between round 2 and 3. When answering the survey, participants were shown the results of the previous rounds with the aim of fostering consensus regarding critical outcomes. The heat-map (Figure 2) suggests that the process has triggered some changes along the way, while other outcome ratings were consistent.

The results also showed that patients and relatives participating in the survey did not rate any outcomes as not important, and only a few outcomes were rated not important by the clinicians and researchers. Thus, it wasn't possible to exclude any outcomes based on the survey alone.

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Figure 2. Heat map

All participants rated the 50 outcomes (“Question”) on a Likert scale from 1-9, where 1-3 is ‘not important’, 4-6 ‘important, but not critical’, and 7-9 ‘critical’ to include this outcome. This was rated for each survey round (StudyRound) nr 1, 2, and 3. Greener represents more important outcome.

Research panels

Results of the survey rounds were presented to four research panels comprising patients, family members, clinicians, and researchers (31 people in total). The task of the research panel was to narrow down and sort through what outcomes they could agree were critical outcomes. Unlike the survey participants, the research panels had to consider the individual outcomes in relation to each other. Whether one outcome was more important than another.

As a result of this process, the four research panels ended up rating between 9 to 13 outcomes as critical outcomes to assess across all clinical trials. The cumulative number of critical outcomes reached 19, as they varied across the different research panels (Table 1). In several cases, the research panels included multiple outcomes under an inclusive outcome. This includes patients' well-being, health-related quality of life after ICU discharge, patients' independent performance of activities of daily living after ICU discharge, and mental health after ICU discharge.

As for well-being, the original survey question addressed the patients' overall well-being. However, all research panels found that 'well-being' referred to the patients' well-being during their stay in the ICU. Well-being outside the ICU was considered included in health-related quality of life after ICU discharge.

Finally, all panels reached a consensus that three outcomes were not important and were excluded from the further consensus process. These three were: 1) whether to measure blood values within normal limits while in ICU, 2) whether to record vital signs within normal limits while in ICU, and 3) whether to record new medications prescribed for the patient after ICU discharge.

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Table 1. The cumulative number of the 19 critical outcomes across the four research panels

Outcomes
1. Survival
2. ICU length of stay
3. Hospital length of stay
4. ICU readmission rate during a hospital stay
6. Patients' overall well-being
7. Health economic consequences of a particular treatment in ICU
11. Duration of mechanical ventilation while in ICU
12. Duration of pharmacologic circulatory support while in ICU
14. Duration of sedation while in ICU
15. Duration of delirium while in ICU
19. Experience pain while in ICU
23. Discharge location after hospitalization
26. Health-related quality of life after ICU discharge
30. Family caregivers' experienced quality of life after the ICU stay
34. Independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge
37. Experience newly onset shortness of breath after ICU discharge
39. New onset of speaking troubles after ICU discharge
45. Mental function (cognitive function) after ICU discharge
51. Psychological health after ICU discharge (new outcome added during the research panel consensus meetings)

The colors refer to the number of panels who have agreed on the importance of each outcome. Dark green is 4/4 panels, light green 3/4 panels, yellow 2/4 panels, and orange 1/4 panels.

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Stakeholder group

The national stakeholder group involved in the development of the COS for the general ICU population gathered to define the primary COS. The stakeholder group was asked to consider the results of the research panel discussions in relation to whether an outcome would be too difficult to define or measure (methodological considerations), whether an outcome would be too resource consuming (feasibility considerations), and whether an outcome targeted the entire heterogeneous population. Thus, the stakeholder group had to consider a broader range of factors influencing COS consensus than both research panels and survey participants. There was no predetermined maximum number of outcomes, but it was discussed that both Cochrane and GRADE recommend a maximum of 7 outcomes in a COS.

As a starting point for the meeting, the results of the research panels discussions were presented. Subsequently, the debate was centered on the 19 outcomes chosen as critical outcomes by the research panels. This discussion led to consensus on 6 critical outcomes defining the primary COS (Figure 3). The rationale behind each outcome is explained below.

Figure 3. Primary COS

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Rationale behind each outcome

Survival

The original question in the survey was “How important is it to record ICU survival?” The stakeholder group agreed that ICU survival was not an optimal outcome due to the considerable variation in the definition of intensive care units worldwide. However, survival was considered as a critical outcome among all participants in both survey, research panels, and the stakeholder group. But the outcome 'survival' is to be recorded at predetermined timepoints.

Days alive without life support (respiratory, renal, and circulatory)

This outcome expresses organ failure and disease severity, consisting of various elements from the survey, including the duration of mechanical ventilation, circulatory support, and dialysis. Each intervention represents a different aspect of organ failure. The stakeholder group considered days alive without life support as a better measure of severity compared to time in the hospital, readmission to the ICU, or time in intensive care. For example, days in intensive care could be synonymous with the various treatments we offer our patients." For both mechanical ventilation, circulatory support, and dialysis, it was discussed whether different practices could affect the use of the outcome. Given substantial variations, the degrees of treatment need to be defined. However, this should occur after external validation, as relevant comments may influence the definition.

Days alive and out of hospital (DAAOOH)

Admission time at hospital and at ICU was discussed as well as re-admissions, but there may be large variation in practice. When is a patient admitted to an ICU and when is the patient discharged, this could be according to resources, when looking across countries. Therefore, DAAOOH may be a more neutral and covering outcome, which is also well known as a trial outcome. The elements of DAAOOH like length of hospital stay/ICU stay and re-admissions is graded critical according to the participants and is integrated in DAAOOH.

Health-related quality of life (HRQoL)

All participants agree that HRQoL is a critical outcome. HRQoL covers many outcomes (Table 3) including the patient's physical, mental, and social health. It was discussed that well-being may be a part of HRQoL. Also, it was discussed if post intensive care syndrome (PICS) could constitute the overarching outcome to cover both HRQoL and cognitive function. But the stakeholder group agreed that this outcome is not that well performing as

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a core outcome, yet, and there is uncertainty about how to assess it. All the underlying outcomes will be taken into consideration when deciding what tool to use for assessing HRQoL. Whether HRQoL should be assessed at fixed timepoint is also to be discussed.

Days alive without coma OR delirium

Both duration of coma and duration of delirium were rated as critical outcomes in 3/4 research panels. As well as respiratory failure, delirium is a prominent organ failure among many ICU patients. The stakeholder group discussed whether delirium and coma could be included in the aggregated outcome Days alive without life support. One argument against doing this, was that it would be easier to compare future data with data from previous trials. Also, life support refers to interventions, whereas delirium or coma refers to a syndrome or condition.

Cognitive function

This outcome was not much debated, due to consensus. However, it was pointed out, that the outcome must be measured at a fixed timepoint.

Other outcomes not included in the primary COS

6. Patients' overall well-being. The degree of well-being was critical for three out of four panels as a core outcome, but due to its broad definition and not being realistic to assess in all trials (though the comfort-scale may be close), it was not included as a core outcome. Several outcomes were found to be related to well-being, with well-being serving as an umbrella term that encompasses outcomes such as pain, shortness of breath and anxiety during ICU admission (Table 2).

7. Health economic consequences of a particular treatment in ICU. This outcome was considered to comprehensive to evaluate in all clinical trials. Depending on the tool assessing health-related quality of life this outcome may be optional to calculate.

19. Experience pain while in ICU. Is a subjective outcome and can be difficult to assess if the patients can not cooperate. However, this outcome is covered by the well-being outcome and must be considered important when defining measurement tools for well-being.

23. Discharge location after hospitalisation

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30. Family caregivers' experienced quality of life after the ICU stay. Is considered as a part of the patients' HRQoL. Caregivers' experienced quality of life may have a mutual impact on the patients HRQoL.

34. Independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge. Regarded as a part of the patients' HRQoL.

37. Experience new onset of shortness of breath after ICU discharge.

39. New onset of speaking troubles after ICU discharge. Regarded as a part of the patients' HRQoL.

51 (new outcome). Psychological health after ICU discharge (new outcome added during the 'consensus meetings). Regarded as a part of the patients' HRQoL.

Table 2. Outcomes related to well-being

16. Nausea and vomiting while in ICU
17. Thirst while in ICU
18. Short of breath while in ICU
19. Pain while in ICU
20. Anxiety while in ICU
21. Sleep while in ICU
22. Ability to communicate while in ICU

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Table 3. Outcomes related to health-related quality of life

24. Record patients' outpatient or general practitioner visits related to the long-term effects of intensive care
27. Newly onset tiredness or fatigue, unrelieved by sleep or rest, after ICU discharge
28. Newly onset pain after ICU discharge
29. Resume their usual roles in daily life after ICU discharge
32. Record whether patients after ICU discharge, compared to before, have the same labour market attachment
34. Independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge
35. Independently able to get dressed after ICU discharge
36. Mobile after ICU discharge
38. New onset speaking troubles after ICU discharge
39. New onset of swallowing difficulties after ICU discharge
40. Bowel function after ICU discharge
41. Urinary function after ICU discharge
42. Sexual function after ICU discharge
43. Senses: vision, hearing, touch, smell, and taste after ICU discharge
44. Physical strength to perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge
46. Loneliness after ICU discharge
48. Anxiety after ICU discharge
49. Depression after ICU discharge

The colors refer to the number of panels who have agreed on the importance of each outcome. Dark green is 4/4 panels, light green 3/4 panels, yellow 2/4 panels, and orange 1/4 panels

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Table S5. Summary minutes from all participating countries holding an international validation meeting

	Survival	Number of days alive without life support	Number of days alive without coma or delirium	Number of days alive out of hospital	Health-related quality of life	Cognitive function	Additional	Evaluation/ conclusion
<p>Australia summary for both the general ICU patient and the sepsis patients</p> <p><i>(Summary separated in the following two rows)</i></p>	<p>There was near unanimous agreement to accept this measure, acknowledging that it should not be the only measure and that the measurement time point is important and may vary between studies.</p>	<p>Accepting this measure was supported, but with a substantial minority favouring adapting the measure with further specification, including for example adapting the measure to specify relation to life support machines and ensuring that each component is also considered individually.</p>	<p>There was no support for accepting this measure and a majority favoured rejecting the measure. Coma and Delirium were not considered equivalent or appropriate to include in a single measure.</p>	<p>This measure was generally supported. A consistent theme was that it was being at home and not simply out of hospital that was important. Another consistent theme was that being at home was considered important by ICU survivors but that this outcome measure was questioned by clinicians and researchers as more a resource than patient-centred measure.</p>	<p>This measure was unanimously supported, noting the need to be able to compare to quality of life prior to intensive care and that quality of life valued by one person may be different to another.</p>	<p>There was no support to accept this measure. Predominant view to reject based on cognitive function being an essential component of quality of life.</p>	<p>The main domain considered important but not currently included in the proposed core outcome set were measures of psychosocial wellbeing, contribution to society and place in community, and return to work.</p>	
<p>Australia, New South Wales summary for sepsis patient</p>	<p>Survival is important. Shouldn't be the sole outcome - the time point is equally important. Median to longer term survival (60/90days – 6/12mths). Stable differential timepoint for a trial, longer time to results if main trial follow up outcome is too long, also</p>	<p>May not be sensitive enough. Very blunt instrument. Very difficult to implement. Quality of the data is varied across hospitals (delirium) Patient perspective – delirium was very impactful and linked with PTSD – would want this as an outcome or adapted within the cognitive outcomes.</p>	<p>May not be sensitive enough. Very blunt instrument. Very difficult to implement. Quality of the data is varied across hospitals (delirium) Patient perspective – delirium was very impactful and linked with PTSD – would want this as</p>	<p>Supportive but more detail required – what is considered out of hospital. Place of discharge – is it the same as the place prior to admission? Days alive and at home perhaps a better description. Measuring this outcome is hard. Analysis hard. We</p>	<p>All agreed this outcome was important and should be part of the minimum standard BUT the caveat is how we measure it and with what instrument. Sepsis survivors put forward that the measures for this outcome may be different for sepsis vs general</p>	<p>Most thought this outcome was limited to only one component of psychological function and if cognition is to be included separately to HRQoL, so should the other psychological components. Discussion to expand to psychological</p>		

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	Survival	Number of days alive without life support	Number of days alive without coma or delirium	Number of days alive out of hospital	Health-related quality of life	Cognitive function	Additional	Evaluation/ conclusion
	increases loss to follow-up, trial practically and costs. Reference to Marshall study <u>All agreed as a minimal outcome.</u>	Most agreed this outcome shouldn't be part of a minimal core outcome set. Adapt delirium under cognition or HRQoL – downstream effects may be picked up with HRQoL and qualitative studies. <u>9 voted to reject – 3 to adapt into the cognitive or HRQoL outcome.</u>	an outcome or adapted within the cognitive outcomes. Most agreed this outcome shouldn't be part of a minimal core outcome set. Adapt delirium under cognition or HRQoL – downstream effects may be picked up with HRQoL and qualitative studies. <u>9 voted to reject – 3 to adapt into the cognitive or HRQoL outcome.</u>	don't know enough about it. Is this about resource use rather than patient centred outcomes. Should be picking up the patient outcomes in other outcomes. Potentially very varied within health systems <u>10 agreed with the outcome but that it should be adapted to not be out of hospital (i.e., days alive and at home). 1 rejected. Created a lot of discussion that this outcome is used a lot but perhaps is more about resource use than patient centredness.</u>	critical illness. Consultation from sepsis survivors required. Important in trials to recognise that caregivers' outcomes are important and should be incorporated in to the follow up. <u>All agreed with this as a core outcome (with the caveat that it is important to have stakeholders discuss what will be measured and with what instrument. Sepsis may be different to general critical illness)</u>	function and not only cognitive function, i.e., include depression, anxiety, PTSD and psychosocial health. Wellbeing, communication, cognitive communication was also thought to be important to be included in this outcome. Delirium to be adapted in this outcome. <u>Adapt. All agreed that this outcome should be adapted to include the broader psychological and psychosocial functioning (which includes cognition). Cognitive function should not be the only measure included in a COS.</u>		
Australia Perth, Western Australia + virtual Summary for the general ICU patient	High degree of consensus that this outcome is 'key' and that survival is the main objective of intensive care treatment on which other outcomes are contingent. Issued considered included	General agreement that this is an important outcome measure but that it should specify that life support related to machines (e.g. breathing machines, pumps for continuous	Predominant view to adapt as coma and delirium considered to be very different entities and not appropriate to measure as a single outcome by attendees due to a	Predominant view to adapt, primarily recognising that it is essential that home is important and recognised, not other places outside of	A unanimous view that this was an important core outcome measure, noting the need to be able to compare to quality of life prior to intensive care and that quality of life	Predominant view to reject based on cognitive function being an essential component of quality of life.	Physical function outcome measure (e.g. ability to achieve independent mobilisation) Look at the patients ability to return to occupation/school Contribution to society- Would be	

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	<p>survival versus quality of life, the need for defined and potentially multiple measurement time points and the challenging terminology of ‘survival’ as a long-term outcome in relation to intensive care treatment (i.e. can survival still relate to intensive care long after discharge?).</p> <p><u>Quotes, comments, and themes:</u> If the patient does not survive, the rest of the COS are not relevant; the pt may survive ICU but may not survive their hospital admission, “it is important to look at survival long-term not just ICU/hospital survival” “Survival is a very important aspect to look at” To also look at the quality of survival; if a pt survives but has poor function, this is important to know Questions about the timepoint in which this COS measuring;</p>	<p>intravenous infusion of medicines), and that should specify new life support to differentiate from patients with pre-existing needs for machines including dialysis.</p> <p><u>Quote, comments, and themes:</u> It would also be important to have a measure of the impact on the body “Should life support specify machines?” Important to have this definition defined, “what do we mean by life support?” This core outcome measure is vague and needs clarification In terms of ECMO this is an “Important measure” Multiple opinions to adapt this COS to “life support machines” Not all machines may apply for all research projects</p>	<p>number of factors including the very different causes (medically induced or illness induced) of coma, that delirium may have more experiential impact on ICU patients than coma, and that long-term outcomes are more important than this short-term outcome.</p> <p><u>Quote, comments, and themes:</u> This core outcome needs specification; what do we mean by coma (induced or not induced); not sure is coma should be stated together with delirium May not be very valid for research trials as certain clinicians’ sedate patients more than others; there are going to be a lot of variables between practice of sedation depending on each clinician; physiological function is more</p>	<p>hospital like a nursing home or rehabilitation facility.</p> <p><u>Quote, comments, and themes:</u> This core outcome is important as it also links with survival; alive and out of hospital is important but it is also important to look at how much time a patient has spent at home; cannot look at this in isolation because it will not give enough information Going forward we probably have more transition of hospital to community-based healthcare, how will this affect this core outcome measure?</p>	<p>valued by one person may be different to another.</p> <p><u>Quote, comments, and themes:</u> “This core outcome will be very important”, nurses tend to establish a relationship with a patient so it would be nice to know how the patient is, are they living the life they want to? “An important measure; to see if a patient can get their life back on track is very meaningful to see” Does quality of life need to compare pre-ICU admission to post ICU? Which tool will be used to assist with this measurement? If we don’t have a tool that everyone agrees on it will be hard to compare outcomes globally</p>	<p><u>Quote, comments, and themes:</u> It would be better to measure functional impairment than cognition itself. Cognition is multifactorial May be better to look at whether a patient can go back to work/study/school rather than what is their memory like? Would this core outcome exclude people who had brain surgery? Important to consider people who had cognitive surgery therefore may need to adapt COS Patients who had their cognitive function measured found it stressing and confronting; patients said they felt like being tested and was very anxious, felt “down” that they did not do well on test To measure how the patient is prior vs post ICU, cognitive function</p>	<p>important to know if patient is able to return to work, can’t provide for family, or the extend they are able to contribute to community Important to also look at patient wishes, survival may not be a good thing for every patient Supporting network: Would be good to what social support the patient may have access to. Important to look at study tools used in research to best capture these outcome</p>	

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	<p>to look at survival itself is very vague, which timepoint in ICU would be appropriate to see a correlation</p> <p>Questions on how consistent ICU missions are at each hospital, and how this might influence outcome measures</p> <p>Hospitals may not all have the same written mission statement; these COS is to be used for research purposes to determine if care has helped the pt to become better; main purpose is to determine what outcomes are important to the patient that should be monitored whilst conducting a research project</p> <p>Thoughts to adapt this COS and will depend on a timepoint; a longitudinal approach is good; to look at not just one timepoint but multiple timepoints (3M,6M,12M)</p> <p>Unsure as this COS may be important to families but may not be important to the</p>		<p>important than delirium and may need to be a part of a separate core outcome</p> <p>Delirium can be more impacting than being in coma; first 24h out of coma can be a worse experience than coma.</p> <p>“Delirium is a huge consideration, it was the sickest and worst during my admission”</p> <p>Measure of delirium is more important as it is the main issue that is causing a patient to stress; days out of ICU and in ward traumatic with delirium</p> <p>Coma and delirium are two separate things, these outcomes needs to be separated</p> <p>There are other things that have effect on a patient’s long-term outcome; not sure if this core outcome should only focus on delirium and not the other factors</p>			<p>could fall under quality of life</p> <p>Patients performed a cognitive test and found it confronting, test could be affected by multiple factors such as quality of sleep, may have had a stressful morning. Patients felt as though they may have done better if the call was scheduled on another day, there may be variability on health status when reporting on measures</p> <p>This core outcome may not be relevant; cognitive function could be part of quality of life</p>		

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	<p>pt; may be difficult to adapt</p> <p>Survival is important but not sure if it should be a COS; “cannot put everybody in same basket”, what may the quality of life be if the pt survives but is left with cognitive impairment</p> <p>Survival is important in ICU, but survival as a COS may be a “waste of a measure”, “Survival should be an assumed outcome,” and if the pt survives we should measure other things relating how well did they survive</p> <p>Questions regarding if the pt survived well, why is there a post survival measurement? It was confusing for pts when they have survived but studies look at mortality within 3yrs-5yrs</p> <p>It is important to look at survival to determine whether an intervention is safe</p>							
Czech Republic	Was accepted by 100% of panel members but survival with	Days alive without life support (respiratory, renal, and circulatory) – six	Days alive without coma OR delirium – outcome accepted by all	Days alive and out of hospital – outcome was again not as	Health-related quality of life – the panel considered	Cognitive function – outcome was accepted by 100% of panel members,		Overall everyone in the meeting felt it was successful and very

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	Survival	Number of days alive without life support	Number of days alive without coma or delirium	Number of days alive out of hospital	Health-related quality of life	Cognitive function	Additional	Evaluation/ conclusion
	meaningful cognitive outcome was favoured.	out of eight panel members accepted. The outcome was not so important for patients as long as comfort, cognitive function, communication and hope were present. Outcome was important for clinicians and researchers, family members. E.g. length of ventilation not considered important as long as dyspnoea was not experience. (I'd rather be ventilated longer, earlier intubation or later extubation than to experience dyspnoea) Comfort included important aspect of the ability to communicate with staff and family – this helped to avoid/limit anxiety. Pain was also included but could be tolerated as long as other aspects, in particular, communication were attended to.	and considered more important than outcome	important for patients as long as comfort, cognitive function, communication and hope were present. Outcome was important for clinicians and researchers, family members.	four domains of QoL Physical – less important for patients, family members more important for clinicians and researchers Psychological – more important for patients, even more for family members Non-religious spirituality – important to be able to integrate ICU stay and critical illness into the context of one's life Social – family presence and a degree of self sufficiency important aspect It was noted that physical domain is not as important for patient and families as the other 3 domains of QoL	psychological health considered very important but very inter-individual.		important to discuss these issues and all agreed that new information and perspectives came to light. They were all happy to continue the discussions in the future.
Finland (Helsinki)	It was discussed and unanimously stated	It was discussed and unanimously stated	It was discussed and unanimously stated that the	It was discart and unanimously stated that the	It was discussed and unanimously stated that the	It was discussed and unanimously stated that the	It was discussed and it was unanimously concluded that 6	What worked well was that participants were

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	<p>that the variable is important. Comments; Patient: It is absolutely important that this is measured. However, it has felt strange when, after intensive care, a survey was sent home, asking about being alive, and not being more interested in health. Doctor: It is important to include this variable because it can be clearly measured. Death is a significant outcome in intensive care. Doctor: Surviving the intensive care unit alive is important, but this alone is not enough, you have to look at how the patients survive holistically. Patient: If the person is satisfied, the treatment has gone well</p>	<p>that the variable is important. Comments; Doctor: Hospital and doctor-centric measure, commits the patient to the intensive care unit. It is significant in terms of ICU performance and resources. Doctor: In terms of resources, it is significant from the point of view of costs to the society. Patient: With vital function support treatments, the patient can live normally even outside the hospital. Doctor: The criteria for starting and stopping ventilator treatment and other life support in studies should be the same in all countries. Patient: But do the outcome variables work in every country with different income levels.</p>	<p>variable is important. Doctor, researcher: Unconsciousness can be due to sedation or injury Doctor: Delirium is very critical in intensive care. It is very welcome that this is raised and included in the variables. Patient: It is good that this is taken into account, the patient's delirium or coma is also, very difficult for the relatives. Doctor: Intensive care environment predisposes to delirium, drugs can also cause it.</p>	<p>variable is important. However, it should also be specified how to define outside the hospital (rehabilitation, supported housing, hospital bed department, etc.) Comments Patient. This is a significant treatment outcome variable. Doctor: For many, it is important to return home. It should be defined what means outside the hospital. Patient: It is important to return home or to where you came from.</p>	<p>variable is important. The quality of life measure should always include physical, psychological and social quality of life. Comments Doctor: Quality of life is routinely measured after intensive care, looking at different areas of life, and general health (on a scale of 0–100). Patient: It can be difficult to define the perceived state of health, or to relate the assessment of the state of health to one's own normal condition. Doctor: The survey is always subjective, a person can have functional limitations and still be satisfied with their quality of life. Patient: The quality of life indicator should also take into account relatives</p>	<p>variable is important. It was considered whether adverse events in intensive care should also be taken as a separate core outcome variable Comments Doctor: Will there be a problem if we screen. In this case, there should be a readiness to refer to further investigation if necessary. Doctor: If cognition deteriorates, it affects everything about recovery, quality of life and the patient's loved ones.</p>	<p>core outcome variables of intensive care can be considered suitable for Finnish conditions.</p>	<p>eager to discuss and all thought this was interesting and important. There were no feelings of difficulties to speak out one's opinions e.g. due to hierarchy or other obstacles, the environment at both library rooms was relaxed. The structured approach by using the standardised power point presentation (translated to Finnish) was good base for the introductory phase. The video was also good to have. Things that were slightly challenging: In both meetings it was sometimes necessary to repeat that the focus is in general ICU research and comparison of the study groups It is challenging for the lay people to fully understand the principles of</p>

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					Patient: It would be good if there was a customized self-care questionnaire for each intensive care patient			clinical studies (randomization etc), when explained only shortly Some outcomes are essentially measured within a given time limit (days alive without...) and it might have become easier to grasp if the tools would have been already chosen (QoL, cognition etc) Sometimes the discussion drifted to the patients own recovery process that they wanted to share,, but that was allowed. For me as a coordinator in the first meeting it was slightly challenging not to interfere too much with my own opinion. I felt that I could have stressed the importance of delirium more and maybe interfered, but I chose not to, for keeping the authenticity.
Finland (Tampere)	It was unanimously agreed that survival	This was generally perceived slightly	J.H. first explained delirium to the	All: This was largely discussed	Patients: This should be	Patients and family members:	Patients and family members suggested	Same as for Finland (Helsinki)

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	<p>is an important outcome and belongs to the core outcome set. Doctor: It has been the traditional measure of outcome and it is easy to measure and absolute of nature Doctor: It is a condition that has to be fulfilled for all the other outcomes to be achieved Patients and family members agreed to including this outcome in the COS.</p>	<p>less clear. Coordinator explained the concept and the benefits in study populations with high mortality when mortality is a competing event. And it was explained that this outcome always is measured within a certain time period. Doctor: This outcome requires that the criteria of initiating and ending a certain treatment need to be well defined. We also discussed the impact of different centres and their practices in this context. Doctors and patients: This may not be so much of importance to the patient. Doctor and researcher-doctor: But it may be important when calculating the benefit to the organization, economics, and thus benefit to society. Doctors: The life support is actually close to a measure</p>	<p>panel. The concept of coma was a bit difficult, and we discussed whether it covers both pharmacologically induced and non-pharmacological coma. This may have caused some confusion. The patients shared their experiences, both had experienced delirium. One of them had had delirium with only positive content in the delusions. The patients and family members thought that delirium is important but were not sure whether it should be included in the COS. Doctor and doctor-researcher: Delirium is important but can be slightly less easy to detect in many cases. They said that it is a good outcome in some studies but were</p>	<p>from the aspect of what out of hospital means. What will be counted as out of hospital, for example in cases when healthcare institutions are still involved. Patients: The patients want to go home, and sometimes this requires extra care that can be provided from healthcare providers. Doctors: So this depends on the systems in each participating center. Conclusion: This was however considered an important outcome and to be included.</p>	<p>interpreted carefully, whether there are some new unrelated problems or is the result reflecting problems related to intensive care. Coordinator: Explained that this is a composite and that when comparing groups, both groups should have equal amounts of "external causes" in addition to the ICU related causes. Patients: How would cultural differences be taken into account? Patients and family members: It is important to know that quality of life can also improve due to different values after critical illness. Doctors and researcher: The validity of this measure is dependent of which tool is going to be chosen</p>	<p>This is a very important outcome to be included in the COS, it affects many aspects of life. Doctors and researchers: Agree We discussed a little how this can be measured and how the baseline situation is affecting the results. Conclusion: It was unanimously agreed that this should be included in the COS.</p>	<p>that the well-being of family members should also be studied as an outcome.</p>	

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		that determines the need of ICU care. Patient and family member: How well does this outcome describe recovery? Patient and family member: In our experience, discharge from ICU may also be an impairment, because the sudden drop of the time when personnel are available. This was discussed and well understood. We also discussed whether the number of readmissions would be influencing this outcome. Conclusion: Consensus was reached that this outcome is important and should be in the COS	slightly hesitant to have it included in all studies. On the other hand, they pointed out that this is also an organ dysfunction, and therefore important. Conclusion: There was some hesitance in accepting this outcome to the COS.		and what is the timing of the assessment. Conclusion: This was accepted conditionally.			
Iceland	All individuals in panel agreed that this was an important outcome, both for the patient as well as the clinicians. No barriers for measurement in Iceland	All individuals in panel agreed that this was an important outcome, both for clinicians and patients. No barriers for measurement in Iceland. Discussions revolved around timing of assessment, and how various support would need to be	All individuals in panel agreed that this was an important outcome, both for clinicians and patients. No barriers for measurement in Iceland. Discussion revolved around the varying aspects of delirium	All individuals in panel agreed that this was an important outcome, both for clinicians and patients. No barriers for measurement in Iceland. Discussion revolved around the importance of	All individuals in panel agreed that this was an important outcome, both for clinicians and patients. No barriers for measurement in Iceland. Also that this is frequently not measured, and would be a big	No comments	No comments	There was a lively discussion amongst all participants, and all agreed that the outcome set was very patient-centred – which was positively regarded by all. There was some discussion about a lack of outcomes

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		clearly defined – as some organ support is possible outside of the ICU depending on hospital resources.	and its fluctuating course, where a person might classify as having or not having delirium based on time of assessment. This would increase inaccuracy of this measurement, and mandates that the measurement is very clearly defined.	defining what “out of hospital means” – outpatient rehabilitation, nursing home etc. Also that this outcome not only measures the ICU treatment but also the hospital treatment and rehabilitation, dependent on timing of assessment.	benefit of a more global adoption of core outcome set.			describing more closely the ICU course of participants, but overall felt that at least three of the outcomes could reflect this. For things to improve, there was a discussion whether readmission rate within a specific timeframe would be beneficial. In general, some examples of potential measurements would have benefitted the discussion and ensured that all stakeholders had a mutual understanding of what individual outcome could mean. These examples were provided to facilitate understanding when prompted by the primary investigator for Iceland, emphasizing that the exact timing and choice of tools to measure were

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								without the scope of the meeting.
India (Chennai)	Survival was explained (not just ICU survival) and explained that the length of survival is still debated but the consensus has been that it is one of important outcomes. From the perspective of intensive care patient, when they go into ICU, they are concerned about their life. Ultimately what does matter, including for the family member is whether they are going to come out alive from ICU. There is no doubt that mortality/survival is going to be a very valid outcome. Survival is a hard outcome compared to other outcomes that can be manipulated. For eg. days in ICU (dependent on intensivist if he wants to keep patient for an extra day or bed availability in the ward). These are	It was explained what the outcome means through examples and asked if anyone has any doubts regarding the outcome understanding and opened floor for discussion. There was confusion even amongst intensivists. The person must be alive and free from any kind of support. If the person has lived for 15 days without support and then passes on, then their days are counted as zero. Another point is that sometimes patient's family members insist on taking the patient back home for providing a peaceful end (DAMA, LAMA etc.), in trials we report them as alive, but we really don't know what happened to them. We should keep these in mind while discussing this COS. It may be important to know the severity of the health condition; based on	It was discussed that delirium and Coma should be covered in the mental health component of post ICU evaluation? It was clarified that in this case the outcome was being measured while in hospital or until a prespecified time point (to be determined). This could be a part of being free of organ support. As clinician it is our goal to keep the patient as awake as possible and limit the harmful impact of sedation. That's why this outcome is considered separately. This can be modified by clinician so I am not convinced that it can be an outcome. In ICU everything we do is directed towards the brain. It is not directly supported, but	Going to hospital and turned into vegetative state was discussed, I am still alive and out of hospital but that's not the quality of life I would want. So, its shades of grey. It takes a toll on care giver as well. We should have scales like GOSC or RANKIN Score where its not black and white but shades of grey. Having a metric that incorporates quality of life would make the outcome more relevant. It may be statistically important in clinical trials but in GOSC the story would be different. As a core outcome parameter, I am little hesitant to say this is essential. We are going to cover the health-related quality of life in the next outcome.	This outcome talks about the several aspects of health physical health, social health, mental health, and cognitive health, after discharge from ICU. Time points are not defined. The parameter should also consist of how nutrition improves post critical care to be added to HR-QoL. Three aspects to be considered, viz it should be easily measurable, it should be repeatable, and it should be replicable.	No disagreements. Consensus was achieved on adopting this outcome.	It was discussed whether financial consequences/health economic consequences should be mentioned here. It is more relevant in Indian setting. Can we have access to all the other outcomes? They might be more relevant to us in Indian setting.	

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	<p>subjective, soft outcomes and may be manipulated but survival can't be manipulated. It is definitely important, at what timepoint, that may be dialogued further. As a caregiver, lay person, for me, survival is one of the reasons we agree for trials, even without knowing much of background about it. We understand that the patient needs it. Survival is the 'must have' outcome. She was reminded of the incident where doctors told her husband is a cat on the wall, at that point of time, it was the survival which was most important thing to consider. Bhuvana: Survival is the most important outcome for any patient. When it comes to ICU, it's even more important. We can always think about the timeframe. It is a patient centred outcome and important for doctors as well.</p>	<p>that, we can decide if the outcome is important. Also, this outcome is important because being alive and hooked up to machines affects the quality of life and survival as the patient may deteriorate. There should be a corollary when we talk about ventilation because hi-flow nasal therapy which is not conventionally classified as ventilator. There would be patients on this kind of support. How do we classify those patients? Second point is, patients with low blood pressure, we have to personalize targets. We say that is the MAP is above 65, we cut off vasopressor support, irrespective of whether we think the patient needs a higher map or not. This is a grey zone. It was summarized that there is lack of clarity about the non-invasive type of respiratory support, and whether the</p>	<p>indirectly. It is a patient centric outcome. We may need to go in details to refine the outcome so that it is measured appropriately. VJ: It reflects the special value that is placed by the stakeholders on brain function. It's important to hear from patients and caregivers whether they think it is an independent and important outcome. Shree Lekha: It is obvious that I would want my family member to be communicating to me because it makes me believe that they are recuperating successfully, despite the machines attached. Doctors may give reassurance, but the blink of the eye or wave of hand is a good sign for me emotionally. Does the parameter have</p>	<p>It is an essential outcome as a single measure. Of course, quality of life can be looked at separately. It is important to know that you can be alive and survive outside hospital for a longer period. Most of us are confusing between the technical issues related to analysis vs what is relevant to the patient and their families and clinicians. This outcome is also going to capture the resources that's used and trauma to the patient and their families and to the healthcare systems. Days alive does take these factors into account. The 3rd and 4th outcomes are overlapping but not necessarily identical parameters. Getting into hospital again</p>				

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	<p>Consensus was achieved on adopting.</p>	<p>definition was broad enough to include them. Besides the technical definition, the outcome is quite relevant from anyone's perspective. Other than living in the ICU, living without support is a very valuable outcome to have. I would rather be alive without a ventilator than with it. It is a valuable endpoint. Apart from the statistical point of view which I didn't understand, I feel it is very important outcome to have. It was asked if we could add on with some categorization for stable and unstable patients, like patients who require large support, a stable patient who doesn't need inotrope support? It was explained that in this outcome they are trying to club all the support together. Three key types of support - dialysis support, breathing support</p>	<p>without sedation? BK clarified, in the text of outcome, the impact of sedation is mentioned. It is important, and patient centered but how will we measure it? We may have to put clauses like, without sedation. VJ: If we measure something badly, it ceases to be useful outcome, even if we prioritise it. We hope that trial conduct will be standardized, and randomization would take care of some of the variations. We should look at the importance of outcome, keep in mind the challenges of measurement and ensure the standardization of the trial. We are not looking at it from patient's comfort or their family's point of view, we are looking at it from the technicalities of</p>	<p>and again is not only going to affect quality of life but so many other parameters like health economics, people end up spending more due to repeated hospitalizations. We must keep in mind that the outcome should be measurable and be practical, otherwise the value goes down. This outcome makes sense and is important. I also agree that it is an important and must have outcome.</p> <p>Consensus was achieved on adopting this outcome.</p>				

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		<p>and blood pressure support. If a new treatment is being tested, does it keep you free of all these supports? Needed clarification if we need to consider all three supports? In that case, it is going to be a bit tough. Others had similar concerns because someone may require renal therapy for longer time and clubbing them with someone on respiratory support. Second how do you account for someone who is on chronic kidney dialysis support? Will they be considered being on organ support? As an outcome is it good, no problem, but the nitty-gritty have to be sorted. To counter Urvi's concern, I suppose randomization will address these choices. We have lapsed into how to measure the outcomes which is different from the fact that whether we think the outcome is important or not. I</p>	<p>measurements which we clearly need to ignore. Someone who doesn't need sedation and is not delirious is obviously recovering and that is a good indicator of the success of the treatment. (Probably sedation was given more because the treatment was ineffective). So it is a good outcome to have. I do have reservations about the definitions and appropriateness of measurements of each outcome, but I am staying out of it completely and trying to understand if it's a valuable endpoint. We need to look at the outcomes from this perspective. Consensus was achieved for adopting this outcome.</p>					

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		<p>suppose we did agree that the outcome is important and that there are some challenges and subjectivity in measuring it as it is not a hard outcome to some extent, and we hope that randomization will take care of those uncertain variables. It was concluded that all agree that this is an important outcome and there are no disagreements on the outcome itself; of course there are few challenges in measuring it.</p> <p>Consensus was achieved on adopting.</p>						
India (Mumbai)	<p>Both patients did not value survival if it was on life support Physiotherapist and Occupational Therapist said survival without quality of life had no meaning For the doctors and researchers and family, this was the most important outcome</p>	<p>All agreed that this was important</p>	<p>Patients and nurses valued this the most</p>	<p>Only the 2 patients felt this was most important Family views- How does it matter where you are, if you can't eat, walk, or have cognitive dysfunction. Difficult to manage for the family if out of hospital, with no</p>	<p>Physiotherapist, Occupational therapist, and nurses valued this the most</p>	<p>Patients and relatives valued cognitive function the most Physiotherapist, Occupational therapist, and nurses valued this the most Doctors felt it was important, but not most important</p>		

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				health care support (paid from pocket mostly in India)				
Lithuania	Discussion on this point started with defining the difference of ICU survival and hospital survival. Small proportion of participants felt that ICU survival per se is of limited value and focus should be shifted to hospital survival. Since clinical studies often focus on entirety of clinical episode, thus if positive outcome in ICU is not followed by positive hospital, the initial success is of limited value to patients and research. Proponents of ICU survival as a core outcome listed five key points for consideration: 1.It allows to focus on processes, treatments and interventions carried out on ICU, thus may be of relevance to mixed general ICU patient population, when clinical trials often study general approaches (for	Panel debated definition provided in the COS presentation. Discussion focused on whether using this as a definition of disease severity is appropriate or whether definition should define this outcome more in terms of recovery (or completeness of recovery) from critical illness. This aspect is also supported by the middle section of definition (comparing this to such outcomes as time in hospital or ICU readmissions). Panel agreed that initiation and discontinuation of organ support is likely to be a lot less variable, than other outcomes. Panel suggested that additional standard explanation regarding ambulatory organ support should be included with definition of this	Debating this as a composite outcome caused the widest variation in opinions and some difficulty in reaching consensus. Panel agreed that both coma and delirium reflect CNS failure and its severity, but somewhat struggled with the concept of combining both in a single outcome. There was a consensus that both contribute to increased hospital length of stay and worsening of other key outcomes. There was an opinion from nursing and patient representatives, that both coma and delirium result in significantly increased care requirements and may have significant negative impact on carers,	Panel was unanimous in adopting this as one the most important outcomes. There was only limited discussion regarding this outcome due to consensus. Further discussion focused on benefits of reporting as many of the core outcomes as possible as this would provide a more complete picture of patient outcomes.	Panel agreed that this is critically important outcome and unanimously supported its adoption. Discussion followed on methodological aspects. As there are several scoring and assessment systems, trials may use different ones, which would make it more difficult to compare results, even though the outcome may appear the same. Panel felt that it would be preferable to have recommendations on which scoring systems should be used (for example SF-36 for general population, Glasgow Outcome Scale Extended for patients with neurological injury). Panel acknowledged that traditional assessment of HRQoL	Panel agreed that this outcome is critically important and has clear links to HRQoL. However, there were multiple uncertainties regarding methodology, consistency, tools, time-points. Acceptable degree of cognitive decline may be dependent on multiple factors, including patient preferences, family, social and system-wide resources. Healthcare and social care systems with more extensive resources may accept different levels of acceptable cognitive decline in comparison to those where long-term care is predominantly depended on family members, privately funded or private		

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	<p>example fluid balance, sedation, ventilation, etc.), rather than treatments aimed at specific pathology.</p> <p>2. Patient representatives suggested that even limited survival after ICU may be of benefit to the patient, especially if cognitive function is preserved. Some examples included terminal conditions diagnosed during the same ICU episode and survival after ICU gave patients and their families much needed time to come to terms with the diagnosis and poor short-term outcome.</p> <p>3. While ICU care is likely to have some variation, but the range of this variation is likely to be relatively minor in majority of European countries (possibly to a comparable range of the outcome variances amongst ICUs in the same country). However, there is likely to be</p>	<p>outcome. Specific example is intermittent chronic dialysis. In cases of irrecoverable renal failure after critical illness, there is a time point when dialysis dependence is established, and patients transition to ambulatory renal replacement. After this time point dialysis reflects chronic health condition and is no longer representative of acute disease severity. This led to the next discussion point regarding completeness of recover. Sever panel members felt very strongly about importance of measuring impact of our interventions on the likelihood of organ recovery. Panel agreed that this could be primary (or key secondary outcome) in selected trials investigating new treatments and interventions. There was some discussion about ambulatory</p>	<p>especially family members who look after their relatives with significant neurological disability. There was some disagreement on the value and impact of this core outcome on decision making. Some felt that duration of coma and delirium is an important factor in their decision making, but there were those who made very clear distinction between the two stating that prediction of coma or delirium would have very different weight in interpretation of research results and decision making. Overall it was agreed that days without coma or delirium could be used as a surrogate marker for survival with good neurological function. There was an absolute consensus, that</p>		<p>(patient/family interviews at fixed time points) is very resource intense, therefore concerns were raised regarding feasibility of testing this in majority of clinical trials. Panel also commented on the fact that due to nature of critical illness, background information of HRQoL is seldom available, therefore it is hardly ever feasible to make before and after comparisons of HRQoL. Some opinions were expressed on the use of secondary healthcare data (for example prolonged need of care, repeated hospital admissions, new diagnoses or new regular treatments after ICU admission, or similar indicators) could be used as surrogate indicators of</p>	<p>insurance funded long-term care. In many cases absence of close relatives may be deciding factor. Therefore, major variations are likely even amongst the EU member states, even more so worldwide, thus limiting general applicability of this outcome. Similarly to HRQoL, issues were raised in regard to lack of baseline information and limited scope of before and after comparison and also resources required to measure this outcome in clinical trials. Panel felt that wider adoption of this core outcome would depend on recommended tools, simplicity of use and applicability in variety of systems/countries with varying long-term care arrangements.</p>		

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	<p>significant variation in post-ICU care, especially with regards to provision of nursing care (nurse to patient ratio), rehabilitation, physiotherapy, speech and language, psychology, etc. Therefore, ICU mortality is likely to be a more standardised and comparable outcome, then hospital mortality.</p> <p>4. Follow-up from point 2 was raised by several panel members - intensivists may have limited scope of initiating significant change in post-ICU care, thus if clinical trial protocols use hospital mortality as a primary outcome, there may be increasing pressure to standardise not only ICU, but post-ICU management as well. This may reduce the number of units participating in multi-centre trials.</p> <p>5. It was stated that hospital mortality following ICU</p>	<p>respiratory support in select conditions (end-stage motor-neurone disease) and ambulatory cardiovascular support (ventricular assist devices) but it was felt that these issues are less likely to be the subject of general ICU research.</p> <p>Overall panel recommended to adopt this outcome.</p>	<p>could be one of the most important outcomes. This position was supported by all participants. However, there is a challenge to this approach, as this definition does not cover patients with debilitating neurological injury, but who are neither in coma nor delirium. For example, patients with persistent GCS score of 12-14 (spont eye opening, obey simple commands, unable to communicate, respond). While this is not a large cohort, it is not insignificant. While days alive with favourable neurological condition was mentioned as a better option, panel did acknowledge that standardising such definition is more difficult and may be prone to various biases. Panel agreed that</p>		<p>HRQoL. While these indicators lack fidelity provided by patient interviews, such data can be collated from already existing sources (health and social insurance or similar governmental bodies), thus significantly reducing resources needed and could be more uniformly applied. Panel also acknowledged, that there may be significant legislative variations in EU member states (and even more so worldwide), thus reducing its uniform applicability. Panel also discussed subjective versus objective perception of HRQoL. Patient representatives felt that same degree of disability may be perceived as acceptable to</p>			

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	<p>survival can fall into two categories – expected and unexpected deaths. Focusing solely on hospital mortality, may reduce our ability to focus on preventable post-ICU deaths and design prevention systems.</p> <p>Panel debated fixed time points for ICU mortality. General consensus was that it should be measured as <i>de facto</i> ICU and hospital mortality, irrespective of ICU/Hospital length of stay. Panel was not in favour of arbitrary time points (such as 28-day mortality). Some examples were provided from evidence of cardiothoracic ICU research, that demonstrated significant differences between 30 and 90 day mortality and measurable proportions of those deaths arose from post 30-day, but in-ICU mortality. Fixed time points might be</p>		<p>incorporation of cognitive function in this outcome would be important, especially in research projects, that do not use COS outcome 6 (cognitive function).</p>		<p>some and unacceptable to others. Some examples were provided by clinical colleagues on patients who adapted well to disability following critical illness, resulting in acceptable quality of life in spite of significantly reduced objective HRQoL scores. Panel advocated wider adoption of subjective QoL evaluation tools to capture above mentioned aspects.</p>			

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	greater value when measuring long-term outcomes (for example 6, 12 months, 5 years). Overall panel recommended to adopt this outcome.							
Norway	There was broad agreement that survival is a central goal in the treatment of critically ill patients and an important outcome in clinical studies. Everyone agreed that it should be included in the dataset. There was a discussion about when it is most appropriate to define the time of death without the group reaching a conclusion. This will be discussed later.	There was a debate whether “days alive outside the intensive care unit” could replace the proposed elements of organ support treatment, but we concluded that the proposed endpoint is important, necessary, easy to measure, reflects resource use in the intensive care unit, and provides a fairly good insight into patient’s severity of illness.	This can be perceived as a measure of central nervous system dysfunction during the intensive care stay, and input from patients clearly emphasized that delirium is a strongly undesirable experience. It is therefore essential to minimize intensity and duration of delirium if possible. Furthermore, it was pointed out that delirium as a symptom is an important prognostic factor for the mental health in survivors. Thus, there was broad agreement about the importance of delirium as a phenomenon, but	In 4 out of 6 proposed outcomes, survival is part of the endpoint. There was broad agreement that survival was adequately addressed in points 1 and 2. The group therefore saw no significant added value in including this endpoint. On the contrary, there was broad agreement that this endpoint could be removed in favour of other important endpoints that have been omitted from the proposed COS (see below). The group pointed out significant variation in the organization of intensive care units and	The group considered this to be very important endpoint, highly relevant, and essential to include in a COS. Throughout the discussion, it was emphasized very clearly that the endpoint is poorly specified in the Danish proposal, and therefore, some apprehension regarding the further process regarding its precise content, as well as concern that later choice of instruments to measure HRQoL may limit or broaden the scope of this domain.	Similarly, the group unanimously agreed that cognitive function is a very important endpoint. Much time was spent discussing how cognitive function can be measured in two ways (subjectively and objectively), and that results from previous studies may be difficult to compare. Nevertheless, the group wanted to retain this endpoint.	The group believed that the draft had significant shortcomings. Two absent issues were highlighted: physical function and mental health. Both elements represent central symptom domains in the “post-intensive care syndrome” (PICS), and the group considers it a clear weakness in the proposed COS that these have been omitted. Although HRQoL might possibly include both elements, the group agreed that both aspects should be specifically addressed as endpoints in a COS.	The group has conducted a meeting in accordance with the guidelines provided. The group had a good and open discussion about the 6 proposed endpoints. The group agrees with inclusion of endpoints 1, 2, 5, and 6 but rejects endpoints 3 and 4. Furthermore, the group believes that a common dataset should specifically include physical function and mental health and therefore calls for this inclusion.

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			<p>the group was critical of including it as a separate endpoint in a COS. The following issues were raised: a) the combination of delirium and coma is artificial as these are two distinct phenomena; b) delirium is a fluctuating mental state and will therefore often be difficult to capture; c) systematic monitoring of delirium is labour-intensive, not performed in all intensive care units, and will therefore be difficult to implement without extraordinary resources. The group was also critical of placing delirium in a context with the number of days alive, as survival is already implemented in other endpoints.</p>	<p>hospitals in different parts of the country, which may affect the validity and consistency of such data.</p>				
Netherlands	No need for discussion, clear for	There was a discussion because of the choice for	This is a very important outcome because	Outcome of great value. It is important to	All participants agreed that this outcome is very	Very important from the patient's perspective	We discussed a lot of the outcomes that were mentioned in	It worked well that we took our time for the

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	all participating panel members.	<p>'days alive without life support' instead of days on the ventilator or days with ECMO etc. We discussed that, in the end, you could still calculate the outcome 'days on a ventilator'.</p> <p>However, seen from the patient' perspective it is more important to measure the days without life support instead of days on life support as it is more based on the question; what do you contribute to the patient's life? What really matters (and what the treatment is meant for) is the days alive without support. The participants also mentioned that it is important to determine a cut-off point for each study.</p>	it can affect recovery after the ICU (and may possibly result in long-term complaints)	measure this outcome as days alive and discharged from the hospital because there is a lot of variation in the length of stay among the different hospitals (in the ICU and on the wards as well)	important. We discussed what HRQoL really means and how this can be measured. But also which outcomes are related to HRQoL as it seems to be a collection of outcomes (well-being, daily functioning etc) – more like an umbrella term	because cognitive functioning can have a significant impact on daily life and is not part of the HRQoL-questionnaires	the 19 outcomes list including performing daily activities, well-being, pain and discomfort in the ICU etcetera but agreed that some of these outcomes are less important because they are inconvenient for a short period of time (i.e., discomfort, thirst, pain during ICU-admittance) and also that HRQoL covers a lot of these outcomes including well-being, stress and daily functioning. The panel did not come up with any additional outcomes.	introduction, to get to know each other a little bit. Some participants did not know what to expect so it was really helpful to show them the YouTube video and to take enough time to introduce the benefits of a panel and the COS. We took a lot of time for this first meeting, in a place far from the ICU which also worked well. Other than that, apart from an emergency power test, there were no distractions in the form of phones ringing or people leaving or entering the room. Everyone was also present in civilian clothes, which lowered the threshold between professionals and patients. If I have to mention something that could be improved, it is the emergency power test, but these tests are only planned shortly in

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								advance and fortunately the power was back after fifteen minutes. Also, the attendees were prepared for the emergency testing by the moderator.
Poland	The panel members agreed that this was a universal, relevant endpoint that was quite obvious from all points of view. The issue of timepoints was raised	The experts noted that this outcome requires a clear definition. Is it ICU-limited support or long-term support? The problem of end stage renal disease/dialysis was noticed (supporting kidney function in the long term is not as burdening as supporting the respiratory system) and the fact that often discharge from intensive care of a patient who requires respiratory or renal support is possible, unlike supporting the circulatory system	Very important from the point of view of the patient’s families. The definition of coma and delirium – potentially difficult to define due to its continuous nature (wide spectrum of disorders). An56articipant indicator of the quality of care.	Requires defining what does out of hospital mean? How to approach long-term care and rehabilitation facilities? Also, the issue of timepoints was raised	Potential difficulty in the assessing the outcome due to lack of “post-ICU” outpatient clinics. In the panel’s opinion, a very important outcome, but with numerous limitations – different tools, lots of aspects. Quite complex outcome. A large group of patients with communication problems (aphasia, paresis) – is the caregiver’s assessment important then? The issue of the care-givers quality of life was also mentioned at this point.	As in the point above, possible difficulties in the assessment were mentioned, depending somewhat on the time point at which the assessment will be made. The moment of discharge from the ICU, the moment of discharge from the hospital – less difficulties. Distant time point – is it possible and reliable to remotely assess cognitive functions (e.g. by telephone?) It seems necessary to use the same (universal?) tools to make this outcome objective and comparable		It seems that each panel member understood the purpose of the meeting and was able to present their point of view on specific aspects. The opinions complemented each other and it is indeed very important that people from various interested groups participated in such a panel. It was mentioned in the presentation that <i>“Frequency and tool will be discussed in another meeting, not here. Definitions are provided in the notes”</i> but we found it not sufficient for our discussion. Different panel

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								<p>members understood some outcomes differently, in their own style, and the lack of clear definitions or the time and circumstances in which they would be assessed made discussions somewhat difficult, especially regarding two last outcomes.</p> <p>To sum up, the meeting went smoothly and the discussions were interesting and developing. For the future, we think it would be useful if at least one of the panel members had been involved in an earlier stage of COS creation or had some type of training/mentoring from the previous stakeholders.</p>
Sweden	All participants agreed on that survival should be included in a core outcome set. One patient emphasized that "survival is important, but one	There was a discussion regarding the definition of life support " is for example intermittent dialysis and high flow oxygen included?"	The ICU survivors (former patients) firmly stated that they wished that duration of delirium was as short as possible, since it may save	This might be important from a financial perspective but not from a patient perspective. It is an outcome that	All participants agreed on that this was an important outcome. However, it was highlighted that the measurement should preferably	The 57 participants stated that cognitive function is important to be able to manage daily life, to work, and is a part of one's personality.	The 57 participants suggested adding psychological function (51) to the core outcome set. One patient stated that you may have good HRQL even	The joint discussion was audio recorded, which provided us an opportunity to return to the discussion in case there were

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	does not want to end up as a vegetable”.	Circulatory support is not as burdensome for the patient as respiratory support might be. Yet, circulatory support is essential for survival. In the end it was concluded that all days without life support could potentially reduce the risk of complications and time of recovery. There might be a difference in duration of life support because of cultural differences. In Sweden it is common to terminate life support in desolate cases, which is not the case in all countries.	patients (and family) the trauma of being exposed to hallucinations, worry and anxiety, which potentially can mitigate the risk of PTSD. They stated that losing “mental anchor to reality” was by far the worst experience. It was perceived as positive to include delirium as it will lead to more focus on the evaluation of delirium. “Dare to ask” about delirium was highlighted. One patient shared that his hallucinations fluctuated and remained even after discharge from hospital. However, delirium may be difficult to measure, as it varies over time. Being in coma may sometimes be inevitable and was therefore not necessarily considered to be an adverse outcome. There was a discussion regarding whether	depends on the resources in the health system rather than being a patient-centered outcome. All patients expressed that they had been discharged from hospital too early due to lack of resources. Also, at home patients may receive extensive support both from health care and from next of kin. Being in an acceptable condition (good shape) and able to manage daily activities independently, were more important to the patients compared to an (too) early discharge. Plus, that many other factors, except recovery, do influence the time point of discharge. We were hesitant to adopt this outcome and spend a lot of time on this	be adapted to intensive care patients (and not to a general population) and such questionnaire should have a distinct differentiation between physical and psychological health. We also discussed if the physical function should also be estimated by objective measures or whether self-rated function is sufficient. The patients stated that psychological well being should be emphasized more than in existing HRQL questionnaires, as it is very important for their recovery.	One patient expressed that cognitive recovery is indicative of returning to the person you were before the illness or injury. It was also questioned whether mental function and cognitive function are equivalent.	though you are physically disabled, but it is impossible if you have detrimental psychological symptoms. An argument to add this was that HRQL is self-reported, and that there are many objective ways of measuring psychological function that might be overlooked.	uncertainties about differences of opinions. We believe it was important to highlight that other outcomes were not less important in clinical practice and these outcomes were related to randomized controlled studies only. Providing concrete examples of what can be evaluated in RCTs also helped to guide the discussion.

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			coma should be a key core outcome variable (or not), and that there is a difference between illness induced coma and medically induced sedation. One patient expressed that he believed that his hallucinations were due to the sedative drugs he received, and that he would never accept being sedated again.	discussion and returned to the question several times. After a lengthy discussion, we agreed that we will adopt the outcome as it might be important to measure this outcome in Sweden where health care resources are sparse. We suggest to clarify if "Days alive out of hospital" includes discharge to rehabilitation centres, and nursing homes or only applies to home.				
Switzerland	<p><u>Patients:</u> very important outcome, however it is also very important what comes after, survival is not the only goal, meaning full living is key</p> <p><u>Relatives:</u> the first step, most important, primary aim and focus during the first phase of treatment. Relatives</p>	<p><u>Nurses:</u> Patients without these support measures are usually not on the ICU anymore</p> <p>Inverse relationship between devices/types of devices and relatives' distress is well proven in the literature</p> <p><u>Physicians:</u></p>	<p><u>Patients:</u> Important outcome Very powerful and bad "dreams", thought to be real, even thereafter for a time it was not clear what was real and what was not</p> <p>Impact on personal well-being huge</p> <p><u>Nurses:</u></p>	<p>Adjustment: " Days alive and return to previous living situation" Importance to go "home" (wherever or whatever this is)</p> <p>"Home is where the heart is" – meaning that it is one of the primary aims of ICU care to</p>	<p>(discussed after survival because of the question when survival is meaningful) <u>Patients:</u> Very important outcome, time points difficult to define as undulating wave. Psychological quality of life more important than physical. Professional post-</p>	<p><u>Physician:</u> More objectively measurable</p> <p>Coping with cognitive dysfunction is very individual and also the level of dysfunction that is acceptable to patients</p> <p><u>Relatives:</u></p>	<p><u>Mobility:</u> should it be assessed separately. <u>Independency/self-efficacy in ADL:</u> Being able to be self-sufficient or be care independent is a key ability/wish for all groups and runs very strongly in Swiss society</p> <p>Difficult to assess and very individual regarding what is</p>	<p>The meeting went very well, and the atmosphere was good and productive. Everybody agreed to be available for further meetings to discuss research matters in the future. One challenge was that to give everybody sufficient "space" to voice opinions the session was a</p>

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	<p>often are not aware what the outcome with survival may entail on the long run (i.e., disability, length of the recovery process etc)</p> <p><u>Physician/nurses:</u> survival primary aim/focus in the first phase, thereafter, question of “meaning full living” becomes more important. When measured is important</p> <p><u>Physiotherapist:</u> survival first, all other considerations come next, potentially a question of when measured (after ICU discharge maybe not, but maybe yes after 1 year)</p> <p>Further discussion: “<i>meaning-full survival</i>” Patients: difficult to define, many aspects go in to this</p> <p>Relatives: entails several aspects, difficulty to support patients, especially with long-term</p>	<p>Indicates the trajectory of recovery and is thus importance</p> <p>Also, an indirect measure of effectiveness of treatment</p> <p><u>Physiotherapist:</u> Shows how sick a patient is</p> <p>May has implications on quality of life and potential for recovery</p> <p><u>Relatives:</u> Important as it signifies a sort of progress “having less devices/medication”. Less dependency. The less invasive the better, thus liberation form organ-support is important</p> <p><u>Patients:</u> All the devices are not memorable. Took little notice of pharmacological support. The only thing that was memorable was the inability to speak and being taken off</p>	<p>Patients often suffer from very powerful and long episodes of hyperactive delirium</p> <p>Strain on nurses/health-care professionals considerable, i.e., hard to watch</p> <p>Needs a lot of resources</p> <p>Most important variable in this core outcome set</p> <p>Important for more targeted resource use (i.e. physiotherapists)</p> <p><u>Relatives:</u> Very difficult to cope with: A) to see relative so in distress B) being in conflict with patients as patients often think that they are not understood by relatives</p> <p>Time to wait until the patient is out of coma is important</p> <p><u>Physiotherapist:</u></p>	<p>enable the patient to return to the pre-ICU living situation</p> <p>It is also important to measure how many days are spent in (health) care institutions (rehabilitation, nursing home, home for the elderly) post ICU stay, not only the hospital</p>	<p>ICU care, would help tremendously, as the “normal” doctors do not understand the diseases and their potential long-term consequences (physically, psychologically) Multi-modal assessment (social, financial, psychological, re-integration) necessary</p> <p><u>Nurses:</u> In combination with survival the most important outcome, if we knew the health-related quality of life resulting of an ICU stay, the discussion about survival would sometime be redundant</p> <p>The question is whether relatives are included in this outcome</p> <p><u>Relatives:</u> Important outcome</p>	<p>Important outcome</p> <p>Difficult to cope with for relatives because “disability” is not visible</p> <p>Level of cognitive dysfunction is evaluated differently by patients and relatives, difficulty to draw a clear line to health-care related quality of life</p> <p>Very subjective as somebody can happy with major cognitive dysfunction, but the relatives may be very distressed by the same level of dysfunction “patient not being him/herself anymore”</p> <p><u>Patients:</u> Especially micro-cognitive deficits and tiredness are very difficult to cope with as often not accepted by society</p>	<p>acceptable and what not</p> <p>Part of the panel feels that this is part of health-care related quality of live, however the panel feels that it should be assessed separately to give the Issue more strength</p> <p>outcome should include financial, working and social aspects of life</p> <p><u>Family outcomes (functioning, resilience, or mental health (wellbeing, psychological distress):</u> More integrative view on outcomes including relatives, care givers and patients (i.e. quality of life, cognitive decline) Take the view of the society in consideration (resource use, costs)</p>	<p>bit longer than anticipated (4 hours) and the patients (both with remaining concentration issues) were very tired at the end.</p>

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	Survival	Number of days alive without life support	Number of days alive without coma or delirium	Number of days alive out of hospital	Health-related quality of life	Cognitive function	Additional	Evaluation/ conclusion
	<p>consequences of critical illness (physical, financial, psychological)</p> <p>Probably summarized in health-care related quality of life</p>	<p>the respirator for suctioning</p>	<p>Very important</p> <p>The earlier the patient is out of coma/delirium the earlier one can start to work with the patients/start rehabilitation</p> <p><u>Physician:</u> Important outcome, because rehabilitative measures can only start after the patient is out of coma/delirium</p> <p>Puts a lot of strain on health-care personnel "mental load"</p> <p>Prolongs the duration of treatment and has detrimental effects if prolonged (cognitive decline, muscular waste etc)</p> <p>Further discussion: Should coma and delirium be separated?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • short discussion 		<p>Emphasis should be on psychological outcomes</p> <p>Include the relatives viewpoint, respectively their quality of life</p> <p><u>Physician:</u> Many different factors</p> <p>Doubtful that current assessment tools are inclusive enough as focused on physical problems, the instruments should include psychological, financial, social and well-being factors</p> <p><u>Physiotherapist:</u> Very important outcome measured factors should be tailored to what is important to patients e.g., driving a car is not assessed in any tool.</p> <p>Remark: New tools are necessary</p>	<p>Very difficult as also very much is dependent on the situation, there are situations (a lot of noise, tiredness) where cognitive function is worse than in other situations, this needs to be incorporated in the measurement of this outcome</p> <p>The "how" it is measured is difficult</p> <p><u>Nurses:</u> Important outcome</p> <p>Subjective and objective aspects of quality of life, not only health related quality of life</p> <p>Important also for regulatory purposes/social security (i.e., to get financial support from the state)</p> <p><u>Physiotherapist:</u> Important outcome</p>		

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	Survival	Number of days alive without life support	Number of days alive without coma or delirium	Number of days alive out of hospital	Health-related quality of life	Cognitive function	Additional	Evaluation/ conclusion
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> both sort of in a continuum <p>panel feels that both put the same strain on all groups and should be evaluated together</p>		<p>Multi-modal assessment (social, financial, psychological, re-integration) necessary</p> <p>Professional post-ICU care necessary for standardization</p> <p>Include the relative's viewpoint or their quality of life</p>	<p>HRQoL is more important than cognitive, there is a lot of common ground, should we only measure the former? However we feel that it should be included in the HRQoL category if new multi-modal assessment tools are developed that include social, financial, psychological, re-integration etc</p>		
UK Cardiff, Wales	<p>Essential outcome – if you are not recording survival how can any of the others be examined – ICM Consultant, Relative, Physiotherapist and SALT.</p> <p>“This is key. Once I was aware of my situation all I was focused on was surviving and getting out of intensive care” – Previous patient.</p> <p>“Survival must be measured or how will you know whether treatments for patients are working” – Current patient.</p>	<p>“I feel this is massively important. The side effects, and the physical and mental impacts that come with needing each machine or treatment are huge and can really affect how you cope each day when you are a patient. This outcome should definitely be looked at and measured because its’ really important to patients” – Current patient.</p> <p>“Each time I had to go back on the ventilator, or needed dialysis again, it was such a blow to me</p>	<p>“I feel this is massively important. The side effects, and the physical and mental impacts that come with needing each machine or treatment are huge and can really affect how you cope each day when you are a patient. This outcome should definitely be looked at and measured because its’ really important to patients” – Current patient.</p>	<p>“ICU Consultants should know if a patient is readmitted back to hospital, even if they don’t need to come back to the ICU, because if the patient survives ICU but they are constantly in and out of hospital and their health is terrible, is it worth it?” – Relative</p> <p>“This is important to measure – if a patient survives ICU but has chronic health problems should this be</p>	<p>Generated the most amount of discussion.</p> <p>Previous and current patients confirmed experience of each of the 6 outcomes described on the slide and felt very strongly that these were vitally important to be measured. All shared experiences along with the two relatives about things that had affected their HRQoL both in and out of the ICU.</p> <p>Putting up the slide that showed</p>	<p>Also generated a lot of discussion. All parties felt that this was a vitally important outcome to measure and that regaining cognitive function as quickly as possible was vital to patients and their relatives wellbeing and quality of life.</p> <p>“The temporary disruption to my cognitive function while in the ICU I can deal with now I’m past it. But had I not been able to recover my cognitive function sufficiently to be</p>		<p>We felt it went very well and had positive feedback from all members of the panel. We were lucky to have a very good panel from a variety of backgrounds but all with experience of Intensive Care. They were all talkative and happy to contribute which generated lots of discussion. The informal setting helped to facilitate this. We can’t think of anything that didn’t work well</p>

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	Survival	Number of days alive without life support	Number of days alive without coma or delirium	Number of days alive out of hospital	Health-related quality of life	Cognitive function	Additional	Evaluation/ conclusion
	<p>"If we can survive the ICU admission, we've at least got a shot at further recovery once we leave the ICU, so initial survival must be recorded, the difficulties afterwards can be captured in other research" – Previous patient.</p> <p>Dates for measuring survival are very important and should be specified in the COS. FICM recommend that 1 year should be the maximum time frame for recording survival – Psychologist, Physiotherapist.</p>	<p>and my family. But each time I came off the ventilator or the dialysis machine I felt like I was doing better and this pushed me on to survive and try my best to get better: - Previous patient.</p> <p>"When he had to go back on the ventilator or kept needing the drugs to keep his blood pressure up, I wanted to know if this meant he was never going to get better. I couldn't get any information on the internet or from asking others and so if this was something that was measured in this COS, I may have been able to find that information out myself – its important information to have and should be measured" – Relative.</p> <p>Very important to measure these parameters because it helps us with treatment plans and predicting trajectory of illness – ICU Consultants,</p>	<p>"Each time I had to go back on the ventilator, or needed dialysis again, it was such a blow to me and my family. But each time I came off the ventilator or the dialysis machine I felt like I was doing better and this pushed me on to survive and try my best to get better: - Previous patient.</p> <p>"When he had to go back on the ventilator or kept needing the drugs to keep his blood pressure up, I wanted to know if this meant he was never going to get better. I couldn't get any information on the internet or from asking others and so if this was something that was measured in this COS, I may have been able to find that information out myself – its important information to have and should</p>	<p>considered a bad outcome and should we be considering the socio-economic burden on the patient, their family and society?" – ICU Consultant</p> <p>The Physiotherapist and the Psychologist felt that the number of days and number of occasions admitted back into hospital should be measured separately.</p>	<p>the 6 outcomes related to the well-being helped direct the discussion.</p> <p>All parties agreed that this was the most important of all the 6 COS they were being asked to discuss.</p> <p>Key statements were "This is the purpose, getting patients a decent quality of life both in and out of the ICU should be the aim everyone is working towards"</p> <p>"It's about a life saved vs a life lived"</p>	<p>able to return to my life before I was admitted to the ICU, I can't say in all honesty that I would have wanted to survive, especially if I had been left with a significant cognitive deficit" – Previous patient.</p> <p>All the healthcare professionals discussed how objectively reporting on cognitive function could provide evidence for providing more resources towards helping regain maximum cognitive function, e.g. preventing delirium, giving treatments that do the least amount of damage to cognitive function, providing more therapy involvement while in ICU from SALT, Physio and OT.</p>		<p>and when we asked some members of the panel if there was anything they thought could have gone better or could be added/improved no suggestions were given, all gave positive feedback from their experience of participating.</p>

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	Survival	Number of days alive without life support	Number of days alive without coma or delirium	Number of days alive out of hospital	Health-related quality of life	Cognitive function	Additional	Evaluation/ conclusion
		Physiotherapist, SALT	be measured" – Relative. Very important to measure these parameters because it helps us with treatment plans and predicting trajectory of illness – ICU Consultants, Physiotherapist, SALT					
UK London, England					Health related quality of life should include "mental well-being"; if it is not included, it should be added as a separate core outcome			Consensus: Quality of life and functional independence after ICU were considered very important; for some patients, this was more important than survival Burden and impact on family after ICU is important but also during ICU stay Not considered to be very important: - duration of mechanical ventilation - duration of pharmacological cardiovascular support -health economics Some panel members were

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	Survival	Number of days alive without life support	Number of days alive without coma or delirium	Number of days alive out of hospital	Health-related quality of life	Cognitive function	Additional	Evaluation/ conclusion
								<p>surprised to see that “mental health” was not included in the top 19 outcomes</p> <p>Primary Core Outcome set Consensus: agreement with key outcomes Quality of life very important Quality of life more important than days alive without organ support Some panel members felt that “mental well-being” should be included if possible</p> <p>Overall conclusion: Adoption of all core outcomes apart from “days alive without organ support” (patients felt that they were asleep when they were on mechanical ventilation and therefore not aware of the exact duration of organ support)</p>

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Table S6. Distribution of stakeholders registered for the Delphi survey

Stakeholders	Registered for the survey	Respondents round 1 ^b	Respondents round 2 ^{b,c}	Respondents round 3 ^{b,c}
	264	249 (94%)	202 (81%)	203 (82%)
Patients	65	61	43	48
Family members	49	46	35	34
Clinicians	136	129	110	107
Researchers^a	14	13	14	14

^a Researchers conducting research in the ICU setting or in adjacent populations of critically ill patients.

^b Respondents completing the survey.

^c For round 2 there were 208 respondents, but 6 without completing the survey, and for round 3 there were 207 respondents, and 4 not completing the survey. Due to less than 20% attrition between round 1 and 2, as well as round 1 and 3 we present the complete cases with last observation carried forward as planned [1].

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Table S7. Outcomes derived from the semi-structured interviews

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• How important is it to record new diagnoses after ICU admission?• How important is it to measure hope?• How important is it to record balance as an ability?• How important is it to avoid infections?• Time until returning home• Number of inter- and intra-hospital transfers• How important is it to quickly remove invasive tubes and lines?• Resource utilization for personnel providing intervention/treatment?• Withdrawal of therapy

Table S8. The 50 outcomes in the survey including help-text

These are the questions raised for the 50 outcomes including the help text for the 3rd round.

	OUTCOME	HELP TEXT
1	How important is it to record ICU survival?	Your response is only regarding ICU survival - not life after ICU or long-term survival.
2	How important is it to record the ICU length of stay?	Your response is only regarding the importance of recording number of days in ICU.
3	How important is it to record the hospital length of stay?	Your response is only regarding the importance of recording the number of days in hospital.
4	How important is it to record the ICU readmission rate during a hospital stay?	Your response is only regarding the importance of recording ICU readmission - not the reason why.
5	How important is it to record hospital readmission?	Your response is only regarding the importance of recording hospital readmission - not the reason why.
6	How important is it to record patients' overall well-being?	Well-being is a combination of feeling good and functioning well, including the feeling of safety, harmony, joy, and satisfaction, as well as having positive, meaningful social relationships.
7	How important is it to measure the health economic consequences of a particular treatment in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording how society gets the best value for the money.
8	How important is it to measure the environmental consequences of a particular treatment in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording the environmental consequences of a treatment, e.g., in the form of the CO2 footprint.
9	How important is it to measure whether blood values are within normal limits while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording whether blood tests taken in ICU are in the expected range.
10	How important is it to record whether vital signs are within normal limits while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording whether e.g., heart rate, blood pressure, temperature, respiratory rate, and oxygen saturation are within normal limits while in ICU.

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11	How important is it to record the duration of mechanical ventilation while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording how long a patient needs artificial respiratory assistance while in ICU.
12	How important is it to record the duration of pharmacologic circulatory support while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording how long a patient needs pharmacologic circulatory support while in ICU.
13	How important is it to record the duration of dialysis while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording how long a patient needs to have artificial blood cleansing by dialysis due to kidney failure while in ICU.
14	How important is it to record the duration of sedation while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording how long a patient needs to be sedated while in ICU.
15	How important is it to record the duration of delirium while in ICU?	Delirium is an acute confusional state characterized by inattention, incoherent thinking, and speech, and altered level of consciousness - many experience not being themselves and that events are not real (hallucinations).
16	How important is it to record whether patients experience nausea and vomiting while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording whether a patient experiences nausea and vomiting while in ICU.
17	How important is it to record whether patients experience thirst while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient experiences thirst while in ICU.
18	How important is it to record whether patients are short of breath while in ICU.	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient experiences shortness of breath while in ICU.
19	How important is it to record whether patients experience pain while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient is pain free while in ICU.
20	How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient experiences fear or anxiety while in ICU.
21	How important is it to record patients' sleep while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient gets any sleep while in ICU.
22	How important is it to record patients' ability to communicate while in ICU?	Please consider the importance of whether the patient is able to exchange information or express meaning by verbal/nonverbal communication or augmentative and alternative communication devices while in ICU.

23	How important is it to record patients' discharge location after hospitalization?	Please consider the importance of recording the discharge location, e.g., home, care home, rehabilitation, or other.
24	How important is it to record patients' outpatient or general practitioner visits following hospitalization?	Please consider the importance of recording the number of follow-up visits conducted as a consequence of undesired effects of intensive care and hospitalization.
25	How important is it to record whether new medications are prescribed for the patient after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient needs to take new medications as a consequence of the ICU stay?
26	How important is it to record patients' health-related quality of life after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording the patient's self-reported life situation from the perspective of goals, expectations, and worries, including affluence, environment, and physical and psychological health.
27	How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset tiredness or fatigue, unrelieved by sleep or rest, after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of whether the patient experiences tiredness, weakness, or lack of energy, unrelieved by sleep, after ICU discharge?
28	How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset pain after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording the patient's pain after ICU discharge.
29	How important is it to record whether patients resume their usual roles in daily life after ICU discharge?	The usual role in daily life is the individual's function, characteristics or behavior in different situations, e.g., in private life, work life, or leisure time, as before the ICU stay.
30	How important is it to record family caregivers' experienced quality of life after the ICU stay?	Please consider the importance of recording the family caregiver's view of own life situation viewed in relation to the individual's goals, expectations and worries, including affluence, environment, and physical, psychological and mental health.
31	How important is it to record patients' financial capabilities after, compared to before, the ICU stay?	Please consider the importance of the patient's financial independence after ICU discharge, e.g., by return to work, right to sick leave, or early retirement, or by not needing to take a loan to maintain the standard of living.
32	How important is it to record whether patients after ICU discharge, compared to before, have the same labor market attachment.	Please consider the importance of recording the patient's labor market attachment after ICU discharge, if the patient was attached to the labor market before.

33	How important is it to record patients' physical impediments such as scars, wounds, or ostomy after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether patients have impediments such as scars, or poor wound healing after e.g., pressure sores, "throat tubes" (tracheotomy), or ostomy on the stomach, etc.
34	How important is it to record whether patients independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording the patient's ability to independently perform activities of daily living, such as personal care, shopping, cooking, driving and other daily chores.
35	How important is it to record whether patients are independently able to get dressed after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient is independently able to dress after ICU discharge.
36	How important is it to record whether patients are mobile after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether a patient is independently able to move about after ICU discharge, e.g., get out, drive, bicycle, shop, go for a walk or take the stairs.
37	How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset shortness of breath after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient experiences being breathless or short of breath after ICU discharge.
38	How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset trouble speaking after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient experiences e.g., hoarseness, voice fatigue, sore throat, lump in the throat, need to clear the throat, loss of voice, or continuous cough related to the ICU stay.
39	How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset difficulty swallowing after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether a patient to a greater or lesser extent has difficulty chewing and swallowing after ICU discharge. Some avoid coarse rye bread and red meat, while others require minced food and thick liquids.
40	How important is it to record patients' bowel function after ICU discharge?	Bowel function is the patient's ability to maintain normal digestion after ICU discharge and ability to eat normally without nausea and vomiting and have usual stool frequency.
41	How important is it to record patients' urinary function after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient has normal bladder control without the need for urinary aids and without involuntary urination.
42	How important is it to record the patient's sexual function after ICU discharge?	Sexual function is the ability to receive and give sexual pleasure.

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43	How important is it to record patients' senses: vision, hearing, touch, smell, and taste after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording the patient's ability to see, hear, touch, smell and taste.
44	How important is it to record whether patients have the physical strength to perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient has the strength to perform basic physical needs such as eating, drinking, using the toilet or holding a telephone after ICU discharge.
45	How important is it to record patients' mental function (cognitive function) after ICU discharge?	Mental function includes concentration, attention, memory, problem solving, learning, sense of direction or spatial orientation.
46	How important is it to record whether patients experience loneliness after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether the patient feels involuntarily alone (isolated or abandoned) after ICU discharge.
47	How important is it to record whether patients are diagnosed with posttraumatic stress syndrome (PTSD) after ICU discharge?	PTSD is a diagnosis describing a stress response to a traumatic event where the individual experiences flashbacks and tries to avoid things or situations that are a reminder of the event. Many survivors experience irritability and have trouble sleeping, concentrating, or remembering.
48	How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether a patient experiences anxiety preventing the performance of normal daily activities.
49	How important is it to record whether patients experience depression after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether a patient is less happy, lacks joy of life, is more tired than usual, or feels that life is unmanageable.
50	How important is it to record whether patients experience nightmares after ICU discharge?	Please consider the importance of recording whether a patient experiences unpleasant, scary or anxiety provoking dreams.

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Figure S1-S50. Graphs for the first survey round

Figure S1: How important is survival?

How important is survival? (n = 251)

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Figure S2: How important is the ICU length of stay?

How important is the ICU length of stay? (n = 259)

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Figure S3: How important is the hospital length of stay?

How important is the hospital length of stay? (n = 259)

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Figure S4: How important is it whether one is readmitted to ICU?

How important is it whether one is readmitted to ICU? (n = 242)

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Figure S5: How important is it whether one is readmitted to the hospital?

How important is it whether one is readmitted to the hospital? (n = 247)

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Figure S6: How important is it to have an overall sense of well-being?

How important is it to have an overall sense of well-being? (n = 261)

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Figure S7: How important is a health economic measurement of the specific treatment in relation to the outcome?

How important is a health economic measurement of the specific treatment in relation to the outcome? (n = 247)

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Figure S8: How important is the environmental consequences of a particular treatment in ICU?

How important is the environmental consequences of a particular treatment in ICU? (n = 250)

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Figure S9: How important is it for blood test values to be within the normal limits during the ICU stay?

How important is it for blood test values to be within the normal limits during the ICU stay? (n = 232)

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Figure S10: How important is it for vital signs measurements to be within the normal range during the ICU stay?

How important is it for vital signs measurements to be within the normal range during the ICU stay? (n = 234)

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Figure S11: How important is the time spent on a mechanical ventilator during the ICU stay?

How important is the time spent on a mechanical ventilator during the ICU stay? (n = 235)

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Figure S12: How important is the length of time one receives pharmacologic circulatory support during the ICU stay?

How important is the length of time one receives pharmacologic circulatory support during the ICU stay? (n = 222)

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Figure S13: How important is the length of time one receives dialysis during the ICU stay?

How important is the length of time one receives dialysis during the ICU stay? (n = 205)

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Figure S14: How important is the length of time one is in an artificial coma during the ICU stay?

How important is the length of time one is in an artificial coma during the ICU stay? (n = 226)

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Figure S15: How important is it to spend the shortest possible time in delirium during the ICU stay?

How important is it to spend the shortest possible time in delirium during the ICU stay? (n = 234)

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Figure S16: How important is the absence of nausea and vomiting during the ICU stay?

How important is the absence of nausea and vomiting during the ICU stay? (n = 244)

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Figure S17: How important is the absence of thirst during the ICU stay?

How important is the absence of thirst during the ICU stay? (n = 246)

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Figure S18: How important is the absence of shortness of breath during the ICU stay?

How important is the absence of shortness of breath during the ICU stay? (n = 241)

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Figure S19: How important is the absence of pain during the ICU stay?

How important is the absence of pain during the ICU stay? (n = 246)

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Figure S20: How important is the absence of anxiety during the ICU stay?

How important is the absence of anxiety during the ICU stay? (n = 248)

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Figure S21: How important is sleep and maintaining circadian rhythm during the ICU stay?

How important is sleep and maintaining circadian rhythm during the ICU stay? (n = 247)

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Figure S22: How important is it to be able to communicate during the ICU stay?

How important is it to be able to communicate during the ICU stay? (n = 249)

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Figure S23: How important is the place one is discharged to after the ICU stay?

How important is the place one is discharged to after the ICU stay? (n = 250)

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Figure S24: How important is the number of outpatient appointments or general practitioner visits in the follow-up after ICU discharge?

How important is the number of outpatient appointments or general practitioner visits in the follow-up after ICU discharge? (n = 244)

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Figure S25: How important is it to avoid needing new medication after ICU discharge?

How important is it to avoid needing new medication after ICU discharge? (n = 240)

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Figure S26: How important is health-related quality of life after ICU discharge?

How important is health-related quality of life after ICU discharge? (n = 250)

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Figure S27: How important is it to not experience fatigue that cannot be slept away after ICU discharge?

How important is it to not experience fatigue that cannot be slept away after ICU discharge? (n = 249)

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Figure S28: How important is it to not have pain after ICU discharge?

How important is it to not have pain after ICU discharge? (n = 250)

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Figure S29: How important is it to resume one's usual role in daily life after ICU discharge?

How important is it to resume one's usual role in daily life after ICU discharge? (n = 250)

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Figure S30: How important is family caregivers' experienced quality of life after ICU discharge?

How important is family caregivers' experienced quality of life after ICU discharge? (n = 248)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S31: How important is it to be financially independent after ICU discharge?

How important is it to be financially independent after ICU discharge? (n = 243)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S32: How important is it to return to work after ICU discharge?

How important is it to return to work after ICU discharge? (n = 243)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S33: How important is it to avoid physical impediment after ICU discharge?

How important is it to avoid physical impediment after ICU discharge? (n = 254)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S34: How important is it to be able to perform activities of daily living independently after ICU discharge?

How important is it to be able to perform activities of daily living independently after ICU discharge? (n = 250)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S35: How important is it to be able to dress oneself after ICU discharge?

How important is it to be able to dress oneself after ICU discharge? (n = 251)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S36: How important is it to be mobile after ICU discharge?

How important is it to be mobile after ICU discharge? (n = 250)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S37: How important is it to be free from shortness of breath after ICU discharge?

How important is it to be free from shortness of breath after ICU discharge? (n = 249)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S38: How important is it to be free from voice problems after ICU discharge?

How important is it to be free from voice problems after ICU discharge? (n = 248)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S39: How important is it to be free from swallowing difficulties after ICU discharge?

How important is it to be free from swallowing difficulties after ICU discharge? (n = 250)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S40: How important is it to maintain bowel function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to maintain bowel function after ICU discharge? (n = 253)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S41: How important is it to maintain urinary function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to maintain urinary function after ICU discharge? (n = 249)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S42: How important is it to have intact sexual function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to have intact sexual function after ICU discharge? (n = 244)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S43: How important is it to have preserved senses after ICU discharge?

How important is it to have preserved senses after ICU discharge? (n = 253)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S44: How important is it to have physical strength to perform activities, of daily living after discharge from the hospital?

How important is it to have physical strength to perform activities of daily living after discharge from the hospital? (n = 251)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S45: How important is it to maintain mental function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to maintain mental function after ICU discharge? (n = 254)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S46: How important is it to record whether patients experience loneliness after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience loneliness after ICU discharge? (n = 252)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S47: How important is it to record whether patients experience a post-traumatic stress reaction after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience a post-traumatic stress reaction after ICU discharge? (n = 251)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S48: How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety after ICU discharge? (n = 253)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S49: How important is it to record whether patients experience depression after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience depression after ICU discharge? (n = 253)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S50: How important is it to record whether patients experience nightmares after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience nightmares after ICU discharge? (n = 252)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S51-S100. Graphs for the second survey round

Figure S51: How important is it to record ICU survival?

How important is it to record ICU survival? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S52: How important is it to record the ICU length of stay?

How important is it to record the ICU length of stay? (n = 262)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S53: How important is it to record the hospital length of stay?

How important is it to record the hospital length of stay? (n = 262)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S54: How important is it to record the ICU readmission rate during a hospital stay?

How important is it to record the ICU readmission rate during a hospital stay? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S55: How important is it to record hospital readmission?

How important is it to record hospital readmission? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S56: How important is it to record patients' overall well-being?

How important is it to record patients' overall well-being? (n = 264)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S57: How important is it to measure the health economic consequences of a particular treatment in ICU?

How important is it to measure the health economic consequences of a particular treatment in ICU? (n = 255)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S58: How important is it to measure the environmental consequences of a particular treatment in ICU?

How important is it to measure the environmental consequences of a particular treatment in ICU? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S59: How important is it to measure whether blood values are within normal limits while in ICU?

How important is it to measure whether blood values are within normal limits while in ICU? (n = 243)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S60: How important is it to record whether vital signs are within normal limits while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether vital signs are within normal limits while in ICU? (n = 247)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S61: How important is it to record the duration of mechanical ventilation while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of mechanical ventilation while in ICU? (n = 246)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S62: How important is it to record the duration of pharmacologic circulatory support while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of pharmacologic circulatory support while in ICU? (n = 235)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S63: How important is it to record the duration of dialysis while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of dialysis while in ICU? (n = 219)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S64: How important is it to record the duration of sedation while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of sedation while in ICU? (n = 242)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S65: How important is it to record the duration of delirium while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of delirium while in ICU? (n = 245)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S66: How important is it to record whether patients experience nausea and vomiting while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether patients experience nausea and vomiting while in ICU? (n = 251)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S67: How important is it to record whether patients experience thirst while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether patients experience thirst while in ICU? (n = 251)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S68: How important is it to record whether patients are short of breath while in ICU.

How important is it to record whether patients are short of breath while in ICU. (n = 248)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S69: How important is it to record whether patients experience pain while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether patients experience pain while in ICU? (n = 253)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S70: How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety while in ICU? (n = 254)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S71: How important is it to record patients' sleep while in ICU?

How important is it to record patients' sleep while in ICU? (n = 254)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S72: How important is it to record patients' ability to communicate while in ICU?

How important is it to record patients' ability to communicate while in ICU? (n = 255)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S73: How important is it to record patients' discharge location after hospitalization?

How important is it to record patients' discharge location after hospitalization? (n = 255)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S74: How important is it to record patients' out-patient or general practitioner visits related to the long-term effects of intensive care?

How important is it to record patients' out-patient or general practitioner visits related to the long-term effects of intensive care? (n = 254)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S75: How important is it to record whether new medications are prescribed for the patient after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether new medications are prescribed for the patient after ICU discharge? (n = 253)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S76: How important is it to record patients' health-related quality of life after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' health-related quality of life after ICU discharge? (n = 255)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S77: How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset tiredness or fatigue, unrelieved by sleep or rest, after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset tiredness or fatigue, unrelieved by sleep or rest, after ICU discharge? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S78: How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset pain after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset pain after ICU discharge? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S79: How important is it to record whether patients resume their usual roles in daily life after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients resume their usual roles in daily life after ICU discharge? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S80: How important is it to record family caregivers' experienced quality of life after the ICU stay?

How important is it to record family caregivers' experienced quality of life after the ICU stay? (n = 255)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S81: How important is it to record patients' financial capabilities after, compared to before, the ICU stay?

How important is it to record patients' financial capabilities after, compared to before, the ICU stay? (n = 252)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S82: How important is it to record whether patients after ICU discharge, compared to before, have the same labor market attachment.

How important is it to record whether patients after ICU discharge, compared to before, have the same labour market attachment. (n = 253)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S83: How important is it to record patients' physical impediments such as scars, wounds, or ostomy after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' physical impediments such as scars, wounds, or ostomy after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S84: How important is it to record whether patients independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge? (n = 257)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S85: How important is it to record whether patients are independently able to get dressed after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients are independently able to get dressed after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S86: How important is it to record whether patients are mobile after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients are mobile after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S87: How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset shortness of breath after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset shortness of breath after ICU discharge? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S88: How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset trouble speaking after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset trouble speaking after ICU discharge? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S89: How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset difficulty swallowing after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset difficulty swallowing after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S90: How important is it to record patients' bowel function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' bowel function after ICU discharge? (n = 257)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S91: How important is it to record patients' urinary function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' urinary function after ICU discharge? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S92: How important is it to record the patient's sexual function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record the patient's sexual function after ICU discharge? (n = 252)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S93: How important is it to record patients' senses: vision, hearing, touch, smell, and taste after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' senses: vision, hearing, touch, smell, and taste after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S94: How important is it to record whether patients have the physical strength to perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients have the physical strength to perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S95: How important is it to record patients' mental function (cognitive function) after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' mental function (cognitive function) after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S96: How important is it to record whether patients experience loneliness after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience loneliness after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S97: How important is it to record whether patients are diagnosed with posttraumatic stress syndrome (PTSD) after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients are diagnosed with posttraumatic stress syndrome (PTSD) after ICU discharge? (n = 257)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S98: How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S99: How important is it to record whether patients experience depression after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience depression after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S100: How important is it to record whether patients experience nightmares after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience nightmares after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S101-150. Graphs for the third survey round

Figure S101: How important is it to record ICU survival?

How important is it to record ICU survival? (n = 261)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S102: How important is it to record the ICU length of stay?

How important is it to record the ICU length of stay? (n = 263)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S103: How important is it to record the hospital length of stay?

How important is it to record the hospital length of stay? (n = 263)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S104: How important is it to record the ICU readmission rate during a hospital stay?

How important is it to record the ICU readmission rate during a hospital stay? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S105: How important is it to record hospital readmission?

How important is it to record hospital readmission? (n = 260)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S106: How important is it to record patients' overall well-being?

How important is it to record patients' overall well-being? (n = 265)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S107: How important is it to measure the health economic consequences of a particular treatment in ICU?

How important is it to measure the health economic consequences of a particular treatment in ICU? (n = 260)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S108: How important is it to measure the environmental consequences of a particular treatment in ICU?

How important is it to measure the environmental consequences of a particular treatment in ICU? (n = 262)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S109: How important is it to measure whether blood values are within normal limits while in ICU?

How important is it to measure whether blood values are within normal limits while in ICU? (n = 247)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S110: How important is it to record whether vital signs are within normal limits while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether vital signs are within normal limits while in ICU? (n = 251)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S111: How important is it to record the duration of mechanical ventilation while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of mechanical ventilation while in ICU? (n = 255)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S112: How important is it to record the duration of pharmacologic circulatory support while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of pharmacologic circulatory support while in ICU? (n = 243)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S113: How important is it to record the duration of dialysis while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of dialysis while in ICU? (n = 228)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S114: How important is it to record the duration of sedation while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of sedation while in ICU? (n = 250)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S115: How important is it to record the duration of delirium while in ICU?

How important is it to record the duration of delirium while in ICU? (n = 252)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S116: How important is it to record whether patients experience nausea and vomiting while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether patients experience nausea and vomiting while in ICU? (n = 255)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S117: How important is it to record whether patients experience thirst while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether patients experience thirst while in ICU? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S118: How important is it to record whether patients are short of breath while in ICU.

How important is it to record whether patients are short of breath while in ICU. (n = 254)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S119: How important is it to record whether patients experience pain while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether patients experience pain while in ICU? (n = 257)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S120: How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety while in ICU?

How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety while in ICU? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S121: How important is it to record patients' sleep while in ICU?

How important is it to record patients' sleep while in ICU? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S122: How important is it to record patients' ability to communicate while in ICU?

How important is it to record patients' ability to communicate while in ICU? (n = 257)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S123: How important is it to record patients' discharge location after hospitalization?

How important is it to record patients' discharge location after hospitalization? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S124: How important is it to record patients' outpatient or general practitioner visits following hospitalization?

How important is it to record patients' outpatient or general practitioner visits following hospitalization? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S125: How important is it to record whether new medications are prescribed for the patient after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether new medications are prescribed for the patient after ICU discharge? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S126: How important is it to record patients' health-related quality of life after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' health-related quality of life after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S127: How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset tiredness or fatigue, unrelieved by sleep or rest, after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset tiredness or fatigue, unrelieved by sleep or rest, after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S128: How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset pain after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset pain after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S129: How important is it to record whether patients resume their usual roles in daily life after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients resume their usual roles in daily life after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S130: How important is it to record family caregivers' experienced quality of life after the ICU stay?

How important is it to record family caregivers' experienced quality of life after the ICU stay? (n = 257)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S131: How important is it to record patients' financial capabilities after, compared to before, the ICU stay?

How important is it to record patients' financial capabilities after, compared to before, the ICU stay? (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S132: How important is it to record whether patients after ICU discharge, compared to before, have the same labor market attachment.

How important is it to record whether patients after ICU discharge, compared to before, have the same labour market attachment. (n = 256)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S133: How important is it to record patients' physical impediments such as scars, wounds, or ostomy after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' physical impediments such as scars, wounds, or ostomy after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S134: How important is it to record whether patients independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S135: How important is it to record whether patients are independently able to get dressed after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients are independently able to get dressed after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S136: How important is it to record whether patients are mobile after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients are mobile after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S137: How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset shortness of breath after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience newly onset shortness of breath after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S138: How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset trouble speaking after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset trouble speaking after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S139: How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset difficulty swallowing after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients have newly onset difficulty swallowing after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S140: How important is it to record patients' bowel function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' bowel function after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S141: How important is it to record patients' urinary function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' urinary function after ICU discharge? (n = 258)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S142: How important is it to record the patient's sexual function after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record the patient's sexual function after ICU discharge? (n = 255)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S143: How important is it to record patients' senses: vision, hearing, touch, smell, and taste after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' senses: vision, hearing, touch, smell, and taste after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S144: How important is it to record whether patients have the physical strength to perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients have the physical strength to perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S145: How important is it to record patients' mental function (cognitive function) after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record patients' mental function (cognitive function) after ICU discharge? (n = 261)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S146: How important is it to record whether patients experience loneliness after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience loneliness after ICU discharge? (n = 260)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S147: How important is it to record whether patients are diagnosed with posttraumatic stress syndrome (PTSD) after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients are diagnosed with posttraumatic stress syndrome (PTSD) after ICU discharge? (n = 259)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S148: How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience anxiety after ICU discharge? (n = 260)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S149: How important is it to record whether patients experience depression after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience depression after ICU discharge? (n = 260)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S150: How important is it to record whether patients experience nightmares after ICU discharge?

How important is it to record whether patients experience nightmares after ICU discharge? (n = 260)

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S151. Heatmap showing the three Delphi survey round responses for all stakeholders

All participants rated the 50 outcomes (“Question”) on a Likert scale from 1-9, where 1-3 is ‘not important’, 4-6 ‘important, but not critical’, and 7-9 ‘critical’ to include this outcome. This was rated for each survey round nr 1, 2, and 3. Greener represents more important and more orange less important.

A core outcome set for adult general ICU patients

Figure S152. Heatmap showing the three Delphi survey round responses by stakeholder groups

All participants rated the 50 outcomes ("Question") on a Likert scale from 1-9, where 1-3 is 'not important', 4-6 'important, but not critical', and 7-9 'critical' to include this outcome. This was rated for each survey round nr 1, 2, and 3. Greener represents more important and more orange less important.

Table S9. Outcomes related to health-related quality of life

Outcomes	Number of panels (out of 4) who agreed on the importance of each outcome
Record patients' outpatient or general practitioner visits related to the long-term effects of intensive care	2
New onset tiredness or fatigue, unrelieved by sleep or rest, after ICU discharge	4
New onset pain after ICU discharge	4
Resume their usual roles in daily life after ICU discharge	3
Record whether patients after ICU discharge, compared to before, have the same labor market attachment	2
Independently perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge	1
Independently able to get dressed after ICU discharge	1
Mobile after ICU discharge	1
New onset speaking troubles after ICU discharge	2
New onset swallowing difficulties 'after ICU discharge	1
Bowel function after ICU discharge	3
Urinary function after ICU discharge	1
Sexual function after ICU discharge	1
Senses: vision, hearing, touch, smell, and taste after ICU discharge	3
Physical strength to perform activities of daily living after ICU discharge	1
Loneliness after ICU discharge	2
Anxiety after ICU discharge	2
Depression after ICU discharge	2

The colours refer to the number of panels who have agreed on the importance of each outcome. Dark green is 4/4 panels, light green 3/4 panels, yellow 2/4 panels, and orange 1/4 panel.

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Table S10. Results from the international validation meetings across the participating countries

Country	Initial outcomes ^a						Additional outcomes ^a
	Survival	Days alive without life support	Days alive without coma or delirium	Days alive out of hospital	HRQoL	Cognitive function	
Australia ^b General ICU patient	Adopt	Adapt	Adapt	Adapt	Adopt	Reject	Physical function, ability to return occupation/school, Contribution to society, supporting network
Australia ^b Sepsis survivors	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt	Adapt	Adopt	Adapt	
Czech Republic	Adopt	Adapt	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt	Adopt	
Denmark (Copenhagen) ^c	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Wellbeing
Denmark (Køge) ^d	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Wellbeing
Denmark (Kolding) ^e	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Wellbeing
Denmark (Aalborg) ^f	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Wellbeing
Finland (Helsinki)	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	No additional outcomes
Finland (Tampere)	Adopt	Adopt	Reject	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Wellbeing should be added.
Iceland	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Readmission
India (Chennai) ^e	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Financial consequences
India (Mumbai)	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Reject	Adopt	Adopt	
Italy	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Wellbeing of patients and families
Lithuania	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt	Impact of intervention,
Norway	Adopt	Adopt	Reject	Reject	Adopt	Adopt	Physical function and mental health
Netherlands	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	No additional outcomes
Poland	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt	Adapt	No additional outcomes
Sweden	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Physical function and psychological function
Switzerland	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt	Adopt	Adopt	Mobility, Independency (self-efficacy in ADL), family outcomes
United Kingdom (Cardiff)	Adopt	Adopt	Adapt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	No additional outcomes
United Kingdom (London)	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Adopt	Mental well-being
Total adopted	21 (100%)	19 (90%)	15 (71%)	16 (76%)	19 (90%)	17 (81%)	
Total adapted	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	4 (19%)	3 (14%)	2 (10%)	3 (14%)	
Total rejected	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	1 (5%)	

HRQoL: Health-related quality of life, ADL: activities of daily living

Green/Adopt=adopting the outcome, yellow/Adapt=adapting the outcome, and red/Reject=rejecting the outcome.

Number (percentages).

^a Detailed minutes in Table S10.

^b Number of participants from different areas of Australia: 1 Aboriginal participants, 11 Western Australia, 5 New South Wales, 4 Victoria, 3 Queensland, and 1 Northern Territory.

^c The Capitol Region of Denmark

^d Region Zealand

^e The Region of Southern Denmark

^f The North Denmark Region

^e Indian areas represented: Chennai, Bangalore, Vellore, Pune, and New Delhi

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Comments to the adjusted core outcomes

Australia: full summary in the end of this section.

Czech Republic: would like to add ‘non-vegetative state’ to survival as the panel considered that worse than death (may not reflect everyone feelings in the Czech Republic). ‘Free of life support’ was not considered important for patients if comfort, communication, and no dyspnea feelings were present, why they want to adapt the outcome to ‘free of life support and not dyspneic’. With HRQoL the physical component is not as important to patients and families if they can accept, adapt to a condition, that make sense of it or hope for improvement.

Lithuania: changed two outcomes from adapt to adopt after the core outcome set has been revised. Regarding ‘free of delirium’ the main challenge with the previous outcome was the definition of coma. No major concerns raised regarding identification of delirium. It is a different outcome from one intended in the initial core outcome set, but it is a very important outcome. Regarding ‘cognitive function’ they were unanimous to its importance, but concerns raised regarding the methodology and tools used for this outcome.

Netherlands: after discussing the changes in the core outcome set their research panel agrees with the new set, which covers the most important outcomes.

Norway: the majority are against ‘free of delirium’ due to it is impractical and that it is unfortunate omitting specific and separate domains for physical and mental outcomes.

Sweden: the only outcome we are hesitant about is ‘out of hospital’. It is financially and clinically important, but perhaps not so important from a patient perspective. However, this might perhaps be addressed in the next step of development

Switzerland: finds ‘out of hospital’ okay, however they favor what have been suggested at the consensus meeting; ‘returning to pre-ICU condition’.

Australian full summary ‘20240118’ for the general ICU patients and sepsis survivors:

A. Initial outcomes of the two Australian consumer group meetings

	Initial core outcomes						Additional outcomes
	Survival	Days alive without life support	Days alive without coma or delirium	Days alive and out of hospital	Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL)	Cognitive function	
General ICU patient/Fiona Stanley	Ok	Adapt	Adapt	Adapt	Ok	Reject	Physical function, ability to return occupation/school,
Sepsis survivors/TGI	Ok	Ok	Adapt	Adapt	Ok	Adapt	Contribution to society, supporting network

B. Changes proposed by Danish Group based on international feedback

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1. SURVIVAL: No change.
2. DAYS ALIVE WITHOUT LIFE SUPPORT: Changed to FREE OF LIFE SUPPORT. Specifics of how to define to be determined.
3. DAYS ALIVE WITHOUT COMA OR DELIRIUM. Changed to FREE OF DELIRIUM. Removal of coma.
4. DAYS ALIVE AND OUT OF HOSPITAL: Changed to OUT OF HOSPITAL.
5. HRQOL: No change.
6. Cognitive function: No change.
7. Additional outcomes: No change (none added).

C. Proposed final Australian feedback

	Proposed final core outcomes						Nil Additional outcomes
	Survival	Free of life support	Free of delirium	Out of hospital	HRQoL	Cognitive function	
General ICU patient/Fiona Stanley	Ok	OK	OK	Adapt	Ok	Adapt	Adapt
Sepsis survivors/TGI	Ok	Ok	OK	Adapt	Ok	Adapt	

1. SURVIVAL, FREE OF LIFE SUPPORT, FREE OF DELIRIUM and HEALTH RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE: Accept.
2. OUT OF HOSPITAL: Suggest adapt core outcome to include a caveat about return to home and/or previous level of function.
3. COGNITIVE FUNCTION: Suggest adapt core outcome. Add caveat that the impact of cognition on function should be considered in any measure of HEALTH RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE and that cognitive function should not be measured as a stand alone core outcome.
4. ADDITIONAL OUTCOMES: Suggest add to Australian core outcomes that physical, cognitive, psychological and social function should be considered in any measure of HEALTH RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE

Table S11. Core Outcome Set-Standards for Reporting: The COS-STAR Statement Checklist

SECTION/TOPIC	ITEM No.	CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE NUMBER
TITLE/ABSTRACT			
Title	1a	Identify in the title that the paper reports the development of a COS	1
Abstract	1b	Provide a structured summary	5
INTRODUCTION			
Background and Objectives	2a	Describe the background and explain the rationale for developing the COS.	6
	2b	Describe the specific objectives with reference to developing a COS.	6
Scope	3a	Describe the health condition(s) and population(s) covered by the COS.	6
	3b	Describe the intervention(s) covered by the COS.	6
	3c	Describe the setting(s) in which the COS is to be applied.	6
METHODS			
Protocol/Registry Entry	4	Indicate where the COS development protocol can be accessed, if available, and/or the study registration details.	7
Participants	5	Describe the rationale for stakeholder groups involved in the COS development process, eligibility criteria for participants from each group, and a description of how the individuals involved were identified.	7-8 and SDC
Information Sources	6a	Describe the information sources used to identify an initial list of outcomes.	8 and SDC
	6b	Describe how outcomes were dropped/combined, with reasons (if applicable).	8 and SDC
Consensus Process	7	Describe how the consensus process was undertaken.	8-9
Outcome Scoring	8	Describe how outcomes were scored and how scores were summarised.	8 and SDC
Consensus Definition	9a	Describe the consensus definition.	8
	9b	Describe the procedure for determining how outcomes were included or excluded from consideration during the consensus process.	8 and SDC
Ethics and Consent	10	Provide a statement regarding the ethics and consent issues for the study.	10 and SDC
RESULTS			
Protocol Deviations	11	Describe any changes from the protocol (if applicable), with reasons, and describe what impact these changes have on the results.	11

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Participants	12	Present data on the number and relevant characteristics of the people involved at all stages of COS development.	11 and Table 1
Outcomes	13a	List all outcomes considered at the start of the consensus process.	Figure 1 and SDC
	13b	Describe any new outcomes introduced and any outcomes dropped, with reasons, during the consensus process.	11
COS	14	List the outcomes in the final COS.	12-13 and Figure 3
DISCUSSION			
Limitations	15	Discuss any limitations in the COS development process.	14-15
Conclusions	16	Provide an interpretation of the final COS in the context of other evidence, and implications for future research.	15
OTHER INFORMATION			
Funding	17	Describe sources of funding/role of funders.	18
Conflicts of Interest	18	Describe any conflicts of interest within the study team and how these were managed.	18

COS: core outcome set

From: Kirkham JJ, Gorst S, Altman DG, Blazeby JM, Clarke M, Devane D, et al. (2016) Core Outcome Set–STAndards for Reporting: The COS-STAR Statement. *PLoS Med* 13(10): e1002148. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002148> [10].

Table S12 Guidance for Reporting Involvement of Patients and the Public short form: The GRIPP2-SF checklist

Section and topic	Item	Reported on page No
1: Aim	Report the aim of PPI in the study	6
2: Methods	Provide a clear description of the methods used for PPI in the study	7 and Figure 1
3: Study results	Outcomes—Report the results of PPI in the study, including both positive and negative outcomes	SDC 23-32, 33
4: Discussion and conclusions	Outcomes—Comment on the extent to which PPI influenced the study overall. Describe positive and negative effects	Figure 1 and SDC 232
5. Reflections/critical perspective	Comment critically on the study, reflecting on the things that went well and those that did not, so others can learn from this experience	SDC 232-233

PPI patient and public involvement

From: Staniszewska S, Brett J, Simera I, et al (2017) GRIPP2 reporting checklists: tools to improve reporting of patient and public involvement in research. *BMJ* j3453. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j3453> [11].

GRIPP2-SF Item 4; Discussion and conclusion

Figure 1 provides an overview of all processes in which the research panels participated. Detailed explanations of these processes are available on page 3 in the SDC.

All research panels involved in the research process received consistent training through a shared slide-show introduction. This training covered the principles of randomised clinical trials, the importance of outcomes in trials and in general, and the validity of a COS repeated across trials [8]. The teaching material was based on a video developed by the COMET initiative – [link](#).

The Danish research panels responded positively to the introduction. Similarly, the international research panels evaluated and commented on the educational material and the process with their own panels (SDC, page 33). Overall, the challenging part was to avoid the discussion of how to define and assess the core outcomes, which will be the next step. Another challenge was to clarify that the core outcomes were intended for use across all conceivable trials in the ICU and therefore it was necessary to adopt a meta-perspective when reflecting on the importance of each of the core outcomes.

GRIPP2-SF Item 5; Reflections and critical perspective

The Danish research panels were involved in most of the consensus discussions, except for Step 4 (Figure 1), where the 19 outcomes were discussed and condensed to 6 outcomes. The rationale behind this

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discussion is detailed on pages 23-32 of the SDC. Step 4 (Figure 1) was the only step with limited involvement, which could have influenced the core outcomes chosen. However, the discussion closely followed the results of the three round Delphi survey and the Step 3 (Figure 1) and discussion across all research panels. Any disagreements or additional outcomes are included in Table S10 in the SDC with further details provided in the rationale behind the Danish COS (SDC, page 23-32) and the summary from the international research panels (SDC, page 33).

Involving all 14 countries in all 6 steps (Figure 1) might have improved the conclusion. Nonetheless, the pragmatic process of involving countries to internationally validate the Danish findings did enhance the conclusion. The pragmatic approach proved to be a functional way to develop the international validation and will strengthen the continued development concerning definitions of the core outcomes, selection of appropriate instruments, and timing of their assessment.

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